

Variability in the composition of Tense and Attitude reports

by

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Zusammenfassung in deutscher Sprache

Sprachen variieren in der Bandbreite der temporalen Interpretationen, die sie für ein unter einem vergangenheitszeitigen Einstellungsbericht eingebettetes Präsens oder Präteritum zulassen. Im Englischen weisen Konstruktionen mit Vergangenheit-in-Vergangenheit eine systematische Ambiguität zwischen einem gleichzeitigen (SIM) und einem vorzeitigen (BACK) Lesart auf, wie unten dargestellt.

- (1) Jerry said that Elaine **was** upset.
a. Jerry: “Elaine is upset.” ’ (Gleichzeitigkeit)
b. Jerry: “Elaine was upset.” ’ (Vorzeitigkeit)

Im Gegensatz dazu ergibt im Japanischen Past-unter-Past eindeutig eine zurückversetzte Lesart, während eine gleichzeitige Lesart unter Präsens-unter-Past Einbettungen entsteht (siehe unten).

- (2) a. Jerry-wa Elaine-ga okot-te-**iru** to itteimash-ita.
Jerry-TOP Elaine-NOM upset-PROG-**PRES** COMP say-PAST
Jerry: “Elaine is upset.” ’ (Gleichzeitigkeit)
b. Jerry-wa Elaine-ga okot-te-**ita** to itteimash-ita.
Jerry-TOP Elaine-NOM upset-PROG-**PAST** COMP say-PAST
Jerry: Elaine was upset.” ’ (Vorzeitigkeit)
N/a: ‘Jerry: Elaine is upset.’ ’ (#Gleichzeitigkeit)

Diese Beobachtungen haben Wissenschaftler dazu veranlasst, die Existenz eines speziellen Mechanismus im Englischen vorzuschlagen, einer **Sequence of Tense (SoT) Regel**, die optional den semantischen Beitrag der Vergangenheitsmorphologie in übereinkonfigurationen ‘löscht’ (Kratzer, 1998; Ogihara, 1996; Sharvit, 2003). Aus dieser Perspektive unterscheidet eine populäre typologische Klassifikation zwischen SoT-Sprachen – wie Englisch, die eine SoT-Regel haben, die eine eingebettete Zeitform semantisch leer macht – und Nicht-SoT-Sprachen – wie Japanisch, die keine SoT-Regel haben und eine transparentere Form-zu-Bedeutung Abbildung aufweisen (vgl. Bochnak et al., 2019; Ogihara & Sharvit, 2012).

Diese grundlegende crosslinguistische Unterscheidung wurde durch das Auftreten einer dritten Gruppe bereichert. Diese Sprachen können, obwohl sie die SoT-Regel nicht haben, SIM-Lesarten unter Vergangenheit-in-Vergangenheit Einbettungen durch eine *de re* Interpretation der eingebetteten Zeitform ausdrücken (Grønn & Von Stechow, 2010; Khomitsevich, 2008; Ogihara & Sharvit, 2012). Während **temporales de re** traditionell als marginal möglich in einigen Nicht-SoT-Sprachen oder in anderen als nicht existent angesehen wurde, hat jüngere Forschung (Bochnak et al., 2019) ein graduelleres crosslinguistisches Bild offenbart, obwohl dies an zurückversetzte Interpretationen gebunden ist.

Diese Dissertation befasst sich mit diesen beiden Punkten der crosslinguistischen Variation – dem SoT-Parameter und der Graduierbarkeit des temporalen *de re* – sowohl aus einer engen Perspektive, mit einer eingehenden Untersuchung zweier typologisch nicht verwandter Sprachen: Italienisch und Asante Twi, als auch aus einer breiteren crosslinguistischen Perspektive, wobei Bedingungen identifiziert werden, die die Variabilität in Bezug auf beide Parameter bestimmen.

In Kapitel 2 führten wir zwei Parameter der crosslinguistischen Variation ein: den SoT-Parameter und den temporalen *de re* Variabilitätsparameter, wobei wir feststellten, dass die binäre Natur dieser Parameter der erheblichen Mikrovariation, die kürzlich in der Literatur aufgedeckt wurde, nicht gerecht wird.

Die Kapitel 3 und 4 präsentieren Fallstudien zu Asante Twi und Italienisch. Für Asante Twi zeigte unsere Untersuchung ein zusammengesetztes System, bei dem temporale Interpretationen aus verschiedenen morpho-syntaktischen Repräsentationen entstehen. Mit Fokus auf die simultane Lesart zeigten wir, dass Asante Twi sowohl *de se* als auch *de re* Mechanismen einsetzt. Erstere resultieren aus einer transparenten Ableitung und sind nicht mit der SoT-Regel verknüpft. Letztere sind besonders interessant, da sie sowohl das imperfektive distale Tempus *n'a* als auch das perfektive Präteritum LEN anvisieren. Bemerkenswert ist, dass temporales *de re* am prominentesten bei *n'a* auftritt, was auf überraschende interlinguistische Variation hinweist. Darüber hinaus zeigt Asante Twi einen bisher nicht dokumentierten kompositionellen Weg zur Simultanität, der mit dem Perfekt *a* in Verbindung mit Zustandswechsel-Prädikaten verbunden ist. Im Gegensatz dazu ähnelt das Italienische eher dem Englischen und anderen SoT-Sprachen. Allerdings argumentierte ich aus empirischen Gründen gegen die Existenz einer SoT-Regel und nahm stattdessen eine kompositionelle Strategie an, die auf selektives λ -Binding und eine epistemische Interpretation des eingebetteten Imperfekts setzt.

Kapitel 5 integriert die empirischen und theoretischen Erkenntnisse der vorherigen Kapitel, um umfassendere crosslinguistische Verallgemeinerungen zu bieten. Eine eingehende Untersuchung der *de re* Muster identifizierte sowohl sprachspezifische als auch sprachunabhängige Faktoren, die zur Verfügbarkeit von temporalem *de re* innerhalb und zwischen Sprachen beitragen. Im Gegensatz dazu schwächte eine anschließende empirische Untersuchung den SoT-Parameter erheblich ab, der nur auf eine kleine Untergruppe von Sprachen beschränkt zu sein scheint. Ich schlage vor, dass dies wahrscheinlich auf eine allgemeine Präferenz in der natürlichen Sprache für eine transparente Zuordnung von Form zu Bedeutung zurückzuführen ist. Aus dieser Perspektive sollte die SoT-Regel als eine Notfallstrategie für eine Sprache betrachtet werden, die nur verwendet wird, wenn keine andere transparente Option verfügbar ist, um *de se*-ähnliche Interpretationen auszudrücken. Angesichts des geschwächten Status des SoT-Regel-Parameters schlage ich ein alternatives, auf Ökonomie basierendes Modell vor, das auf der semantischen Natur des Präsens und seinem Grad der Verschiebbarkeit beruht: Ein hoher Grad der Verschiebbarkeit des Präsens in einer Sprache prognostiziert eine höhere Wahrscheinlichkeit, dass das konkurrierende Präteritum semantisch interpretiert wird (und somit einen höheren Widerstand gegen Löschung und temporales *de re*) und umgekehrt. Wesentlich ist, dass dieses Modell im Gegensatz zu bestehenden Theorien die Existenz von Sprachen ausschließt, die mehrere *de se* Mechanismen aufweisen, die denselben wahrheitsbedingten Beitrag leisten (vgl. Ogihara & Sharvit, 2012). In diesem Zusammenhang stellte ich die Gültigkeit von Washo und Neugriechisch als echte SoT-Sprachen mit einem verschiebbaren Präsens in Frage.

Die Hauptbeiträge dieser Dissertation lassen sich in drei Punkten zusammenfassen: (i) sie betont die Rolle der Verschiebbarkeit des Präsens als gültiges Diagnoseinstrument der crosslinguistischen Variation und erhebt sie zu einem Ersatz für den SoT-Parameter; (ii) sie stützt sich nicht auf willkürliche oder nachträglich konstruierte Annahmen über die

Semantik des Tempus als pronominal/quantifikational oder absolut/relativ, sondern integriert diese in das Modell als Prädiktoren für temporales *de re*; (iii) sie wirft weiteres Licht auf die kompositionellen Feinheiten im Zusammenhang mit der temporalen Interpretation von Einstellungsberichten und den verfügbaren Strategien unter Berücksichtigung einer begrenzten Anzahl von Hilfsannahmen.

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List of Glossing Conventions

1	First Person
2	Second Person
3	Third Person
ACC	Accusative Case
APRF	Analytic Perfect
A	Asante Verb Prefix, aspect marker <i>a</i>
CL	Clitic
COMP	Complementizer
COP	Copula
CONS	Consecutive Aspect
DAT	Dative Case
DEF	Definite Determiner
DEM	Demonstrative
DEP	Dependent
FOC	Focus Marker
FUT	Future Modal
GEN	Genitive Case
HAB	Habitual Aspect
IMP	Imperfect
IND	Indicative Mood
INF	Infinitive
LEN	Asante Vowel-Lengthening Suffix, past perfective
NA	Asante Clausal Particle <i>ná</i>
NEG	Negation
NDEF	Indefinite Determiner
NOM	Nominative Case
NPAST	Non-Past Tense

List of Glossing Conventions

PERF	Perfect
PL	Plural
PAST	Past Tense
POSS	Possessor Marker
PRES	Present Tense
PROG	Progressive Aspect
PROSP	Prospective Aspect
PTCL	Particle
REL	Relativizer
SG	Singular
SPRF	Synthetic Perfect
SUBJ	Subjunctive Mood
TOP	Topic Marker

1 Introduction

Languages vary in the range of temporal interpretations they allow for a present or a past tense embedded under a past-tensed attitude report. In English, past-under-past constructions display a systematic ambiguity between a simultaneous (SIM) and a backward-shifted (BACK) interpretation, as illustrated below.

- (1) Jerry said that Elaine **was** upset.
a. ‘Jerry: “Elaine is upset.” ’ (Simultaneous reading)
b. ‘Jerry: “Elaine was upset.” ’ (Backward-shifted reading)

By contrast, in Japanese, past-under-past embeddings unambiguously yield a backward-shifted reading, with a simultaneous interpretation arising under present-under-past embeddings (see (2)).

- (2) a. Jerry-wa Elaine-ga okot-te-**iru** to itteimash-ita.
Jerry-TOP Elaine-NOM upset-PROG-**PRES** COMP say-PAST
‘Jerry: “Elaine is upset.” ’ (Simultaneous reading)
b. Jerry-wa Elaine-ga okot-te-**ita** to itteimash-ita.
Jerry-TOP Elaine-NOM upset-PROG-**PAST** COMP say-PAST
‘Jerry: “Elaine was upset.” ’ (Backward-shifted reading)
N/a: ‘Jerry: “Elaine is upset.” ’ (#Simultaneous reading)

These observations have led scholars to propose the existence of a special mechanism in English, a **Sequence of Tense (SoT) rule**, that optionally ‘erases’ the semantic contribution of past tense morphology in agreement configurations (Kratzer, 1998; Ogihara, 1996; Sharvit, 2003). From this perspective, a popular typological classification distinguishes between SoT languages — like English, which have an SoT rule rendering an embedded tense semantically vacuous—and non-SoT languages — like Japanese, which do not have an SoT rule and exhibit a more transparent form-to-meaning mapping (cf. Bochnak et al., 2019; Ogihara & Sharvit, 2012).

This basic cross-linguistic distinction has been enriched by the emergence of a third group. These languages, despite lacking the SoT rule, can express SIM-readings under past-under-past embeddings through a *de re* interpretation of the embedded tense (Grønn & Von Stechow, 2010; Khomitsevich, 2008; Ogihara & Sharvit, 2012). While **temporal *de re*** has traditionally been considered marginally possible in some non-SoT languages or nonexistent in others, recent work (Bochnak et al., 2019) has revealed a more gradable cross-linguistic picture, albeit tied to backward-shifted interpretations.

This thesis addresses these two points of cross-linguistic variation — the SoT parameter and the availability of temporal *de re* — from both a narrow perspective, with an in-depth investigation of two typologically unrelated languages: Italian and Asante Twi, and from

a broader cross-linguistic perspective, identifying conditions that determine variability relative to both parameters.

1.1 Methodology

The data presented in this thesis were primarily collected with the assistance of native consultants or result from the author's introspective judgments.

The data from Japanese and Russian in section 2.7 of chapter 2 were collected through email exchanges with two native speakers with a background in linguistics. The Russian speaker served as a consultant also for the data in chapter 5.

The data from Akan (chapter 3) were collected between March 2022 and November 2023 from six native speakers of the Asante Twi dialect through in-person or online elicitation sessions. Five of the speakers have a background in linguistics, and two speak Fante as their second language. The elicitation method followed the standards outlined in Matthewson (2004) for semantic fieldwork. Almost all the data were gathered using acceptability judgment tasks, in which speakers were asked to evaluate whether a given sentence was true in a specified context. While the target sentences were in Asante Twi, the contexts were provided in English and were occasionally supplemented with diagrams or timelines for more complex scenarios. At times, target sentences were volunteered by the speakers themselves when no provided target was an ideal fit. In some instances, translation tasks were used as an initial prompt. The acceptability of both translated and volunteered targets was subsequently tested with different consultants. Although not all the data were tested with all six speakers, the core data supporting the central claims were validated with at least three consultants. Two primary consultants, both from Kumasi in the Ashanti region, provided judgments for nearly all the data featured in this chapter. Inter-speaker variation was minimal, occurring in only a few contexts, and is explicitly noted in the text.

The data from Italian (Chapter 4) are based on the author's introspective judgments, unless specified otherwise. The core data on attitude reports were additionally validated by native speakers from both northern and southern regions of Italy. An online questionnaire with acceptability judgments with three additional speakers was set up to test reports of X-marked conditionals (see Appendix A).

The data from French and Spanish (chapter 5) were collected in January 2024 through an online acceptability judgment questionnaire (see Appendix A) and subsequent in-person elicitation. For French, two of the three native speakers have a background in linguistics, one speaker is from the French-speaking area of Switzerland. For Spanish, all three speakers have a background in linguistics. Of the Spanish speakers, two are from Spain (Madrid and Valencia), and one is from Peru.

The data from Russian in chapter 5 were collected through online acceptability judgment questionnaires and follow-up email exchanges with three native speakers, all of whom have a background in linguistics.

The data from German (Chapter 5) were collected between October 2023 and January 2024. Data on simple attitude reports were gathered through in-person elicitation sessions with five native speakers. Data on reports of X-marked conditionals were obtained through

an online questionnaire with six different native speakers (see Appendix A). All eleven consultants have a background in linguistics.

The data from Dutch and English (Chapter 5) were also collected through an online questionnaire (see Appendix A), with three native speakers of each language, all of whom have a background in linguistics. Of the three English speakers, two are from the UK and one is from the US. No differences in judgment were observed between British and American English.

The data from Modern Greek were collected using the same methodology between January and February 2024, with an extended version of the online questionnaire used for French, Italian, Spanish, German, Dutch, and English (see Appendix A). Eighteen native speakers served as consultants. Seven speakers were recruited from among colleagues and their friends, while the remaining participants were recruited through Facebook or, thanks to Prof. Winfried Lechner, as students of German Linguistics at the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens. Additional data were gathered from one other native speaker who did not participate in the questionnaire.

Unmarked examples indicate that all the speakers consulted accepted the sentence in the given context. Marked examples are categorized as follows (see (3)):

- (3)
- a. Single question mark ‘?’ if (i) the sentence was judged acceptable by most, but not all, speakers, or (ii) the sentence was universally accepted but slightly dispreferred compared to an alternative sentence.
 - b. Double question mark ‘??’ if (i) the sentence was rejected by most, but not all, speakers, or (ii) the sentence was universally considered only marginally acceptable.
 - c. The symbol ‘#’ indicates that the sentence was rejected by all speakers.

I refrain from using the symbol ‘%’ to represent inter-speaker variation, as I find it to be not particularly informative.

1.2 Main research questions

As previewed, this thesis investigates the temporal interpretation of attitude reports through a language-specific as well as a cross-linguistic lens. The main research questions can be summarized as follows.

Variation and Theory

- (4)
- What is the crosslinguistic variation that we observe and what is the most suitable model to describe it?
 - a. Are the existing **SoT+*de re* models** descriptively satisfactory? (Grønn & Von Stechow, 2010; Ogihara & Sharvit, 2012; Sharvit, 2018)
 - b. What kind of micro-variation, if any, do we observe with regard to the SoT parameter? Do all SoT languages align with English?
 - c. What kind of micro-variation, if any, do we observe with regard to temporal *de re* and the expression of SIM? Does it point to a more nuanced picture as found in Bochnak et al. (2019) in relation to BACK?

- d. Do Asante Twi and Italian provide novel insights into the observed variation?

Language-specific questions

- (5) **Asante Twi (Akan):** (i) How does the language compose temporal meaning and (ii) what strategies does it adopt to derive simultaneity? Are these part of the current model or do they constitute an innovation in the cross-linguistic landscape?
- (6) **Italian:** (i) Does Italian pattern with English and standard SoT languages or does it form a sub-group thereof? (ii) How does aspectual and mood competition affect the temporal interpretation of attitude reports?

1.3 Preview of the main findings

Variation and Theory:

- (7) Existing models need to integrate economy-based constraints indicating a clear division of semantic labour between present and past tense as well as limiting their range of temporal interpretations in attitude contexts.
 - a. Current models predict high and unconstrained variability, neglecting the possibility of interplay between the parameters assumed. It is demonstrated that these parameters do not operate independent of one another, but rather they interact in predictive ways. Specifically, the degree of shiftability of present tense in a language directly constrains the possibility for past tense to express simultaneity (through either *de se* or *de re*).
 - b. Several commonly labelled SoT languages do not involve deletion-like mechanisms (Western-Romance, German, Modern Greek). In particular, Italo-Western Romance languages, despite empirically aligning with English, generate semantically null readings through an epistemic interpretation of the embedded imperfect. As a result, the Sequence of Tense rule is restricted to a small subset of languages and, thus, not regarded as an efficient parameter of variation. It emerges as a ‘last resort mechanism’ under pressure from the Embeddability Principle (cf. Sharvit, 2003).
 - c. The degree of availability of simultaneous interpretations under temporal *de re* exhibits both inter- and cross-linguistic variability, as a function of the following factors: (i) The semantic shape of the tense - Pronominal and deictic tenses favour *de re* compared to quantificational and relative tenses); (ii) *Prefer de se!* (Schlenker, 2005) - *de re* LFs are dispreferred when competing with *de se* LFs for generating the same interpretation; (iii) *Prefer unbounded structures!* - Simultaneity is more naturally construed under aspectually unbounded structures compared to bounded ones as a consequence of the temporal profile of attitude verbs and the upper limit constraint they impose on their complement; (iv) The type of embedding predicate - Perception and factive verbs (as well as deictic adverbials in the complement clause) facilitate simultaneous readings under *de re*.

- d. Many non-Indo-European languages blur the semantic difference between aspectual and tense categories, making tense-based models in need of revision (cf. Bochnak et al., 2019; Hohaus, 2019).

Language-specific findings

(8) **Asante Twi (Akan):**

- (i) Asante Twi showcases an intriguing co-existence of pronominal and quantificational temporal-aspectual forms, pointing to diverse ways to convey temporal information. Specifically, the particle *ná* is viewed as a distal deictic tense, the suffix LEN combines perfective aspect with a relative pronominal past and the prefix *a* denotes a hybrid perfect yielding both existential and universal interpretations.
- (ii) Asante Twi displays a multi-faceted system in expressing simultaneous interpretations in attitude reports:
1. A *de se* mechanism with the bare form, akin to that associated with the embedded present in non-SoT languages.
 2. A *de re* mechanism, productive with the particle *ná*, but only marginal with LEN.
 3. An XN resultative+binding mechanism through the hybrid perfect *a* with change of state predicates.

The investigation of Asante Twi reveals a systematic ambiguity between SIM and BACK for embedded *ná*, that is reminiscent of that found for past-under-past in SoT languages. However, based on a novel diagnostic, both interpretations are linked to a *de re* analysis due to *ná*'s deictic nature. Furthermore, the derivation of simultaneous readings through the extended now resultative semantics of the perfect *a* manipulating result-states of change-of-state predicates contributes a new compositional mechanism to the cross-linguistic landscape.

(9) **Italian:** Temporal interpretation in Italian is constrained by TAM in systematic ways.

- (i) Simultaneous readings in Italian, as well as in Western Romance languages, are tied to the imperfect. Contrary to English, however, the imperfect is not semantically vacuous in SoT configurations, but yields *de se* readings through local binding (temporal interpretation) or manipulating the accessibility relation of a covert modal (modal/epistemic interpretation).
- (ii) Double access readings are governed by pragmatic constraints related to mood and aspect competitions. In particular, DAR can be blocked by principles of *Maximize Mood Presupposition!* (Heim, 1991; Schlenker, 2005) and cessation implicatures (Altshuler & Schwarzschild, 2012).

Similarly to Asante Twi, Italian involves a *de re* mechanism with the two perfect forms, which explains the exceptional availability of simultaneous interpretation under perception verbs. However, contrary to Italian, simultaneous *de re* interpretations are much more salient under *ná*.

1.4 The structure of this thesis

Chapter 2 sets the stage with a comprehensive (though not exhaustive) introduction to how semantic theory addresses the meaning of tense and aspect categories. For tense, I outline two major approaches: the pronominal approach, which views tense as a variable of type ⟨i⟩ that receives its value through context assignment, and the quantificational approach, which treats tense as an existential quantifier over times. Additionally, I discuss the possibility of treating tenses as relative (i.e., relativized to the local evaluation time) or absolute (i.e., relativized to the utterance time). Building on these foundational notions, I examine the temporal interpretation of attitude reports in English, focusing on past-under-past constructions as in (1). I show that the simultaneous interpretation of these sentences has been handled in three different ways in the literature: (i) structural approaches, which postulate an SoT rule deleting the semantic input of past tense under an agreeing tense morpheme; (ii) aspectual-pragmatic approaches, which attribute these readings to pragmatic reasoning based on the peculiar temporal profile of statives; (iii) a *de re* theory of tense, where temporal interpretations are not grammatically encoded but stem from contextually given acquaintance relations between the attitude holder and the time denoted by the embedded tense. I then turn to the cross-linguistic picture, where languages vary according to the existence of an SoT rule and the degree of availability of temporal *de re*.

In Chapter 4, I focus on Asante Twi, an Akan language of the Kwa branch of the Niger-Congo phylum. By examining the bare form, the particle *n'a*, and the affixes LEN and *a*, I conduct a detailed empirical investigation of their temporal and aspectual properties, which leads to a formal analysis of how temporal meaning is composed in the language. Building on these insights, I explore the temporal interpretation associated with these four forms in attitude reports, discussing the compositional options available for each one.

Chapter 4 follows a similar pattern, investigating temporal meaning in Italian. I review the substantial descriptive and formal literature, focusing on present-tensed forms (present and simple future) as well as the two perfects and the imperfect. I then examine embedded contexts, focusing on the derivation of double access readings for the embedded present and simultaneous readings for the embedded imperfect. This analysis shows that, contrary to common assumptions, Italian does not employ an SoT rule.

The empirical and theoretical insights gained from these two chapters serve as a foundation for Chapter 5, where I consider the broader cross-linguistic picture. Here, I pay close attention to two parameters of cross-linguistic variation: the SoT parameter and the temporal *de re* variability parameter, identifying the conditions that determine the observed variation under both.

Chapter 6 draws conclusions.

2 Background: Embedded tense and semantic variation

2.1 Time in natural language

Time is an inherent aspect of natural language since every sentence conveys temporal information. The truth of a sentence can vary depending on *when* it is uttered. For example:

(1) Jannik Sinner **is** the world number three in the ATP rankings.

The truth of (1) depends on the temporal context. As of February 2024, Jannik Sinner is ranked number 3 in the world, but this statement wouldn't hold true if evaluated in January 2024. This illustrates that the truth-conditional meaning of a sentence must be evaluated with respect to a time parameter, which, for (1), is the *time of utterance*.

Consider another example:

(2) The cookie jar **was** open.

According to Klein (1994), a finite sentence like (2) can be analyzed as having two components: a non-finite part (*INF*) that describes the situation and a finite part (*FIN*) that locates the situation in time. In English, *FIN* is marked morphologically by the past tense:

(3) a. *INF* = the cookie jar be open
b. *FIN* = -ed

The inflected component, *FIN*, encodes the temporal perspective from which the situation is observed, while *INF* describes the eventuality (here, the state of the jar being open). This temporal perspective, traditionally referred to as *tense*, can be further specified by an overt adverbial, as in (4):

(4) When I opened the door, the cookie jar was open.

At a superficial level, temporal reference appears to require only two times: present (see (1)) and past (see (2)). Analytic forms, however, show that a two-time system is insufficient to capture the full range of temporal interpretations in natural language. One example is given below:

(5) At 21 years old, Alcaraz **had** already **won** two Slams.

Sentence (5) does not convey that Alcaraz won two Slams in the year he turned 21,

rather than that at that age he was already a 2-time Grand Slam holder, having achieved the feat at an earlier time. Similar observations led to the first systematic attempt by Reichenbach (1947) to model temporal reference with a three-time system. Reichenbach argued that in order to express the meaning of tense forms, three points are necessary: the reference time **RT**, the eventuality time **ET** and the utterance time **UT**.¹ In Reichenbach’s theory, tense forms may be characterized by ordering these three points in time according to two relations: anteriority (‘-’) and simultaneity (‘,’), thus giving rise to 13 different constellations, not all attested. A simplified schema is given in Table 2.1.

Ordering relations	Tense forms	Example
ET - RT - UT	Past Perfect	John had already left.
ET,RT - UT	Simple Past	John left.
ET - UT,RT	Present Perfect	John has left.
UT,RT,ET	Simple Present	John leaves.
UT,RT - ET	Simple Future	John will leave.
UT - ET - RT	Future Perfect	John will have left

Table 2.1: English tense forms in Reichenbach (1947)’s system

The relevance of the reference time is exemplified by Reichenbach’s perfect forms. For instance, in ‘John had already left’, the leaving eventuality must have occurred by some reference point that is located before UT. Eventuality and utterance times are more intuitive concepts. The eventuality time denotes the running time of the depicted eventuality. The utterance time refers to the time at which an utterance is formulated. Alternative terms to utterance time found in the literature and used in this thesis are speech time and context time.

To fully describe a temporal situation, we also need to consider the **Evaluation Time** (EvalT), that is the time at which the sentence is evaluated. In matrix clauses, the evaluation time equates to the utterance time.

Drawing on Reichenbach’s system, Klein (1994) defines both tense and aspect categories in terms of relations between these three points.² Specifically, tense expresses temporal reference relating RT to UT, while aspect reveals the internal structure of an eventuality mediating between RT and ET.³ The latter is also known as viewpoint aspect.

Following Klein’s characterization, a three-way tense system emerges, as the one depicted in (6).

- (6) a. Present tense: $RT \supseteq \text{EvalT (UT)}$ (\supseteq = ‘surrounds’)
 b. Past tense: $RT < \text{EvalT (UT)}$ ($<$ = ‘before’)

¹I’m not being entirely faithful to the original terminology, in an attempt to introduce the one I’ll be using throughout the dissertation. Reichenbach’s original work identifies a point of reference R (here RT), an event E (here ET) and a point of speech (here UT). Nothing hinges on this labelling choice.

²The canonical distinction in Reichenbachian terms between UT, RT and ET does not reflect the terminology found in Klein (1994). Klein names RT ‘Topic Time’ and ET ‘time of situation’.

³Some frameworks do without the notion of reference times (see Kusumoto, 1999 among others). These are generally not concerned with aspect and the internal structure of eventualities. Therefore, they simply collapse reference times into event(uality) times.

- c. Future tense: $RT > \text{Eval}T$ (UT) ($> =$ ‘after’)

Viewpoint aspect offers an internal view of an event, action or state, describing it for example as a whole or as ongoing. The former is traditionally associated with perfective aspect, the latter with imperfective aspect. Viewpoint aspect is also dubbed grammatical aspect, in that several languages grammaticalize the distinction between perfective and imperfective viewpoint. In Kleinian terms, perfective and imperfective aspect can be represented as follows:

- (7) a. Perfective aspect: $ET \subseteq RT$ ($\subseteq =$ ‘within’)
 b. Imperfective aspect: $ET \supseteq RT$

Aspectual meaning is not exclusively expressed grammatically. It can also be lexically encoded. Lexical aspect (also named *Aktionsart*) concerns the *inherent temporal features of the lexical content* (Klein, 1994, p. 73). Following Vendler’s classification (Vendler, 1957), we can categorize eventualities into statives (love, be happy), activities (run, dance), accomplishments (build a house, draw a painting), achievements (arrive, die) and semelfactives (sneeze, knock).⁴

We have briefly introduced three important ingredients for a theory of temporal reference in natural language, namely tense, viewpoint aspect and lexical aspect. Although these are key building blocks of temporal meaning in languages with obligatory tense marking on the verb, many more languages employ alternative ways to express temporal meaning. Some languages, for instance, do not mark tense morphologically, or do so only optionally. Yet, they may still express temporal reference at a logical-semantic level through covert *semantic tense* (cf. Mucha, 2015), or resort to temporally restricted aspect (cf. Lin, 2003 for Mandarin Chinese), perspective shift (cf. Pancheva & Zubizarreta, 2023) or other (extra-)linguistic strategies (for an overview, see also Tonhauser, 2015).

2.2 Basic theoretical assumptions

Logical-semantic representations are fashioned within a type-theoretic framework akin to that outlined in Heim & Kratzer (1998). Variables with their respective semantic type and domain are given in (8).

- (8) a. ‘ x ’ $\in D_e$, ‘ x ’ ranges over entities of type e .
 b. ‘ e ’ $\in D_v$, ‘ e ’ ranges over eventualities of type v .
 c. ‘ t ’ $\in D_i$, ‘ t ’ ranges over times of type i .
 d. ‘ w ’ $\in D_s$, ‘ w ’ ranges over worlds of type s .
 e. Truth-values, such as ‘1’ (true) and ‘0’ (false), are of type $t \rightarrow D_t = \{0,1\}$
- (9) If a and b are semantic types, then $\langle a,b \rangle$ is a semantic type.
 Nothing else is a semantic type.

The truth-conditional meaning of a sentence is derived in a compositional fashion, starting from the meaning of its lexical units and following the set of rules sketched in Heim &

⁴This is merely an introduction to the terminology, but it will do for the moment. For a more exhaustive discussion, see Comrie (1976).

Kratzer (1998).

Lexical units as well as any linguistic expression are assigned a denotation through the interpretation function ‘ $\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket$ ’. The interpretation function is relativized to the two parameters g and c , denoting a variable assignment function and a context index, respectively. Therefore, given a linguistic expression α , its denotation ‘ $\llbracket \alpha \rrbracket^{g,c}$ ’ is evaluated with respect to g and c . In this thesis, denotations are always evaluated relative to g and c , although the two superscripts might be omitted from the interpretation function. Variables indexed with c are associated with the speech context. For instance, t_c rigidly designates the context or utterance time (UT), while w_c refers to the actual world. c -indexed expressions are indexicals just like the first person pronoun *I* or the adverb *here*. As a consequence, their value is independent of the syntactic environment and is not assigned through the function g .

Times as closed temporal intervals

It is important to note that in the current framework, times are conceptualized as closed temporal intervals governed by the relations in (10) (Bennett & Partee, 1972; von Stechow, 2009).

- (10)
- a. $<$ (anteriority/precedence): $t_1 < t_2$ iff t_1 is before t_2
 - b. $>$ (posteriority/succession): $t_1 > t_2$ iff t_1 is after t_2
 - c. \circ (overlap): $t_1 \circ t_2$ iff $t_1 \not\prec t_2$ & $t_2 \not\prec t_1$
 - d. \subseteq, \supseteq (inclusion): $t_1 \subseteq t_2$ ($t_2 \supseteq t_1$) iff t_1 is entirely included in t_2 (or t_2 surrounds t_1)
 - e. \subset, \supset (proper inclusion): $t_1 \subset t_2$ ($t_2 \supset t_1$) iff t_1 is entirely included in t_2 & $t_1 \neq t_2$

Despite possessing a low semantic type, times are not to be viewed as indivisible atomic units, but as exhibiting some degree of internal complexity. In particular, they can be subdivided into subintervals as well as atomized into infinitesimal moments or instants, as illustrated below.

- (11) *Times as intervals:*
 Given the set of all moments in time $T = \{-\infty, +\infty\}$, t is an interval of T iff $t \subset T$ & given two moments $m_1, m_2 \in t$, such that $m_1 \leq m_2$, if there is m , such that $m_1 \leq m \leq m_2$, then $m \in t$.

The concept formalized in (11) draws on the notion of a temporal continuum as characterized in von Stechow (2009), where time intervals are defined such that they include all partially ordered elements between any two elements within the interval.⁵ Unless explicitly noted, times are viewed as *closed* intervals.

- (12) *Times as closed intervals:*
 Given a temporal interval $t = \{m_i, \dots, m_f\}$, t is a closed temporal interval iff m_i

⁵Alternatively, a time interval can be viewed as a convex subset of the set T , containing all moments in history.

$\in t$, $m_f \in t$ & there is no moment m , such that $m \in t$ & $m < m_i \vee m > m_f$.⁶

Analogous properties and considerations can be extended to eventualities. Eventualities are mapped to times through the function τ . Given an eventuality e , $\tau(e)$ denotes the running time of e . Since, for the purposes of this thesis, the internal structure of eventualities is reduced to that of time intervals through the function τ , I will not address their mereology further.

With this basic setup in place, we turn now to how tense and aspect have been treated in the formal semantic literature.

2.3 Tense in formal semantics

In formal research, two approaches to tense meaning have emerged: a quantificational approach (see a.o. Bar-Lev, 2015; D. R. Dowty, 1982; Ogihara, 1996; Prior, 1967; von Stechow, 2009), treating semantic tense as an existential quantifier ranging over times, and a pronominal approach (see a.o. Abusch, 1997; Enç, 1987; Heim, 1994; Kratzer, 1998; Partee, 1973), likening tense to a pronoun picking up a salient temporal referent. Formally, the two approaches traditionally translate into the formulas in (13). For clarity of exposition, lowercase is associated with pronominal tense, while uppercase with quantificational tense.

- (13) a. *Quantificational tense*: $\llbracket \text{TNS} \rrbracket (p_{(i,t)}) = \exists t'[t' \sim t_c \ \& \ p(t')]$
 (\sim = ‘is related to’)
- b. *Pronominal tense*: $\llbracket \text{tns}_2 \rrbracket$ defined iff $g(2) \sim t_c$
 When defined, $\llbracket \text{tns}_2 \rrbracket = g(2)$

For a generic tense, the formulas in (13) superficially reveal an important difference between the two approaches: the relation between RT and EvalT is asserted for the quantificational tense in (13-a), whereas it’s presupposed for the pronominal tense in (13-b).

2.3.1 Quantificational approach

The first attempt to formalize tense meaning under a quantificational approach can be traced back to Arthur Prior’s seminal work on tense logic (Prior, 1967). Under Prior’s account, tense operates at sentence level, updating its EvalT-index. This is illustrated in (14).

- (14) *Prior’s semantics for past tense*:
 $\llbracket \text{PAST } \alpha \rrbracket^t = \exists t'[t' < t \ \& \ \llbracket \alpha \rrbracket^{t'}]$ (with $t = t_c$ in matrix clauses)

Importantly, under this approach, predicates receive purely extensional denotations which are not time-dependent. The overall temporal evaluation of a sentence is ultimately supplied by the EvalT-index.

⁶Moments are viewed here as the smallest building blocks of time (and, therefore, of temporal intervals). It follows that the smallest subintervals of times are moments, which can be considered as singleton temporal sets.

Despite its pioneering role in tense semantics, Prior’s theory faces several challenges, which have been extensively discussed in the literature (see, a.o., Kusumoto, 1999). Notably, this system is built on one single index, which severely restricts the range of temporal interpretations of a sentence. Specifically, it only allows for temporally ‘opaque’ interpretations (i.e., interpretations relative to the local EvalT), excluding for any linguistic expression in the scope of a temporal operator attested ‘transparent’ interpretations (i.e., relative to the utterance time). A few examples of cases that Prior’s system cannot easily handle are given below, with the temporal evaluation represented by subscripts

- (15) a. Viola gave birth to the person [who first stepped onto the Moon.]_{UT/#EvalT}
 b. [Chasten Buttigieg’s husband]_{UT/#EvalT} was a naval officer.

Similar observations led Cresswell (1990) to propose that natural language has the power to explicitly quantify over time variables (and, more generally, intensional variables). As a consequence, predicates’ denotations include time-variable slots, which can be explicitly quantified over by sentential operators like tense. Drawing on these insights, a possible quantificational semantics for past tense in the spirit of Kusumoto (1999) is given in (16) (see also Abusch, 1994; Ogihara, 1995; von Stechow, 1995).

$$(16) \quad \llbracket \text{PAST} \rrbracket = \lambda p_{\langle i,t \rangle} . \lambda t_i . \exists t' [t' < t \ \& \ p(t')]$$

According to (16), *PAST* takes a property of times p and an evaluation time t , quantificationally binding the temporal argument of p with a time t' that precedes t . To illustrate the workings of this semantics, consider the example in (17).

- (17) Elaine was upset.

At structural level, *PAST* scopes above the verb phrase, heading the a dedicate tense projection. In (18), I am assuming for simplicity reconstruction at Logical Form (LF) of the subject DP in [spec,VP], since syntactic transformations as A-movement do not affect the truth-conditions of the sentence. Note that each sentence is ultimately evaluated with respect to the utterance time, here projected at LF as the proform t_c adjoined to the CP-node.

Following (16) and (18), the denotation of the main predicate *upset* is a function from individuals to functions from times to truth-values, as sketched in (19-a). For the computation of the truth-conditions in (19-b), the copula *be* is assumed to be semantically

vacuous, as it only carries ϕ -feature specifications.

- (19) a. $\llbracket \text{upset} \rrbracket = \lambda x: x \in D_e. \lambda t: t \in D_i. x \text{ is upset at } t$
 In reduced form: $\llbracket \text{upset} \rrbracket = \lambda x_e. \lambda t_i. \text{upset}(x)(t)$ ⁷
 b. $\llbracket (17) \rrbracket = 1 \text{ iff } \exists t' [t' < t_c \ \& \ \text{Elaine is upset at } t']$

According to the truth-conditions we derive in (19-b), (17) asserts that there is some time preceding the utterance time at which the state of Elaine being upset obtains.

In a similar fashion, present tense also receives a quantificational analysis (see (20)), wherein the operator *PRES* quantifies over times surrounding the local evaluation time.

- (20) $\llbracket \text{PRES} \rrbracket = \lambda p_{(i,t)}. \lambda t_i \exists t' [t' \supseteq t \ \& \ p(t')]$ ⁸

This brief overview cannot do justice to the plethora of semantic approaches to tense grouped under the quantificational label. Abstracting away from notational differences, all these accounts involve existential quantificational force. As a consequence, quantificational tense directly correlates with an indefinite or existential temporal interpretation. This seems to be a desirable outcome in the light of the so-called experiential readings exhibited by the English Simple Past (see (21)).

- (21) a. Amy graduated at Harvard.
 b. Sinner won at least one Grand Slam.
 c. Once upon a time there was a linguist who disliked phonology.

Clearly, tensed predicates can express more than purely indefinite interpretations. The pronominal approach seeks to bridge this gap.

2.3.2 Pronominal approach

The first attested analogy between pronouns and tenses goes back to Partee (1973). Partee highlighted the deictic usage of tenses in sentences like (22), which a quantificational theory of the kind previously illustrated is unable to capture.

- (22) I didn't turn off the stove. (from Partee, 1973, p. 602)

The past tense in (22) does not locate the sentence at some indefinite point in the past. In fact, the sentence is best understood within a context, where for example the speaker left the stove after leaving her place. In this instance, the past tense would refer to a specific time interval preceding the speech time, namely the temporal interval between using the stove and leaving the place.

Crucially, the quantificational approach derives the wrong meaning for (22) under both scope constellations between the past tense and negation, as shown below:

- (23) *LFs for (22).*

⁷The ':' symbol depicts domain restrictions on partial functions. For simplicity, I will be using the reduced form in most semantic derivations.

⁸Note that a faithful translation of Prior's denotation of *PRES* would render it semantically vacuous, essentially serving as an identity function that leaves the evaluation time parameter unchanged.

2 Background: Embedded tense and semantic variation

- a. [not [PAST [VP I turn off the stove]]]
 b. [PAST [not [VP I turn off the stove]]]
- (24) *Truth-conditions for (22) under a quantificational approach.*
- a. $\llbracket (23\text{-a}) \rrbracket = 1$ iff $\neg\exists t' [t' < t_c \ \& \ \text{the speaker turns off the stove at } t']$
 Par: ‘There is no time interval preceding the speech time within which the speaker turns off the stove.’
- b. $\llbracket (23\text{-b}) \rrbracket = 1$ iff $\exists t' [t' < t_c \ \& \ \neg(\text{the speaker turns off the stove at } t')]$
 Paraphrase: ‘There is some time interval preceding the speech time and it is not the case that the speaker turns off the stove at this time.’

The truth-conditions in (24) convey either that there is no single past time at which the speaker turned off the stove ((23-a)) - which is trivially false - or that at least once before the speaker didn’t turn off the stove ((23-b)) - trivially true. Unfortunately, neither constitutes a good proxy for the meaning of the sentence. What the sentence conveys instead is that the speaker forgot to to turn off the stove within a given temporal interval, which is recoverable from the context.

The crucial observation that tenses might be interpreted as anaphoric to a contextually salient (temporal) referent led to the incorporation of a pronominal component into the semantics of tense. Specifically, under a purely pronominal view, tenses denote pronominal expressions whose value is assigned by the assignment function g , akin to canonical pronouns. In keeping with this analogy, pronominal tenses also exhibit a restriction on their reference. Following Heim (1994), this restriction is introduced at the presuppositional level (see (25)).

- (25) a. $\llbracket \text{past}_k \rrbracket^9$ is defined iff $g(k) < t_c$
 When defined, $\llbracket \text{past}_k \rrbracket = g(k)$
- b. $\llbracket \text{pres}_k \rrbracket$ is defined iff $g(k) \supseteq t_c$
 When defined, $\llbracket \text{pres}_k \rrbracket = g(k)$

Syntactically, sentences with pronominal tenses generate the same structure. Semantically, the temporal pronoun composes with the main predicate as its external argument, thus closing off the open proposition as illustrated below.

- (26) a.
-
- b. $\llbracket (22) \rrbracket = 1$ iff $\neg(\text{the speaker turns off the stove at } g(1))$

⁹In the notation I will adopt, lowercase tense will be pronominal, while the uppercase variant PAST will be quantificational.

with $\llbracket (22) \rrbracket$ defined iff $g(1) < t_c$

In (26-a), the UT-denoting t_c does not feature in the structure, since the relation between RT and UT is lexicalized in *past₁* in the form of a presupposition.

The merit of Partee’s theory is that it elegantly account for several pronominal properties associated with tense, thus elucidating tense’s behaviour as a definite description. Alongside the deictic uses illustrated by the *stove*-sentences, tenses additionally share with pronouns anaphoric and bound uses (see (27)-(28)).¹⁰

(27) *Anaphoric uses* (Partee, 1973, p. 605)

When Susan walked in, Peter left.

(28) *Bound uses* (Partee, 1973, p. 606)

Whenever Susan comes in, John immediately leaves.

Despite its theoretical appeal, a purely pronominal approach comes short of convincingly deal with indefinite and experiential readings, at least for English. Consider once more the example in (22). Reasonably, it would take the speaker only a few seconds to turn off the stove. Yet, the contextually salient time considered is much larger than that. In other words, unless a definite temporal instant is specified, the sentence receives some sort of indefinite interpretation within a definite one.¹¹ Additional evidence supporting a quantificational view comes from Ogihara (1995, p. 667), as a purely pronominal approach struggles to account for examples like (29):

(29) a. Did you see Mary?

b. Yes, I *saw* her, but I don’t remember exactly when.

In (29), both instances of the past tense refer to some time in the past, restricted to a contextually salient interval. In (29-a), the inquirer plausibly refers to a time on the day of the speech (and not to any arbitrary past time). Meanwhile, in (29-b), it is evident that the addressee has no definite time in mind, though the interval is constrained by the preceding context. A pronominal approach cannot adequately capture the meaning of *saw* in (29-b), as it would erroneously predict a contradictory interpretation, which is not attested.

These observations suggest that English tenses may exhibit both referential and existential properties. In the next subsection we review an attempt at fusing the two views under a unified account.

2.3.3 Hybrid approaches and quantifier domain restriction

So far, the analyses characterized as “quantificational” or “pronominal” have been presented in their purest formalization, thus revealing a clearcut distinction between the two. However, the end of the previous subsection has suggested that a more nuanced treatment of English tenses is probably needed, where these display features commonly ascribed to

¹⁰In (27), the when-clauses serves as a temporal antecedent to the past tense in the matrix. Sentence (28) arguably involves tense binding, as John’s leaving time co-varies with Susan’s walking-in time.

¹¹This appears to be a general problem with accomplishments, as observed in von Stechow (2009).

both accounts. Hybrid approaches of this kind usually delegate referential and quantificational meaning components to different syntactic elements. In Kusumoto (2005), for instance, tenses are referential but do not carry any temporal restriction, which in turn is introduced by a higher quantificational operator (for details, see also section 2.6.1). By contrast, the restriction is incorporated in the tense’s presupposition, à la Heim, in Ogihara & Sharvit (2012), with existential closure provided by a higher operator (see also Grønn & Von Stechow, 2016). Similarly, in Kratzer (1998), existential readings can be construed combining pronominal tense with an existential operator, which may be lexicalized into perfective aspect.

Alongside these technical implementations, the most popular attempt to reconcile the quantificational and pronominal approaches to tense semantics involves building the referential component in the domain restriction of the tense quantifier. According to this view, quantificational tenses no longer quantify over times indefinitely. Instead, their range is restricted to a specific time interval provided by the context.

The possibility of imposing a contextual restriction on the domain of the existential quantifier goes back to an idea of Stalnaker’s, further developed in Ogihara (1995).¹²

The version I offer here builds on Kusumoto (1999, pp. 45–46) and von Stechow (2009, pp. 21–22). Specifically, following von Fintel (1994), the domain of the existential quantifier is contextually restricted through an indexed variable C , as is given below.

- (30) a. $\llbracket C_k \rrbracket \in D_{\langle i,t \rangle}$, the set of contextually relevant times:
 b. $\llbracket C_k \rrbracket = g(k) = \{t: t \text{ is the set of contextually salient time intervals}\}$

C_k is syntactically represented as sister to the restricted tense. We can revise accordingly the semantics of *PAST* and the LF in (26-a):

- (31) a. $\llbracket \text{PAST} \rrbracket = \lambda C_{\langle i,t \rangle} . \lambda p_{\langle i,t \rangle} . \lambda t_i . \exists t' [C(t') \ \& \ t' < t \ \& \ p(t')]$

Under a restricted quantificational semantics of *PAST*, the stove-sentence receives the following simplified truth-conditions.

- (32) $\llbracket (22) \rrbracket = 1$ iff $\exists t' [g(7)(t') \ \& \ t' < t_c \ \& \ \neg(\text{the speaker turns off the stove at } t')]]$
 (where $g(7)(t') = 1$ iff t' is included in the set of salient times extending from the use of the stove to leaving the apartment)

¹²According to Heim & von Fintel (2007), this was formulated by Stalnaker during a conference.

The domain restriction approach to quantificational tense, as outlined here, closely parallels the nominal domain, where quantifiers are restricted by the nominal NP and take the clause as their nuclear scope. In this framework, the proform C functions as the restrictor, while the tenseless clause serves as its nuclear scope. Notably, in this implementation, the reference time (RT) introduced by the quantificational tense depends on a local evaluation time, determined by the binder λt in the formula in (31-a). In contrast, the pronominal approach is fundamentally deictic, as the RT is always evaluated relative to the utterance time. The designation of the evaluation time (EvalT) as either local or contextual introduces an additional parameter of variation in tense semantics, which I explore further in subsection 2.3.4.

2.3.4 Relative vs absolute tense

We have shown that the commonly assumed semantics for quantificational and pronominal tense differ in the way they encode the relation between RT and UT/EvalT. In one case it is part of the asserted content, in the other it is tucked into its presuppositional content. As already hinted at, the two semantics differ in one more respect. In a Kusumoto-style quantificational analysis, tenses denote functions of local evaluation times (the time-argument t in (31-a)). By contrast, a Heim-style pronominal semantics is independent of a local EvalT, in that the reference time is rigidly relativized to the utterance time t_c .

Tenses (like (31-a)) interpreted relative to a local evaluation time have been dubbed ‘relative tenses’. Tenses (like (13-b)) interpreted relative to the utterance time have been dubbed ‘absolute tenses’. Relative tenses are often called ‘shiftable tenses’, whereas other terms found in the literature for absolute tenses are ‘indexical tenses’ or ‘deictic tenses’. Given the equivalence $\text{EvalT} = \text{UT}$, matrix clauses do not reveal any discernible difference between the two types. However, we will see that in embedded contexts the temporal interpretations associated with a relative and an absolute tense may diverge.¹³

It is worth noting that, although the literature has often tied a relative tense semantics to a quantificational analysis and an absolute tense semantics to a pronominal analysis, these two parameters in reality cross-cut one another. In other words, quantificational force is not exclusively linked to relative tense, nor must absolute tense be inherently pronominal.¹⁴ Nonetheless, there seems to be a trend for which absolute tenses pattern more closely with pronominal ones and relative tenses with quantificational ones, to the extent that relative and deictic properties have served (in my opinion incorrectly) as diagnostics for quantificational and pronominal tenses, respectively. Adding to the complexity of categorization is the previously discussed observation that, in contemporary research, the boundaries between quantificational and referential approaches are often blurred, with the two sometimes treated as interchangeable variants. Similarly, the distinction between relative and absolute tense faces comparable challenges. In particular, analyses invoking indexical shift render the relative-absolute dichotomy increasingly tenuous (cf. Cable,

¹³For empirical arguments distinguishing between relative and absolute tenses, see Declerck (1995). Declerck, in particular, argues that the English past tense exhibits a systematic ambiguity between a relative and an absolute interpretation.

¹⁴Note that some approaches ascribe the relative/quantificational component of the tense form to perfect aspect (cf. Klein, 1994; Kratzer, 1998).

2005; Deal, 2020; Schlenker, 2003a).¹⁵

As a final note, recent cross-linguistic research has uncovered a greater variability in tense semantics than previously thought. This indicates that the nature of tense in any given language should not be simply assumed as a theoretical starting point but instead warrants thorough investigation in its own right.¹⁶

2.4 Aspect in formal semantics

Although aspect does not play a primary role in this thesis,¹⁷ I will briefly outline the main theoretical assumptions adopted regarding the semantics of aspect. The discussion that follows focuses on viewpoint and lexical aspect alone, given the introductory nature of this section.¹⁸

First of all, we have distinguished between grammatical or viewpoint aspect on the one hand and lexical aspect on the other. Grammatical aspect reveals the inner structure of an eventuality. Glossing over world-variables, the canonical contrast between perfective (PFV) and imperfective (IPFV) aspect can be formalized as in (33) (after Kratzer, 1998, p. 107).

- (33) a. $\llbracket \text{PFV} \rrbracket = \lambda p_{\langle v,t \rangle} . \lambda t_i . \exists e [\tau(e) \subseteq t \ \& \ p(e)]$
 b. $\llbracket \text{IPFV} \rrbracket = \lambda p_{\langle v,t \rangle} . \lambda t_i . \exists e [\tau(e) \supseteq t \ \& \ p(e)]$

According to (33), viewpoint aspects introduce an inclusion relation between the eventuality time and the reference time. For the perfective aspect in (33-a), the running time of the event is entirely included in its reference. For the imperfective aspect in (33-b), this relation is reversed. It is worth noting that these basic formulas cannot capture all the semantic nuances associated with perfective and imperfective aspect. For our current purposes, however, they are sufficiently adequate.

Viewpoint aspect is structurally situated between TP and VP. One important consequence of the semantics in (33) is that the main predicate denotes a predicate of eventualities rather than times. This is illustrated for the predicate *faint* in (34).

- (34) a. (While Mary was singing,) John fainted.
 b. LF: $[t_c \text{ [}_{\text{TP}} \text{ PAST}_{C_7} \text{ [}_{\text{AspP}} \text{ PFV [}_{\text{VP}} \text{ John faint}]]]]$
 c. $\llbracket \text{leave} \rrbracket = \lambda x_e . \lambda e_v . \textit{faint}(x)(e)$
 d. $\llbracket (34\text{-a}) \rrbracket = \exists t' [g(7)(t') \ \& \ t' < t_c \ \& \ \exists e [\tau(e) \subseteq t' \ \& \ \textit{faint}(J)(e)]]$
 With $g(7) = \{t: \text{Mary is singing in } t\}$
 Par: ‘There is some time t' , such that t' is a time at which Mary is singing

¹⁵From this perspective, tenses can be understood as indexicals that may, or may not, undergo shifting. We return to this point in chapter 4.

¹⁶Due to space constraints, I cannot delve into the entire body of work. However, see, among others, Armenante & Lecavelier, 2024; Bertrand et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2021; Zhao, 2023

¹⁷The distinction between perfective and imperfective aspect will prove crucial in explaining contrasting interpretations in attitude contexts in the next chapters.

¹⁸A comprehensive analysis of the perfect aspect lies beyond the scope of this section. However, its semantics will be thoroughly explored in section 3.3.4 of chapter 3, with particular reference to the Asante Twi aspectual marker *a*.

and that precedes the utterance time and there is an eventuality e , such that e is temporally included in t' and e is an eventuality of John fainting.’

Assuming that the eventive predicate “fainted” is perfective, the truth-conditions derived above correctly view the fainting event as entirely included in the reference time t' , whose contextual restriction is explicitly supplied by the bracketed while-clause.

As previously mentioned, information on the internal structure of an eventuality can also be lexically encoded. Since Vendler (1957), predicates have been grouped into four aspect classes or *Aktionsarten*: statives, activities, accomplishments and achievements. Following Smith, 1997, we can characterise Vendler’s classes based on their semantic features.¹⁹

	Stativity	Durativity	Telicity	
Statives	+	+	-	<i>Zoe is late.</i>
Activities	-	+	-	<i>Zoe is sleeping.</i>
Accomplishments	-	+	+	<i>Zoe ate an ice-cream</i>
Achievements	-	-	+	<i>Zoe won the contest.</i>

Table 2.2: Aspect classes and semantic features

Vendler’s classification is not merely descriptive; it plays a key role in understanding how categories like viewpoint and lexical aspect interact with the temporal meaning of a clause. As we will see, different viewpoints and *Aktionsart* can even influence, or block, certain temporal interpretations in attitude reports.

This close connection between aspectual and temporal meaning has been further explored in recent research, which has uncovered markers that defy clear categorization as strictly temporal or aspectual. These markers are generally considered aspectual but impose additional restrictions on their temporal reference (see a.o. Armenante & Lecavelier, 2024; Bittner, 2014; Bochnak et al., 2019; Hohaus, 2019; Mucha, 2013). This debate is closely tied to a broader discussion on temporal reference in tenseless languages, that is in languages with no overt tense marking.²⁰

While this variability may challenge traditional typological distinctions between tense and aspect, especially those derived from Indo-European languages, the expression of temporal reference and event structure remains a fundamental component of natural language. This remains true regardless of whether these categories are lexicalized separately or conflated in a single marker, expressed overtly, or understood contextually.

Having established the basic building blocks of temporal meaning, we now turn to more complex constructions, such as propositional attitude complements, which are the focus of this thesis.

¹⁹For further details, see Mucha, 2015.

²⁰I cannot possibly do justice to the vast body of work on the topic. For a comprehensive overview, I refer the reader to Dahl (2021), Mucha (2015), and Tonhauser (2015).

2.5 Attitude reports and sequence of tense

This section introduces the central topic of this thesis: the temporal interpretation of propositional attitude reports, i.e. clausal arguments selected by a propositional attitude verb like *say* or *believe*. Having English as our starting point, the ultimate goal is to extend our theory in order to capture the meaning of sentences like (35), which have been associated with a very well-known temporal ambiguity between a simultaneous and a backward-shifted interpretation.

- (35) a. George believed **that Kramer was sick**.
 b. Jerry said **that Elaine was upset**.

Before we analyze these sentences, we need two new ingredients: an intensional semantics for propositional attitude verbs and a theory of how intensional variables enter semantic composition.

2.5.1 Propositional attitudes and intensional variables

So far, we have omitted in our discussion the modal meaning associated with the interpretation of sentences. These, albeit only indirectly, have been essentially interpreted relative to the actual world w_c through the context parameter c . Departing from this simplified view, when in the scope of intensional operators such as propositional attitude verbs, clauses are evaluated with respect to the attitude world and time rather than relative to the context world and time. As a first step, we introduce world-variables in our system, thus revisiting the semantics of predicates. As a further amendment, in accordance with the relevant literature (Keshet, 2010; Percus, 2000; Schwarz, 2012), intensional variables enter semantic compositions as internal arguments of predicates (see (37)) and, thus, are bound in the object language by freely-inserted λ -abstractors.²¹ Similarly, intensional parameters of evaluations, such as w_c and t_c , adjoin at LF to the respective top nodes.²² The characteristic function of predicates is schönfinkelized accordingly (see (36)).

$$(36) \quad \llbracket \text{upset} \rrbracket = \lambda w_s. \lambda t_i. \lambda x_e. x \text{ is upset at } t \text{ in } w$$

For propositional attitude verbs, I adopt a Hintikka (1962)-like semantics (revised in

²¹This framework departs from Heim & Kratzer (1998), where λ -abstractors are generated by syntactic movement.

²²Alternatively, intensional parameters of evaluation are represented as superscripts of the interpretation function ‘ $\llbracket \rrbracket$ ’, while intensional arguments may not project syntactically but are abstracted over via a dedicated rule that intensionalizes an extensional denotation (along the lines of “Intensional Functional Application”, cf. Heim & Kratzer, 1998; Heim & von Stechow, 2007). Nothing hinges on this choice.

subsequent work, see Ogihara & Sharvit, 2012), according to which attitude verbs universally quantify over ordered world-time pairs that are compatible with the attitude holder's mental state.

$$(38) \quad \llbracket \text{believe} \rrbracket = \lambda w_s. \lambda t_i. \lambda p_{\langle s, \langle i, t \rangle \rangle}. \lambda x_e. \forall \langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Dox}(x, w, t) \rightarrow p(w')(t')$$

Where $\text{Dox}(x, w, t) = \{ \langle w, t \rangle : \langle w, t \rangle \text{ is compatible with what } x \text{ believes in } w \text{ at } t \}$

$$(39) \quad \llbracket \text{say} \rrbracket = \lambda w_s. \lambda t_i. \lambda p_{\langle s, \langle i, t \rangle \rangle}. \lambda x_e. \forall \langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Say}(x, w, t) \rightarrow p(w')(t')$$
²³

The functions *Dox* and *Say* represent accessibility relations that are doxastic and reportative, respectively.²⁴ These impose (lexically encoded) restrictions on the domain of quantification of the verb.

What follows from the semantics in (38) and (39) is that (complement) clauses no longer denote truth-values, but predicates of worlds and times, as they are evaluated relative to the world and time at which the attitude holder project herself. Note that extending self-location to the temporal domain constitutes a point of departure from Hintikka's original formulation. The idea, however, that attitude reports involve *de se* ascriptions (i.e., ascriptions about oneself) was defended in von Stechow (1982). Consider the following example adapted from von Stechow (2009, p. 157):

(40) Context: Jerry forgot to adjust the timezone on his watch. It shows 4 o'clock, but it's actually 5 o'clock.

(41) Jerry believes *it's 4 o'clock*.

If the italicized clause in (41) denoted only a set of worlds, the sentence would receive the nonsensical interpretation: *Jerry believes that 5 o'clock is 4 o'clock*. To assign the correct meaning to the sentence, the attitude time quantified over by *believe* must access the reference time of the embedded clause. In other words, attitude holders self-ascribe the property denoted by the complement clauses. In our example, Jerry self-ascribes the property of being at 4 o'clock (or locates himself at a time that is 4 o'clock).

2.5.2 The sequence of tense ambiguity

In English, sentences as (35), in which a past stative verb is embedded under an attitude verb, are usually ambiguous between a backward-shifted (*BACK*) and a simultaneous (*SIM*) reading. These are illustrated for (35-b), repeated below:

- (42) Jerry said that Elaine was upset.
- a. Jerry said: 'Elaine is upset' (*SIM*)
- b. Jerry said: 'Elaine was upset' (*BACK*)

Notoriously, the simultaneous interpretation in (42-a) poses a challenge to semantic theory. Under a relative tense approach, for instance, the system derives a backward-shifted reading only, as is illustrated below.²⁵

²³Reads: ' $\langle w', t' \rangle$ is a doxastic alternative of $\langle w, t \rangle$ '. Analogously, $\text{Say}(x, w, t) = \{ \langle w, t \rangle : \langle w, t \rangle \text{ is compatible with what } x \text{ says in } w \text{ at } t \}$, with *Say* introducing the Say-alternatives.

²⁴For modality and accessibility relations, see Hacquard (2006), Kratzer (1981), and Lewis (1973).

²⁵For simplicity, intensional variables are represented as subscripts

(43) Backward-shifted Reading

- b. $\llbracket (35\text{-b}) \rrbracket = 1$ iff $\exists t' [g(5)(t') \ \& \ t' < t_c \ \& \ \forall \langle w', t'' \rangle \in \text{Say}(J, w_c, t') \rightarrow \exists t''' [g(6)(t''') \ \& \ t''' < t'' \ \& \ \text{Elaine is upset in } w' \text{ at } t''']]$
Paraphrase: ‘There is a time t' preceding UT, such that for all the world-time pairs $\langle w', t'' \rangle$ which are compatible with what Jerry says in the actual world at the time t' , there is a time t''' before t'' at which Elaine is upset in w' .’

In (43-a), the world and time arguments w_1 and t_4 of the embedded predicate *upset* are bound by the λ -abstractors λw_1 and λt_4 . This generates for the embedded CP a property of type $\langle s, \langle i, t \rangle \rangle$ to be fed to the embedding verb *say*. The world and time open slots of the embedded propositions are saturated by the world-time pairs the attitude predicate quantifies over. The resulting interpretation is backward-shifted.

What accounts for the simultaneous interpretation then? Within a quantificational analysis, one possibility is to assume that quantificational tenses, just like quantificational NPs, can QR out of the scope of an intensional operator, leaving a co-indexed trace behind.

(44) QR reading

- b. #Par: “There is a time t , such that t precedes UT and there is a time t' preceding t , such that for all the world-time pairs $\langle w', t' \rangle$ which are compatible with what Jerry says in the actual world at the time t' , Elaine is upset in w' at t .”²⁶

This approach allows a *de re*/transparent interpretation of the embedded past tense (i.e., relative to the utterance time), thus preventing shifting with respect to the attitude time. An obvious problem with this approach is that it generates an uninterpretable LF. As shown in (44), the attitude time abstractor ‘ λt_9 ’ binds into thin air, leading to vacuous quantification over times on the part of the attitude verb.²⁷

A more promising solution is offered by a pronominal (absolute) approach. Recall that under Partee’s account, tenses, just like canonical pronouns, can be bound. A variable-binding construal for (42) produces the Logical Form in (45) (I only report the detailed structure for the matrix V' , since the matrix clause remains unchanged).

²⁶Given the relative semantics assumed for quantificational tense, the resulting interpretation for the “QR LF” in (44) is only compatible with a shifted interpretation: a backward-shifted one if the embedded past QR’s below the matrix one, or a forward-shifted one if it QR’s above it.

²⁷The binder λt_9 is inserted above the TP to produce a property of times, so that the attitude verb can access embedded proposition. Removing it would disrupt compositionality and not solve the vacuous quantification issue.

In (45), the pronominal past tense $past_7$ is co-indexed with the EvalT-binder λt_7 , thus preventing vacuous quantification by the attitude verb. Given that the reference time of the embedded clause is quantificationally bound by the attitude predicate, a temporal *de se* reading obtains, for which Elaine’s upset state is located at a time that is compatible with when she spoke. Importantly, the restriction imposed by $past_7$ ’s presupposition projects up to its binder, thus being checked against the attitude time t'' . Given that the latter is compatible with a time that precedes t_c , the bold-faced presupposition is satisfied (see (46)).²⁸

$$(46) \quad \llbracket (45) \rrbracket = 1 \text{ iff } \forall \langle w', t'' \rangle \in \text{Say}(J, w_c, g(5): g(5) < t_c): \mathbf{t''} < \mathbf{t_c} \rightarrow \text{Elaine is upset in } w' \text{ at } t''$$

The pronominal account of *SIM* offered above is reminiscent of proposals discussed in Enç (1987), Giorgi & Pianesi (1997), and Partee (1973), but revisits them in a modern way within the general framework developed here.

Although the pronominal approach can handle the simultaneous interpretation in past contexts, a significant issue arises with the backward-shifted reading. If the embedded temporal pronoun refers to a contextually salient time that precedes the attitude time, we encounter the same problem as before: vacuous quantification of the attitude verb (see (47)).

²⁸In (46), the presuppositional meaning of the two pronominal tenses - $g(5)$ for the matrix past and t'' for the bound embedded past - are incorporated in the truth-conditions, following the colon ‘:’.

In (47), the tense variable $past_7$ cannot remain free in attitude contexts, since this would lead to the wrong semantic type for the embedded CP. In fact, we will demonstrate in the next section that the *de re* analysis associated with a freely interpreted pronominal tense relies on additional structural manipulations in order to preserve interpretability.

2.5.3 Null readings and sequence of tense diagnostics

The previous subsection suggested that the ambiguity of past-under-past attitude reports in English can only be resolved by considering both quantificational and pronominal semantics. Specifically, while a backward-shifted interpretation is naturally derived under the a quantificational approach, an absolute tense analysis under a variable-binding construal seems to capture the simultaneous reading. Unfortunately, this is not entirely accurate.

Even an absolute pronominal theory of tense cannot systematically derive simultaneous readings in attitude contexts. In particular, simultaneous interpretations arise in past-under-past constructions even when the embedded past does not convey any *pastness*, as illustrated by the so-called *breakfast sentences* below (Abusch, 1994, p. 105):²⁹

- (48)
- a. John decided a week ago that in ten days at breakfast he would say to his mother that they **were having** their last meal together.
 - b. John $past_1$ decided a week ago that in ten days at breakfast he $past_2$ would say₃ to his mother that they $past_3$ were having their last meal together.³⁰

In (48), the most embedded past tense, $past_3$, refers to a time that follows UT. Therefore, a compositional analysis that treats tenses as absolute would result in a presupposition failure (i.e., the condition $g(3) < t_c$ is not met here). In this context, the embedded

²⁹Abusch's breakfast sentence is based on a French example by Kamp & Rohrer (1984).

³⁰I am faithfully adopting Abusch's notation here. Each tense is a referring expression a-la-Partee. The index of *say* refers to the future reference introduced by *would*, that is the time within which the saying event occurs.

tense seems to make no discernible semantic contribution, and the resulting simultaneous reading appears to be a genuine *null reading*.

The null reading in (48) exemplifies the quintessential **Sequence of Tense** (SoT) reading, where the embedded past tense marker is semantically vacuous and can only be licensed within an appropriate morpho-syntactic sequence. In other words, languages like English that have Sequence of Tense permit vacuous or null readings of past-under-past embeddings. For this reason, English-like languages are generally referred to as SoT languages.

Beside in breakfast-sentences, past tense is typically ‘vacuous’ in reports that include permanent states of affairs, such as generics and i-level predicates. (Armenante & Braun, 2022; Khomitsevich, 2008; Ogihara & Sharvit, 2012).

- (49) Context (2150 years ago): Ptolemy to himself: ‘Eureka, the Sun revolves around the Earth!’
- a. Ptolemy believed that the Sun **revolved** around the Earth.
- (50) Bill thought that 9 **was** a prime number!

In (49) and (50), the bold-faced tense does not locate the embedded eventuality at any particular time in the past. In fact, these predicates are typically ‘atemporal’, and restricting them to a designated temporal interval conflicts with our idea of physics and mathematics. This is also why predicates expressing permanent states of affairs cannot surface with past tense morphology in matrix environments, without giving rise to very odd interpretations.

- (51) a. ??The Sun revolved around the Earth.
b. #9 was a prime number.

There have been several attempts in the literature to develop an SoT theory that accurately captures the simultaneous interpretation produced by past-under-past embeddings. These theories can be categorized into two groups:

1. Structural accounts, which rely on structural ambiguity and derive simultaneity through an SoT rule based on morpho-syntactic agreement (Abusch, 1994; Kratzer, 1998; Kusumoto, 1999; Ogihara & Sharvit, 2012; Stowell, 2007).
2. Aspectual-pragmatic accounts, which rely on underspecification, with the simultaneous reading arising from the unique aspectual properties of statives and pragmatic reasoning (Altshuler & Schwarzschild, 2012; Gennari, 2003).³¹

I will review some of the most prominent proposals in the next section.

³¹For a hybrid approach that is underspecification-based but additionally relies on tense agreement, see Kauf & Zeijlstra, 2018.

2.6 Approaches to the SoT puzzle

2.6.1 Structural accounts

(i) The SoT rule of Ross and Comrie

Traditional grammars commonly address SoT phenomena in terms of tense-shifting, where a tense born as present is shifted into past in reported speech. In early generative work, Ross (1967) formulated these insights in terms of a rule that changes an underling present tense into a past tense:

$$(52) \quad \text{a. } [\text{TP } T_{[\alpha]} \dots V \dots [\text{TP } T \dots V \dots]] \quad (52\text{-a}) \Rightarrow (52\text{-b})$$

$$\text{b. } [\text{TP } T_{[\alpha]} \dots V \dots [\text{TP } T_{[\alpha]} \dots V \dots]]$$

$$(53) \quad \text{a. } [\text{TP } T \dots V \dots [\text{TP } T_{[\alpha]} \dots V \dots]] \quad (53\text{-a}) \Rightarrow (53\text{-b})$$

$$\text{b. } [\text{TP } T_{[\alpha]} \dots V \dots [\text{TP } T_{[\alpha]} \dots V \dots]]$$

According to Ross, this rule accounts for the (un)grammaticality of sentences like (54) and (55)

$$(54) \quad \text{I believed that the sun } *is/was \text{ out.} \quad (\text{Ross, 1967, p. 333})$$

$$(55) \quad \text{That the sun } *is/was \text{ out } \mathbf{was} \text{ obvious.} \quad (\text{Ross, 1967, p. 333})$$

The **SoT rule** stated in (52) and (53) provides a feature-copy mechanism responsible in the above examples for the occurrence of the italicized tense morpheme, copied from the boldfaced tense morpheme. Note that the rule is bidirectional, as the feature-assigner does not need to (asymmetrically) c-command the assignee.

This approach is echoed in Comrie (1986), who proposes the rule in (56).

$$(56) \quad \textit{Comrie's SoT rule} \text{ (Comrie, 1986, p. 284):}$$

If the tense of the verb of reporting is non-past, then the tense of the original utterance is retained; if the tense of the verb of reporting is past, then the tense of the original utterance is backshifted into the past, except that if the content of the indirect speech has continuing applicability, the backshifting is optional.³²

One caveat to Comrie's rule is that it is defined in purely morpho-syntactic terms, as the backshifting operation is not sensitive to the temporal meaning of the relevant tense form (Comrie, 1986, p. 290).

(ii) Ogihara's deletion theory

Similarly, Ogihara posits an SoT rule within a quantificational theory of tense. However, unlike the bidirectional rule proposed by Ross, Ogihara's SoT rule only applies downward. More specifically, Ogihara (1995, p. 673) suggests that an embedded tense can be deleted under morphological agreement with a superordinate tense marker (see (57)).³³

³²The notion of "continuing applicability" must be related to properties that temporally extend beyond the attitude time to overlap with the context time. This is the case, for instance, of generic and permanent states such as those discussed in section 2.5.3. In modern tense semantics, temporal interpretations involving continuing applicability are more commonly referred to as double access readings (see section 2.6.3).

³³For a similar account, see Sharvit, 2003.

- (57) **SoT Rule:** A tense morpheme α can be deleted if and only if α is locally c-commanded by a tense morpheme β (i.e., there is no intervening tense morpheme between α and β), and α and β are occurrences of the past tense morpheme.

Ogihara adopts a restricted quantificational view of tense, which generates *BACK* as a default reading. When the SoT rule in (57) applies, the system generates *SIM*, as illustrated below.

- (58) Jerry said that Elaine was upset.
- a. $[\text{TP Jerry PAST say that } [\text{TP PAST } \lambda t_4 \text{ Elaine be-upset}_{t_4}]]$ (*BACK*)
 - b. $[\text{TP Jerry PAST say that } [\text{TP } \cancel{\text{PAST}} \lambda t_4 \text{ Elaine be-upset}_{t_4}]]$ (*SIM*)
 - c. $[[(58\text{-b})] = 1 \text{ iff } \exists t' [t' < t_c \ \& \ \forall \langle \mathbf{w}', \mathbf{t}'' \rangle \in \text{Say}(J, w_c, t') \rightarrow \text{upset}(\mathbf{w}')(\mathbf{t}'')(\mathbf{E})]]$
(where Jerry locates himself at a time simultaneous to Elaine's being upset.)

Note that the SoT rule stated in (57) is not a constraint but an optional rule. It could not be otherwise given that these sentences are genuinely ambiguous. Moreover, Ogihara's deletion rule, albeit governed by a structural relationship like c-command, only applies post-syntactically at LF-level.

Ogihara subsequently revisits the SoT rule in (57) for a broader empirical coverage, thus extending it to present tense as well (Ogihara, 1996, p. 124):

- (59) **SoT Rule (2nd version):** If a tense α is locally c-commanded by another tense β at LF and α and β are occurrences of the same tense (i.e., either present or past), α is optionally deleted.

The new version of the SoT rule accommodates *SIM* readings of embedded present tenses under future attitude verbs, a phenomenon first pointed out by Stump (1985):

- (60) Meryl will claim that she is Jerry's wife.

Assuming a context in which the DP *Jerry's wife* cannot receive a (temporal) *de re* interpretation, the sentence in (60) can only yield a *SIM* reading (Meryl locates herself at a later-than-now time within which she is Jerry's wife). The rule in (59) can generate an LF compatible with this reading:

- (61) a. $[\text{TP PRES will Meryl claim that } [\text{TP } \cancel{\text{PRES}} \text{ she be-Jerry's-wife}]]$
 b. $[[(60)] = 1 \text{ iff } \exists t [t \supseteq t_c \ \& \ \exists t' [t' > t \ \& \ \forall \langle \mathbf{w}', \mathbf{t}'' \rangle \in \text{Say}(M, w_c, t') \rightarrow \text{wife}(\mathbf{w}')(\mathbf{t}'')(\mathbf{J})(\mathbf{M})]]]$

Deletion is triggered this time by a(n uninterrupted) sequence of present tense. This is possible if we assume that *will* is the spell out of a present-tensed futurity modal WOLL (cf. Abusch, 1988).

Ogihara's SoT rule can also comfortably handle the breakfast sentences, which posed a challenge to Partee's pronominal approach. Applying (59) to (48) repeated below, we predict the correct interpretation of the sentence (under a *SIM* reading).

- (62) a. John decided a week ago that in ten days at breakfast he would say to his mother that they **were having** their last meal together.

- b. [_{TP} PAST John decide a week ago that [_{TP} ~~PAST~~ WOLL in-ten-days at-breakfast he say to his mother that [_{TP} ~~PAST~~ they be-having their-last-meal-together]]]
- c. $\llbracket (48) \rrbracket = 1$ iff $\exists t[t < t_c \ \& \ t \text{ is a week before } t_c \ \& \ \forall \langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Dox}^{34}(J, w_c, t) \rightarrow \exists t'' [t'' > t' \ \& \ t'' \text{ is 10 days after } t' \ \& \ \text{at-breakfast}(t'') \ \& \ \forall \langle w'', t''' \rangle \in \text{Say-to-his-mother}(J, w', t'') \rightarrow \text{have}(w'')(t''')(last \ meal)(they)]]$
 Par: ‘There is a time t , such that t precedes UT by a week and for all world-time pairs $\langle w', t' \rangle$ compatible with John’s beliefs at t in the actual world, there is a time t'' , such that t'' follows t' by 10 days and t'' is part of the set of breakfast times and for all world-time pairs $\forall \langle w'', t''' \rangle$ compatible with what John will say to his mother at t'' in w' , t''' is a time at which John and his mother have their last meal together.’

Importantly, simultaneous readings are not expected to arise for past-under-will, given that the present tense on the modal cannot license past tense deletion. This prediction seems to be borne out.

- (63) a. John decided a week ago that in ten days at breakfast he will say to his mother that they were having their last meal together.
 b. [_{PAST} John decide [_{PRES} WOLL he say [_{PAST} they be-having their-last-meal-together]]]

A potential downside of Ogihara’s proposal, as noted in Kusumoto (1999, pp. 71–72), is that the SoT rule must obligatorily delete the past tense morpheme on *would* to avoid non-attested interpretations. If we omit the temporal adjuncts in (48), we get the sentence in (64-a), which can receive a nonsensical interpretation if the past tense on *would* is not vacuous:

- (64) a. John decided that he would say to his mother they were having their last meal together.
 b. PAST John decide that PAST WOLL he say to his mother ~~PAST~~ they be-having their-last-meal-together.
 c. $\llbracket (64\text{-a}) \rrbracket = 1$ iff $\exists t[t < t_c \ \& \ \forall \langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Dox}(J, w_c, t) \rightarrow \exists t''[t'' < t' \ \& \ \exists t''' [t''' > t'' \ \& \ \forall \langle w'', t^4 \rangle \in \text{Say-to-his-mother}(J, w', t''') \rightarrow \text{have}(w'')(t^4)(last \ meal)(they)]]$

The truth conditions in (64-c) allow for a scenario in which John locates himself at a time t^4 , which is compatible with a future time t''' preceding t' . However, John can never tell his mother something before even deciding to do so

The advantage of Ogihara’s theory is that it assumes only one denotation for tenses in English, with vacuous tenses simply being deleted by a structural transformation. The disadvantage, however, is the need to postulate an ad-hoc optional rule.

(iii) *Stowell & Kusumoto’s tense polarity theory*

Stowell (2007), building on his earlier work (Stowell, 1993, 1995, 1996), maintains a syntactic approach to SoT phenomena that accounts for the unexpected *SIM* readings in

³⁴For sake of simplicity I will assume that *decide* involves doxastic alternatives just like belief-verbs.

English without stipulating any restructuring rules.³⁵ Stowell’s theory relates past tense morphemes to polarity items: just as negative polarity items (NPIs) do not have negative meaning but occur in downward-entailing environments within the scope of a licensor, past polarity items (PPIs) do not contribute pastness but must feature within the scope of a past operator. In short, in Stowell’s system, past tense morphemes are hosted by dedicated Zeit Phrases (ZP), are always semantically vacuous, and are only licensed in the scope of a covert semantic past. On this view, past-under-past embeddings can exhibit two structures: one where both T-heads are PAST operators and another where only the matrix T-head hosts PAST.

In (65), the lowest T-head can either host a cover PAST or a covert PRES, since both past tense morphemes are licensed by the matrix PAST. A structure containing PAST in the lower CP will yield *BACK*, the competing structure having PRES head the lower TP will generate *SIM*.

By contrast, present tense morphemes are past *anti-polarity* items (PAI), in that they cannot be in the scope of a covert PAST.

Returning to the breakfast sentences, Stowell’s solution is quite straightforward: the vacuous past tenses embedded under the two attitude verbs are locally c-commanded by PRES, so no back-shifting occurs.

³⁵Syntactically-oriented proposals similar to Stowell’s polarity account include Demirdache & Uribe-Etxebarria (2004), Khomitsevich (2008), and Zagana (2014).

- (66) [[PAST past John decide ... [PRES past WOLL he say ... [PRES past they be-having ...]]]]

However, there are two potential problems with this analysis. Firstly, according to Stowell’s analysis, the two embedded *past* tenses admit a local PAST as their licenser. This correctly predicts the backward-shifted reading when we replace the lowest PRES with PAST, but it encounters the same issue observed in Ogihara’s analysis if the intermediate operator is expressed by PAST. Secondly, there’s a concern with sentences like (63), where a simultaneous reading is not attested. The absence of locality and clause-mate constraints in Stowell’s theory permits PRES in the most embedded clause, as all instances of overt past are already licensed by the matrix PAST. This would incorrectly predict a simultaneous reading. I see no straightforward solution to these two issues.

Building on Stowell’s proposal, Kusumoto (1999, 2005) adopts a polarity theory of tense, offering a semantic implementation of Stowell’s insights. Her proposal can be summarized in two key points:

1. Tense morphemes denote time intervals in the spirit of Partee (1973), saturating the time-argument of the verb. Crucially, they do not impose any presuppositional restriction to the reference time

$$\llbracket \text{pres}_k \rrbracket = g(k);$$

$$\llbracket \text{past}_k \rrbracket = g(k).$$
2. past_k must be locally c-commanded (i.e. no operator PRES must intervene) by a PAST operator, which denotes a restricted existential quantifier.

Once again, the SoT ambiguity is handled at the level of structural ambiguity, as is sketched below.

- (67) a. $[\text{TP PAST} [\text{TP } 2 [\text{T}' \text{past}_2 [\text{VP} \dots [\text{TP PAST} [\text{TP } 3 [\text{T}' \text{past}_3 [\text{VP} \dots]]]]]]]]$
 (BACK)
- b. $[\text{TP PAST} [\text{TP } 2 [\text{T}' \text{past}_2 [\text{VP} \dots [\text{TP } 3 [\text{T}' \text{past}_3 [\text{VP} \dots]]]]]]$
 (SIM)

I will omit the details of Kusumoto’s analysis, as the core of her proposal closely aligns with that of Stowell. What (67) demonstrates is that a simultaneous interpretation corresponds to an LF containing a single semantic PAST, which long-distance binds the embedded tense variable, while a backward-shifted interpretation emerges when tense variables are bound within their local domain.

The advantage of Kusumoto’s theory lies in its sheer simplicity: with a limited set of assumptions, it can easily handle the SoT ambiguity without requiring a dedicated SoT rule. However, this comes at the cost of severely weakening the semantics of past tense morphology, reducing it to a mere placeholder.

(iv) Kauf & Zeijlstra’s Upward Agree theory

Along these lines, Kauf & Zeijlstra (2018)’s derivation of the simultaneous reading relies on morphosyntactic agreement between a past tense operator —denoting a relative past— and the c-commanded clausal tense morphemes. This analysis is couched within the feature-checking framework developed in Zeijlstra (2004), in which tense morphemes

carry uninterpretable tense features that are checked by a tense operator endowed with a matching interpretable feature.³⁶

Contrary to Kusumoto’s approach, in Kauf & Zeijlstra (2018), past tense morphemes are semantically active, as they introduce “no later than” relations, making them compatible with both ongoing and anterior readings. It is thus the past operator carrying an interpretable feature that strengthens the past interpretation of the sentence. As a result, this account derives an interpretation compatible with both simultaneous and backward-shifted contexts from the same LF, as illustrated in (68).

- (68) Jerry said that Elaine was upset.
- a. $[_{CP} Op-Past_{[iPAST]} [_{J} Jerry say-ed_{[uPAST]} [_{CP} Elaine be-ed_{[uPAST]} upset]]]$
 b. $\exists t^4 [t^4 < t_c \ \& \ \exists t'' [t'' \leq t' \ \& \ \forall \langle t''', w' \rangle [t''' \in Say(J, w_c, t'') \rightarrow \exists t^4 [t^4 \leq t''' \ \& \ Elaine \text{ is upset in } w' \text{ at } t^4]]]]$

For t^4 before the attitude time t''' , the truth-conditions in (68-b) are compatible with a *BACK*-context, while $t^4 = t'''$ verifies a *SIM*-scenario.

Interestingly, Kauf & Zeijlstra (2018)’s approach does not consider SoT sentences in English to be ambiguous in the first place. This underspecification view sets the account apart from all other structural approaches discussed in this section. In fact, it brings it closer to the aspectual-pragmatic accounts that I will discuss in section 2.6.2. This view comes with a possible downside: the semantics of past tense morphology is once again weakened. However, it has the clear advantage of linking SoT to more general principles of agreement, thereby avoiding the need to stipulate an ad hoc rule to derive null readings. Moreover, unlike Kusumoto’s approach, it does so without eliminating the semantic distinction between present and past.

(v) *Kratzer’s zero tense theory*

The structural accounts reviewed so far share one important assumption: at some level of their semantic representation, tense is taken to involve existential quantification over times. Departing from this view, Kratzer (1998)’s approach to SoT adopts a strictly pronominal analysis of tense in attitude reports. Extending Partee’s seminal analogy, Kratzer notes that tenses, just like pronouns, can serve as zero variables. Specifically, Kratzer shows that the indexical component of deictic pronouns is exceptionally suspended when these are embedded under certain operators. This is illustrated in (69).

- (69) Only I drove a car that I liked.

Sentences like (69) give rise to two readings, a sloppy reading — ‘no one happened to drive a car that he liked’ — and a strict reading - ‘no one drove a car that the speaker liked’. While the strict reading correlates with an indexical interpretation of the first person pronoun ‘I’, the sloppy reading does not.

- (70) a. $\llbracket (69)_{Sloppy} \rrbracket = 1 \text{ iff } \nexists x [drive(car(y))(x) \ \& \ like(y)(x)]$
 b. $\llbracket (69)_{Strict} \rrbracket = 1 \text{ iff } \nexists x [drive(car(y))(x) \ \& \ like(y)(Speaker)]$

³⁶This analysis of agreement assumes that multiple probes can stand in an agreement relation with an upward goal, as outlined in Zeijlstra (2012). For a similar approach, see also Grønn & Von Stechow, 2010; von Stechow, 2009.

Under the sloppy reading in (70-a), the indexicality of the pronoun becomes *invisible* to semantic composition, and a bound-variable interpretation obtains.

According to Kratzer, the SoT ‘null’ reading of past-under-past is reminiscent of sloppy readings of indexicals. Indeed, the presuppositional content of the embedded pronominal tense is suspended in a similar licensing configuration. Semantically, zero tenses surface as bound variables, thus yielding a derivation which is akin to that driven by tense deletion (Ogihara, 1995) or temporal polarity (Kusumoto, 1999; Stowell, 2007). However, in contrast to deletion approaches, but in alignment with polarity accounts, zero tenses are born without any tense features. Nonetheless, at PF level (that is, in the phonological component of the computational system), zero tenses may acquire their morphological shape through an agreement-based feature-transmission mechanism.

Under this approach, a simultaneous interpretation is derived as given in (71).

- (71) a. $[_{\text{TP}} \text{past}_2 \text{ Jerry say } [_{\text{TP}} 3 \text{ that } [_{\text{TP}} \emptyset_3 \text{ Elaine be-upset }]]]$
 b. $\llbracket (71\text{-a}) \rrbracket$ is defined iff $g(2) < t_c$
 $\llbracket (71\text{-a}) \rrbracket = 1$ iff $\forall \langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Say}(J, w_c, g(2)) \rightarrow \text{upset}(w')(t')(E)$

The embedded tense in (71-a) surfaces as the zero tense \emptyset_3 , bound by the local intensional binder. The insertion of a co-indexed binder generates a property of times, thus yielding the desired meaning in (71-b).

One key asset of this analysis is the neutralization of the pronominal tense’s presupposition. The fact that in an SoT configuration the embedded tense’s reference need not be restricted to times before t_c allows for the derivation of genuine null readings even in breakfast contexts (see (72)) and for permanent states of affairs.

- (72) $[_{\text{TP}} \text{past}_1 \text{ John decide a-week-ago } [_{\text{TP}} 2 \text{ that in-ten-days at-breakfast he } \emptyset_2 \text{ WOLL say to his mother } [_{\text{TP}} 3 \text{ that } \emptyset_3 \text{ they be-having their last meal together}]]]$.

The two embedded zero tenses in (72) are semantically vacuous, thus leading to no presupposition failure when a simultaneous interpretation obtains under local binding.³⁷

Semantically, the result is a *de se* interpretation of the embedded (zero) tense. This, in turn, only generates a simultaneous reading. For the backward-shifted interpretation, Kratzer suggests that the English past simple may occasionally spell out a perfect aspect instead of a pronominal past tense.³⁸ Reasons to assume a perfect-like analysis of the English simple past must be ascribed to indefinite uses, such as the one given in (73) (Kratzer, 1998, p. 106).

- (73) Who built this church?

When uttered out of the blue, the question in (73) cannot be evaluated with respect to

³⁷Morpho-phonologically, zero tenses surface as past/present tenses due to a feature transmission mechanism. In short, whenever at PF a T-head lacks tense features, the computational system probes the structure in search of the closest c-commanding T-head carrying interpretable tense-features. Features are then transmitted to the closest c-commanded binder and then pasted onto the T-head under binding (for details, see Kratzer, 2009).

³⁸While it may seem conceptually unappealing for a tense form to denote aspect, in Kratzer’s system aspect-heads undergo V/Asp-to-T movement, thus adjoining to a tense node. In essence, what surfaces as a tense phonologically/morpho-syntactically, from a semantic standpoint is categorically flexible.

any salient reference time. Kratzer argues that in these instances, the simple past behaves like a perfect aspect, whose denotation resembles that of a relative past (see (74)).

$$(74) \quad \text{Kratzer's perfect aspect} \quad (\text{after Kratzer, 1998, p. 107}). \\ \llbracket \text{PRF} \rrbracket = \lambda p_{\langle s, \langle i, t \rangle \rangle} . \lambda w_s . \lambda t_{\langle t \rangle} . \exists e [\tau(e) < t \ \& \ p(w)(t)]$$

Assuming the semantics in (74) for the embedded past tense, the backward-shifted interpretation is derived as follows.³⁹

$$(75) \quad \text{Jerry said that Elaine was upset.} \\ \text{a. } \llbracket \text{past}_3 \text{ Jerry say [that PERF Elaine be-upset]} \rrbracket \\ \text{b. } \forall \langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Say}(J, w_c, g(3): g(3) < t_c) \rightarrow \exists e [\tau(e) < t' \ \& \ \text{Elaine is upset throughout } \tau(e).]$$

Kratzer's account captures the SoT ambiguity while treating tenses as pronominal. Although her feature-transmission mechanism at PF may resemble alternative formulations found in tense agreement analyses,⁴⁰ the novelty of her approach lies in its ability to derive the intended interpretations in embedded contexts from the intrinsic semantic properties of tense forms.⁴¹ Moreover, Kratzer's feature-transmission mechanism — like the agreement-based approach proposed by Kauf & Zeijlstra (2018) — is not stipulative in nature, as it reflects a more general property of pronominal expressions: their ability to function as semantic zeroes.

Potential challenges to structural approaches

Despite their popularity, purely morpho-syntactic implementations of the SoT rule face several challenges, which have often been neglected in the literature. In what follows, I offer a critical discussion of some of these issues, proposing possible amendments.

(i) Non-tense SoT triggers

The structural accounts we have seen so far differ from one another in how they engineer the licensing relation between the matrix and the embedded tense. This may involve an agreement or concord relation, as well as a deletion or a feature transmission mechanism. However, most of these accounts remain vague regarding the nature of the licenser, i.e. the element that triggers Sequence of Tense. While this is fairly transparent in the case of a simple past embedded under simple past — where both tense markers exhibit matching past tense “-ed” morphology — it is less obvious for other past-oriented forms.

Specifically, Ogihara (1996) discusses examples where SoT may be triggered even by a perfect. The relevant examples are given in (76) (Ogihara, 1996, p. 131).

$$(76) \quad \text{Past-under-perfect embeddings}$$

³⁹For simplicity, the presupposition of the matrix pronominal past is indicated in the truth-conditions as a restriction on its reference time $g(3)$, following the colon symbol.

⁴⁰Setting aside certain important differences, similar approaches that rely on a feature-transmission mechanism include Abusch, 1988; Heim, 1994; Schlenker, 1999.

⁴¹As we will see in the remainder of this thesis, this point is often overlooked in the literature, as SoT accounts too frequently rely on a priori stipulations about whether a tense form is pronominal or quantificational.

- a. John believes Mary to **have claimed** that she **was** innocent.
 \rightsquigarrow ‘Mary according to John: “I am innocent”’ (SIM)
- b. **Having realized** that she **was** in the wrong, Mary is now trying to change.
 \rightsquigarrow ‘Mary: “I am in the wrong”’ (SIM)

In (76), a null reading obtains although in both sentences the superordinate predicate is not inflected with past tense morphology.

While one could claim that the morphology of the two participles in (76) resembles that of the simple past — it is indeed homophonous —, it is harder to explain why similar interpretations are attested even in clausal complements of NPs. This is illustrated in (77) (Ogihara, 1996, p. 132).

(77) *Past-under-NP embeddings*

- a. **John’s (earlier) claim** that he **was** innocent is well known.
- b. I still recall **John’s public announcement** that he **had** cancer.

In (77), the embedded past tense is licensed by the bold-faced NP.

While the perfects in (76) as well as the NPs in (77) can serve as SoT triggers despite the absence of past tense morphology, both display a past temporal orientation. Clearly, eventuality-denoting nouns like “claim” and “announcement” have a strong temporal connotation.

In light of these facts, Ogihara has to concede that a purely morpho-syntactic rule come short of explaining the full empirical picture. Thus, he ultimately revises the SoT rule in (59) as follows (after Ogihara, 1996, p. 134):

(78) **SoT rule (definitive version):**

- a. If a tense feature α is locally c-commanded by another tense feature β at LF and α and β are occurrences of the same feature (i.e., either [+pres] or [+past]), α is optionally deleted:
- b. *Further specifications:*
- (i) The tense features include [+past] and [+pres] and nothing else.
 - (ii) A tense feature α is in the scope of a tense feature β iff β is associated with a common noun and asymmetrically c-commands α , or β is associated with a tense or a perfect and asymmetrically c-commands α .
 - (iii) A tense feature β is the local tense feature of a tense feature α iff α is in the scope of β and there is no tense feature γ in the scope of β such that α is in the scope of γ .

The SoT rule in (78) governs tense deletion via the same mechanism illustrated in earlier formulations of the rule. Compared to its predecessor in (59), the revised version refers to tense *features* rather than overt tense *morphemes*. Following Ogihara, I understand tense features to encompass both morpho-syntactic and abstract semantic features indicating the temporal orientation of a syntactic head — potentially extending beyond T-heads, as we have seen.

By incorporating non-tense triggers, Ogihara’s version of the SoT rule offers a more comprehensive account than strictly morpho-syntactic approaches, capturing null readings in non-canonical SoT configurations. However, its broader scope comes at a potential cost:

the looser formulation risks overgenerating unattested interpretations.

(ii) *Analytical tense forms*

SoT triggers involving analytical tense forms pose an obvious challenge to structural accounts, as they comprise more than one potential licenser within the same verbal complex. This becomes problematic when, although the two components of the SoT trigger do not match in tense features, the licensee shows no optionality in tense marking. One good example is the ever elusive present perfect (see (79)).

- (79) Jerry has claimed that he was sick. (BACK / SIM)
 SIM-Par: ‘Jerry (at some point): “I’m sick”’

The sentence in (79) displays the same SoT ambiguity observed for canonical past-under-past embeddings. Yet, the matrix tense forms involves a present tense alongside a perfect aspect. The licensing of a vacuous embedded past (on a simultaneous reading) obtains under Ogihara’s SoT rule, given that perfects may surface with [+past] features. However, the presence of a present tense seems to predict that SoT readings should arise even for present-under-present perfect embeddings, contrary to facts (see (81)).

- (80) (81) Jerry has claimed that he is sick. (DAR / #SIM)
 #SIM-Par: ‘Jerry (at some point): “I’m sick”’

These data are even more challenging when looking at languages other West-Germanic languages or at Romance languages, where the present perfect behaves essentially like a past tense and can freely license SoT in the embedded clause (see also chapter 5. One way to explain these data is to assume that, despite its superficial present tense morphology, the present perfect projects exclusively [+past] features. This stipulations seems to run against odds when the same form appears in the complement clause, as (82) illustrates.

- (82) Context: Jerry had already been sick for three days when he informed Elaine last Tuesday.
 a. Jerry told Elaine that he ??has/had been sick for three days.

The absence of a null reading for the present perfect in (81) suggests that the present tense is actively obstructing the agreement relation between the past-tensed attitude verb and the embedded perfect. Thus, we should conclude that the present tense must carry non-past/present features. This has also the welcome consequence of correctly capturing simultaneous readings for the present perfect-under-future embeddings.

- (83) Tonight Jerry will say that he has already eaten.
 a. BACK-Par: ‘Jerry (tonight): “I have already eaten”’

The availability in (83) of a relative backward-shifted interpretation signals that the embedded present’s indexicality may be erased under SoT licensing (i.e., due to a superordinate present-tensed future).

This brief discussion of the present perfect in SoT environments points toward a more flexible system, where a single analytical tense form may be specified with both [+past] and [+present] features. For English, the observed interpretive variation of the present

perfect results from two factors: the fixed inflectional hierarchy between tense and aspect, and the variable LF position of the present perfect. The resulting generalization can be characterized as follows: the present perfect can serve as a trigger for licensing past morphology, but can only have its present tense feature licensed when it functions as a licensee.

(iii) *Aspectual asymmetries in the licensee*

A major criticism of structural theories is their difficulty in explaining why SoT readings in English are largely limited to stative or progressive predicates. This asymmetry is shown in (84)

- (84) a. Jerry believed that George called him. [eventive; #*SIM/BACK*]
 b. Jerry believed that George was calling him. [eventive, prog; *SIM/BACK*]
 c. Jerry believed that George was sad. [stative; *SIM/BACK*]

While a few attempts have been made to downplay the significance of data such as (84) in the structural literature (cf. Kusumoto, 1999; Sharvit, 2018), the generalization emerging from this aspectual contrast appears to be robust, even cross-linguistically. Since structural accounts all rely on some morpho-syntactic notion of tense agreement, incorporating aspectual features into their theories is far from trivial.

Interim summary: Tense agreement and licensing conditions

To summarize this section, we have examined some of the most prominent structural approaches to Sequence of Tense in close detail. These accounts generally motivate the semantic vacuity of tense morphology in SoT configurations through a structural mechanism based on an agreement relation between a temporal licenser and a c-commanded agreeing licensee. Theories converge in assuming that the temporal licenser is semantically contentful, while they vary as to whether the licensee — typically, the tense morpheme — contributes any semantic content at all and, if so, how specified that content is.

The strength of these accounts lies in the simplicity and elegance of their underlying mechanisms, as well as their ability to connect with broader grammatical phenomena such as agreement and concord. Despite this appeal, one of the main criticisms of these theories is that they struggle to explain why SoT readings in English are mostly confined to stative or progressive predicates. Aspectual-pragmatic accounts, which I turn to next, offer a potential solution to this issue.

2.6.2 Aspectual-pragmatic accounts

Aspectual-pragmatic accounts (APA) along the lines of Altshuler & Schwarzschild (2012) and Gennari (2003) represent a radical departure from the structural accounts discussed so far. While structural approaches to SoT phenomena assume two syntactic structures and derive two distinct readings for SoT configurations in English, APAs argue that there is no ambiguity in the first place: the illusion of a simultaneous reading stems from a weakened backward-shifted interpretation.⁴²

⁴²Recall that Kauf & Zeijlstra (2018) constitute an exception, in that they align with APAs in ruling out an ambiguity at LF.

Gennari's superinterval theory

Gennari (Gennari, 1999b, 2003) observes that Sequence of Tense phenomena only arise with certain aspectual classes. Specifically, simultaneous readings require the presence of embedded stative verbs. By contrast, eventive verbs are only compatible with a backward-shifted reading. See the contrast in (84), repeated below.

- (85) a. Jerry believed that George **called** him. [eventive; #*SIM/BACK*]
 b. Jerry believed that George was calling him. [eventive, prog; *SIM/BACK*]
 c. Jerry believed that George was sad. [stative; *SIM/BACK*]

Gennari demonstrates that only stative (see (85-c)) and progressive predicates (see (85-b)) are compatible with simultaneous readings, owing to their aspectual properties.

Crucially, under Gennari's account, past stative or progressive predicates embedded under past-tense attitude verbs are not genuinely ambiguous between a *SIM* and a *BACK* reading. Rather, they permit a *BACK+SIM* interpretation, in which the embedded state is temporally located prior to the attitude time but may extend forward to overlap with it. In contrast, eventive predicates do not allow for such an extended *BACK+SIM* interpretation and instead yield strictly shifted (*BACK*) readings.

The reason why statives, unlike eventives, allow for *BACK+SIM* readings must be attributed to a special property stative or stativized predicates (such as progressives) possess, which is what Gennari terms the **superinterval property**. This property can be described as follows:⁴³

- (86) *Superinterval property of statives* (adapted from Gennari, 2003, p. 50)
 For any stative predicate p , for any temporal interval t , such that $p(t)$,
 $\exists t_{sup}[t_{sup} \supset t \ \& \ p(t_{sup})]$

The superinterval property in (86) states that, for each stative predicate p and temporal interval t , such that p holds true of t , there is a superinterval t_{sup} that includes t and at which p still holds true. In a way, this property stems from very familiar notions regarding the temporal homogeneity of statives (cf. a.o. Bennett & Partee, 1972; D. Dowty, 1977). The key insight from this theory is that dynamic aspectual classes like eventives denote change of states and, therefore, lack a superinterval property. This is reflected by the fact that event structures, as opposed to states, have discreet boundaries and clear endpoints.

While Gennari doesn't clearly spell-out how the superinterval property affects semantic composition, she maintains that this does not arise pragmatically in the strict sense, but as an inference related to the lexical content of the verb. A possible derivation of a *SIM*-compatible reading (adjusted to this framework), under Gennari's account, is illustrated below. Note that, before computing the superinterval entailment, the generated truth-conditions are identical to those of a backward-shifted reading under Ogihara's analysis.

- (87) Jerry said that Elaine was upset.

⁴³Gennari does not provide a general formulation of the superinterval property but only illustrates how it applies to specific examples.

- a. *Truth-conditions*: $\exists t[t < t_c \ \& \ \forall \langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Say}(J)(w_c)(t) \rightarrow \exists t'[t'' < t' \ \& \ \text{upset}(\mathbf{E})(w')(t'')]]$
- b. *Superinterval inference*: $\exists t[t < t_c \ \& \ \forall \langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Say}(J)(w_c)(t) \rightarrow \exists t'[t'' < t' \ \& \ \exists \mathbf{t}_{sup}[\mathbf{t}_{sup} \supset \mathbf{t}'' \ \& \ \text{upset}(\mathbf{E})(w')(\mathbf{t}_{sup})]]]$

In (87-b), enrichment via the superinterval entailment yields an embedded state that holds over a temporal interval (i.e., \mathbf{t}_{sup}) that properly contains the time t'' , which precedes the attitude time t' . This allows \mathbf{t}_{sup} to extend indefinitely and potentially include t' itself. When this occurs, an overlapping interpretation arises, which supports a simultaneous reading. By contrast, eventive embeddings do not support this additional enrichment step and instead align only with the truth conditions in (87-a), which correspond to a genuinely backward-shifted interpretation.

Notably, the derivation of temporally overlapping readings in this account is independent of the tense in the matrix clause. In principle, overlapping readings should even arise in non-SoT configurations; however, they are typically unattested. To address this potential overgeneration, Gennari proposes that overlapping *BACK+SIM* readings are blocked when a past tense is embedded under a present or future tense, due to competition with the present tense.⁴⁴ Crucially, because of its indexical nature, the present tense does not compete with the past tense in past-tense contexts — hence the availability of simultaneous readings in these configurations.

Gennari's theory has the advantage of integrating different properties of tensed predicates — namely, their aspectual profile and their temporal interpretation in attitude complements — into a theory that transparently explains SoT facts. The downside of this theory is that it does not convincingly rule out unattested simultaneous readings in non-SoT contexts. Since the superinterval property is not pragmatic in nature but rather directly contributes to the truth-conditions of the sentence, it's not clear how it can be blocked under a competition story.

(ii) *Altshuler & Schwarzschild's implicature theory*

In a similar manner, Altshuler & Schwarzschild (2012) (henceforth A&S) rule out the existence of a stand-alone simultaneous reading for past statives embedded under past attitudes. They argue that the simultaneous reading is merely a side-effect resulting from the absence of a pragmatic implicature, leading to an apparent simultaneous reading alongside a true backward-shifted reading.

In line with Gennari's view, A&S claim that SoT phenomena are limited to embedded stative verbs due to their temporal homogeneity.

- (88) Temporal Profile of Statives: (Altshuler & Schwarzschild, 2012, p. 45)
 For any tenseless stative clause ϕ , if ϕ is true at moment m , then there is a moment m' preceding m at which ϕ is true and there is a moment m'' following m at which ϕ is true.

Given (88), statives, as opposed to eventives, do not involve a moment indicating a change of state. This assumption accounts for what A&S refer to as *cessation*. This scalar

⁴⁴Gennari discusses this issue only in relation to matrix clauses. However, I suggest that the same reasoning applies to embedded contexts as well.

implicature arises whenever a stronger statement could have been made, but a weaker one was made instead. In this case, the stronger statement corresponds to one containing a present tense, while a weak statement correlates with a past tense. This follows from A&S’s semantics of the English present in (89) and the temporal profile of statives in (88).

$$(89) \quad \text{PRES}(\phi)(t_c) = 1 \text{ iff } \exists m_i[m \subseteq t_c \ \& \ \phi(m) = 1]$$

From (88), we derive:

$$(90) \quad \exists m'_i[m' < m \ \& \ \phi(m') = 1]$$

The expression in (90) shows that a present tense entails a past tense, given that present states may hold true of moments immediately preceding t_c . A&S conclude that *PRES* is a stronger statement compared to *PAST*, in that *PRES* asymmetrically entails *PAST*.

To illustrate why a cessation implicature arises when the past tense is used in place of the present, consider the following scenario (after A&S):

- (91) a. George: ‘How is Elaine doing?’
 b. Jerry: ‘She was upset’
 \rightsquigarrow Elaine is not upset at t_c

In (91), George’s present-tensed question sets the reference time at t_c . Jerry’s use of the past tense leads George to infer that Elaine is no longer upset at t_c . Had Elaine still been upset, Jerry would have more appropriately used the present tense, which constitutes a stronger statement and more directly answers George’s question. George thus computes a cessation implicature: from the tense mismatch between question and answer, he concludes that the relevant state — Elaine being upset — has ceased to hold.

By contrast, a cessation implicature is not triggered when answer and question match in tense (see (92)).

- (92) (A&S, p. 48, after Klein, 1994)
 a. Judge: ‘What did you see when you opened the door?’
 b. Witness: ‘There was a book on the table. **It was Russian**’
 $\not\rightsquigarrow$ The book is not Russian at t_c

The contrast between (91) and (92) is due to the different reference times set by the question in the two contexts (see (93)).

- (93) a. $C_{(91)} = \{t: t \text{ surrounds } t_c\}$
 b. $C_{(92)} = \{t: t \text{ is part of the whole visit of the addressee after opening the door}\}$

Recall that, under a quantificational approach to tense, context-dependent variables such as $C_{(91)}$ and $C_{(92)}$, may restrict the domain of quantification of the tense. Following (89), the present tense is further restricted to times included in the utterance time t_c . This indexical condition is compatible with (93-a), but not with (93-b) (the time of the hearer’s visit strictly precedes t_c). As a result, the present tense is not a viable alternative to the

past tense in contexts like (92), where the topic time — i.e., the time under discussion (or reference time) — is located in the past. Consequently, no cessation implicature can be computed in such cases.

A&S extend this analysis to attitude reports in English, as illustrated in (94). In embedded contexts, in the absence of an overt adverbial in the complement clause, the topic time is supplied by the matrix clause — specifically, a temporal interval during which the attitude holder formed their belief (i.e., the attitude time).

- (94) Context: Yesterday, George stopped by Kramer’s place to say hello. Kramer, however, looked pale and couldn’t stop coughing and sneezing.
- a. George believed **that Kramer was sick**.
 - b. George $PAST_{C_1}$ believe that Kramer $PAST_{C_1}$ be-sick.
 $C_1 = \{t: t \text{ is part of George’s visit to Kramer yesterday, during which Kramer showed symptoms of illness.}\}$

As previously observed for (92), a past-oriented reference time like C_1 in (94-b) rules out present tense alternatives (see (95)), since C_1 includes only times that strictly precede t_c . This is illustrated in (95).

- (95) a. George believed **that Kramer is sick**.
 b. George $PAST_{C_1}$ believe that Kramer $PRES_{\#C_1/C_2}$ be sick.
 $C_2 = \{t: t \text{ surrounds } t_c\}$

As a result, no cessation inference can be computed from (94). If past statives under past-tensed attitudes do not give rise to an inference of cessation, nothing prevents the embedded state from stretching forward, giving the *illusion* of a simultaneous interpretation. This point reveals a key difference to Gennari’s account. Although the two theories are rooted in similar theoretical assumptions, temporal overlap in Gennari is semantically derived from the superinterval property. In A&S, this is a mere pragmatic illusion.

Altshuler & Schwarzschild (2012)’s theory hinges on the temporal profile of statives and the deictic nature of present tense in English. One cross-linguistic prediction of this theory is that languages with a relative present exhibit a systematic competition between present and past in attitude embeddings. These languages are therefore expected to express *SIM*-readings only with an embedded present, as temporal overlap for the embedded past would always be blocked by a cessation implicature. We will see in section 2.7 that this seems to be the case of Japanese and other ‘non-SoT languages’. From this perspective, A&S has the remarkable merit of providing a principled explanation of tense semantic variation, without resorting to language-specific rules or mechanisms in the spirit of structural approaches.⁴⁵

With this in mind, the obvious drawback of aspectual-pragmatic theories is their weakening of the SoT ambiguity. In particular, the lack of a genuine simultaneous interpretation, especially in Altshuler & Schwarzschild (2012), is problematic in light of SoT patterns in Romance languages (see chapters 4 and 5), where simultaneity appears to be the default interpretation for past-under-past. It is rather peculiar that the most natural

⁴⁵However, we will see in the remainder of this thesis that the cross-linguistic picture shows a higher complexity than what expected under an implicature-based theory.

reading is a semantic illusion. Moreover, cross-linguistic investigations have revealed that simultaneous interpretations are available for past-under-past even in languages with a relative present (cf. Grønn & Von Stechow, 2010; Khomitsevich, 2008; Ogihara & Sharvit, 2012, this thesis).

The weakening of the simultaneous interpretation is especially evident for attitude complements that contain atemporal i-level predicates, i.e. predicates whose truth is independent of a specific temporal interval (see also section 2.5.3). Consider the example in (96).

- (96) Kramer believed that 9 was a prime number.
 a. *ASA's paraphrase*: Kramer: '9 was a prime number and still is/might still be.'

A paraphrase of the ASA-generated simultaneous reading is given in (96-a). For (96), Gennari's theory would derive a *BACK+SIM* reading which can be paraphrased as '9 was a prime number and still is a prime number.' — a reading that is, at best, odd. The interpretation derived under A&S is similarly weak, amounting to something like "9 was a prime number and might still be." This points to a critical challenge for both accounts: while their stativity-based explanations may plausibly capture *SIM*-readings with stage-level predicates, it is unclear how they handle null readings of individual-level predicates, especially those expressing atemporal or permanent properties. For such predicates, the idea of extending — or even merely *appearing* to extend — a temporal interval from an earlier time is nonsensical.

These theoretical concerns have been supported by recent typological and experimental work, which has also cast doubt on the validity of implicature-based accounts of Sequence of Tense.⁴⁶ In particular, Mucha et al. (2023) show that in a non-SoT language like Polish, the cessation implicature in SoT configurations is not sensitive to monotonicity — contrary to what is expected of scalar implicatures. Specifically, in an inference task experiment, interpretations of past-under-past embeddings did not yield stronger cessation inferences in positive contexts compared to negative ones. This suggests that the unavailability of simultaneous readings cannot plausibly be attributed to a pragmatic inference.⁴⁷

(iii) *Portner's hybrid structural-aspectual approach*

Despite its shortcomings, can a pragmatic-aspectual account still be rescued? An interesting — though often overlooked — attempt to unify structural and aspectual-pragmatic approaches is offered by Portner (2003).⁴⁸ Portner proposes that an Ogiharean deletion-like mechanism is obligatory in English. As a result, the temporal interpretation of the tenseless embedded clause is determined solely by its aspectual profile, in accordance with general principles of temporal relations in discourse (cf. a.o. Kamp & Rohrer, 1983). More specifically, with eventive complements, the event time must precede the reference time (i.e., the matrix attitude time, after deletion has applied). In contrast, stative comple-

⁴⁶For additional empirical and theoretical arguments against pragmatic theories, see also Kusumoto, 1999; Sharvit, 2018.

⁴⁷In fact, Mucha et al. (2023) found no clear evidence that speakers even endorse the cessation inference.

⁴⁸Note that Portner is primarily concerned with the interpretation of the present perfect in English. The discussion of SoT facts emerges as a byproduct of his theory, which may help explain why it has often been overlooked in the relevant literature.

ments allow the event time to either precede or overlap with the attitude time. This accounts for the observed pattern: eventive predicates are associated only with *BACK* readings, while statives permit both *BACK* and *SIM* interpretations.

2.6.3 The *de re* theory of tense and double access readings

So far, our overview of SoT accounts has largely focused on past-under-past embeddings under a quantificational analysis of the embedded past tense. While we have remained mostly silent on the interpretation of pronominal tenses in attitude contexts, a critical discussion of Kratzer's zero tense theory has revealed a clear challenge in deriving temporally shifted interpretations under a referential analysis of tense.

Generally speaking, as briefly discussed in section 2.5.2, absolute (pronominal) tenses pose a challenge to semantic theory, as on the one hand they resist a *de se/de Dicto* interpretation (i.e., relative to the attitude time); on the other, their free evaluation within intensional contexts clashes with the *de se* semantics of attitude complements. The need for a *de re* analysis of tense is not restricted to the past tense, but especially concerns the interpretation of the English present tense, which is inherently indexical.

Present-under-past in English gives rise to a distinctive interpretation, dubbed 'double access reading' (DAR), which is exemplified as follows.

- (97) Jerry said that Elaine is upset.
 a. 'There is an upset-state of Elaine holding at AT (i.e., the time Jerry spoke) and at UT.'

The rough paraphrase in (97-a) shows that the embedded predicate *upset* in (97) needs to *access* two times: the attitude time and the utterance time. We will see that, while the latter stems from present tense's indexicality, the former is owed to a cognitive constraint named 'Upper Limit Constraint' (ULC). In particular, the indexical component of the interpretation we obtain becomes clearer in the following examples.

- (98) a. Two years ago Mike believed that Claire {#is/was} pregnant.
 b. Lena knew that Whitney Houston #is/was from New Jersey.

Both present-tensed attitude reports in (98) display DAR effects. The unacceptability of the present tense in (98-a) is linked to the implausibility for a pregnancy in humans to last well over nine months. In (98-b), the present tense triggers lifetime effects, given that Whitney Houston is dead at UT.

In her seminal work, Dorit Abusch (Abusch, 1988, 1994, 1997) provides an account of the double access reading of an embedded indexical present, and more generally of the puzzling interpretation of absolute tenses in attitude contexts. She proposes an *extensional* theory of tense that is based on three key assumptions:

- (99) *Abusch's theory of absolute tenses in attitude reports.*
 a. Tenses are referring expressions in the spirit of Partee (1973);
 b. Tenses are evaluated with respect to the utterance time, independently of the syntactic context;
 c. Like nominal referring expressions, tenses can be interpreted *de re*.

Building on Partee’s analogy, the *de re* theory of tense draws on well-known ambiguities associated with referring NPs and pronouns under propositional attitude verbs. Consider Quine (1956)’s famous example:

- (100) Context: *Ralph caught a glimpse of Ortcutt wearing a brown hat and thinks that the man he had so glimpsed is a spy. On a separate occasion he caught a glimpse of Ortcutt in a gray hat, thinking that the man glimpsed in a gray hat is not a spy.*

In this context, Ralph can form apparently conflicting beliefs about Ortcutt, namely:

- (101) a. Ralph believes that Ortcutt is a spy.
 b. Ralph believes that Ortcutt is not a spy.

The apparent contradiction can be overcome when taking into account descriptions of how Ralph, the attitude holder, is acquainted with Ortcutt. These are what Lewis (1979) calls *acquaintance relations*.

Acquaintance relations are established between the attitude holder and the object of the holder’s beliefs, such that the believer can ascribe (even mutually incompatible) properties to that object. Returning to Quine’s example, Ralph can attribute to the object of his beliefs (the man in the brown/gray hat) the property of being/not being a spy, as long as Ralph is unaware of the two men’s identities being the same in the actual world. What should the two acquaintance relations look like in order for the sentences in (101) to hold true?

- (102) a. $\llbracket R_{brown} \rrbracket = g(\text{brown}) = \lambda w_s. \lambda att_e. \lambda z_e. att \text{ glimpsed } z \text{ in a brown hat in } w.$
 b. $\llbracket R_{gray} \rrbracket = g(\text{gray}) = \lambda w_s. \lambda att_e. \lambda z_e. att \text{ glimpsed } z \text{ in a gray hat in } w.$

The predicted truth-conditions for (101) can be paraphrased as follows:

- (103) a. $Par(101-a)$: ‘Ralph believed of the man glimpsed in a brown hat to be a spy.’
 b. $Par(101-b)$: ‘Ralph believed of the man glimpsed in a gray hat not to be a spy.’

In order to capture the meaning of (101-a), Abusch adds two more ingredients: a revised LF of attitude context where the embedded DP has undergone *res-movement* and a revised semantics for the attitude verb.⁴⁹

As exemplified by the paraphrases in (103), the object of belief composes directly with the attitude verb. This is achieved through movement of the individual *res* (that is the individual denoted by the DP interpreted *de re*) from its base position to an internal argument position of the attitude verb. Thanks to this peculiar operation known as *res-movement*, the object of belief, may escape binding of a local intensional λ -abstractor and be interpreted in an extensional position.

⁴⁹The version of a *de re* analysis does not adhere to that proposed in Abusch’s work, but draws on several subsequent attempts to formalize her theory (cf. a.o. Heim, 1994; von Stechow, 1994).

To keep track of the relation between the *res* and the attitude holder, acquaintance relations are incorporated in the semantics of the attitude verb as the free variable R^{50} . The revised denotation of *believe*, under a *de re* analysis, is given in (104).

$$(104) \quad \llbracket \text{believe}_{deRe} \rrbracket = \lambda w_s. \lambda R_{\langle s, \langle e, \langle e, t \rangle \rangle} \cdot \lambda Res_e. \lambda p_{\langle s, \langle e, t \rangle \rangle} \cdot \lambda att_e. Res = \iota z_e [R(w)(att)(z)] \\ \& \forall w' \in \text{Dox}(att, w) \rightarrow p(w')(\iota z [R(w')(att)(z)])$$

Res-movement of the embedded DP produces for (101-a) the structure in (105-a), whose meaning is computed in (105-b).

(105) a.

b. $\llbracket (101\text{-a}) \rrbracket = 1$ iff $\text{Ortcutt} = \iota z [g(\text{brown})(w_c) (\text{Ralph})(z)] \& \forall w' \in \text{Dox}(\text{Ralph}, w_c) \rightarrow \text{spy}(w')(\iota z [g(\text{brown})(w')(\text{Ralph})(z)])$.

The truth-conditions in (105-b) assert that for all worlds compatible with Ralph's beliefs, the individual z that stands in an acquaintance relation $g(\text{brown})$ with Ralph is a spy. Applying the relation in (102-a) to $g(\text{brown})$, we obtain that the predicate *spy* is true in the belief-worlds w' of the individual z in a brown hat that Ralph glimpsed in w' . This ensures that Ralph ascribes the property of being a spy to the $g(\text{brown})$ -described man rather than to the one he knows to be Ortcutt. However, the restriction ' $\text{Ortcutt} = \iota z [R(w_c)(\text{Ralph})(z)]$ ' guarantees that the individual *res* is evaluated with respect to the actual world.

Turning now to the *de re* interpretation of embedded tense, consider the present-under-

⁵⁰For clarity of exposition, I will omit for the moment variables that are not crucial for the interpretation of (101-a).

past sentence in (97), repeated below in the given context.

- (106) Context: *Elaine is upset with her friends because they forgot her birthday. A few days ago, Jerry finally realized this after Elaine stood him up at a dinner party. He told George, “She is upset.” Now, Kramer is trying to reach her, but she won’t pick up the phone. He wonders what happened, George tells him:*
- a. Jerry said that Elaine is upset.

Sentence (106-a) receives a double access interpretation, according to which the state of Elaine being upset holds of an earlier time compatible with Jerry’s statement as well as at the utterance time. Importantly, sentence (106-a) cannot be used to report a future-oriented statement like ‘Elaine is going to be upset’. Furthermore, this embedded state cannot be anchored to UT in the attitude worlds either. In other words, Jerry could not have said: ‘Elaine is upset now and she will be upset in a few days’. For all he knows, Elaine might be no longer upset.⁵¹ The impossibility of forward-shifted interpretations (*FORW*) for present-under-past embeddings are not an isolated case. Indeed, they are commonly found in past-tensed embeddings as well (see (107)).

- (107) #Two days ago George believed that Kramer was sick yesterday.

Sentence (107) cannot receive a forward-shifted interpretation, even if the embedded past tense is interpreted relative to the utterance time. While this restriction is trivially explained in the case of Ogihara-style relative tenses, it is less easy to account for under an absolute tense analysis. These observations led Abusch to postulate an upper limit constraint, as given in (108).

- (108) *Upper Limit Constraint (ULC):*
The now of an epistemic alternative is an upper limit for the reference of tenses. (Abusch, 1994, p. 110)

Following the *ULC* in (108), a tense’s reference time cannot extend beyond the local EvalT, which is expressed by the attitude time in attitude contexts. This constraint explains the absence of forward-shifted readings for sentences such as (107) and (106-a).

More importantly, the *ULC*, combined with the indexical nature of the English present tense, offers a clear solution to the observed double access reading. If the temporal interval t denoted by the present tense cannot strictly follow the attitude time t' (due to the *ULC*), and must include t_c (due to the present tense’s indexicality), then t must encompass both t' and t_c .

The *de re* semantics of attitude verbs is revised to accommodate temporal *res* arguments. Furthermore, I follow Heim (1994, p. 149) in formalizing the *ULC* in terms of a presuppositional constraint on embedded tenses (see (109)).

- (109) If α_k is a tense and t' is its local EvalT, then $\llbracket \alpha_k \rrbracket^{g,c}$ is only defined if $\neg g(i) > t'$.

⁵¹The semantic nuances of the double access reading will be explored in greater detail in Chapter 4, when we discuss the relevant interpretation for Italian present-under-past.

For the *ULC* to operate, the *EvalT* is made compositionally accessible in the complement clause. Therefore, the new type of the embedded proposition is $\langle s, \langle i, \langle i, t \rangle \rangle \rangle$.⁵² The resulting denotation for *say* is given in (110).

$$(110) \quad \llbracket \text{say}_{tempdeRe} \rrbracket = \lambda w_s \cdot \lambda t_{Refi} \cdot \lambda R_{\langle s, \langle i, \langle i, t \rangle \rangle} \cdot \lambda t_{Resi} \cdot \lambda p_{\langle s, \langle i, t \rangle \rangle} \cdot \lambda x_e \cdot t_{Res} = \iota z [\mathbb{R}(w)(t_{Ref})(z)] \\ \& \forall \langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Say}(x, w, t_{Ref}) \rightarrow p(w')(t')(\iota z [\mathbb{R}(w')(t')(z)])$$

In the following, I break down the revised semantics for the attitude verb under a temporal *de re* analysis.

- (111)
- | | |
|--|--|
| λw_s : | the world of evaluation (w_c , in matrix) |
| λt_{Refi} : | the RT supplied by tense |
| $\lambda R_{\langle s, \langle i, \langle i, t \rangle \rangle}$: | the acquaintance relation |
| λt_{Resi} : | the temporal res |
| $\lambda p_{\langle s, \langle i, \langle i, t \rangle \rangle}$: | the attitude complement |
| λx_e : | the attitude holder |

Armed with this formal tools, we derive the double access reading for (106-a) from the LF in (112). In line with Abusch and Heim’s proposals, I adopt a pronominal analysis of tense.

In (112), the indexical present tense has been *res*-moved into an argument position of the

⁵²Alternatively, the *ULC* can be built into the acquaintance relation. This is the approach pursued in Bochnak et al., 2019.

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matrix verb, out of the scope of the local EvalT binder ‘ λt_{Eval} ’. Here it can be assigned a value through the context-sensitive function g . A suitable acquaintance relation for the context in (106) is given in (113). The meaning of the sentence is computed accordingly.

(113) $\llbracket R_{25} \rrbracket = g(25) = \lambda w. \lambda t_{Ref}. \lambda z. z$ is the temporal interval that is ongoing at t and throughout which Elaine is unreachable in w .

(114) *Denotation of the embedded CP:*
 $\llbracket CP_{\langle s, \langle i, \langle i, t \rangle \rangle} \rrbracket = \lambda w. \lambda t'. \lambda t. \neg t > t'. upset(w)(t)(E)$

(115) *Definedness conditions of (112):*
 $\llbracket (112) \rrbracket$ defined iff
 $g(2) < t_c \ \& \ \boxed{g(4) \supseteq t_c} \ \& \ \boxed{\forall \langle w', t' \rangle \in Say(J, w_c, g(2)) \rightarrow \neg \iota z [g(25)(w')(t')(z)] > t'}$

(116) *Truth-conditions of (112):*
 $(112) = 1$ iff
 $g(4) = \iota z [g(25)(w_c)(g(2))(z)] \ \& \ \forall \langle w', t' \rangle \in Say(J, w_c, g(2)) \rightarrow upset(w')(\iota z [g(25)(w')(t')(z)])(E)$

The definedness conditions in (115) include two key framed restrictions on the temporal res $g(4)$: its inclusion of the utterance time (via $pres_4$'s presupposition) and the its impossibility to follow the attitude time t' (via the *ULC*). By construction, $g(4)$ equals a time that holds throughout Elaine's absence (via R_{25}). This temporal interval, if defined, necessarily includes t_c and t' . A double access reading obtains.

The *de re* theory outlined here can be successfully extended to pronominal past tenses that receive an absolute interpretation. This is illustrated for (117).

(117) George **believed** that Kramer **was** sick.
 a. George believed: ‘Kramer is sick’. (*SIM*)
 b. George believed: ‘Kramer was sick’. (*BACK*)

As exemplified by the two paraphrases above, (117) is ambiguous between a *SIM* and a *BACK* reading. The beauty of Abusch's *de re* theory lies in the possibility of capturing both readings based on the particular acquaintance relation the context provides.

(118) a. $\llbracket R_{Sim} \rrbracket = g(Sim) = \lambda w_s. \lambda t. \lambda z. z$ is the interval of time covering the whole state of health **surrounding** t in w .
 b. $\llbracket R_{Back} \rrbracket = g(Back) = \lambda w_s. \lambda t. \lambda z. z$ is the interval of time covering the whole state of health **preceding** t in w .

Similarly to our previous case, the embedded past tense undergoes *res*-movement, thus being interpreted from an extensional position, as illustrated in (119)

As a key observation, the structure for the two interpretation is the same, except for the relation picked out by the variable R . For R_{Sim} , the system yields the simultaneous reading in (120). For R_{Back} , semantic derivations lead to the backward-shifted interpretation in (121).

- (120) a. $\llbracket (119) \rrbracket_{SIM}$ is defined iff $g(2) < t_c \ \& \ g(4) < t_c \ \& \ \neg \iota z[g(\text{Sim})(w')(t')(z)] > t'$
 b. When defined, $\llbracket (119) \rrbracket_{SIM} = 1$
 $g(4) = \iota z[g(\text{Sim})(w_c)(g(2))(z)] \ \& \ \forall \langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Dox}(G, w_c, g(2)) \rightarrow$
 $sick(w')(\iota z[g(\text{Sim})(w')(t')(z)])(K)$
- (121) a. $\llbracket (119) \rrbracket_{BACK}$ is defined iff $g(2) < t_c \ \& \ g(4) < t_c \ \& \ \neg \iota z[g(\text{Back})(w')(t')(z)] > t'$
 b. When defined, $\llbracket (119) \rrbracket_{BACK} = 1$ iff
 $g(4) = \iota z[g(\text{Back})(w_c)(g(2))(z)] \ \& \ \forall \langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Dox}(G, w_c, g(2)) \rightarrow$
 $sick(w')(\iota z[g(\text{Back})(w')(t')(z)])(K)$

The truth-conditions are identical, except for the sort of acquaintance relating the temporal res to the attitude holder.

This analysis, however, is not without problems. It relies on a unique instance of syntactic transformation targeting a theta-position, typically seen as a starting point rather than a destination for movement. Additionally, *res*-movement does not create a standard binding chain: it neither leaves a trace nor generates a λ -binder immediately

below its landing site.

Fortunately, alternative *de re* theories use acquaintance-based descriptions that can access the *res* without moving it out of its intensional position (Charlow & Sharvit, 2014; Percus & Sauerland, 2003; Sharvit, 2018). These theories generate suitable concepts (i.e., descriptions of acquaintance) directly within the complement clause. However, this comes at the cost of increasing the internal complexity of embedded tenses. This analytic alternative is explored in chapters 3 and 4.

Irrespective of its formal implementation, acquaintance-based accounts come short of explaining the full range of SoT phenomena. While they can handle the availability of simultaneous readings in past contexts, the derivation genuine null readings under this approach is notoriously challenging. Consider once more the breakfast sentence in (122).

- (122) a. John decided a week ago that in ten days at breakfast he would say to his mother that they were having their last meal together.
 b. John past_1 decide a week ago that in-ten-days at-breakfast he past_2 WOLL say $_3$ to his mother that past_3 they be-having their last meal together.
 c. \llbracket (122-b) \rrbracket defined iff $g(1) < t_c \ \& \ g(2) < t_c \ \& \ g(3) < t_c$

Under a *de re* theory, each past tense in (122-b) denotes a time preceding t_c (see (122-c)). Clearly, these definedness conditions conflict with the later-than-now reference of the most-embedded tense under a simultaneous interpretation.

The *de re* theory also fails for reports of permanent states of affairs (see (123)).

- (123) John believed that 9 was a prime number.

(123) does not convey that John is acquainted with a specific past time at which 9 was a prime number.

Observations like these led Abusch to advocate for the co-existence of an SoT theory alongside a *de re* one, a position strongly defended in more recent work (Bochnak et al., 2019; Grønn & Von Stechow, 2010; Ogihara & Sharvit, 2012; Sharvit, 2018).

2.6.4 A tense agreement + *de re* theory

The discussion in this section suggests that a comprehensive account of embedded tense in English requires both a tense agreement mechanism and a *de re* theory. On the one hand, indexical tenses such as the present clearly pattern with a *de re* interpretation. On the other hand, this analysis alone is insufficient to explain SoT effects, particularly in past-under-past contexts. For these, a *de se* account is needed — one that can erase the temporal contribution of the embedded tense.

Looking at English, an interesting pattern emerges: regardless of whether the embedded tense is interpreted pronominally or quantificationally, present tense must be interpreted *de re*, whereas past tense may be interpreted *de se*. This raises the question: can the English present ever be interpreted *de se*? While this is generally ruled out in present-under-past configurations — which yield double access readings and preclude strict simultaneity — *de se* interpretations do appear in present-under-future embeddings, such

as in (124). In such cases, the resulting interpretation has been attributed to the same tense agreement mechanism operative in past-under-past constructions.⁵³

- (124) Context: Tomorrow Jerry is going to tell Elaine that he won't be able to attend her wedding. You expect her to be upset when Jerry reports their conversation tomorrow.
- a. Jerry will say that Elaine is upset.
 - b. *SIM possible*: 'Jerry (tomorrow): "Elaine is upset"'
 - c. [PRES [WOLL... Jerry say [λt_0 [~~PRES~~ t_0 [Elaine be-upset]]]]]

The availability of *de se* interpretations for present tense in SoT environments reinforces two key points: the indexical nature of the English present and the availability of an SoT rule in the grammar.

Interestingly, though less transparently, the English simple past may also support *de re* interpretations. This was shown formally at the end of the previous subsection. However, unlike present-under-past whose double access interpretation is unequivocally *de re*, the potential *de re* readings arising for past-under-past can be obscured by their truth-conditionally similar *de se/de Dicto* alternatives. This is to say that, in many contexts, both simultaneous and backward-shifted interpretations can be derived either via a *de re* construal (see (120) and (121)) or via *de se* (as structural approaches show), without distinctive truth-conditional differences. This is problematic.

In Section 2.5.3, I argued for the SoT status of English based on the availability of temporally vacuous readings in certain contexts — such as “breakfast sentences” and reports of permanent states. These contexts favor *de se* interpretations and are incompatible with a *de re* analysis. By parallel reasoning, we should also look for diagnostics that force *de re* readings while excluding *de se* interpretations. A few examples of this kind are discussed in Schlenker (1999) and Ogihara & Sharvit (2012), one of which is reproduced in (125).

- (125) Context (after Schlenker, 1999, p. 143):
On Tuesday, Mary read a chart that read: ‘Tuesday — doctor on duty: John’.
However Mary mistakenly thought that that day's date was Thursday.
- a. #On Tuesday Mary believed John to be the doctor on duty.
 - b. On Tuesday Mary believed that John was the doctor on duty.
de re: ‘The speaker: “According to Mary, on Tuesday John was the doctor on duty”’
#*de se*: ‘Mary (on Tuesday): “Today John is the doctor on duty”’

As the paraphrases make clear, the simultaneous reading required by the context in (125) can only be interpreted *de re*: Mary does not locate herself at the time of John's duty. The felicity of (125-b) in a *de re*, non-*de se* context thus supports the availability of a *de re* construal for past tense in English. Notably, this interpretation appears to be unavailable for the infinitival complement in (125-a), a fact that leads Schlenker to propose a *de se* analysis for infinitivals.⁵⁴

⁵³Assuming, as discussed, that the modal *will* is present-tensed.

⁵⁴One possible objection to Schlenker's *de re* diagnostic is that the complement clause in (125-b) might still contain a *de se* tense, interpreted under a backward-shifted reading. Since Mary situates herself

If both structural and *de re* accounts are necessary to accurately characterize the temporal interpretation of attitude reports in English, it raises the question of what cross-linguistic variation looks like. Do languages pattern like English or do we observe divergent patterns when it comes to SoT constellations? The next section introduces the broad typological picture and presents the basic facts.

2.7 The SoT parameter and semantic variation

The previous section demonstrated that simultaneous readings in English correlate with past-under-past embeddings, whereas present-under-past attitude reports only yield double-access readings. Analytically, the past tense in English may be invisible to semantic composition, following an agreement-based mechanism. Conversely, the present tense in non-agreeing configurations can only be evaluated in relation to the time of the utterance and thus interpreted *de re*.

From a cross-linguistic perspective, the English case is not universally attested. On the contrary, several languages seem to display the opposite pattern, wherein simultaneity is primarily expressed through a relative present, while past-under-past conveys most naturally shifted interpretations. The paradigmatic example is often Japanese, as illustrated by the minimal pair below (see also Kubota et al., 2011; Kusumoto, 1999; Ogihara, 1996).

- (126) Context: Jerry (speaking two years ago): ‘Elaine is upset.’
- a. Jerry-wa Elaine-ga okot-te-**iru** to itteimash-ita.
 Jerry-TOP Elaine-NOM upset-PROG-**PRES** COMP say-PAST
 ‘Jerry said that Elaine was upset (at that moment).’ (SIM)
- b. #Jerry-wa Elaine-ga okot-te-**ita** to itteimash-ita.
 Jerry-TOP Elaine-NOM upset-PROG-**PAST** COMP say-PAST
 lit.‘Jerry said that Elaine had been upset.’ (BACK)

Under a simultaneous context like (126), only the option with the embedded present is felicitous. By contrast, the past-tensed counterpart is only compatible with a backward-shifted interpretation. It is worth stressing that the simultaneous reading in (126-a) is not the by-product of a double access reading. Its implausibility is highlighted by the topic time introduced by the context (two years ago). The fact that the Japanese present is not an indexical is supported by the following data point.

- (127) Ninen mae, Taroo-wa Hanako-ga ninshin shi-te-iru to
 two.years ago Taroo-TOP Hanako-NOM pregnancy do-PROG-PRES COMP
 it-ta.
 say-PAST
 ‘Two years ago, Taroo said that Hanako was pregnant.’

Similar facts have been observed in the languages listed in (128):

on Thursday, John’s shift on Tuesday would obviously precede the attitude time — that is exactly the temporal interpretation expected under a non-vacuous quantificational or relative past tense.

- (128) **Non-SoT languages** (self-compiled non-exhaustive list): **Atayal** and **Javanese** (Chen et al., 2021); **Awing** (Mucha & Fominyam, 2017); **Bulgarian** (Vesela Simeonova, p.c.); **Farsi** (Sameri & Karimi-Doostan, 2019), **Hungarian** and **Latvian** (Armenante & Braun, 2022), **Korean** (Chung, 1999, 2012; Ko & Yoo, 2023), **Mbyá** (Thomas, 2014), **Medumba** (Mucha, 2017), **Modern Hebrew** (Ogihara & Sharvit, 2012; Sharvit, 2003), **Nez Perce** (Deal, 2024); **Polish** (Kozłowska-Raś, 1987; Mucha et al., 2023), **Romanian** (Giorgi, 2010a; Lungu, 2008), **Russian** (Altshuler, 2008; Grønn & Von Stechow, 2010; Khomitsevich, 2008), **Serbo-Croatian** (Todorović, 2015), **South Baffin Inuktitut** (Hayashi & Oshima, 2017), **Turkish** (Enç, 2004), **Vietnamese** (Bui, 2018), among others.

By contrast, aside from English, the availability of Sequence of Tense has been attributed to the languages listed in (129):

- (129) **SoT languages** (self-compiled, non-exhaustive list): **Dutch** (Khomitsevich, 2008; Zeijlstra, 2012), **French** (Demirdache, 2021; Grønn & Von Stechow, 2010; Schlenker, 1999), **German** (Grønn & Von Stechow, 2010; Kamp, 2022; von Stechow, 1999), **Icelandic** (Sigurðsson, 2010), **Italian** (Armenante, 2024b; Costantini, 2007; Giorgi & Pianesi, 1997), **Modern Greek** (Sharvit, 2014; Tsilia, 2021a), **Norwegian** (Grønn & Von Stechow, 2010; Stausland Johnsen, 2009), **Portuguese** (Ferreira, 2017), **Spanish** (Genari, 2003; Rodríguez, 2004; Sharvit, 2014), **Swedish** (Kozłowska-Raś, 1987), **Washo** (Bochnak, 2016; Bochnak et al., 2019).

Considering Sequence of Tense as a parameter of semantic variation, languages similar to English, as listed in (ii), are categorized as SoT languages. In contrast, languages in group (i) are referred to as non-SoT languages (cf. Bochnak et al., 2019; Grønn & Von Stechow, 2010; Ogihara & Sharvit, 2012). A non-exhaustive list of the two groups also features in Bošković (2012, p. 227):

- (130) a. **SoT languages:** English, Dutch, Modern Greek, Spanish, French, German, Italian.
 b. **Non-SoT languages:** Russian, Polish, Czech, Serbo-Croatian, Romanian, Hebrew, Japanese, Korean, Hindi, Turkish, Malayalam, Bangla, Angika.

The SoT parameter responsible for the above distribution can be formulated as follows (cf. Bochnak et al., 2019).

- (131) *The SoT parameter of semantic variation.*
 A Languages has/{does not have} the SoT rule.

At first glance, the SoT group does not exhibit a degree of linguistic diversity one might expect: most candidate languages are confined to the Indo-European family, with a strong representation of the Germanic and Romance branches — and, more broadly, of languages under Latin influence.

Interestingly, no language has yet been documented that both lacks an SoT rule and displays a strictly indexical present tense. Arguably, such a language would be unable

to express *de se* simultaneous readings at all, whether through an embedded present or past tense. This gap is precisely what Sharvit (2003)’s Embeddability Principle seeks to account for:

- (132) *Embeddability Principle (EP)* (Sharvit, 2003, p. 674)
 If A is a well-formed LF of a matrix sentence, then there is an A’ such that A and A’ match in content, and [CP *Tense* V [CP A’]] is also a well-formed LF (where *V* is a suitable attitude verb and *Tense* is a past or a present tense).

Viewed through the lens of this principle, it is not surprising that SoT languages like English — which lack a dedicated *de se* tense form — resort to structural mechanisms such as the SoT rule. In effect, the availability of Sequence of Tense may be understood as a grammatical strategy to obviate a possible EP violation.

As is often the case in linguistics, things are not so clear-cut. Micro-variation within both groups has emerged, prompting the proposal of additional parameters beyond (131) (cf. a.o. Grønn & Von Stechow, 2010; Khomitsevich, 2008; Ogihara & Sharvit, 2012).

In particular, several non-SoT languages permit simultaneous readings even with past-under-past configurations, though these tend to be less natural than their present-under-past counterparts. A prototypical example is offered by Russian (see below).

- (133) *Žénja skazal čto Lena byla (togda) beremenna.*
Zhenya say.PAST.PFV COMP Lena be.PAST then pregnant.
SIM possible: ‘Zhenya said that Lena was pregnant (then).’

Simultaneous interpretations in Russian past-under-past attitude reports such as (133) are generally possible only if the embedded clause contains a stative or an imperfective root of the predicate. Despite their alleged marginality, it has been observed that these readings can be strengthened by a *then*-like deictic adverb (cf. Armenante, 2024a; Tsilia, 2021b; Vostrikova, 2018). However, crucially for our classification here, genuinely null readings are ruled out for past-under-past in these languages, indicating that the simultaneous interpretation cannot result from deletion or tense agreement. This is illustrated for Russian in (134) with a report of a permanent state and in (135) with a breakfast sentence (see also Khomitsevich, 2008 for Russian and Ogihara & Sharvit, 2012 for similar observations concerning Modern Hebrew).

- (134) Context (2150 years ago): Ptolemy to himself: ‘Eureka, the Sun revolves around the Earth!’
 a. Ptolemey veril, čto Solntse vrashchayetsya vokrug Zemli.
 Ptolemy believe.PAST that Sun revolve.PRES around Earth.
 b. #Ptolemey veril, čto Solntse vrashchalos’ vokrug Zemli.
 Ptolemy believe.PAST that Sun revolve.PAST around Earth.
 Intended: ‘Ptolemy believed that the Sun revolved around the Earth.’

- (135) Context: One week ago John finally found the courage to confess his true feelings to Mary next time they see each other. He will visit her in 2 weeks, so two weeks from now, he will tell her: ‘Mary, I love you’.

- a. Dzhon reshil skazat' Meri, chto lyubit yeye.
John decide.PAST say.INF Mary that love.PRES her.
- b. #Dzhon reshil skazat' Meri, chto lyubil yeye.
John decide.PAST say.INF Mary that love.PAST her.
Intended: 'John decided he would tell Mary he loved/loves her.'

For (134-b), native speakers report strong a cessation implicature, leading to an implausible interpretation for which the Sun used to orbit around the Earth but stopped at some point. Similarly, only a backward-shifted interpretations is available for (135-b), with a strong implicature that John no longer loves Mary.

Based on these empirical facts, the simultaneous reading of past-under-past in non-SoT languages has been linked to a *de re* analysis, where the embedded past tense is semantically interpreted rather than vacuous (see Grønn & Von Stechow, 2010; Khomitsevich, 2008, for Russian).⁵⁵

Languages whose tenses have been argued to allow for *de re* ascriptions include Russian, Polish, Hebrew, Hungarian, Farsi, and others. Conversely, languages that do not seem to exhibit temporal *de re* at all include Japanese, Atayal, Javanese, Vietnamese, and many superficially tenseless languages. This distribution suggests a second parameter of variation, exemplified in (137).

- (136) *The de re variability parameter*
A language has/does not have temporal *de re*.

The parameter in (137) views the availability of temporal *de re* across languages in binary terms. This perspective has long dominated the literature (cf. Grønn & Von Stechow, 2010; Ogihara & Sharvit, 2012). However, Bochnak et al. (2019), by extending the investigation to under-researched languages with optional or non-obligatory tense, have revealed a more nuanced picture, where the availability of temporal *de re* across languages exhibits a gradient distribution. In light of these findings, the original parameter in (137) is revised as follows (adapted from Bochnak et al., 2019, p. 431).

- (137) *The de re variability parameter (revised)*
Languages vary in the degree of availability of temporal *de re*.

It is worth pointing out that Bochnak et al. (2019) base *de re* variability parameter in (137) on the (gradient) distribution of (*de re*) backward-shifted interpretations in the languages under investigation. That is to say that, to the best of my knowledge, the cross-linguistic distribution of both *de re* and *de se* simultaneous interpretations continues to be characterized in binary terms, following the parameters in (131) and (137). However, in the remainder of this thesis we will see that a categorical characterization of temporal *de re* when it comes to simultaneous interpretations is also too strong.

⁵⁵This view is further supported by the availability of *SIM*-readings in several non-SoT languages for past-under-past, when the context involves a mistaken temporal location (as given in (125)) (see Ogihara & Sharvit, 2012; Sharvit, 2018). We will return to this point in chapter 3, where this diagnostic is applied to Akan *n'a*.

2.8 Summary

This chapter has laid the groundwork by introducing key concepts in tense semantics. Following standard definitions of tense and aspect, we examined how these two categories interact compositionally. In particular, we observed that tensed expressions — much like DPs — can be analyzed either pronominally or quantificationally. Additionally, we discussed how semantic tense may be interpreted either as absolute/indexical (i.e., relative to the time of the speech context) or as relative (i.e., relative to a local evaluation time).

With these definitions in place, we turned to embedded contexts, focusing on the temporal interpretation of complement clauses and the phenomenon known as Sequence of Tense (SoT). We showed that past-under-past embeddings in English are systematically ambiguous between a backward-shifted and a simultaneous interpretations, with *SIM*-reading possibly associating with a semantically vacuous interpretation. Crucially, the availability of such temporally null readings challenges a transparent form-to-meaning mapping. Through an extensive review of the literature, we outlined several families of approaches that aim to account for SoT effects. Structural approaches attribute the ambiguity to an agreement-like mechanism whereby temporal features can be optionally licensed in syntactic agreeing configurations. In contrast, aspectual-pragmatic accounts derive the ambiguity from the temporal profile of stative predicates and the resulting pragmatic competition between present and past tense forms.

Expanding the empirical scope beyond English, we demonstrated that languages differ in whether they exhibit SoT effects. Beyond this broad typological split, several non-SoT languages nevertheless permit simultaneous interpretations via a *de re* construal of the embedded past tense — where the past tense is interpreted indexically, relative to the context time. From this perspective, we highlighted that tenses across languages may allow both *de se* construals (either transparently or through SoT-like mechanisms) and *de re* ones.

Building on these foundational notions, Chapter 3 focuses on Asante Twi, an aspect-prominent language with rich TAM morphology. The various compositional pathways Asante Twi employs to express the full range of temporal interpretations in attitude reports makes this language an intriguing testing ground for the parameters of variation introduced in this chapter.

3 Temporal meaning and the composition of attitude reports in Asante Twi (Akan)

This chapter provides an in-depth study of how temporal meaning is encoded in Asante Twi (Akan), with a focus on the temporal interpretation of complement clauses of propositional attitude verbs. Central to this investigation are three morphemes that can express temporal anteriority: the sentence particle *ná* and the two affixes LEN and *a*. While recent years have witnessed a burgeoning interest in Akan languages, most work on TAM markers has targeted phonological and morpho-syntactic issues, neglecting semantic ones, particularly from a formal perspective. Consequently, the exploration of an aspect-prominent language like Asante Twi can offer fresh insights to the crosslinguistic discussion, especially since fieldwork research on tense semantics is still in its early stages, as highlighted in chapter 2.

This research contributes significantly both methodologically and theoretically. Methodologically, it refines diagnostic tools for a nuanced exploration of the semantic properties of tense and aspect forms, especially within attitude contexts. Theoretically, the study offers a compositional analysis of temporal meaning in Asante Twi, deconstructing its building blocks to illuminate the interplay between various temporal markers. Such an approach enriches the cross-linguistic picture by examining parameters of variation and identifying semantic universals. Notably, this endeavor poses challenges, primarily because seminal works in tense semantics are rooted in English and Indo-European languages, whose TAM systems differ remarkably from those of Western-African languages. This leads to the question of whether TAM markers in Asante Twi can be characterized by rigid tense/aspect categories, given the blurred distinction between aspectual and temporal meaning within several Western African languages.

To accomplish this, this chapter unfolds in two main segments: initially, it examines the meanings of the three markers expressing temporal anteriority and how their implications for the interpretation of main clauses. Subsequently, the focus shifts to a comprehensive investigation of propositional attitude reports. Given the abundant formal accounts and machinery available, it remains paramount to develop a theory for embedded tense forms rooted in their intrinsic properties, thereby circumventing potential pitfalls such as unwarranted stipulations and empirically unmotivated formal approaches that pervade existing literature.

Building on the overview presented in chapter 2, I will primarily address the following questions:

- (i) How does Asante Twi manipulate reference and eventuality times?

- (ii) Are there pronominal, quantificational or hybrid tense forms in Asante Twi?
- (iii) How can the language be categorized in relation to the SoT/non-SoT distinction?
- (iv) Does Asante exhibit any novel compositional pathways to deriving simultaneity in SoT environments?

The chapter is structured as follows: In the first section, I offer a concise introduction to the language and discuss the methodology adopted for the data collection, following the approach developed by Matthewson (2004). Moving on to section 3.2, I present novel data on the semantic properties of the three temporal anteriority markers, briefly referencing previous claims in the literature. These empirical findings lay the groundwork for the formal analysis in section 3.3. Specifically, I suggest that both *ná* and LEN denote pronominal tenses. While *ná* operates as a distal deictic tense excluding the utterance time, LEN receives a relative past tense semantics. Additionally, their aspectual profiles differ: *ná* pairs exclusively with stative/habitual aspect, whereas LEN also incorporates a perfective aspect at LF. In contrast, *a* allows for a broader range of interpretations, including experiential, resultative and universal readings. I propose that its underlying semantic representation involves an extended now perfect, combining with either a resultative or a stative viewpoint aspect. Crucially, interpretations arising from resultative viewpoint are semantically underspecified and vary based on the QuD, thus leading to either an experiential or a resultative interpretation. In section 3.4, attention shifts to propositional attitude contexts. Here, I note that bare and LEN-embeddings correlate with simultaneous and backward-shifted interpretations, respectively. In contrast, *ná* and *a*-embeddings display ambiguity between the two readings. Section 3.5 shows that for both bare and LEN-embeddings the attested interpretations arise from the attitude time binding into the embedded evaluation time. However, I argue that the same analysis cannot be extended to *ná*-marked reports, wherein attested meanings must be attributed to a *de re* construal. For *a*-embeddings, the picture becomes nuanced: while both binding and *de re* construals yield backward-shifted interpretations, certain change-of-state verbs under binding produce a simultaneous reading - a noteworthy innovation. Finally, section 3.6 concludes with a comprehensive summary of the key findings.

3.1 Background and methodology

Akan is a linguistic cluster comprising several languages spoken in Ghana and the south-eastern region of Ivory Coast. These languages belong to the Kwa branch of the Niger-Congo family and are usually reported to be mutually intelligible, though with distinct orthographies. The Akan cluster primarily consists of three main dialects: Asante (Twi), Akuapem (Twi), and Fante. Over time, these dialects have evolved as literary standards and are actively taught in schools as well as used in media and radio networks.

In this chapter, the claims made will primarily focus on the Asante (Twi) dialect. However, it is worth noting that some of these claims may also apply to the broader Akan language cluster. According to the 2000 census conducted by the Ghana Statistical Service, it was reported that approximately 14.7% of the population in Ghana spoke

Asante Twi as their native language.

In Asante Twi vowels are paired based on vowel harmony, which is influenced by the [ATR] feature. Correspondingly, they divide into five [+ATR] and five [-ATR] vowels. There exist three phonemic tones in the language: a high tone (HT), a mid tone (MT) and a low tone (LT). Mid tones are restricted to non-initial syllables. I will follow orthographic convention and not mark tone unless it becomes relevant to the discussion.¹

Asante Twi has a rigid Subject-Verb-Object word order. NPs are not marked for case and exhibit the following linear order: Possessive/Demonstrative > Noun > Adjective > Numeral > Quantifier/Article > Preposition > Relative Clause (cf. Philipp, 2022, p. 129). Asante Twi only allows for object pro-drop and lacks subject-verb agreement.

The data presented in this chapter are the result of data elicitation from March 2022 to November 2023 with six native speakers of Asante Twi. Five of the speakers have a background in linguistics, two speak Fante as their second language. The methodology adopted follows the guidelines illustrated in Matthewson (2004) for semantic fieldwork. Almost all the data were elicited using acceptability judgment tasks, whereby speakers were asked to judge whether a sentence was true in a given context. While target sentences were in Asante Twi, contexts consisted of English sentences and were occasionally accompanied by diagrams or timelines for more complex scenarios. In some instances, translation tasks were used as a first prompt or for long-winded text.

3.2 Tense-aspectual markers in Asante Twi

In this section, I introduce the TAM system of Asante Twi, focusing on the grammatical means the language employs to express temporal anteriority (TAnt). Depending on the context, Asante Twi makes use of three markers² to express pastness: the clausal particle *ná*, the prefix *a* and the suffix LEN.

3.2.1 Phonological and morpho-syntactic properties

The particle *ná* carries a high tone.³ Being a free morpheme, it does not attach to the verb's stem but occupies a left-peripheral position before the clausal subject, as indicated in the following example.

- (1) (Bre áa) Kofi ba-à ha nó, **ná** Ama re-di akokε.
 time REL Kofi arrive-LEN here DEF NA Ama PROG-eat chicken
 'When Kofi arrived here, Ama was eating chicken.'

¹HT will be marked by the diacritic ´, indicating acute accent, whereas LT by the diacritic ` , indicating grave accent.

²I am using the term 'marker' somewhat improperly here. Traditionally, markers are non-root bound morphemes that are attached to a root or a stem. This definition only applies to the two affixal markers *a* and LEN, with the particle *ná* constituting a free morpheme. However, for purely descriptive reasons, I will group the three items into the same class of anteriority markers in that they may variously mark the temporal meaning of anteriority when used in a sentence.

³Note that the segment /na/ in Asante Twi is found in fairly different contexts. For instance, low tone *ná* is used as a coordinator and a focus marker. To avoid confusion with any of its homographs, the temporal marker *ná* will always be marked with a HL diacritic.

3 Temporal meaning and the composition of attitude reports in Asante Twi (Akan)

On the other hand, the morphemes *a* and LEN are attach to the verb's stem in prefixal and suffixal position, respectively. The tone of *a* assimilates with the tone of the last syllable of the subject, whereas LEN involves the lengthening of the stem's final vowel, with its tone being always low.

- (2) a. Esí **á**-bu mfensere nó.
 Esi A-break window DEF
 'Esi has broken the window.'
- b. Esí bu-**ù** mfensere nó.
 Esi break-LEN window DEF
 'Esi broke the window.'
- (3) a. Yàw **à**-bu mfensere nó.
 Yaw A-break window DEF
 'Yaw has broken the window.'
- b. Yàw bu-**ù** mfensere nó.
 Yaw break-LEN window DEF
 'Yaw broke the window.'

It is worth stressing that, while *ná* transparently indicates the spell-out of the particle, the terms *a* and LEN serve descriptive purposes. Specifically, although LEN typically involves vowel lengthening, it may alternatively manifest as a high vowel *i/e* if the verb ends with a consonant.⁴

Interestingly, *a* and LEN trigger polarity effects under negation,⁵ as demonstrated by the following minimal pairs:

- (4) Affirmative sentences:
- a. Kofi **a**-noa aduane.
 Kofi **A**-cook food.
 'Kofi has cooked food.' (a)
- b. Kofi noa-**a** aduane.
 Kofi cook-**LEN** food.
 'Kofi cooked food.' (LEN)
- (5) Negative sentences:
- a. Kofi **a-n**-noa aduane.
 Kofi **LEN-NEG**-cook food.
 'Kofi didn't cook food.' (LEN)
- b. Kofi **n**-noa-**a** aduane.
 Kofi **NEG**-cook-**A** food.
 'Kofi hasn't cooked food.' (a)

These 'chessboard' distributions do not have semantic implications. Therefore, despite potential confusion, I will continue to refer to two markers as LEN and *a* even under negation, where they 'swap' their morphological forms. Since I have nothing to contribute

⁴For further phonological restrictions related to LEN, refer to Paster (2010).

⁵For polarity effects, see Lahne, 2007; Wunderlich, 2012, among others.

on this matter, I will simply note in passing that this intricate morpho-phonological phenomenon has not yet undergone systematic investigation.⁶

3.2.2 Brief review of the literature

Before presenting the elicited data on their semantic distribution, let me provide a brief sketch of how the literature has descriptively characterized Akan's temporal anteriority markers from a semantic standpoint.

Following Dolphyne (1987)'s seminal work, the two affixes *a* and LEN are classified as perfect aspect and past tense, respectively. However, no additional defining (aspectual) values are attributed to the two markers. Along the same lines, Duah & Savić (2020) views LEN as an aspectually neutral past tense, while *a* is treated as the Reichenbachian perfect aspect, which locates the event time before the reference time. Similarly, Boadi (2008) and Osam (2008) take *a* to denote a perfect aspect, with the event bearing some relevance to the utterance time. However, the two theories diverge when it comes to LEN: while Boadi views it as a past tense (with perfective uses), Osam argues that the suffix denotes a completive (or perfective) aspect that depicts the eventuality as a whole. Osam further suggests that Akan is an aspect-prominent language that lacks the canonical opposition between present and past tense. On his view, Akan languages only exhibit an overt future tense (the prefix *bɛ*) alongside a non-future one, that is the null form \emptyset . By contrast, unmarked clauses are treated as present-tensed in Duah & Savić (2020) and Boadi (2008). The latter further assumes that additional silent morphemes can convey stative or habitual aspect. Their position differs from the one taken by Dolphyne (1987), according to which the null form only involves (stative/habitual) aspect, but no present tense. Finally, the particle *ná* has received less attention and often simply glossed as a clausal determiner. Boadi (2008) appeals to a lexical ambiguity analysis, assuming the co-existence of both a future- and a past-oriented *ná*, whose homophony is regarded as merely coincidental.⁷ In contrast to Boadi's view, Osam characterizes *ná* as an imperfective temporal marker, without any specific mention of a temporal restriction. A prominent formal account is formulated in Zimmermann & Duah (2022), where *ná* picks out a contextually salient time other than the local evaluation time (for formal details, see section 3.3.2). A summary of the these accounts is illustrated in Table 3.1.

⁶A comprehensive discussion of polarity effects in Asante TAM markers goes beyond the scope of this dissertation. Nonetheless, It's worth noting that this phenomenon most likely relates to morpho-phonology rather than semantics. Throughout my empirical investigation, I tested the two markers in various contexts, considering both affirmative and negative meanings. Clearly, restrictions on one marker persisted despite its 'divergent' morphology.

⁷Boadi states that the fact that future-oriented and past-oriented *ná* constitute different lexemes "is not in doubt [...]. It would be pointless to speculate here about the likely historical processes that must have occurred for two diametrically opposed semantic units to be expressed by the same form *ná*. intriguing though this is. Perhaps, a detailed study of these two forms in related dialects and languages will, one day, give clues."

	<i>Null form</i>	<i>a</i>	LEN	<i>ná</i>
<i>Dolphyne (1987)</i>	{HAB, STAT}	PERF	PAST	n/a
<i>Boadi (2008)</i>	{PRES, HAB, STAT}	Resultative PERF ⁸	(PFV) PAST	PAST/FUT
<i>Osam (2008)</i>	non-future	Resultative PERF	PFV	(NPFV) TM ⁹
<i>D & S (2020)¹⁰</i>	PRES	Experiential PERF	PAST	CD

Table 3.1: Summary: Temporal markers in Akan

In summary, the discussion of the literature above — which is far from exhaustive — reveals a lack of consensus regarding the semantic status of the TAnT markers (as well as the null form) in Akan languages. While these proposals converge on the notion that the prefix *a* denotes some type of perfect aspect, they fall short of providing a comprehensive characterization of all its uses. This aspect is particularly crucial, considering recent work has shown that what is often referred to as “the perfect” cross-linguistically does not represent a universal category (Bertrand et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2021). Even less clear is the status of LEN, which has been defined as a perfective aspect or a past tense or anything in between. Lastly, we’ve observed that disagreement also exists concerning the temporal orientation of both unmarked and *ná*-marked clauses. Against this backdrop, the next section offers a more nuanced empirical investigation of temporality in Asante Twi, and more broadly in Akan. To this aim, I will present the findings of novel fieldwork data, which will subsequently inform a formal analysis of the meaning of the three TAnT markers.

3.2.3 The data: semantic properties

In this section I will focus on the uses of the three anteriority markers and their combinatorial restrictions. Given their partial overlap in use, it will be of particular importance to highlight contexts where the three markers cannot be used interchangeably. The diagnostic approach employed here is rooted in recent semantic fieldwork research on TAM (Bertrand et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2021). The empirical properties tested in this context have been variously attributed to different categories, generally associated with past tense and perfect aspect. These findings will, therefore, contribute to crafting an accurate formal description of the meaning conveyed by the three TAnT markers.

(i) Referential readings

TAM forms are expected to be felicitous in referential contexts if they can identify the contextually salient time-interval throughout which the situation described by the main predicate holds. As we have seen in Chapter 1, the ability to refer to reference/topic times

⁸The types of perfect labelled here go back to the classification found in Bertrand et al. (2022). I will come back to this point later.

⁹Temporal Marker, with no temporal restriction.

¹⁰Duah & Savić (2020).

is typical of referential tense forms, as opposed to indefinite ones that usually introduce a new temporal referent in the discourse.

- (6) Context (stative predicate): Last week, you visited Afiba. Since she had gotten the flu, you couldn't stay long. Today, one of your friends asks you about Afiba. You tell them why you had to cut your visit short:
- a. Afiba yare-è.
Afiba sick-LEN
'Afiba was/got sick.'
 - b. #Afiba a-yare.
Afiba A-sick
'Afiba has been sick.'
 - c. Ná Afiba yare.
NA Afiba sick
'Afiba was sick.'

LEN and *ná* are both acceptable in referential contexts as opposed to *a*, with one important difference in meaning: while (6-c) merely depicts Afiba's state at the moment of the visit, consultants report that in (6-a) the state is very likely to have ceased by the utterance time. Eventive predicates, by contrast, show slightly different patterns, with *ná*-marked sentences being rejected in past episodic scenarios:

- (7) Context (eventive predicate): Yesterday, there was salmon and beef at the canteen, but Kofi picked salmon. Today, one of your friends asks you about Kofi's choice. You answer:
- a. #Kofi a-di salmon.
Kofi a-eat salmon
'Kofi has eaten salmon.'
 - b. Kofi di-ì salmon.
Kofi eat-LEN salmon
'Kofi ate salmon.'
 - c. #Ná Kofi di salmon.
NA Kofi eat salmon
'Kofi used to eat salmon.'

While consultants' judgments consistently replicate for *a* and LEN, independent of the predicate's Aktionsart, the use of *ná* in referential contexts is reported to be possible only for stative predicates. When the predicate is eventive, as in (7-c), the sentence is interpreted habitually. I will return to this point later.

(ii) *Experiential readings*

Experiential readings arise for properties holding at some point in time. Contrary to referential ones, experiential contexts are purely indefinite in that they have no specific temporal anchor and, thus, are expected to be felicitous if the sentence involves an event that occurred at least once before. To strengthen the existential component of these

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readings, the following sentences were tested both with and without the existential particle *da* ('ever/before').

- (8) Context (stative predicates): One of your friends tells you that they are quite envious of Afiba, who always seems to be in great health and energetic. However, you think that this is quite exaggerated: in fact, even Afiba was sick at some point in the past...
- a. Afiba **a**-yare (da).
Afiba **a**-sick ever
'Afiba has been sick (before).'
 - b. #Afiba yare-**è** (da).
Afiba sick-**LEN** ever
Intended: 'Afiba was sick (before).'
 - c. #**Ná** Afiba yare (da).
NA Afiba sick ever
Intended: 'Afiba was sick (before).'

Compared to referential contexts, judgments are reversed: the prefix *a* is compatible with an experiential reading, whereas both **LEN** and *ná* are not. The same findings are replicated with sentences containing an eventive predicate as shown in (9) and (10).

- (9) Context (eventive): Your friend wants to impress Kofi with salmon for dinner, thinking he hasn't tried it before. However, you point out that he already knows its taste.
- a. Kofi **a**-di salmon (da).
Kofi **A**-eat salmon ever
'Kofi has had salmon (before).'
 - b. #Kofi di-**ì** salmon (da).
Kofi eat-**LEN** salmon ever
Intended: 'Kofi had salmon before.'
 - c. #**Ná** Kofi di salmon (da).
NA Kofi eat salmon ever
Intended: 'Kofi had salmon (before).'
- (10) Context (eventive): Your village at the border with Togo lies at the foot of a high mountain. You barely know anyone who has ever attempted to climb it, but rumor has it that Afiba has succeeded at least once before.
- a. Afiba **a**-foro bepɔ́ nó.
Afiba **A**-climb mountain DEF
'Afiba has climbed the mountain.'
 - b. ??Afiba foro-**ò** bepɔ́ nó.
Afiba climb-**LEN** mountain DEF
Intended: 'Afiba climbed the mountain.'
Comment: *Grammatical, but doesn't follow from the context. When did she climb? Is it just now? Was it yesterday?*
 - c. #**Ná** Afiba foro bepɔ́ nó.
NA Afiba climb mountain DEF

Intended: ‘Afiba climbed the mountain (then).’

Comment: *No, it means that she used to climb the mountain.*

Whereas *a*-marked sentences readily yield (existential) experiential readings, my consultants strongly dislike¹¹ LEN-marked ones due to the specificity requirement imposed by LEN on the temporal reference, which is indefinite in these contexts — as indicated by one speaker’s comment on sentence (10-b). Moreover, *ná* seems to be independently ruled out due to an obligatory habitual interpretation (see also one consultant’s comment reported for (10-c)).

(iii) *Modification by locating temporal adverbials*

One additional testing ground for the meaning of TAM markers is given by modification via temporal expressions. This semantic property goes hand in hand with referentiality in that only TAM forms that are compatible with referential readings should, in principle, allow locating temporal adverbials (LTA).¹² In English, for instance, LTAs can modify VPs containing a preterite but not a (present) perfect.

(11) Yesterday Liz {visited}/#{has visited} the city museum.

This leads us to expect LTAs to occur felicitously with LEN and possibly *ná*, but not with *a*. This prediction is borne out:

(12) Context: Speaking of an expensive purchase made in 2016...

a. Me-tɔ-ɔ́ / #m’a-tɔ́ aponkye aboɔden wɔ́ afe 2016.
1SG-buy-LEN / 1SG.a-buy goat expensive at year 2016
Intended: ‘In 2016 I bought an expensive goat.’

b. #Ná me-tɔ́ aponkye aboɔden wɔ́ afe 2016.
NA 1SG-buy goat expensive at year 2016
Intended: I bought an expensive goat in 2016.

Comment: It means that I used to buy expensive goats back in 2016, implying that now I only buy cheap ones..

As shown in (12), only LEN-inflected predicates can be modified by a locating temporal adverbial¹³. Since the predicate denotes an event, the particle *ná* yields a habitual interpretation. My consultants’ judgments do not vary if the temporal adverbial describes an event in the near past¹⁴. This is illustrated in (13) (after Duah & Savić, 2020, p. 83).

(13) Context: You need to take some medicine once a day. Your mum is worried you forgot yesterday. But you reassure her:

¹¹One out of three consultants didn’t fully reject (10-b), which was however dispreferred compared to (10-a) and for this reason marked with a double question mark.

¹²I am using the term “locating temporal adverbial” informally here. An LTA should encompass any adverbial that provides or restricts the reference time of the sentence in which it appears, regardless of its deictic (e.g., *yesterday*), anaphoric (e.g., *the week before*), or referential nature (e.g., *in 2016*).

¹³Preposing the adverbial in (12) does not result in any difference.

¹⁴These findings contradict Duah & Savić, 2020, p. 83’s data, where modification of *a*-marked predicates by *yesterday* does not lead to unacceptability. We will return to this point later.

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- a. #M'a-fa aduro **nnora**.
1SG=**A**-take medicine yesterday
lit. 'I have taken the medicine yesterday.'
- b. Me-fa-à aduro **nnora**.
1SG-take-**LEN** medicine yesterday
'I took the medicine yesterday.'
- c. #Ná me-fa aduro nnora.
NA 1SG-take medicine yesterday
lit. 'I used to take the medicine yesterday.'

Based on the data given in (i), the co-occurrence of the particle *ná* with LTAs should be possible in the presence of stative predicates. This is indeed the case, as demonstrated below.

(14) Context: In 2010, I inherited my family's wealth after my parents died in a car accident. Unfortunately, I spent it all by 2015.

- a. Wɔ afe 2010 ná me-yɛ sikanii.
At year 2010 NA 1SG-COP rich
In 2010 I was rich.

Crucially, *ná* most naturally occurs in combination with adverbial clauses, where it correlates with the clausal determiner *nó* heading the embedded clause (see also Boadi, 2008; Duah & Savić, 2020; Osam, 2003, among others). In these cases, the predicate of the matrix clause depicts an ongoing event and, thus, bears the progressive marker *re*, as exemplified below.

(15) *ná*-clauses modified by adverbial clauses

- a. Ama ba-à yɛ nó, ná Kwame re-noa aduane.
Ama come-LEN COP CD NA Kwame PROG-cook food
'When Ama arrived, Kwame was cooking.'
- b. Ama bue-è εpono nó nó, ná Kwame re-da.
Ama open-LEN door DEF CD NA Kwame PROG-sleep
'When Ama opened the door, Kwame was sleeping.'

In light of the data above, a key point to note is that in sentences such as (15), *ná* may not be dropped. In fact, unmarked sentences in Akan cannot be temporally anchored to a time other than the one indicated by the utterance. Consequently, they can only receive a present interpretation, as demonstrated by the following examples:

(16) Kofi wu *(-ù) nnora.

- Kofi die -LEN yesterday
lit. 'Kofi dies(/died) yesterday.'

(17) Context: I was just wondering what Kofi was up to yesterday when you stopped by...

- a. *(ná) Kofi re-didi nnora.
NA Kofi PROG-eat yesterday.
lit. 'Kofi is(/was) eating yesterday.'

- (18) Context: I finally found out why Kwesi was so grumpy yesterday. Apparently he had skipped lunch...
- a. *(ná) ekɔm de Kwesi ennora.
NA hunger COP Kwesi yesterday
'Kofi was hungry yesterday.'
 - b. #ekɔm a-de Kwesi ennora.
hunger A-COP Kwesi yesterday
lit. 'Hunger has been to Kwesi yesterday.'
 - c. ekɔm de-è Kwesi ennora.
hunger COP-LEN Kwesi yesterday
'Kwesi got hungry yesterday.'

(iv) *Habitual readings*

Habitual readings refer to eventualities that occur repeatedly, regularly or as a habit over time. English lacks a habitual marker, though habitual meaning may be expressed through modals such as *used to* and *would* for past time reference and the present tense for present habits. A few examples are given below:

- (19) a. Angela **used to** dig up treasures with her shovel.
b. Angela **digs up** treasures with her shovel.

In Asante Twi, as we have seen, when combining with eventive predicates, the particle *ná* yields a habitual interpretation. For the markers *-a* and LEN, habitual readings are strongly dispreferred, though they might arise in specific contexts, particularly in the case of LEN. This is illustrated in (20) and (21).

- (20) Context: Kofi turned vegetarian two years ago. One of the things he misses the most is salmon: he used to be very fond of it.
- a. #Kofi (taa) a-di salmon.
Kofi frequently A-eat salmon
'Kofi has eaten salmon.'
 - b. #Kofi (taa) di-ì salmon.
Kofi frequently eat-LEN salmon ever
'Kofi ate salmon.'
Comment: *No, refers to a unique time Kofi ate salmon in the past.*
 - c. Ná Kofi (taa) di salmon.
NA Kofi frequently eat salmon
'Kofi used to eat salmon.'
- (21) Context: Kwame is now perfectly healthy, but you remember that as a child he used to get sick often.
Prompt: Ne nkwadaa birem nó, ... ('As a child, ...')
- a. #Kwame (taa) a-yare.
Kwame frequently a-sick
'Kwame has been sick.'

- b. ?Kwame (taa) yare-è.
 Kwame frequently sick-LEN
 ‘Kwame got sick.’
- c. **Ná** Kwame (taa) yare.
 NA Kwame frequently sick
 ‘Kwame used to be sick.’

One consultant does not entirely reject (21-b)¹⁵, for this reason the sentence is marked with a question mark. However, the by far preferred option in the given context remains (21-c) for all consultants.

Interestingly, a number of predicates, predominantly stative in nature, display a systematic ambiguity wherein stative and habitual interpretations intertwine (cf. Boadi, 2008). In certain instances, this distinction is phonologically encoded¹⁶, with the habitual meaning corresponding to a high tone on the verb’s final syllable¹⁷, as the following examples illustrate:

- (22) Context: You and Kofi just moved into your new shared flat. Being a good host, you show your friend Kwesi the flat, while Kofi is at work. The tour finally reaches Kofi’s new bedroom. You say:
- a. #Kofi **dà** há.
 Kofi sleep.**STAT** here
 ‘Kofi is sleeping here.’
- b. Kofi **dá** há.
 Kofi sleep.**HAB** here
 ‘Kofi sleeps here.’
- (23) Context: You heard that your friend Kofi is currently sleeping at your place. You hear someone snoring, so you step into the guest room. You say:
- a. Kofi **dà** há.
 Kofi sleep.**STAT** here
 ‘Kofi is sleeping here.’
- b. #Kofi **dá** há.
 Kofi sleep.**HAB** here
 ‘Kofi sleeps here.’

Interestingly, the observed ambiguity arises not only in bare clauses, but also in sentences containing *ná*.

- (24) Context: You and Kofi used to live in a shared flat in Kumasi, until he moved to Accra two years ago. You kept the place for yourself, but you’re left with a spare room now. Your friend Awusi asks you why you have an extra room in your flat.

¹⁵One of the consultants that reject the same sentence observes that (21-b) can only mean that Kofi got sick when he was a kid. For this reason, the sentence is odd when the frequency adverb *taa* is added.

¹⁶See Boadi (2008, p. 35) for a list of predicates with stative/non-stative alternation in Akan.

¹⁷Note that a high tone on the final syllable is not solely tied to a habitual meaning, but it may refer to any non-stative interpretation. Yet, in the absence of verb marking, it is most likely to indicate habitual aspect. This is also why Boadi (2008) distinguishes between stative and non-stative forms.

You say:

- a. #ná Kofi **dà** hó.
 NA Kofi sleep.**STAT** there
 ‘Kofi was sleeping there.’
- b. ná Kofi **dá** hó.
 NA Kofi sleep.**HAB** there
 ‘Kofi used to sleep there.’

(25) Context: Last Christmas, you celebrated at your friend Kofi’s place. When it came time to exchange presents, Kofi went missing. You decided to check his bedroom. Guess what Kofi was up to...

- a. ná Kofi **dà** hó.
 NA Kofi sleep.**STAT** there
 ‘Kofi was sleeping there.’
- b. #ná Kofi **dá** hó.
 NA Kofi sleep.**HAB** there
 ‘Kofi used to sleep there.’

(v) *Present and future reference*

We have observed up to this point that the particle *ná* may be used to make reference to specific past times. This, of course, begs the question of what temporal restriction *ná* is subject to: is it only compatible with past temporal intervals, or can it also refer to present or future times? The sentence in (26) taken from Boadi (2008, p. 19) seems to suggest that *ná* can be used in past as well as future contexts.

- (26) ná Kwesi kasá.
 NA Kwesi speak.HAB
 ‘Kwesi {used to}/{will} speak habitually.’

Present interpretations, as opposed to future ones, are strictly ruled out, even with stative predicates, as illustrated by the following data I have collected:

- (27) Context: You look pale and your forehead is burning. I say:
 a. seisei (*ná) wó-yare.
 now NA 2SG-sick
 Intended: ‘You are sick now.’

(28) Context: Kofi is going to an ‘all you can eat’ event tonight. He has barely touched any food today, as he plans to stuff himself like a bottomless pit. However, you warn him that he will most likely feel sick tomorrow.

- a. ɔkyena *(ná) wó-yare.
 tomorrow NA 2SG-sick
 ‘You will be sick tomorrow.’

I take it that the data above provide evidence for a view whereby future reference stems from the particle *ná* rather than from the absence of TAM-marking. Crucially, as (27-a)

shows, *ná* can only refer to a time other than now.¹⁸ Further support for the felicity of *ná* in future contexts comes from the sentences that follow, where *ná* combines with *a* and the progressive aspect *re-*:

- (29) Context: Little Awusi turns 10 tomorrow. He’s quite excited about his birthday and he challenges you to guess his age. You confidently say:
- a. ɔkyena *(ná) wó a-di m-feɛ du!
tomorrow NA 2SG A-eat PL-year ten
‘Tomorrow you will have turned ten!’ (after Duah & Savić, 2020, p. 83)
- b. *ɔkyena ná wó di-ì m-feɛ du!
tomorrow NA 2SG eat-LEN PL-year ten
- (30) Context: Ama is moving in with her boyfriend in September. Ama, unlike her boyfriend, is vegetarian, but you predict she’ll start eating meat by October already!
- a. ahinime bosome mu *(ná) Ama re-di mogyanam!
October month in NA Ama PROG-eat meat.
‘By October you’ll be eating meat!’
- b. ahinime bosome mu *(ná) Ama a-di mogyanam!
October month in NA Ama A-eat meat.
‘By October you’ll have eaten meat!’

Finally, *ná* most naturally occurs in correlation with when-clauses (that is, *nó*-marked clauses) even in future contexts, as the following example shows:

- (31) I’ll be back from holiday tomorrow. Since I didn’t bring my keys with me, I’ve just asked my flatmate to open the door for me. She replies:
- a. wo-bɛ-ba ɔkyena nó, ná me wɔ fie.
2SG-PROSP-come tomorrow CD NA 1SG at home
‘When you return tomorrow, I will be home.’

One relevant point to note is that LEN is independently ruled out in *ná*-marked sentences. This means that, in matrix clauses, a past-in-the-future interpretation is independently unavailable for LEN, as opposed to *a*, due to combinatorial restrictions between TAnt markers and the impossibility for bare clauses to be future-oriented. We’ll come back to this point later.

Having looked at the range of interpretations available for *ná*, let’s now zoom in on some key properties that highlight the contrast between *a* and LEN.

Thus far, we have seen that *a* and LEN are primarily restricted to past reference, and more specifically to experiential and referential interpretations, respectively. To provide a full picture, in what follows we further explore properties traditionally associated with perfect(ive) markers, including resultative and universal readings, as well as narrative progression (cf. Bertrand et al., 2022).

¹⁸Note that the ungrammaticality of (27-a) is independent of the overt adverbial *seisei* (=“now”). In other words, the sentence is not being rejected due to redundancy effects.

(vi) Resultative readings

A resultative interpretation obtains when the result state of the eventuality holds at the reference time. For matrix clauses, in the absence of overt tense, the RT coincides with the utterance time.

The following sentences exemplify a distinct contrast between LEN and *a* in resultative contexts: while for *a*, the result state of the depicted event extends to the RT, this does not apply to LEN.

(32) Context: It is cold in the room, but the window is closed. You wonder...

- a. #wó nà wó **a**-bié mpoma nó anaa?
 2SG FOC 2SG **A**-open window DEF Q
 ‘Was it you that opened the window?’
 ↘ *the window is open now*
- b. wó nà wó bié-è mpoma nó anaa?
 2SG FOC 2SG open-**LEN** window DEF Q
 ‘Was it you that opened the window?’
 ↗ *the window is open now*

(33) Can the visitor have come back? (modelled after Boadi, 2008, p. 31):

- a. ɔhɔhɔɔ nó **a**-fi adi.
 visitor DEF **A**-go out.
 ‘The visitor has left.’
 Consultant’s answer: No.
- b. ɔhɔhɔɔ nó fi-ì adi.
 visitor DEF go-**LEN** out.
 ‘The visitor left.’
 Consultant’s answer: Yes.

Based on the data above, we can conclude that only *a*-marked predicates give rise to a resultative interpretation. One related open question pertains to whether the result state can be cancelled or is part of the asserted meaning of the sentence. Judgments for sentence (33) seem to suggest that the result state cannot be cancelled. However, these are not as firm when considering other scenarios and predicates. For instance, for one consultant, both LEN and *a* can be used interchangeably in the bold-faced coordinate clauses in (34), which is unexpected if the broken state of the fence at UT does not stem from a pragmatic inference. More specifically, if the persistence of the result state is semantically encoded, we would expect the *but*-continuations to be rejected in sentences (34-a) and (34-b).

(34) Context: Kofi had to fix the fence broken by the goat.

- a. apɔnkye nó a-bu ban nó, **nanso Kofi a-siesie nó**.
 goat DEF A-break fence DEF but Kofi A-repair DEF
 ‘The goat has broken the fence, but Kofi has fixed it.’
- b. apɔnkye nó a-bu ban nó, **nanso Kofi siesie-è nó**.
 goat DEF A-break fence DEF but Kofi repair-**LEN** DEF
 ‘The goat has broken the fence, but Kofi fixed it.’

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- c. apɔ̃nkye nó bu-ù ban nó, **nanso Kofi a-siesie nó.**
 goat DEF break-LEN fence DEF but Kofi A-repair DEF
 ‘The goat broke the fence, but Kofi has fixed it.’
- d. apɔ̃nkye nó bu-ù ban nó, **nanso Kofi siesie-è nó.**
 goat DEF break-LEN fence DEF but Kofi repair-LEN DEF
 ‘The goat broke the fence, but Kofi fixed it.’

Due to the observed variability among language consultants, contexts, and predicates used, a definitive assessment is tricky. For this reason, I will leave the issue of cancellability of the result state of *a*-marked predicates for future research.

(vii) Universal readings

Universal readings occur when a predicate holds from an earlier time up to the reference time. The term “universal”¹⁹ goes back to McCawley (1971), where it’s listed as one of the four uses of the English present perfect (McCawley, 1971, p. 104). However, most languages — German being one of these — typically resort to the plain present tense form to express the same meaning.

- (35) Context: Liz moved to Tokyo two years ago and still lives there.
- a. Liz has been living in Tokyo for two years. (English)
- b. *Liz lives in Tokyo for two years.
- c. #Liz hat zwei Jahre lang in Tokio gelebt. (German)
 Liz have.PRES two year.PL long in Tokyo live.PERF
- d. Liz lebt seit zwei Jahren in Tokio.
 Liz live.PRES since two year.PL in Tokyo

Universal readings usually require an overt adverbial determining the duration or the starting point of the time-span stretching until the RT (Iatridou et al., 2001; Kiparsky, 2002). Following the diagnostics developed in Dahl (2021), the data below test the availability of universal readings with duration-quantifying (e.g., *for two weeks*) and left-boundary indicating (e.g., *since 2020*) adverbials.

- (36) Context: Kofi moved to the US three years ago and he still lives there.²⁰
- a. Kofi a-tena America mfie mmiensa.
 Kofi A-live America PL.year three
 ‘Kofi has been living in the US for three years.’
- b. #Kofi tena-à America mfie mmiensa.
 Kofi live-LEN America PL.year three
 ‘Kofi lived in the US for three years.’

¹⁹Universal readings, especially when related to the English present perfect, have also been dubbed “continuous” (McCoard, 1978) or “persistent situation”. For a more detailed overview, see Dahl, 2021.

²⁰For reasons of readability, we omit here target sentences containing *ná*. As expected, these are not compatible with a universal interpretation.

- c. #Kofi tena America mfie mmiensa.
Kofi live America PL.year three
lit. ‘Kofi lives in the US for three years.’
- (37) Context: Kofi moved to the US in 2019 and he still lives there.
- a. Kofi a-tena America firi afe 2019.
Kofi A-live America from year 2019
‘Kofi has been living in the US since 2019.’
- b. #Kofi tena-à America firi afe 2019.
Kofi live-LEN America from year 2019
‘Kofi lived in the US since 2019.’
- c. #Kofi tena America firi afe 2019.
Kofi live America from year 2019
lit. ‘Kofi lives in the US since 2019.’

The data above show that only *a* displays universal readings and, thus, bears similarities with the English perfect. Judgments are replicated for other stative and eventive predicates, as demonstrated by the sentences below. However, in order to avoid ambiguity with an experiential reading, consultants strongly preferred the insertion of the proximal deictic *nie* (=“this”).

- (38) Context: Kofi started feeling ill two weeks ago and hasn’t recovered yet.
- a. Kofi a-yare nnawɔtwe mmienu nie.
Kofi A-sick week.PL two PROX .
‘Kofi has been sick for two weeks now.’
- b. #Kofi yare-è nnawɔtwe mmienu nie.
Kofi sick-LEN week.PL two PROX .
lit. ‘This is two weeks that Kofi was sick.’
- c. #Kofi yare nnawɔtwe mmienu nie.
Kofi sick week.PL two PROX .
lit. ‘This is two weeks that Kofi is sick.’
- (39) Context: Kofi is taking part in a dance marathon. Last person dancing wins! He started forty minutes ago and he’s still going!
- a. Kofi a-sa donhwere aduanan (nie).
Kofi A-dance minute.PL forty PROX
‘Kofi has been dancing for forty minutes (now).’
- b. #Kofi sa-à yɛ donhwere aduanan (nie).
Kofi dance-LEN COP minute.PL forty PROX
‘Kofi danced for forty minutes (now).’
- c. #Kofi re-sa donhwere aduanan (nie).
Kofi minute.PL forty PROX
‘Kofi is dancing for forty minutes (now).’

(viii) *Narrative progression*

TAM forms can also be deployed for narrative progression. Typically, the preterite or the perfective past, unlike the imperfective past, can be used to progress a story from an earlier point to a later point (in the past) (cf. Kamp & Rohrer, 1983). In the following scenario, a short text is being presented to the consultant, who offers a translation in Asante Twi, using their preferred TAnt marker to recall the story. Note that predicates that temporally follow those in the immediately preceding sentence are boldfaced. By contrast, predicates that do not induce a strict narrative progression are underlined.

- (40) *Context:* Kofi’s mum is quite controlling. She wants to know every single detail in Kofi’s daily routine, after he leaves for school in the morning. Kofi makes sure he won’t leave out even the smallest detail!

Target text:

- a. I **walked** to school. I **entered** the classroom. I **sat** at my desk, I **opened** my backpack, I **took out** the notebook. Then I was hungry. I **pulled out** an apple. It was rotten.

Translation offered:

- b. Me nante **kɔ-ɔ̃** Sukuu nà **mewura-à** Sukuu dan nó mu. Me
1SG walk go-LEN school COORD enter-LEN school class DEF inside. 1SG
tena-à m’akonwa so na **me-bue-è** me Bag mu.
sit-LEN 1POSS.1SG=seat on COORD 1SG-open-LEN POSS.1SG bag inside
Me **fa-à** me book nà ná ekɔm de me. Me
1SG take-LEN POSS.1SG book COORD NA hunger COP 1SG 1SG
yi-ì apple nà ná aporɔ̃.
bring.out-LEN apple COORD NA rotten

As the translation in (40-b) shows, the consultant consistently chose LEN to progress the story. Interestingly, *ná* was chosen instead for the only two (stative) predicates that were co-temporal to the preceding event. As a follow-up, the consultant was asked to judge a text where the boldfaced TAM forms were replaced with *a*. The text was rejected.²¹

As part of a task reversal, consultants were asked to order the following sentences chronologically. Consultants’ choices confirm that narrative progression is the default result from the use of LEN (see (41)), unless this is overridden by world knowledge and plausibility considerations (see (42)). Interestingly, a sequence of events cannot be reversed for *a*-marked predicates, even when narrative regression is more plausible than progression, as is demonstrated in sentences (43) and (44).

- (41) a. Kwesi tɔ-ɔ̃ ban.
Kwesi buy-LEN fence
‘Kwesi bought a fence.’ (E₁)
- b. Aponkye bu-ù (ban) nó.
goat break-LEN fence DEF
‘The goat broke the fence.’ (E₂)
Temporal ordering: E₁ < E₂

²¹The consultant’s feedback was: *It would only work if you’re describing things as they happen at the moment. For example during a phone call.*

- (42) a. Kwesi siesie-è ban nó.
Kwesi repair-LEN fence DEF
'Kwesi fixed the fence.' (E₁)
b. Aponkye bu-ù nó.
goat break-LEN DEF
'The goat broke it.' (E₂)
Temporal ordering: E₂ < E₁
- (43) a. Kwesi a-tɔ ban.
Kwesi A-buy fence
'Kwesi has bought a fence.' (E₁)
b. Aponkye a-bu (ban) nó.
goat A-break fence DEF
'The goat has broken the fence.' (E₂)
Temporal ordering: E₁ < E₂
- (44) a. Kwesi a-siesie ban nó.
Kwesi A-repair fence DEF
'Kwesi has fixed the fence.' (E₁)
b. Aponkye a-bu nó.
goat A-break DEF
'The goat has broken it.' (E₂)
Temporal ordering: E₁ < E₂

(ix) Actuality entailments

Finally, we take a look at one last property that has been often associated with perfective aspect (PFV): actuality entailments (AE). It has been observed (Bhatt, 1999; Hacquard, 2009) that PFV-marked ability modals entail the truth of their prejacent in the actual world. Crucially, the same does not follow when imperfective aspect (NPFV) is used instead. This is illustrated in the following French example²² taken from Hacquard (2009, p. 280).

- (45) a. Jane pouvait traverser le lac à la nage, mais elle ne le
Jane can.PAST.NPFV cross DEF lake by DEF swim but she NEG CL
fit jamais.
do.PAST.PFV ever
'Jane could (was able to) swim across the lake, but she never did.'
b. Jane put traverser le lac à la nage, # mais elle ne le
Jane can.PAST.PFV cross the lake by DEF swim but she NEG CL
fit pas.
do.PAST.PFV NEG
'Jane could (was able to) swim across the lake, but she didn't.'

In Asante Twi, both LEN- and *a*-marked predicates combining with the ability modal

²²The sentences are quoted verbatim; the glosses are my own.

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tumi display actuality entailments. To convey past ability, the particle *ná*²³ must be employed instead.²⁴

- (46) Akua [tumi tɔ-ɔ / a-tumi a-tɔ] efiɛ, # nanso w-a-n-tɔ.
 Akua can buy-LEN / A-can CONS-buy house but 3SG-LEN-NEG-buy
 Intended: ‘Akua was able to buy a house, but she didn’t.’
- (47) Ná Akua tumi tɔ efiɛ, nanso w-a-n-tɔ.
 NA Akua can buy house but 3SG-a-NEG-buy
 ‘Akua was able to buy a house, but she didn’t.’

Interim summary

In this section, we have detailed some of the semantic properties exhibited by the three TAnt markers LEN, *a* and *ná*. From a purely temporal standpoint, these show a clear divide between *a* on the one hand, and the other two markers on the other: while LEN and *ná* are strictly compatible with referential readings, the prefix *a* covers the remaining range of interpretations encompassing experiential, resultative and universal readings alike. Moreover, an interesting sub-division emerges when it comes to aspectual properties, with *ná* generally felicitous in imperfective contexts such as stative and habitual, while *a* and LEN both entailing the actuality of a proposition, pointing to a perfective aspectual profile. A summary of the findings in this section is presented in table 3.2. Here, the symbol “[?]x” for LEN’s experiential readings represents the fact that, though largely unavailable, these readings were simply dispreferred by some speakers in certain contexts. The findings reported here will serve as the basis for the semantic analysis put forward in the next section.

²³The fact that *ná* does not give rise to a habitual interpretation in this instance should not surprise, under the assumption that ability modals are stative.

²⁴The sentence in (46) is not a minimal pair, since the possibility modal *tumi* cannot be inflected with LEN when expressing ability. To alleviate concerns about potential confounding factors resulting from having an elided *tumi* in the coordinate clause, the simple sentence *Akua can.buy.a/LEN house.* was additionally tested in a scenario where the house could have been bought but was ultimately rented. Consultants’ judgments remained consistent.

	<i>a</i>	LEN	<i>ná</i>
<i>Referential</i>	x	✓	(stat/hab)
<i>Experiential</i>	✓	?x	x
<i>Modification by LTA</i>	x	✓	(stat/hab)
<i>Habitual</i>	x	x	✓
<i>Future reference</i>	x	x	✓
<i>Resultative</i>	✓	x	x
<i>Universal</i>	✓	x	x
<i>Narrative progression</i>	?	✓	x
<i>Actuality entailment</i>	✓	✓	x

Table 3.2: Summary: Semantic properties of TAnt markers

Combinatorial restrictions

Having looked at the semantic properties of the three TAnt markers mostly in isolation, as a final note, let's consider the co-occurrences of each TAnt marker with the other two. We have already seen in (30-b) that *ná* and *a* can co-occur in future contexts. Their co-occurrence further extends to past contexts, yielding a past perfect-like interpretation. By contrast, LEN is ruled out in *ná*-marked clauses, as illustrated below:

- (48) Context: Ama is such a great cook. She enjoys nothing more in life than baking for her friends. Last Tuesday I stopped by her place and guess what?
- a. **Ná** Ama **a**-noa aduane.
 NA Ama a-cook food
 'Ama had cooked some food.'
 Comment: *By the time you got there she had already cooked (maybe in the morning or so).*
- b. ***Ná** Ama noa-**à** aduane.
 NA Ama cook-LEN food
 Intended: 'Ama had already cooked food.'
- (49) Context: You're going to eat right now but Kofi asks you to wait for him. You reply: 'I will have already eaten by then.'
- a. **Ná** m'**a**-didi dada.
 NA 1SG=A-eat already
 'I'll have eaten already by then.'
- b. ***Ná** me-didí-**ì** dada.
 NA 1SG-eat-LEN already
 Intended: 'I'll have eaten already by then.'

In (48) and (49), the event depicted by the main predicate is located in the past of the time denoted by *ná*. On the other hand, LEN-inflected predicates in *ná*-marked clauses lead to ungrammaticality and are therefore always excluded, regardless of the context.

Note that, when in the scope of *ná*, a *vacuous* interpretation for *a* is not possible.

(50) Context: Your village at the border with Togo lies at the foot of a high mountain. You know barely anyone who ever attempted to climb it, but rumour has it that Afiba has succeeded at least once before.

- a. #Ná Afiba a-foro bepɔ nó.
 NA Afiba A-climb mountain DEF
 Intended: ‘Afiba climbed the mountain (then).’
 Comment₁: *No. But it could work in this situation: Afiba went to the mountain area with her friends. Then suddenly Afiba disappears and no one knows where she is. Later that day they realize why they couldn’t find her.*
 Comment₂: *No. It means that at some given time she had already climbed the mountain.*

The marker LEN exhibits additional combinatorial restrictions in that it cannot surface in the presence of the prefix *a* or any other tempo-aspectual marker, as shown in (51) (cf. Armenante & Lecavelier, 2024; Lecavelier, 2022; Osam, 2008). In fact, all TAM bound morphemes are in complementary distribution with one another, as further illustrated in (52).

(51) *Complementary distribution of LEN with other TAM affixal morphemes:*

- a. Afiba (*a-)noa-à aduane.
 Afiba A-cook-LEN food
 b. Afiba (*re-)noa-à aduane.
 Afiba PROG-cook-LEN food
 c. Afiba (*bɛ-)noa-à aduane.
 Afiba PROSP-cook-LEN food

(52) *Complementary distribution of TAM affixal morphemes (excluding LEN):*

- a. *Afiba a-re-noa aduane.
 Afiba A-PROG-cook food
 Intended: ‘Afiba has been cooking food.’
 b. *Afiba a-bɛ-noa aduane.
 Afiba A-PROSP-cook food
 Intended: ‘Afiba will have cooked food.’
 c. *Afiba re-bɛ-noa aduane.
 Afiba PROG-PROSP-cook food
 Intended: ‘Afiba will be cooking food.’

In contrast, the free morpheme *ná* can not only co-occur with *a*, but also with all the other affixal markers, excluding LEN.

(53) *Complementary distribution of ná with other TAM affixal morphemes:*

- a. Kofi ba-à nó, ná Afiba a-noa aduane.
 Kofi come-LEN CD NA Afiba A-cook food
 ‘When Kofi arrived, Kofi had (already) cooked food.’
 b. Kofi ba-à nó, ná Afiba re-noa aduane.
 Kofi come-LEN CD NA Afiba PROG-cook food

- ‘When Kofi arrived, Afiba was cooking food.’
- c. Kofi ka-à se ná ɔ-bɛ-ba.
 Kofi say-LEN COMP NA 3SG-PROSP-come
 ‘Kofi said he would come.’

We now turn to the analysis of temporal meaning in Asante (Twi), beginning with sentences lacking overt tense/aspectual marking. Subsequently, our attention will shift to the three TAnt markers and their compositional interpretation in clauses containing them.

3.3 The semantics of Asante Twi TAnt markers

Building on the properties and the distribution detailed earlier, this section spells out the semantics of the three TAnt markers in Asante Twi, further exploring how they contribute to the temporal interpretation of matrix clauses. To the best of my knowledge, what follows constitutes the first attempt at a formal semantic analysis of temporal meaning in Asante Twi (or more broadly, in the Akan languages), in that most accounts have only looked at the syntactic or morphophonological properties of Akan’s temporal markers, or — as we have seen in section 3.2.2 — have only offered informal descriptions of their meaning.

In what follows, I will argue that:

- (i) Firstly, the particle *ná* denotes a distal pronominal tense which excludes the utterance time as a suitable antecedent.
- (ii) Secondly, the prefix *a* is a hybrid perfect aspect with meaning components that are akin to both resultative and experiential perfects.
- (iii) Finally, the suffix LEN also involves a hybrid TAM form, in that it conflates past tense and perfective aspect.

Crucially, I will further propose that present reference for Asante unmarked predicates does not arise through a covert present tense, rather via a default interpretation due to the evaluation proform t_c . It follows that a present interpretation emerges only in the absence of any overt tense introducing a reference time (other than UT) into the composition. Despite being semantically tenseless, bare clauses do project covert aspect operators, which are responsible for the observed stative and habitual interpretations.

3.3.1 The temporal interpretation of bare clauses

Before presenting a formal analysis of the three TAnt markers, let’s take a look at the temporal interpretation of clauses lacking overt TAM marking in Asante Twi. This will indeed prove to be relevant for the interpretation of both *ná*- *a*-marked clauses, especially.

In the brief review in section 3.2.2, we saw that the absence of overt TAM marking (or the null form) in Akan languages has been associated with a present (Boadi, 2008; Duah & Savić, 2020), a non-future (Osam, 2008) or a temporally neutral (Dolphyne, 1987) interpretation. Furthermore, most accounts assume that stative/habitual meaning must also be semantically encoded in dedicated covert operators (which may or may not coincide with the covert present). Based on the data presented in section 3.2.3, the

claim that bare clauses yield non-future or temporally unspecified interpretations must be rejected. In fact, past-oriented contexts strictly require overt realization of TAnt marking, as shown in examples (16), (17) and (18-a) repeated below as (54), (55) and (56):

- (54) Kofi wu *(-ù) nnora.
 Kofi die -LEN yesterday
 lit. ‘Kofi dies(/died) yesterday.’
- (55) Context: I was just wondering what Kofi was up to yesterday when you stopped by...
 a. *(ná) Kofi re-didi nnora.
 NA Kofi PROG-eat yesterday.
 lit. ‘Kofi is(/was) eating yesterday.’
- (56) Context: I finally found out why Kwesi was so grumpy yesterday. Apparently he had skipped lunch...
 a. *(ná) ekɔm de Kwesi ennora.
 NA hunger COP Kwesi yesterday
 ‘Kofi was hungry yesterday.’

Moreover, we have demonstrated that bare clauses exhibit stative as well as habitual interpretations, with the distinction marked tonally for certain predicates (see examples (22) and (23)).

Given these observations, we face two options for the analysis of bare clauses: (i) they exhibit a covert present tense that evaluates the clause with respect to the utterance time, akin to English PRES; (ii) they project no tense operator at LF and, thus, receive a default present interpretation if no other operator can supply a reference time. For reasons that will become apparent in section 3.4, I am going to pursue the second option. More specifically, I will assume that, if the reference time is not explicitly introduced into the composition, this is automatically “replaced” by the EvalT.

Recall that each sentence is evaluated with respect to the actual world w_c and the context time t_c (that is the utterance time). As for the aspectual interpretation, I will assume that this comes about via covert aspect operators STAT and HAB, which close off the eventuality argument of the verb.²⁵ Some (simplified) semantics for STAT are given below:

$$(57) \quad \llbracket \text{STAT} \rrbracket = \lambda p_{\langle v, t \rangle} . \lambda t_{(i)} . \exists e [t \subseteq \tau(e) \ \& \ p(e)]$$

According to the semantics formulated in (57), STAT maps a predicate of eventualities to a predicate of times, such that these hold of t if for some eventuality e , its running time surrounds t .

For the habitual meaning, we need something more. I will adopt a slightly revised version of Seth Cable’s analysis of imperfective habitual sentences in Tlingit (Cable, 2022), which introduces modal quantification over possible worlds in which a plurality of p-eventualities obtain.

²⁵Remember that “e” stands for eventualities, which comprise both states and events.

- (58) $\llbracket \text{HAB} \rrbracket = \lambda w_{\langle s \rangle} . \lambda p_{\langle s, \langle v, t \rangle \rangle} . \lambda t_{\langle i \rangle} . \forall w' [w' \in \text{HABIT}(w, t), \exists e [t \subseteq \tau(e) \ \& \ p^*(w')(e)]]$
 a. $\text{HABIT}(w, t) = \lambda w'$. the habitualities²⁶ in w at t are realized in w' .

In (58), pluralities and not single eventualities are considered, in line with much work on habitual meaning (see Ferreira, 2016, a.o.). Importantly, the operator *HABIT* introduces an accessibility-like relation that relates world and time of evaluation w and t , where a certain disposition for an eventuality holds, to possible worlds w' where said eventualities are effectively realized. Following this modal definition of habitual meaning, HAB-marked predicates in Asante Twi may involve non-actualized eventualities (i.e., eventualities which do not hold true of the actual world) as well as actualized eventualities.²⁷

Armed with these tools, let us apply the semantics in (57) to the bare clause in (59) containing a stative predicate. The resulting LF and truth-conditions we derive are given in (60) and (61).

- (59) Afiba yare.
 Afiba sick
 ‘Afiba is sick.’

- (61) $\llbracket (60) \rrbracket = 1$ iff $\exists e [t_c \subseteq \tau(e) \ \& \ \text{sick}(w_c)(e)(A)]$
 ‘There is an eventuality e , such that its running time surrounds the context time t_c and e is an eventuality of Afiba being sick in the actual world.’

Looking at the LF in (60), the computation of the truth conditions produces a predicate of times at TP-level (the set of times that are surrounded by the running time of the given eventuality). Since no structurally higher element provides a suitable RT, the system supplies the framed variable t_c .²⁸ Consequently, the sentence is evaluated with respect to the context time, that is the utterance time in matrix contexts.

²⁶Habitualities comprise “habits”, “propensities”, “dispositions”, “functions”, and “obligations” (cf. Bittner, 2008; Boneh & Doron, 2008; Cable, 2022)

²⁷Whether this is the right treatment for habitual meaning (that is expressed via the covert HAB operator) in Asante is tangential to our general purposes here and offers an interesting question for future research.

²⁸Given the absence of non-present readings for unmarked matrix sentences, I’m excluding the possibility that the TP’s temporal argument is existentially closed.

Let’s turn now to habitual interpretations of bare matrix clauses. One example is illustrated in (62), with LF and truth conditions in (63) and (64), respectively.

(62) Kofi dí
Kofi eat.HAB
salmon.
salmon
‘Kofi eats salmon.’

(64) $\llbracket (63) \rrbracket = 1$ iff $\forall w' [w' \in HABIT(w_c, t_c), \exists e [t_c \subseteq \tau(e) \ \& \ *eat(w')(e)(\iota x[salmon(x)])(K)]$
‘In all possible worlds w' , in which the habitualities that hold in the actual world w_c at t_c are realized, there are (multiple) eventualities of Kofi eating salmon²⁹ that surround t_c .’

The starred function “*eat” in (64) produces a plurality of events of Kofi eating salmon surrounding the utterance time. This, in turn, entails that Kofi *usually* eats salmon at UT. In the current implementation, the clausal verb can only receive an opaque interpretation. Consequently, the eventualities it denotes are realized in all the possible worlds w' , but not necessarily in w_c .³⁰

Having introduced some foundational notions for the composition of (unmarked) clauses in Asante Twi, we will now delve into the semantics of the three TAnt markers *ná*, *a* and LEN, and how these affect the temporal interpretation of a sentence.

²⁹Without going into the details of the computation, I am assuming here that the predicative bare noun “salmon” is turned into an individual via the ι -typeshift (cf. Chierchia, 1998). Note that the resulting meaning of $\iota x[salmon(x)]$ is not definite, given the competition of the bare noun with the definite article *nó* (see Dayal, 2004. For further discussion of why the ι -typeshift is to be preferred to the \exists -typeshift in Akan, see Bombi et al., 2019).

³⁰A transparent/*de re* interpretation of the verb is ruled out by Percus (2000)’s Generalization X, according to which intensional variables of the verb (in this case, “ w_1 ” and “ e_3 ”) must be locally bound. Moreover, co-indexing the verb’s world variable “ w_1 ” with the non-local binder “ λw_0 ” would result in vacuous quantification over habituality worlds.

3.3.2 The semantics of *ná*

In this section, I will present a semantic analysis for the particle *ná* that appeals to a pronominal treatment of tense. More specifically, I will argue that *ná* denotes a deictic distal tense, which locates an event at a specific time that is not the utterance time. For this reason, its distal meaning sits in direct opposition with the proximal meaning conveyed by the unmarked form.

Given the distribution of *ná*, one obvious question is the following: what evidence do we have in support of a (pronominal) tense analysis rather than a temporal adverbial one? As things stand, the particle *ná* shares semantic features akin to the English deictic *then*, which has been argued to involve both anaphoric and deictic (distal) uses (cf. Schiffrin, 1992). Moreover, as we have seen so far, *ná*, unlike all the other TAM markers, does not attach to the stem of the verb but occupies a left-peripheral surface position. If *ná* patterns with *then* from both a semantic and a syntactic standpoint, a tempting option is to treat it as a temporal adverbial. I will argue against an adverbial status for *ná* on conceptual, syntactic and semantic grounds:

(i) Firstly, *ná*, unlike canonical temporal adverbials, does not require any overt tense/aspectual marking — in fact, it’s even incompatible with the past-oriented marker LEN. One possibility is that the particle *ná* is licensed by a covert (past/tense) tense, which introduces the reference time. However, this option is unappealing on purely conceptual grounds, as it involves the ad-hoc stipulation that such a temporal operator only surfaces alongside *ná* — considering unmarked clauses in Akan cannot receive non-present temporal interpretations.

(ii) Secondly, *ná*, as opposed to temporal adverbials, cannot be focused. This point has been convincingly argued by Kandybowicz (2015), whose examples are illustrated below³¹ (orthography and glossing are mine):

(65) *ennora ná Kofi kɔ-ò dwaso.*
 yesterday FOC Kofi go-LEN market
 ‘It was yesterday that Kofi went to the market.’ (Kandybowicz, 2015, p. 9)

(66) **Ná ná Kofi a-kɔ dwaso.*
 NA FOC Kofi A-go market
 Intended: ‘It was then that Kofi went to the market.’ (Kandybowicz, 2015, p. 10)

(iii) Finally, it has been observed that, in languages possessing a relative present, attitude reports in past-under-past but not in present-under-past embeddings can be modified by a deictic adverb like *then*, under a simultaneous interpretation (Ogihara & Sharvit, 2012; Tsilia, 2021a; Vostrikova, 2018). The *then*-puzzle is illustrated below, with examples on Hebrew taken from Ogihara & Sharvit (2012):

(67) “*Then*-effects” in Hebrew

³¹Kandybowicz dispels possible haplology-motivated concerns regarding the pairing of the same segment /*na*/ by showing that the focus marker and the tense particle can co-occur in all other instances (see Kandybowicz, 2015, p. 10).

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- a. lifney alpayim šana, Yosef xašav še Miriam ahava oto
before two-thousand year Yosef think.PAST that Miriam love.PAST him
az.
then
- b. lifney alpayim šana, Yosef xašav še Miriam ohevet oto
before two-thousand year Yosef think.PAST that Miriam love.PRES him
(#az).
then
Intended: ‘Joseph’s thought two thousand years ago: “Mary loves me now”’

Crucially, we will see in section 3.4 that *ná* exhibits the reversed pattern: in the scope of a past-tensed attitude verb, it can still yield simultaneous readings when it modifies unmarked predicates, but not past-tensed ones.

Having presented some empirical evidence in favour of a tense rather than adverbial status for the particle *ná*,³² let’s examine its semantic contribution within a sentence.

In section 3.2.3, we have observed that *ná* is only felicitous in referential contexts, where it picks out a contextually salient time before or after UT. Crucially, present time interpretations were strictly excluded for *ná*, indicating a distal temporal meaning. For these reasons, I will adopt a pronominal analysis (see Heim, 1994; Kratzer, 1998; Partee, 1973, among others) and propose that *ná* simply denotes a temporal interval. This, however, comes with the presuppositional restriction that said temporal interval does not include UT. The lexical entry for *ná*, including its definedness conditions, is provided below.

- (68) a. $\llbracket ná_7 \rrbracket$ defined iff there is a contextually salient time $g(7) [\neg(g(7) \circ t_c)]$
b. When defined, $\llbracket ná_7 \rrbracket = g(7)$

As (68) shows, *ná* denotes an indexed variable, whose value is assigned via the context-dependent function g , which returns a suitable value that satisfies the definedness conditions (i.e., that $g(7)$ does not overlap the utterance time). The semantics adopted here differs only minimally from that proposed in Zimmermann & Duah (2022) (see (69)).

- (69) *Semantics of ná adapted from Zimmermann & Duah (2022, p. 119).*
 $\llbracket ná \rrbracket = \lambda p_{\langle i, \langle s, t \rangle \rangle} . \lambda t^*_{\langle i \rangle} . \lambda t_{\langle i \rangle} : t \neq t^* . \lambda w_{\langle s \rangle} . p(t)(w)$

The two analyses share the core meaning of the particle: its temporal distancing from a deictic center, built in its presupposition. However, they differ in two aspects. In (69), the pronominal component of *ná* is severed from its lexical semantics and outsourced to a different tense pronoun (t). In (68), *ná* is that tense pronoun. Furthermore, following the current approach *ná* is strictly deictic, thus excluding the utterance time. In Zimmermann & Duah (2022), it need not. We will see that a built-in deictic feature will be key to correctly capture the interpretations attested in embedded contexts.³³

³²For a more exhaustive discussion of *ná*’s categorial status, see Kandybowicz (2015).

³³In all fairness, its treatment as a relative rather than deictic tense, does not bear any particular relevance in Zimmermann & Duah (2022)’s account, given that this is primarily concerned with matrix clauses containing *ná*. Also, the semantics sketched in (69) allows for an elegant unified analysis with its LT counterpart.

Given its rigid pre-subject position, I will follow Kandybowicz (2015) and assume that *ná* occupies the T-head position, while subject DPs in Asante are base-generated in [spec,VP].³⁴ Inserting *ná* into a bare clause will produce the following structure:

- (70) **Ná** Afiba yare.
NA Afiba sick.
 ‘Afiba was/{will be} sick (then).’

Compared to bare clauses, *ná*-marked clauses may not project the EvalT t_c at LF. In a way, t_c -evaluation is already lexicalized in *ná*, since this expresses distance from the temporal deictic center.

To compute the meaning of the sentence, a covert aspectual operator once more needs to saturate the eventuality argument of the predicate “yare”. In this case, one suitable operator is STAT, since the verb is stative. Subsequently, applying the predicate of times denoted by the AspP in (71) to $g(7)$ yields the following definedness conditions and truth-conditions:

- (72) a. $\llbracket (71) \rrbracket$ defined iff there is a contextually salient time $g(7)$ $[\neg(g(7) \circ t_c)]$
 b. When defined, $\llbracket (71) \rrbracket = 1$ iff $\exists e[g(7) \subseteq \tau(e) \ \& \ sick(w_c)(e)(A)]$
Paraphrase: ‘There is an eventuality e , such that its running time surrounds $g(7)$ and e is an eventuality of Afiba being sick in the actual world.’

Since the reference time $g(7)$ is only restricted to temporal intervals not including UT, the truth-conditions in (72) are compatible with both past-oriented and future-oriented scenarios.

We are now in a position to explain why *ná* gives rise only to habitual readings when it combines with eventive verbs. In the case of no overt aspect marking, the Asp-head can only be filled by the operators STAT or HAB. The former is however blocked due to incompatibility with the Aktionsart of eventive verbs. It follows that the eventuality argument of the verb can only be quantificationally bound by HAB. It is immaterial whether the T-head position is occupied by *ná* or left empty. This is exemplified by the sentence in (73), whose corresponding LF is in (74).

³⁴Kandybowicz provides convincing evidence against a higher left-peripheral position of *ná* based on syntactic movement of floating quantifiers.

(73) Ná Kofi dí salmon.
 NA Kofi eat.HAB salmon
 ‘Kofi {used to eat salmon}/
 {will be eating salmon}.’

The truth-conditions computed for (74) are as follows:

(75) $\llbracket (74) \rrbracket = 1$ iff $\forall w' [w' \in HABIT(w_c, g(7)), \exists e [g(7) \subseteq \tau(e) \ \& \ *eat(w')(e)(\iota x[salmon(x)])(K)]$
 with $g(7)$ not overlapping UT
 ‘In all possible worlds w' , in which the habitualities that hold in the actual world w_c at $g(7)$ are realized, there are (multiple) eventualities of Kofi eating salmon that surround $g(7)$.’

There is, of course, an alternative view to the one offered above: assume that $ná$ ’s anti-present restriction is not semantically encoded but arises pragmatically. Let’s suppose that $ná$ is temporally unrestricted and, therefore, presupposes nothing at all. Under this hypothesis, its incompatibility with present reference would stem from its competition with the null form. This, in turn, in matrix clauses, projects t_c , thus presupposing UT-inclusion. On this analysis, $ná$ would roughly mean *at any given time*, while the unmarked form strictly refers to the current time.

Since t_c is presuppositionally stronger than $ná$, the anti-present meaning of the overt marker would come about by virtue of not having used the null form. This implicature can be derived via a mechanism akin to Heim’s *Maximize Presupposition!* (Heim, 1991). Despite its elegance, this solution can only account for matrix contexts, whereas it makes the wrong predictions in embedded contexts. As will be demonstrated later in section 3.4, $ná$ -embeddings show a range of interpretations overlapping with bare embeddings, which is unexpected under a pragmatic view. More importantly, $ná$ ’s restriction to non-present reference survives even in complement clauses of past-oriented attitude verbs. In these contexts, the UT-exclusion cannot result from competition with bare clauses, given that in these cases the evaluation time is supplied by the attitude verb. If this is past oriented, then the bare clause will be evaluated with respect to a time preceding t_c rather than t_c itself (for details, see section 3.5. Put differently, $ná$ ’s deictic restriction could be blamed on pragmatic competition only if its competitor were an indexical present. However, Asante Twi does not have one.

3.3.3 The semantics of LEN

We saw in section 3.2.3 that LEN, on the one hand, involves properties that are characteristic of the past tense: it makes reference to (specific) times preceding the local evaluation time and it can be modified by (past-oriented) locating temporal adverbials. On the other hand, it exhibits a perfective aspectual profile in that it actualizes the depicted eventuality (under ability modals) and it is used for narrative progression. The status of LEN as a past perfective is further strengthened by Bertrand et al. (2022)'s crosslinguistic investigation, where forms that share LEN's semantic properties are classified as past perfectives. These forms, typically, lack obligatory resultative readings and cannot yield universal interpretations. However, one point of contrast pertains to the availability of experiential readings. In Bertrand et al. (2022, p. 9), only 2 out of 6 forms identified as past perfectives have been shown to be felicitous in experiential contexts. In this respect, LEN seems to align with those forms not allowing for experiential readings, though, as previously discussed, some speakers do accept these interpretations in certain scenarios. We will come back to this point in the next section.

In the light of its mixed semantic properties, I propose a hybrid semantics for LEN, comprising both a pronominal tense and a perfective aspect. I posit that, structurally, LEN splits into two distinct projections, namely a past-restricted tense pronoun sitting in T and a PFV-like operator in Asp. This analysis combines a pronominal analysis for its tense component and existential analysis for its aspectual part.³⁵ The basic LF structure for a LEN-marked predicate is given in (76), with the semantics for PFV and $past_{2,5}$ in (77).

(77) The meaning of LEN:

- a. $\llbracket \text{PFV} \rrbracket(p_{\langle v,t \rangle})(\llbracket \text{past}_{2,5} \rrbracket(i))$ defined iff $g(2) < g(5)$
- b. When defined, $\llbracket \text{PFV} \rrbracket(p_{\langle v,t \rangle})(\llbracket \text{past}_{2,5} \rrbracket) = 1$ iff $\exists e[\tau(e) \subseteq g(2) \ \& \ p(e)]$

Note that LEN's tense component $past_{2,5}$ is a doubly indexed pronoun whose first index is free and picks out the RT, while the second index is bound by the local EvalT (that is t_c in matrix clauses). These semantics allow us to derive the meaning for the sentence in (78) as follows:

³⁵For a similar proposal for Samoan, see Bochnak et al. (2019) and Hohaus (2019).

(78) Afiba di-ì salmon.
 Afiba eat-LEN salmon
 ‘Afiba ate salmon.’

- (80) a. $\llbracket (79) \rrbracket$ defined iff $g(2) < t_c$
 b. $\llbracket (79) \rrbracket = 1$ iff $\exists e[\tau(e) \subseteq g(2) \ \& \ eat(w')(e)(\iota x[salmon(x)])(A)]$
 ‘There is an eventuality e , such that its running time is entirely included in $g(2)$ and e is an eventuality of Afiba eating salmon in the actual world.’

Compared to the LF for the bare clause in (60), the LF in (79) is not tense-deficient, but introduces the RT into the composition via the pronoun $past_{2,5}$. This receives a value, restricted to times preceding $g(5)$ (i.e., t_c in matrix clauses), via the assignment function g . As a result, $past_{2,5}$ denotes a relative tense, whose EvalT need not coincide with the utterance time. The alternative analysis is to treat LEN’s tense component as an absolute tense. On this view, the EvalT would strictly denote UT, regardless of the syntactic embedding. Although the two analyses yield equivalent truth-conditions for matrix clauses, their predictions crucially differ in embedded contexts, as will be explored in the next section.

A note on LEN and perfectivity

The empirical data discussed so far lend support for a perfective analysis of LEN. However, Duah & Savić (2020) put forward a convincing argument that potentially undermines this analysis, namely the lack of telicity effects for some LEN-marked predicates. This point is elucidated by the following data:

(81) ɔ-si-i n-taadeɛ no, nanso ɔ-a-n-wie.
 3SG-wash-LEN PL-cloth DEF but 3SG-a-NEG-finish
Intended: ‘He washed the clothes, but he didn’t finish (the job).’ (from Duah & Savić, 2020, p. 86)

The *nanso*-continuation in (81) asserts that the event denoted by the preceding sentence is not completed. Yet, the sentence is felicitous despite the LEN marker. What makes matters more complicated is that one cannot appeal to the notion of plurality in that, according to our consultants, (81) is felicitous even in a scenario where not a single piece of clothing has been washed completely.

These data invite reflection on event-structure and part-whole relations. Let's assume that events, just like individual objects, can be subdivided into parts, namely subevents (cf. Portner, 2003). Should perfective events then involve an exhaustivity requirement on all their subevent parts? One possibility is that sentences such as (81) involve the completion of only part of the superevent. This possible explanation is further corroborated by the fact that the consultants who accept (81) do so only on condition that *some washing* was completed within a given temporal window. I speculate that in the default case — that is, when no detelicizing sentence follows — there exists quantification over all the relevant (sub)events of the context set. In other words, all the relevant subevents of clothes-washing within g(2) are considered. These, in sum, amount to a superevent of washing clothes by the agent.

Additional evidence comes from achievements. Verbs belonging to this class typically depict punctual (bounded) events, which cannot be further sub-divided into discrete parts. Crucially, these predicates do exhibit telicity effects when modified by LEN, as the following example illustrates.

- (82) Me-kɔ-ɔ Paris, #nanso **m'a-n-duru**.
 1SG-go-LEN Paris but **1SG=A-NEG-reach**
Intended: 'I went to Paris, but I didn't reach (it).'

One potential objection to (82) is that achievements only constitute an isolated case and yield telicity effects independent of grammatical aspect. This, however, is disputed in the light of the acceptability of incomplete achievements that are modified by non-perfective aspect. If LEN were not perfective but aspectually neutral, then coercion of achievements into non-punctual unbounded actionality classes (e.g., activities) should be possible the way it is generally possible when achievement predicates are modified, for instance, by imperfective aspect (e.g., *John was losing his mind over that girl*).

Further support for a perfective analysis of LEN comes from the interpretation of LEN-marked stative predicates. It is a well-known crosslinguistic fact that statives modified by perfective aspect give rise to an inchoative interpretation (cf. a.o. Anagnostopoulou et al., 1998, p. 171), which is in line with what we find in Asante Twi. This is illustrated in (6-a), repeated below.

- (83) Afiba yare-è.
 Afiba sick-LEN
 Possible: 'Afiba got sick.'

Translations for stative verbs bearing LEN morphology as in (83) can contain “become” or “get”. To express past states whose starting point is indefinite, the particle *ná* must be used instead.

Complementary distribution with *ná*

The analyses put forward for *ná* and LEN suggest a potential overlap in use, in that both markers preferably occur in referential contexts. They, however, show some sort of division of labor in expressing (past) temporal reference, in that LEN correlates with episodic, punctual eventualities while *ná* with states or habits. Their specialized use might

explain one important empirical finding: the fact that *ná* and LEN cannot co-occur. I will suggest that the reason for their mutual exclusive distribution may be ascribed to the fact that both their tense variables occupy the same position as heads of the tense phrase³⁶.

One intriguing possibility not pursued here is that *ná*, as opposed to LEN, comes with an anti-perfective selectional requirement, preventing the particle from combining with a perfective viewpoint aspect. This, in turn, would explain why *ná* can only combine with STAT and HAB.

3.3.4 The semantics of *a*

The analysis that I propose for *a* also involves the interplay of distinct grammatical operators as well as different levels of interpretation. Recall that, given an appropriate context, the prefixal TAnt marker can yield seemingly different readings: resultative, experiential and universal. While the first two have been often lumped together under the rubric of “existential reading”, the latter is associated with rare occurrence in natural languages.

According to the typological classification in Bertrand et al. (2022), perfect forms that exhibit the same properties as Asante *a* are categorized as *hybrid*. This term refers to perfects that share properties of both experiential and resultative forms. Languages with a hybrid perfect include Swahili (“me”), Niuean (“kua”), St’át’imcets (“plan”), Japanese and, of course, English (“Present Perfect”). Crucially, among these, only the English Present Perfect is compatible with both universal readings and locating temporal adverbs. This suggests that, whatever mechanism can derive the attested interpretations for English is likely a good proxy for Asante Twi *a*, modulo differences relating to verb type and morpho-syntactic constraints.

Semantic accounts of the English (Present) Perfect can be grouped into three different types (cf. Bhatt & Pancheva, 2005):

- (i) Anteriority accounts, which adopt a Reichenbachian analysis: the Perfect introduces an anteriority relation between ET and RT (Inoue, 1979; Klein, 1992, 1994; Reichenbach, 1947).
- (ii) Extended-Now (XN) accounts, for which the Perfect introduces a time span extending backwards from the RT (D. Dowty, 1982; Iatridou et al., 2001; McCawley, 1971; McCoard, 1978; Pancheva, 2003).
- (iii) Result state accounts, which appeal to some notion of the result state being relevant/obtaining at UT (Giorgi & Pianesi, 1997; Moens, Steedman, et al., 1988; Portner, 2003)

Abstracting away from the technical details of those theories,³⁷ I will note that what all these accounts have in common is the need for additional machinery and stipulations in order to explain all the observed facts. However, they differ, even within the same group, as to whether they ascribe the source for each reading to the grammar, to the semantics

³⁶Why a language should develop distinct specialized tense forms is an interesting theoretical question worth exploring through a diachronic investigation. I leave this enterprise for future research.

³⁷The brief overview here cannot do justice to the vast literature on the topic. I refer the reader to Bhatt & Pancheva (2005) and Pancheva (2003) for a more exhaustive discussion of the merits and shortcomings of each single theory.

of the perfect or to pragmatics. In what follows, I will defend an analysis that combines elements from all three theories. In short, I will propose a pragmatically enriched XN-theory, whereby the universal-existential distinction is grammatically determined, whereas the contrast between resultative and experiential readings is only contextually resolved.

Before turning to the semantic analysis, let me lay out some of the syntactic assumptions this is based on. In line with much previous work (Iatridou et al., 2001; Pancheva, 2003; Rullmann & Matthewson, 2018), I posit that perfect aspect occupies a syntactically higher position than viewpoint aspect. This hierarchy is often justified in the light of the linear order observed for English Present Perfect sentences as illustrated below.

- (84) Jerry has been dealing with some problems lately.
 a. Jerry has_{PRES} been_{PERF} dealing_{PROG} ...

A resulting structure for the aspect layer is sketched in (85)

What is relevant for the discussion here is that the prefix *a* spells out the XN-Perfect heading the AspP. This, however, will have to further combine with a lower viewpoint aspect hosted in ViewP.

According to the XN theory, the perfect introduces what Iatridou et al. (2001) have called the “Perfect Time Span” (PTS), which is a temporal interval whose right boundary is determined by the clausal tense. Its left boundary, on the other hand, is left unspecified unless an overt adverbial provides one. Building on Pancheva (2003, p. 284), I adopt the semantics for the perfect operator as formulated in (86).

- (86) $\llbracket \text{PERF} \rrbracket (p_{\langle i, t \rangle})(t_{\langle i \rangle}) = 1 \text{ iff } \exists t' [\text{XN}(t', t) \ \& \ p(t')]$
 With $\text{XN}(t', t)$ the time span stretching throughout t' and culminating in t .

As per the formula in (86), PERF is a quantificational tense that quantifies over a temporal interval (the PTS). Its final subinterval t is provided by a structurally higher tense. It follows that, from a semantic standpoint, *a*-marked sentences involve a double tense structure.

Deriving the universal reading

We have seen that *a* can readily produce universal readings when it combines with unbounded predicates (usually statives). One example is repeated below.

- (87) Kofi a-tena America firi afe 2019.
 Kofi A-live America from year 2019
 ‘Kofi has been living in the US since 2019.’ (Universal)

The left-boundary adverbial PP “firi afe 2019” provides the starting point of the PTS, while its right boundary is determined by the default variable t_c — in the absence of an overt superordinate tense (e.g., *ná*). Nevertheless, for a compositional interpretation, one ingredient is still missing: while PERF requires a property of times, the VP “Kofi tena America” denotes a property of eventualities (and worlds). For this reason, PERF needs to further combine with a suitable viewpoint aspect, which, in turn, closes off the eventuality variable of its complement. Since the system already provides two covert operators in STAT and HAB, we assume that the former will be the preferred option here due to the predicate’s actionality. The resulting LF is sketched in (88), with the truth-conditions computed in (89).

- (89) $\llbracket (88) \rrbracket = 1$ iff $\exists t' [XN(t', t_c) \ \& \ \text{Begin}(t', \text{year}(2019))$
 $\ \& \ \exists e [t' \subseteq \tau(e) \ \& \ \text{live}(w_c)(e)(\text{in}(\text{US}))(\text{K})]$

‘There is a PTS t' extending from 2019 until t_c and there is an eventuality e , such that its running time surrounds t' and e is an eventuality of Kofi living in the US in the actual world.’

In order to arrive at the truth-conditions in (89), I am assuming that the left-boundary adverbial PP right-adjoins to ViewP. Setting the technical details aside, the “*Begin*” function³⁸ introduced by “*firi*” sets the starting time of the temporal interval modified by the PP.³⁹

The truth-conditions in (89) present the eventuality as ongoing at t' . Since the PTS is entirely included in the running time of the eventuality, this will hold true of the PTS’s final subinterval t_c . Since t_c includes UT, the meaning thus derived entails that Kofi is still living in the US at the speech time, which aligns with the universal interpretation that the sentence receives.

Existential readings

In order to derive the two existential readings, namely the experiential and the resultative, I propose a unified analysis that relies on the combination of an XN perfect aspect with a resultative viewpoint aspect.⁴⁰ Their lumping together may sound unorthodox, but I will show that the two existential readings are truth-conditionally equivalent and that their difference simply boils down to pragmatic considerations.

The view taken here differs, for example, from that of Brugger (1998) and Pancheva (2003), while it is similar in spirit to Portner (2003). Pancheva opts for a grammatical experiential/resultative distinction on the basis of systematic differences observed for SoT contexts and predicate type. While the first argument does not apply to Asante Twi⁴¹, we do not observe the same variation in terms of predicate’s actionality that Pancheva refers to. In fact, atelic predicates can yield experiential as well as resultative readings (see (90)).

- (90) Kofi *a-di* salmon.
 Kofi *a-eat* salmon
 ‘Kofi has eaten salmon.’
- a. *Exp*: \rightsquigarrow Kofi knows what salmon tastes like.
 b. *Res*: \rightsquigarrow Kofi is not hungry.

Another point worth emphasizing concerns the morpho-syntax of perfect-like constructions. In Indo-European languages, the existential distinction is often morphologically encoded: on the one hand, perfective participles typically only correlate with resultative readings. On the other hand, experiential readings can arise with either neutral or imperfective participles (cf. a.o. Pancheva, 2003, p. 295). Crucially, in Asante, there exists no morphological reflection on *a*-inflected predicates. In fact, both the progressive marker *re* and the perfective marker LEN are excluded. Despite that, sentences containing *a* allow

³⁸ $Begin(p, t) = 1$ iff $\neg\exists t'[p(t') \ \& \ t' < t]$

³⁹More compositionally, $\llbracket firi \rrbracket(\llbracket year(2019) \rrbracket) = \lambda t.Begin(t, year(2019))$

⁴⁰For arguments in favour of a grammatical distinction between universal and existential readings, see Iatridou et al. (2001).

⁴¹As will be demonstrated in section 3.4, Asante Twi lacks an SoT rule.

for both interpretations. For these reasons, I will assume that the two existential readings involve the same underlying representation.⁴²

Existential readings, unlike universal ones, require that the eventuality be completed by RT. This requirement, however, conflicts with the inclusion relation introduced by STAT. Also, existential readings typically arise with eventive predicates. For this reason, I suggest that for contexts and predicates that allow for an existential reading a different operator surfaces in ViewP. Drawing from Pancheva (2003)'s foundational work, I refine the semantics of the resultative viewpoint aspect given in (91) (after Bhatt & Pancheva, 2005, p. 12).

- (91) Semantics of resultative viewpoint (to be revised)
 $\llbracket \text{RES} \rrbracket(p_{\langle v,t \rangle})(t_{(i)}) = 1$ iff $\exists \langle e, e' \rangle [\text{Result}(e', e) \ \& \ t \subseteq \tau(e') \ \& \ p(e)]$

In (91), *Result*(e' , e) reads as “ e' is the result state of e .”⁴³ According to the formula, RES binds the eventuality argument e of the main predicate and further quantifies over its result state e' , whose running time must surround the local RT. Since the latter ends up being the PTS, it follows that the result state must include the utterance time. This formulation, of course, says nothing about the temporal location of the eventuality e , except that it immediately precedes its result state e' .

While the denotation in (91) has previously been adopted to derive purely resultative readings that arise with telic predicates (cf. Bhatt & Pancheva, 2005; Pancheva, 2003), I will show that the same analysis can be successfully extended to experiential readings. For a unified analysis, however, I will provide a few adjustments. The RES operator takes two additional arguments: an eventuality pronoun, denoting the result state, which is contextually “selected”, and the context time t_c . On this analysis, the result state must only include the final subinterval of the PTS, that is the clausal RT. Crucially, the context only selects the *relevant* result state thanks to a relevance function *Rel*, as (92) illustrates.

- (92) Semantics of resultative viewpoint (revised)
 a. $\llbracket \text{RES} \rrbracket(e'_v)(p_{\langle v,t \rangle})(t'_i)(t_i)$ defined iff $\text{Rel}_{Ag}(e')$ ⁴⁴
 b. $\llbracket \text{RES} \rrbracket(e'_v)(p_{\langle v,t \rangle})(t'_i)(t_i) = 1$ iff $\exists e [\text{Result}(e', e) \ \& \ t \subseteq \tau(e') \ \& \ \tau(e) \subseteq t' \ \& \ p(e)]$

Based on the denotation in (92), RES takes an eventuality pronoun and a predicate of eventualities (that is the VP) and returns a property of times. This is a function from times to a predicate of times. The denotation of PERF is revised accordingly.

- (93) The semantics of the existential perfect.

⁴²Of course, a grammatical distinction within the existential readings could be maintained, under the assumption that *a* combines with a perfective/non-perfective viewpoint aspect covertly. This, however, would amount to a mere stipulation. For instance, it would be far less clear why existential readings cannot be simply disambiguated into experiential via a combination of *a* and LEN. (More on this below.)

⁴³More formally, $\llbracket \text{Result}(e', e) \rrbracket = 1$ iff $\tau(e) \supset \tau(e')$, where the symbol “ \supset ” stands for the abutting relation.

⁴⁴ $\text{Rel}_{Ag}(e')$ reads as: “the result state e' is relevant”

$$\llbracket \text{PERF}_{\text{existential}} \rrbracket (\text{p}_{\langle i, \langle i, t \rangle \rangle}) (t_{\langle i \rangle}) = 1 \text{ iff } \exists t' [\text{XN}(t', t) \ \& \ \text{p}(t')(t)]$$

The relevance function Rel_{Ag} in (92) is relativized to the event’s agent and helps identify the result state that is relevant for the current discourse segment. Of course, what is considered relevant is kept deliberately underspecified: this will be determined by context and pragmatic considerations. More specifically, I am going to argue that it’s the question under discussion (QuD) (Büring, 2003; Roberts, 1996) that guides the speakers towards the intended interpretation.

According to Schwarz (2009), topic situations can be derived from the QuD. On a QuD-based approach to discourse structure, every declarative sentence is the answer to an (often implicit) question under discussion. For this reason, there needs to be congruence between the topic situations of both the question and the answer. How does this brief excursus relate back to *a*-marked predicates and result states? The link lies in (Klein, 1994)’s notion of topic time, here the reference time. This view is in line with that outlined in Kratzer (2023), where topic situations are introduced by the semantic tense. Topic times have been argued to be temporal counterparts to topic situations (see Schwarz, 2009, for an in-depth discussion). Consequently, the topic times of question and answer must be equal. In other words, if the QuD is about the utterance time, the answer cannot be about a prior time.⁴⁵

The interplay of QuD and Rel_{Ag} is best illustrated by the following examples.

- (94) Context: We’re coming back from a trip. Afiba looks exhausted and out of breath.
 You ask what happened.
- a. Afiba **a**-foro bepɔ.
 Afiba A-climb mountain.
 ‘Afiba has climbed a mountain.’ (Resultative)

The sentence in (94-a) is situated in a context that obtains at the context time. Since the predicate bears *a*-morphology, it depicts a situation whose result state must be evaluated with respect to the context time too. The output is a resultative interpretation. Its LF-structure is given in (95).

⁴⁵Of course, speakers often provide RT-defying answers, which yield well-known (cessation) inferences (Altshuler & Schwarzschild, 2012).

From (95), the following definedness and truth-conditions are computed.

(96) *Definedness conditions from LF (95):*

$\llbracket \text{CP} \rrbracket^g$ defined iff $\llbracket \text{View} \rrbracket$ defined iff (by FA, 2*Lex)

$[\lambda e'. \text{Rel}_{Ag}(e')](g(4))$ defined iff (by Lex, LC)

$\text{Rel}_{Afiba}(g(4))$

Paraphrase: ‘ $g(4)$ a contextually relevant eventuality whose agent is Afiba that satisfies the QuD (i.e., an eventuality that involves Afiba looking exhausted at t_c).’

(97) *Top-down derivation of the truth-conditions from LF (95):*

When defined, $\llbracket \text{CP} \rrbracket^g = 1$ iff (by FA)

(i) $\llbracket \text{CP}_2 \rrbracket^g(w_c) = 1$ iff (by PA)

(ii) $[\lambda w. \llbracket \text{CP}_3 \rrbracket^{g(0 \rightarrow w)}](w_c) = 1$ iff (by FA, T&P)

(iii) $[\lambda w. \llbracket \text{TP} \rrbracket^{g(0 \rightarrow w)}(t_c)](w_c) = 1$ iff (by Vac, FA)

(iv) $[\lambda w. [\text{PERF}]^{g(0 \rightarrow w)}([\text{ViewP}]^{g(0 \rightarrow w)})(t_c)](w_c) = 1$ iff (by 2*FA, T&P)

(v) $[\lambda w. [\text{PERF}]^{g(0 \rightarrow w)}([\text{RES}]^{g(0 \rightarrow w)}(g(4))([\text{VP}]^{g(0 \rightarrow w)})](t_c)](w_c) = 1$ iff (by Lex, PA)

(vi) $[\lambda w. [\text{PERF}]^{g(0 \rightarrow w, 3 \rightarrow e)}([\text{RES}]^{g(0 \rightarrow w, 3 \rightarrow e)}(g(4))([\lambda e. [\text{VP}_2]^{g(0 \rightarrow w, 3 \rightarrow e)}])](t_c)](w_c) = 1$ iff (by FA)

(vii) $[\lambda w. [\text{PERF}]^{g(0 \rightarrow w, 3 \rightarrow e)}([\text{RES}]^{g(0 \rightarrow w, 4 \rightarrow e', 3 \rightarrow e)}(g(4))([\lambda e. [\text{V}']^{g(0 \rightarrow w, 4 \rightarrow e', 3 \rightarrow e)}([\text{Afiba}]])](t_c)](w_c) = 1$ iff (by 3*FA, 2*T&P, Lex)

(viii) $[\lambda w. [\text{PERF}]^{g(0 \rightarrow w, 3 \rightarrow e)}([\text{RES}]^{g(0 \rightarrow w, 3 \rightarrow e)}(g(4))([\lambda e. [\text{foro}]^{g(0 \rightarrow w, 3 \rightarrow e)}(w)(e)(\iota z[\text{mountain}(z)])(A))](t_c)](w_c) = 1$ iff (by 3*Lex)

(ix) $[\lambda w. [\lambda p. \lambda t. \exists t'[\text{XN}(t', t) \ \& \ p(t')(t)]]([\lambda e'. \lambda p. \lambda t'. \lambda t. \exists e[\text{Result}(e', e) \ \& \ t \subseteq \tau(e') \ \& \ \tau(e) \subseteq t' \ \& \ p(e)]](g(4))([\lambda e. [\lambda w''. \lambda e''. \lambda x. \lambda y. \text{climb}(w'')(e'')(x)(y)](w)(e)(\iota z[\text{mountain}(z)])(A))](t_c)](w_c) = 1$ iff (by LC)

(x) $[\lambda w. [\lambda p. \lambda t. \exists t'[\text{XN}(t', t) \ \& \ p(t')(t)]]([\lambda e'. \lambda p. \lambda t'. \lambda t. \exists e[\text{Result}(e', e) \ \& \ t \subseteq \tau(e') \ \& \ \tau(e) \subseteq t' \ \& \ p(e)]](g(4))([\lambda e. \text{climb}(w)(e)(\iota z[\text{mountain}(z)])(A)](t_c)](w_c) = 1$ iff (by LC)

(xi) $[\lambda w. [\lambda p. \lambda t. \exists t'[\text{XN}(t', t) \ \& \ p(t')(t)]](\lambda t'. \lambda t. \exists e[\text{Result}(g(4), e) \ \& \ t \subseteq \tau(g(4)) \ \& \ \tau(e) \subseteq t' \ \& \ \text{climb}(w)(e)(\iota z[\text{mountain}(z)])(A)](t_c)](w_c) = 1$ iff (by 2*LC)

(xii) $[\lambda t. \exists t'[\text{XN}(t', t) \ \& \ \exists e[\text{Result}(g(4), e) \ \& \ t \subseteq \tau(g(4)) \ \& \ \tau(e) \subseteq t' \ \& \ \text{climb}(w_c)(e)(\iota z[\text{mountain}(z)])(A)](t_c) = 1$ iff (by LC)

(xiii) $\exists t'[\text{XN}(t', t_c) \ \& \ \exists e[\text{Result}(g(4), e) \ \& \ t_c \subseteq \tau(g(4)) \ \& \ \tau(e) \subseteq t' \ \& \ \text{climb}(w_c)(e)(\iota z[\text{mountain}(z)])(A)]$

Paraphrase: ‘There is a PTS t' , such that t' extends until t_c & there is an eventuality e , such that $g(4)$ is the result state of e & t_c is included in the running time of $g(4)$ & the running time of e is included in t' & e is an eventuality in the actual world of Afiba climbing the unique z such that z is a mountain.’

According to the definedness conditions computed in (96), the relevance function selects the contextually salient eventuality, $g(4)$, that satisfies the question under discussion. That is provided by the context, which makes reference to a current state of Afiba being tired. Since the sentence denotes the answer to the QuD, the topic time needs to be preserved and, thus, $g(4)$ needs to be relevant for the context time. This, in turn, translates into a resultative reading. In a way, it is then the QuD (and not the grammar) that sets up a resultative interpretation.

Having demonstrated how the analysis handles resultative interpretations, consider now an experiential-biasing context.

(98) You are organizing a trip with your friends to a local mountain. Your plan is to do some climbing, but you have no previous experience, so you decide to ask someone who does. You wonder whom you could talk to; your friend says:

- a. Afiba a-foro bepɔ nɔ.
 Afiba A-climb mountain DEF
 ‘Afiba has climbed the mountain.’ (Experiential)

Despite the sentence being equivalent to the one in (94-a) — except for the definite marker *nɔ* — no resultative reading arises in this context. In fact, what the sentence conveys is that Afiba climbed the mountain at some point in the past and, as a result of that, she is currently someone to turn to for guidance or helpful advice. This is in line with what the experiential reading of the sentence demands. Based on my analysis, this reading is truth-conditionally indistinguishable from the resultative reading in (97). The definedness conditions are however different, since these are affected by the context-dependent QuD.

(99) $\llbracket (98\text{-a}) \rrbracket$ defined iff
 $Rel_{Afiba}(g(4))$
 With the relevance function picking out a suitable eventuality $g(4)$ that is compatible with Afiba being a mountain-climber at t_c .

(100) When defined, $\llbracket (98\text{-a}) \rrbracket = 1$ iff
 $\exists t' [XN(t', t_c) \ \& \ \exists e [Result(g(4), e) \ \& \ t_c \subseteq \tau(g(4)) \ \& \ \tau(e) \subseteq t']$
 $\ \& \ climb(w_c)(e)(\iota z[mountain(z)])(A)$

Since it is immaterial to the felicity of the answer in (98-a) how long ago Afiba climbed the mountain, no immediateness inference arises. In other words, we don't know exactly when Afiba climbed the mountain. For what it's worth, she might have done it long ago. What matters is that she has acquired some currently relevant knowledge as a result of that. Under this analysis, the experiential reading is viewed as a special instance of a resultative reading, where the result state stretches throughout the experiencer's life, from the time a given event occurred until now.

Evidence and implications of the analysis

Following the proposal adopted here, the distinction between the universal and the two existential readings has been ascribed to the sort of viewpoint aspect the XN-perfect combines with. Some indirect evidence for an analysis involving decomposition into several aspectual projections comes from serial verb constructions (SVC). In Akan, SVCs exhibit TAM morphology on each verb of the series. However, verb series are generally restricted to agreeing sequences (for LEN-predicates) or require the consecutive marker “*à*” (for all other aspectual markers) (cf. Osam, 2003). This is illustrated below (after Owusu, 2022, p. 270).

(101) *Distribution of TAM markers in SVCs:*
 a. Kofi tɔ-ɔ̃ aduane di-ì.
 Kofi buy-LEN food eat-LEN
 ‘Kofi bought and ate food.’

- b. *Kofi tɔ-ɔ̃ aduane re/à-di.
 Kofi buy-LEN food PROG/CONS-eat
 Intended: ‘Kofi bought and is eating it/to eat it.’
- c. Kofi a-tɔ aduane à-di.
 Kofi A-buy food CONS-eat
 ‘Kofi has bought food to eat it.’
- d. Kofi re-noa aduane à-di.
 Kofi PROG-buy food CONS-eat
 ‘Kofi is cooking food to eat it.’

These restrictions have been often motivated in terms of morpho-syntactic agreement (Owusu, 2022) or uniformity (Osam, 2003). For instance, in (101-a), both segments of the sequence agree in aspect features, as they are both perfective. The consecutive marker *à* in these constructions appears to have a telicizing effect, building an endpoint into an ongoing eventuality. On this view, the acceptability of (101-c) and (101-d), as opposed to (101-b), can be attributed to the telicity contrast between the sentences. While the *atɔ* and *renoa* are associated with an atelic interpretation (a persistent result state of having bought food and an ongoing activity of buying food, respectively), the perfective *tɔɔ* denotes a telic event. Applying the consecutive marker *à* to *a-* and *re-*marked predicates returns their endpoint or goal (in this case, eating the food). Obviously, in the case of the inherently telic *LEN*, *CONS* would apply vacuously.

Moreover, it has been observed that *a* can exceptionally be followed by the progressive marker *re* in SVCs, serving as one exception to the patterns in (101) (Dolphyne, 1987; Hellan et al., 2003; Osam, 2003).

- (102) Kofi a-noa aduane re-di.
 Kofi A-cook food PROG-eat
 ‘Kofi has cooked/been cooking food and is eating it.’

I take this to constitute evidence in support of the analysis formulated here. I speculate that the harmonic relation between TAM markers is exceptionally not disrupted in (102) because the lowest projection of the *a*-marked predicate “*noa*” presents the eventuality as unbounded⁴⁶. This, in turn, is compatible with the progressive aspectual profile of the *re*-marked predicate “*di*”.

There is one trivial implication made by the current analysis. Following the proposal outlined here, *a* denotes an existential tense that quantificationally binds the tense variable of the PERF’s complement. As the LF-structures above show, the only referential temporal element of its semantic representation is provided by the distinguished variable t_e , which is rigidly anchored to UT. Against this backdrop, the lack of referential (past) readings for *a*-marked sentences illustrated in (6-b) and (7-a) naturally follows.

One second less trivial implication involves the modification of *a*-marked clauses by adverbials. Recall that *a* is incompatible with locating temporal adverbs.⁴⁷ Consider the sentence in (13-a), repeated below:

⁴⁶This is not only true of STAT but also of RES, since under the current analysis the result state includes the reference time even in existential construals.

⁴⁷This behaviour is part of the well known “present perfect puzzle” (Klein, 1992).

describe eventualities involving dead individuals.

- (110) Context: Kwame Nkrumah was a popular figure in the country. He became head of state after studying in the US. He died in 1972.
- a. #Kwame Nkrumah a-sua adeɛ wɔ America.
Kwame Nkrumah A-learn study at US
lit.‘Kwame Nkrumah has studied in the US.’
- b. Kwame Nkrumah sua-à adeɛ wɔ America.
Kwame Nkrumah learn-LEN study at US
‘Kwame Nkrumah studied in the US.’

In (110), only the LEN-marked variant of the sentence is accepted by my consultants, suggesting that *a* too exhibits lifetime effects. In (110), *a* correlates with an experiential interpretation, thus projecting a resultative viewpoint aspect “RES” at LF. Recall that the relevance function Rel_{Ag} applies to the subject argument, thus selecting in this specific case only result states that are relevant for Kwame Nkrumah. Since the result state has to be included in the context time t_c , the system correctly rules out subject-individuals that are not alive at t_c . Under the current proposal, these effects fall out without further stipulations.

Co-occurrence patterns with *ná* and LEN’s exclusion

As previously noted, the hybrid perfect *a* can co-occur only with the distal deictic *ná*, while the past perfective LEN is strictly ruled out in sentences containing any tempo-aspectual marker. According to the LF architecture developed here for Asante clauses, in *a*-marked sentences *ná* fills the empty T-head slot, thus providing a topic time other than UT. Recall that *a*-marked clauses modified by *ná* typically give rise to a past perfect-like interpretation, as the following example shows:

- (111) Context: Ama is such a great cook. She enjoys nothing more in life than baking for her friends. Last Tuesday I stopped by her place and guess what?
- a. **Ná** Ama a-noa aduane.
NA Ama A-cook food
‘Ama had cooked some food.’
Comment: *By the time you got there she had already cooked (maybe in the morning or so).*

In contrast to T-less clauses, sentences containing *ná* are evaluated with respect to a contextually salient temporal interval that differs from the utterance time. In other words, *ná* supplies a temporal anchor by which a certain eventuality has already occurred. For sentences like (111), a resultative interpretation obtains, according to which the result state of having (previously) cooked food holds at the time of the speaker’s visit (i.e., the time that *ná* picks out. This is illustrated by the simplified LF and truth-conditions for (111) below.

- (112) [CP ... [TP t_c na_7 [AspP $\langle i, t \rangle$ PERF [ViewP $\langle i, \langle i, t \rangle \rangle$ RES $_{e_4}$ [VP $\langle v, t \rangle$ λe_3 ... Ama-noa-aduane $_{e_3}$]]]]]

- (113) $\llbracket (112) \rrbracket = 1$ iff $\exists t'[\text{XN}(t', g(7)) \ \& \ \exists e[\text{Result}(g(4), e) \ \& \ \tau(e) \subset t' \ \& \ \tau(g(4)) \supseteq g(7) \ \& \ e \text{ is an event of Ama cooking food in } w_c]]$
with $g(7)$ not overlapping t_c & $g(7) =$ the time of the speaker's visit.

According to the truth-conditions in (97), the PTS has in $g(7)$ its end point, thus locating the cooking event at some time before the speaker's visit. As a result, an earlier-than-then interpretation arises, though no element in the structure introduces any strict anteriority relation.

By contrast, LEN cannot surface in *a*-marked sentences. This time, the restriction is due to competition for the same position as View-head. Assuming that the aspectual head PERF can only combine with STAT or RES to derive universal and existential readings, respectively, View cannot further host PFV (that is LEN's aspectual projection). In other words, LEN is prohibited from co-occurring with *ná* due to its temporal component, while it's in complementary distribution with *a* due to its aspectual properties.

One additional question that merits more attention is the exceptional availability of experiential readings for LEN in some scenarios. Consider the following contexts and the respective translations offered by one consultant:

- (114) Context: Your mother asked you if Awusi has a degree. You know that he was at the University of Ghana, though you're not sure whether he completed his studies. Here's your answer:

- a. *Target*: 'Awusi studied at the University of Ghana.'
b. Awusi sua-à adeε wɔ Ghana Suapɔn nó mu.
Awusi study-LEN learn at Ghana University DEF PTCL

- (115) Context: You and your friend are discussing sports. He insists that Spain has never won the football World Cup before, while you remember they did at least once. You object:

- a. *Target*: 'Trust me, Spain won the World Cup!'
b. Gye me di, Spain gye-è Wiase Kuruwa no!
believe 1SG.ACC PTCL Spain win-LEN world cup DEF

Based on (114) and (115), it seems that LEN is compatible with indefinite experiential readings after all. I speculate that what these contexts have in common is the fact that the non-salient reference time can be easily accommodated.⁵¹ Moreover, there is a contrastive element to these sentences in that they express a certain distance from the utterance time. If the speaker, for instance, is not fully certain that Awusi has a degree in (114) or is aware (as the consultant was as well) that Spain didn't win the last World Cup, then a resultative marker such as *a* is not the most suitable option. Consequently, the translator's choice for LEN might be driven by the need to contrast it with *a*. More transparently, the same mechanism was for instance at play in (110), where a pragmatic inference forces the choice of LEN over *a*.

⁵¹This can be either a stereotypical time at which a certain situation obtains in someone's life or can be simply extended to encompass someone's entire lifetime. The indefinite meaning component would then be provided by the eventuality existential quantifier. Of course, there need to be restrictions in this respect or any experiential reading could in principle be accommodated. How these restrictions should be formulated constitutes an interesting question worth tackling in future work.

An alternative explanation of the facts illustrated above assumes the possibility for LEN’s tense variable to be existentially closed. This is, for instance, what has been suggested for the English past simple (cf. a.o. Grønn & Von Stechow, 2016). Below is sketched a simplified LF, with its derived interpretation, for existentially closed LEN-marked predicates.

$$(116) \quad [\dots [\exists [_{TP} \lambda_{t_2} [_{T'} t_{2,5}] [_{AspP} [_{Asp} PFV] \dots p \dots]]]]]] \quad (\text{with } t' < g(5))$$

This view is however inconsistent with the empirical observation that experiential readings are far from widespread for Asante LEN compared to the English simple past. Two more grounds for rejecting this view are offered by the lack of temporal co-varying interpretations and the incompatibility with the temporal quantifier *da*. The first argument is illustrated in (117).

- (117) Context: For Kofi’s birthday you decided to play a game: you decorated ten eggs and hid them in the garden. Unfortunately, Kofi struggled quite a bit to find all ten eggs. After a month, he was still looking for the last one, which he finally found two days ago.
- a. ^{??}Kofi hu-ù kosua biara.
Kofi find-LEN egg every
Comment: *It sounds like the eggs were all found at the same time.*
- b. Kofi a-hu kosua biara.
Kofi A-find egg every
Comment: *Much better because the last egg was found two days ago, so the eggs were found at different times.*

Since the context in (117) links the finding events to different times, a co-varying interpretation is only possible if the universal quantifier “biara” scopes over an existential tense. My consultants strongly dispreferred the variant with LEN, suggesting that its tense variable resists quantificational binding by an existential closure-like operator even when the context demands it. Along the same lines, sentences containing the quantificational adverb “da” (“ever”, “before”) are consistently rejected when the predicate is modified by LEN instead of *a*, as demonstrated by the examples in (8) and (9), repeated below.

- (118) Context: One of your friends tells you that they are quite envious of Afiba, who always seems to be in great health and energetic. However, you think that this is quite exaggerated: in fact, even Afiba was sick at some point in the past...
- a. Afiba a-yare da.
Afiba a-sick ever
- b. #Afiba yare-è da.
Afiba sick-LEN ever
- (119) Context: Your friend wants to impress Kofi with salmon for dinner, thinking he hasn’t tried it before. However, you point out that he already knows its taste.
- a. Kofi a-di salmon da.
Kofi a-eat salmon ever

- b. #Kofi di-ì salmon da.
 Kofi eat-LEN salmon ever

Taken together, these empirical findings suggest that the sporadic availability of experiential readings cannot be attributed to an existential analysis of the past tense. Instead, they result from an accommodation mechanism, wherein missing information necessary for resolving discourse referents is directly incorporated into the context.

3.4 The temporal interpretation of embedded clauses

This section provides an in-depth analysis of the temporal interpretation of complement clauses in Asante Twi, with novel data from past-oriented as well as from future-oriented attitude contexts. Building on the insights gained from the discussion in chapter 2, Asante Twi offers an intriguing case study due to the rich tempo-aspectual morphology that can be potentially deployed to convey simultaneous or backward-shifted interpretations.

In what follows, I will show that Asante Twi patterns with non-SoT languages in that it lacks an SoT rule and naturally conveys past simultaneity via the unmarked form (resembling in use a relative present). Alongside this *de se* construal, Asante further deploys *de re* mechanisms — which involve *ná* and LEN’s tense variables — as well as a relative resultative construal — which involves the hybrid perfect *a*.

3.4.1 The data: attitude reports

The data elicited on embedded clauses and reported here follow the methodology adopted in section 3.2.3 for matrix clauses. Contexts here always establish the desired temporal interpretation, either simultaneous (SIM) or backward-shifted (BACK). Embeddings with all three TAnt markers and the unmarked form were tested for each context. However, to avoid confounding factors, attitude verbs were generally limited to *ka* (“say”) and *gye di* (“believe”), inflected with LEN-morphology. Finally, for each temporal interpretation, complement clauses containing both stative and eventive predicates have been examined. Recall that bare and *ná*-marked sentences strictly correlate with habitual readings when the predicate is eventive. For this reason, to prevent a habitual interpretation, eventive predicates in this dataset always pair *ná* or the bare form with the progressive prefix *re-*.

Past-oriented contexts

(i) Simultaneous readings, Stative embeddings

In Asante Twi, (past) simultaneous readings are generally produced by embedding a bare clause under a past-oriented verb. Similar interpretations arise under *ná*-embeddings, though subject to a slight speaker variation. By contrast, *a* and LEN-embeddings are rejected in simultaneous contexts, as the following example illustrates.

- (120) Context: You and Aba were supposed to watch a movie last Friday night. Unfortunately, Aba called you to cancel one hour before the movie. She told you: ‘I am sick’. The week after you explain to your friend why Aba could not make it on Friday night:

3.4 The temporal interpretation of embedded clauses

- a. Aba ka-à sɛ ɔ-yare. (Bare-under-LEN)
 Aba say-LEN COMP 3SG-sick
 ‘Aba said that she was (currently) sick.’
- b. # Aba ka-à sɛ ɔ-yare-è. (LEN-under-LEN)
 Aba say-LEN COMP 3SG-sick-LEN
 ‘Aba said that she had been sick.’
- c. # Aba ka-à sɛ w-a-yare. (*a*-under-LEN)
 Aba say-LEN COMP 3SG-a-sick
 ‘Aba said that she has been sick.’
- d. ? Aba ka-à sɛ ná ɔ-yare. (*ná*-under-LEN)
 Aba say-LEN COMP NA 3SG-sick
 ‘Aba said that she was sick (at that time).’

While bare and LEN-embeddings received consistent judgments, one out of four consultants rejected (120-d), thus expressing a strong preference for a backward-shifted interpretation. Interestingly, one of the three consultants who accepted the sentence reported a slight difference in meaning compared to (120-a): while the bare clause constitutes a faithful report of Aba’s words, the *ná*-marked variant can be paraphrased as ‘that she was sick at the time that the phone call occurred’. Moreover, two consultants, despite rejecting the sentence in the given context, reported that the *a*-marked complement clause in (120-c) may be compatible with a state of sickness not entirely completed at the attitude time. I return to this point later.

All judgments except for *a*-embeddings are replicated with a different stative predicate such as *nyem* (“pregnant”). The following context is of particular interest because it forces a non-DAR interpretation, since the two years time-span does not allow the pregnancy state to extend until UT.

- (121) Context: Two years ago, you gave a farewell party before leaving your hometown. At the party, your friend Awusi fainted and was taken to the hospital. There she received some exciting news from the doctor!
- a. ɔyaresafoɔ nó ka-à sɛ Awusi nyem. (Bare-under-LEN)
 doctor DEF say-LEN COMP Awusi pregnant
 ‘The doctor said that Awusi was pregnant (then).’
- b. # ɔyaresafoɔ nó ka-à sɛ Awusi nyeme-è. (LEN-under-LEN)
 doctor DEF say-LEN COMP Awusi pregnant-LEN
 ‘The doctor said that Awusi had been pregnant.’
- c. ɔyaresafoɔ nó ka-à sɛ Awusi a-nyem. (*a*-under-LEN)
 doctor DEF say-LEN COMP Awusi A-pregnant
 ‘The doctor said that Awusi had got pregnant.’
- d. ɔyaresafoɔ nó ka-à sɛ ná Awusi nyem. (*ná*-under-LEN)
 doctor DEF say-LEN COMP NA Awusi pregnant
 ‘The doctor said that Awusi was pregnant (then).’

The sentence in (121-d) was accepted by all four consultants, including the one that rejected (120-d), thus suggesting that simultaneous readings are generally available for *ná*-embeddings, though they might be subject to predicate and speaker variation. Inter-

estingly, the *a*-under-LEN embedding in (121-c) was judged felicitous in a simultaneous context in this case. According to my consultants, the sentence for this specific predicate receives a resultative interpretation (i.e., Awusi was pregnant then as a result of getting pregnant before) which is compatible with the context of evaluation.

(ii) *Simultaneous readings, eventive embeddings*

No variation is observed, in principle, for eventive predicates. Only bare and *ná*-marked embeddings are felicitous in simultaneous contexts, whereas *a* and LEN-marked complement clauses are rejected. This is illustrated for the eventive predicates *noa* ('to cook') and *di* ('to eat') in (122) and (123), respectively.

(122) Context: Aba is a great cook. Since she has little time during the week, she tries to cook more on Sundays, so that she has meals ready for the whole week. Yesterday was Sunday. You called Aba and asked her what she was up to. Unsurprisingly she was busy making food! You report this later to a friend:

- a. Aba ka-à sɛ ɔ-re-noa aduane. (Bare-under-LEN)
Aba say-LEN COMP 3SG-PROG-cook food
'Aba said that she was cooking (at the moment).'
- b. # Aba ka-à sɛ ɔ-noa-à aduane. (LEN-under-LEN)
Aba say-LEN COMP 3SG-cook-LEN food
'Aba said that she had cooked food.'
- c. # Aba ka-à sɛ w-a-noa aduane. (*a*-under-LEN)
Aba say-LEN COMP 3SG-a-cook food
'Aba said that she has cooked some food (at some point).'
- d. Aba ka-à sɛ ná ɔ-re-noa aduane. (*ná*-under-LEN)
Aba say-LEN COMP NA 3SG-PROG-cook food
'Aba said that she was cooking (then).'

(123) Context: Awusi follows a pescatarian diet, typically enjoying fish every Friday evening. While chatting with Aba over dinner last Friday, she turned to you and remarked: "I bet Awusi is eating fish right now!" You later report Aba's thoughts.

- a. Aba gye di-ì sɛ Awusi re-di fish. (Bare-under-LEN)
Aba believe-LEN COMP Awusi PROG-eat fish
'Aba said that Awusi was eating fish (at the moment).'
- b. # Aba gye di-ì sɛ Awusi di-ì fish. (LEN-under-LEN)
Aba believe-LEN COMP Awusi eat-LEN fish
'Aba said that Awusi had eaten fish.'
- c. # Aba gye di-ì sɛ Awusi a-di fish. (*a*-under-LEN)
Aba believe-LEN COMP Awusi A-eat fish
'Aba said that Awusi has eaten fish (at some point in her life).'
- d. Aba gye di-ì sɛ ná Awusi re-di fish. (*ná*-under-LEN)
Aba believe-LEN COMP NA Awusi PROG-eat fish
'Aba said that Awusi was eating fish (then).'

By contrast, the predicate *da* (“sleep”) yields surprising results which partly conflict with the patterns emerged so far for eventive predicates. Firstly, two out of four consultants disliked *ná*-under-LEN embeddings this time (see (124-d)), pointing out the need for a temporal modifier to strengthen the intended interpretation. Secondly, *a*-under-LEN was considered by far the most natural way to convey simultaneity between the sleeping event and the past attitude time (see (124-c)).

- (124) Context: Last night, you dropped by Kofi’s place after work to pay him a visit. Unfortunately, his flatmate, Kwadwo, mentioned that Kofi couldn’t chat with you as he was already asleep. You report Kwadwo’s words today.
- a. Kwadwo ka-à sɛ Kofi re-da. (Bare-under-LEN)
 Kwadwo say-LEN COMP Kofi PROG-sleep
 ‘Kwadwo said that Kofi was sleeping (at the moment).’
- b. # Kwadwo ka-à sɛ Kofi da-à. (LEN-under-LEN)
 Kwadwo say-LEN COMP Kofi sleep-LEN
 ‘Kwadwo said that Kofi had slept.’
- c. Kwadwo ka-à sɛ Kofi a-da. (*a*-under-LEN)
 Kwadwo say-LEN COMP Kofi A-sleep
 ‘Kwadwo said that Kofi was asleep (at the moment).’
- d. ? Kwadwo ka-à sɛ ná Kofi re-da. (*ná*-under-LEN)
 Kwadwo say-LEN COMP NA Kofi PROG-sleep
 ‘Kwadwo said that Kofi was sleeping (then).’

The fact that *a*-under-LEN may give rise to a simultaneous reading might seem puzzling at first. However, in alignment with (121-c), (124-c) also receives a resultative interpretation, wherein Kofi’s result state of falling asleep (i.e., being asleep) holds true of the attitude time. This surprising finding will be discussed at length in section 3.5.5. Similarly, the lower acceptability of *ná*-under-LEN compared to bare clauses confirms what we noted for stative predicates, where an analogous speaker variation was observed.

On the exceptional simultaneous readings of LEN-under-LEN embeddings

According to one consultant, a simultaneous interpretation can be rescued for LEN-under-LEN, if the embedded verb is modified by a temporal adverbial that forces co-reference between the embedded RT and the embedding AT, as shown in (125).

- (125) Aba ka-à sɛ ɔ-yare-è saa nandwo nó.
 Aba say-LEN COMP 3SG-sick-LEN DEM night DEF
 ‘Aba said that she was sick that night.’ (SIM possible)

The modified sentence offered by the consultant was accepted by all the other native speakers, thus suggesting that, though marginally, SIM-readings are in principle possible even for LEN-embeddings.

As we saw in chapter 2, temporal modifiers have been often deployed to strengthen simultaneous interpretations for past-under-past in non-SoT languages (cf. Ogihara & Sharvit, 2012). This is usually taken as evidence for a *de re* analysis. I will come back to

this point in the next section.

(iii) *Backward-shifted readings, Stative embeddings*

In Asante Twi, backward-shifted interpretations typically arise with LEN- and *ná*-marked complement clauses. By contrast, bare clauses are judged infelicitous if the embedded eventuality no longer holds at UT. Beside *ná* and LEN, *a* may also feature in BACK-biasing contexts, despite being the least preferred option by my consultants. The resulting interpretation, however, is for some speakers temporally independent (i.e., not dependent on the attitude time) and, as such, may be compatible with an anteriority reading depending on predicate type and extra-linguistic information. The following example involves the stative predicate *yare* ('sick').⁵²

(126) Context: Awusi was absent from work last week due to sickness, but she is fine now. When you saw her back at work yesterday, she told you about it. You report her words today:

- a. # Awusi ka-à sɛ ɔ-yare. (Bare-under-LEN)
Awusi say-LEN COMP 3SG-sick
'Awusi said that she was sick (at the time).'
- b. Awusi ka-à sɛ ɔ-yare-è. (LEN-under-LEN)
Awusi say-LEN COMP 3SG-sick-LEN
'Awusi said that she had been sick.'
- c. ? Awusi ka-à sɛ w-a-yare. (*a*-under-LEN)
Awusi say-LEN COMP 3SG-a-sick
'Awusi said that she has been sick.'
- d. Awusi ka-à sɛ ná ɔ-yare. (*ná*-under-LEN)
Awusi say-LEN COMP NA 3SG.sick
'Awusi said that she was sick (then).'

(iv) *Backward-shifted readings, eventive embeddings*

The same judgment patterns obtain for eventive predicates, with the following examples once more involving the predicates *noa* ('to cook') and *di* ('to eat').

(127) Context: Aba is a great cook. Since she has little time during the week, she tries to do most of her cooking on Sundays, so that she has meals ready for the whole week. Today is Monday and you ask Aba how she spent her Sunday. Unsurprisingly she made food the whole day! You report this later to a friend.

- a. # Aba ka-à sɛ ɔ-re-noa aduane. (Bare-under-LEN)
Aba say-LEN COMP 3SG-PROG-cook food
'Aba said that she was cooking (at the moment).'
- b. Aba ka-à sɛ ɔ-noa-à aduane.
Aba say-LEN COMP 3SG-cook-LEN food

⁵²For two consultants, the sentence (126-c) suggests that Awusi has reached a post-state of her being sick. As a consequence "the worst is gone" at AT. Whether this represents a good proxy for the BACK-reading is debatable.

- ‘Aba said that she had cooked food.’
- c. ? Aba ka-à sɛ w-a-noa aduane. (a-under-LEN)
Aba say-LEN COMP 3SG-a-cook food
‘Aba said that she has cooked some food (at some point).’
- d. Aba ka-à sɛ ná ɔ-re-noa aduane. (ná-under-LEN)
Aba say-LEN COMP NA 3SG-PROG-cook food
‘Aba said that she was cooking (then).’
- (128) Context: Awusi follows a pescatarian diet, typically enjoying fish every Friday evening. Today’s Saturday. Talking to Aba at lunch, she said: “I bet Awusi had fish last night!” You later report Aba’s thoughts.
- a. # Aba gye di-ì sɛ Awusi re-di fish. (Bare-under-LEN)
Aba believe-LEN COMP Awusi PROG-eat fish
‘Aba said that Awusi was eating fish (at the moment).’
- b. Aba gye di-ì sɛ Awusi di-ì fish. (LEN-under-LEN)
Aba believe-LEN COMP Awusi eat-LEN fish
‘Aba said that Awusi had eaten fish.’
- c. ? Aba gye di-ì sɛ Awusi a-di fish. (a-under-LEN)
Aba believe-LEN COMP Awusi A-eat fish
‘Aba said that Awusi has eaten fish (at some point in her life).’
- d. Aba gye di-ì sɛ ná Awusi re-di fish. (ná-under-LEN)
Aba believe-LEN COMP NA Awusi PROG-eat fish
‘Aba said that Awusi was eating fish (then).’

Finally, the predicate *da* (‘to sleep’) once again reveals a diverging picture in backward-shifted contexts: on the one hand, BACK is consistently ruled out for bare embeddings but accepted for LEN-embeddings. On the other hand, both *a* and *ná* are dispreferred.⁵³

- (129) Context: Last night at 9pm you stopped by Kofi’s place after work, but when you rang the bell no one came to the door. When you met Kofi this morning he told you why he hadn’t come to the door the night before: apparently at 9pm he was already asleep!
- a. Kofi ka-à sɛ ɔ-re-da. (Bare-under-LEN)
Kofi say-LEN COMP 3SG-PROG-sleep
‘Kofi said that Kofi was sleeping (at the moment).’
- b. # Kwadwo ka-à sɛ ɔ-da-à. (LEN-under-LEN)
Kofi say-LEN COMP 3SG-sleep-LEN
‘Kofi said that Kofi had slept.’
- c. ?? Kwadwo ka-à sɛ w-a-da. (a-under-LEN)
Kofi say-LEN COMP Kofi 3SG-a-sleep
Intended: ‘Kofi said that he has slept (at some point).’
- d. ?? Kofi ka-à sɛ ná ɔ-re-da.
Kofi say-LEN COMP NA Kofi 3SG-PROG-sleep

⁵³Only two out of four participants accept *ná* in this case. The use of *a*, in turn, is accepted by only one consultant and is regarded as marginally acceptable by a second speaker.

‘Kofi said that Kofi was sleeping (then).’

Interim summary

Before turning to future-oriented contexts, let me briefly summarize the main empirical findings for past-oriented attitude reports. It is evident that bare-under-LEN embeddings can yield only a simultaneous interpretation. In the light of the pregnancy-sentence, the latter constitutes an authentic co-temporal interpretation and not the by-product of a double access interpretation. Conversely, LEN-under-LEN correlates with backward-shifted interpretations, with SIM marginally possible only when a temporal modifier forces such interpretation. In contrast to the bare form and LEN, *ná*-embeddings are compatible with simultaneous as well as backward-shifted interpretations, but with a caveat: these embeddings do not represent the preferred option and are subject to inter-speaker variability and variation based on the type of verb used. Finally, the prefix *a* presents a much more nuanced picture, for which both SIM and BACK are possible depending on context and predicate type. These findings for past-oriented contexts are summarized in Table 3.3.⁵⁴

	Bare-under-LEN	LEN-under-LEN	<i>a</i> -under-LEN	<i>ná</i> -under-LEN
Simultaneous	✓	?x	??	?✓
Backward-shifted	x	✓	?	?✓

Table 3.3: The interpretation of past-oriented attitude reports in Asante Twi

Future-oriented contexts

Future-oriented contexts offer an interesting testing ground for the four embeddings examined so far. In contrast to past-oriented contexts, they belong to the realm of what is hypothetical (or what is not yet the actual case), thus potentially shedding light on the true semantic nature of the simultaneous interpretation arising for both bare and *ná*-embeddings. More specifically, if both bare and *ná*-Embeddings correlated with a *de se* LF (that is, a bound variable construal), then both constructions should be readily accepted. Moreover, later-than-now scenarios also allow us to determine whether LEN and *a* involve a relative or an absolute tense semantics.

(i) *Simultaneous readings*

The context in (130) presents the reported sickness state as simultaneous to an attitude time that follows the utterance time. While judgments for (130-a) and (130-b) were

⁵⁴A single question mark indicates that the reading is available to most speakers, though it may be not the most salient and could be affected by context or predicate choice. A double question mark indicates that the interpretation is marginal or subject to high variation among speakers and predicates. A question-marked checkmark symbol indicates that the reading is largely available among speakers, with minor variation. A question-marked cross symbol indicates that the reading is largely unavailable, though marginally accessible in certain contexts.

consistent across the four consultants, with only bare embeddings being acceptable, these were once more split for *a* and *ná*-embeddings. Two out of four consultants accepted (130-c) on condition that the predicate *a-yare* denoted a result state of falling sick. As for (130-d), only one consultant fully accepted the sentence, while a second speaker deemed it acceptable though not very natural.

(130) Context: Kwesi plans to skip school next Friday. His plan is the following: when in the morning his mother checks on him, he'll pretend to feel sick (at that exact moment).⁵⁵

- a. Kwesi bé-ka sɛ ɔ-yare. (Bare-under-PROSP)
 Kwesi PROSP-say COMP 3SG-sick
 'Kwesi will say that he is sick.'
- b. # Kwesi bé-ka sɛ ɔ-yare-è. (LEN-under-PROSP)
 Kwesi PROSP-say COMP 3SG-sick-LEN
 'Kwesi will say that he was sick.'
- c. ?? Kwesi béka sɛ w-a-yare. (*a*-under-PROSP)
 Kwesi PROSP-say COMP 3SG-a-sick
 'Kwesi will say that he's been sick.'
- d. ?? Kwesi bé-ka sɛ ná ɔ-yare. (*ná*-under-PROSP)
 Kwesi PROSP-say COMP NA 3SG-sick
 Intended: 'Kwesi will say that he is sick (then).'

When using the eventive verb *da* ('to sleep') as in (131), similar results are obtained. However, as observed in past contexts, reports containing *a* become fully acceptable on a par with bare clauses.⁵⁶

(131) Context: Kwame wants to go to a party tonight, but he's grounded. His plan is to sneak out through the window from his bedroom and put a few pillows below the blankets, so that when his mother goes upstairs and checks on him, she will think he's sleeping!

- a. Me maame bɛ-gye a-di sɛ ná me-re-da.
 1POSS mother PROSP-believe CONS-PTCL COMP NA 1POSS-PROG-sleep
 'My mother will think that I'm sleeping.' (Bare-under-PROSP)
- b. # Me maame bɛ-gye a-di sɛ me-da-à.
 1POSS mother PROSP-believe CONS-PTCL COMP 1POSS-sleep-LEN
 'My mother will think that I slept.' (LEN-under-PROSP)
- c. Me maame bɛ-gye a-di sɛ m'a-da.
 1POSS mother PROSP-believe CONS-PTCL COMP 1POSS=A-sleep
 'My mother will think that I'm asleep.' (*a*-under-PROSP)
- d. ? Me maame bɛ-gye a-di sɛ ná me-re-da.
 1POSS mother PROSP-believe CONS-PTCL COMP NA 1POSS-PROG-sleep
 'My mother will think that I'm sleeping.' (*ná*-under-PROSP)

⁵⁵This context was additionally tested with *gye di* ('to believe') in the matrix, with the target report reading 'My mother will think that I am sick?'. Judgments did not vary.

⁵⁶*ná*-embeddings were rejected by two speakers and judged acceptable or marginally acceptable by the other two speakers.

(ii) Backward-shifted readings

In line with our findings in past-oriented contexts, backward-shifted readings in future-oriented contexts are available for LEN-marked complement clauses⁵⁷ but unattested for bare attitude reports. A backward-shifted reading can also be readily achieved through *a*-embeddings, while not all speakers accept embedded *ná* in this constellation. This is illustrated by the following example.

- (132) Context: Kwame wants to skip school tomorrow and go to the mall instead. Once he's back the day after, he'll bring a fake note from the doctor to the teacher. This is what he expects: 'she will think I was sick the day before'.
- a. # ɔkyerɛkyerɛni nó bɛ-gye a-di sɛ me-yare.
 teacher DEF PROSP-believe CONS-PTCL COMP 1SG-sick
 'The teacher will believe that I am sick.' (Bare-under-PROSP)
- b. ɔkyerɛkyerɛni nó bɛ-gye a-di sɛ me-yare-è.
 teacher DEF PROSP-believe CONS-PTCL COMP 1SG-sick
 'The teacher will believe that I was sick.' (LEN-under-PROSP)
- c. ɔkyerɛkyerɛni nó bɛ-gye a-di sɛ m'a-yare.
 teacher DEF PROSP-believe CONS-PTCL COMP 1SG=A-sick
 'The teacher will believe that I've been sick.' (*a*-under-PROSP)
- d. ? ɔkyerɛkyerɛni nó bɛ-gye a-di sɛ ná me-yare.
 teacher DEF PROSP-believe CONS-PTCL COMP NA 1SG-sick
 'The teacher will believe that I was sick.' (*ná*-under-PROSP)

Note that the context in (132) establishes a relative backward-shifted interpretation, in that the embedded eventuality holds at some time preceding the attitude time, but following the utterance time. Given the acceptability of (132-b), I conclude that LEN's temporal component is sensitive to the local evaluation time. Similarly, the hybrid perfect *a* in (132-c) can also yield relative BACK, though with some inter-speaker variation: while the sentence was perfectly acceptable for three speakers, for one consultant the most salient interpretation was an experiential-like reading that is temporally independent.⁵⁸

To sum up, bare attitude reports are only compatible with simultaneous readings, regardless of the syntactic environment. By contrast, LEN-embeddings yield backward-shifted interpretations that are relative to the local EvalT, with simultaneous interpretations generally ruled out, but possible in past-oriented contexts when aided by an overt adverbial phrase. Embeddings containing *ná* are ambiguous between the two readings, with the acceptability decreasing in future scenarios. Finally, given an appropriate context and choice of embedded predicate, *a*-marked attitude reports are also compatible with both readings, with BACK being easier to access. For a summary of the findings reported in this section, see Table 3.4

⁵⁷One consultant noted that in the absence of a temporal adverbial in the embedded clause, LEN-marked reports are more likely to be interpreted relative to UT rather than AT and express an experiential-like meaning.

⁵⁸Consultant's comment: 'the sentence is fine but less preferred compared to (132-b). It means that the teacher will believe that I've been sick.'

	Bare-embedding	LEN-embedding	<i>a</i> -embedding	<i>ná</i> -embedding
Past <i>SIM</i>	✓	?x	??	?✓
Past <i>BACK</i>	x	✓	?	?✓
Future <i>SIM</i>	✓	x	??	??
Future <i>BACK</i>	x	✓	?✓	?

Table 3.4: The temporal interpretation of attitude reports in Asante Twi

3.5 The composition of attitude reports in Asante Twi

This section offers a compositional analysis of propositional attitude reports in Asante Twi. The desired outcome is for the interpretations highlighted in the previous section to directly arise from the semantics proposed in section 3.3, with minimal auxiliary assumptions. Ultimately, the goal is to provide answers to the following questions:

- (i) Is Asante Twi an **SoT language**?
- (ii) How does Asante Twi add to the observed crosslinguistic **variation when it comes to *de re* interpretations**
- (iii) Does Asante Twi involve any **novel compositional pathways** to deriving (past) simultaneity (or anteriority)?

One additional methodological contribution I make here pertains to a novel diagnostic I develop to tease apart possible analyses for the observed facts. This is of particular interest with regard to the *deletion* vs *de re* debate set out in the previous chapter.

In subsection 3.5.1, I demonstrate that bare complement clauses involve a *de se* analysis, as the embedded predicate is evaluated with respect to the attitude holder’s now. Due to their tenseless nature, these sentences naturally generate a simultaneous interpretation. Subsection 3.5.2 shows that backward-shifted interpretations for *LEN*-marked embeddings can be captured by a temporal *de Dicto* analysis, wherein the embedded proposition is always temporally shifted relative to the attitude time. Subsection 3.5.3 discusses a second compositional mechanism to derive simultaneous readings: temporal *de re*. This obligatorily targets the deictic *ná* and possibly *LEN*’s tense variable. However, subsection 5.1 shows that *de re* is subject to language-internal variability in compliance to two independently motivated constraints: *Prefer de se!* and *Prefer unbounded Structures!*. The ontological picture is completed in subsections 3.5.5 and 3.5.6, which reveal for embedded *a* a systematic *de re/de se* ambiguity, alongside a novel compositional pathway to *SIM* involving a relative resultative construal with change-of-state predicates. Finally, 3.5.7 wraps up.

3.5.1 Bare embeddings and temporal *de se*

Bare-under-*LEN* embeddings only yield a simultaneous interpretation. Since bare clauses are tenseless, they can only be evaluated with respect to the local evaluation time, in

this case the attitude time provided by the embedding predicate⁵⁹. More specifically, the reference time that the aspectual operator STAT/HAB abstracts over is quantified in by the attitude verb. As a result, bare clauses will always yield temporally dependent interpretations when in the scope of a propositional attitude verb.

Recall that, following the lexical entry proposed in 2, attitude verbs take an RT-argument. In the aspect-based representation developed here for Asante Twi, verbs denote properties of eventualities, whose relation to the RT is mediated by a lower viewpoint projection. The semantics of attitude verbs needs to be amended accordingly (cf. Bochnak et al., 2019, p. 437).

$$(133) \quad \llbracket \text{ka} \rrbracket = \lambda w_s. \lambda e_v. \lambda p_{\langle s, \langle i, t \rangle \rangle}. \lambda x_e. \forall \langle w', t' \rangle [\langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Say}(x, w, \tau(e)) \rightarrow p(w')(t')]^{60}$$

According to the semantics in (133), the attitude time t' and the attitude world w' are accessible from the running time of the matrix event ' $\tau(e)$ ' and from the actual world w_c , respectively. The accessibility relation between the attitude time and the reference time of the sentence is mediated here by the sentence aspect.

Given this semantics, we correctly derive the simultaneous reading for the sentence in (135) from the LF in (136). Recall that LEN-marked clauses comprise a pronominal past tense alongside a perfective aspect. The embedded clause, in turn, displays no semantic tense. Moreover, unlike matrix bare clauses, bare complement clauses do not need to project t_c for interpretability, given the presence of a superordinate temporal operator (i.e., the embedding attitude verb). It follows that the open RT-argument in the embedded bare clause is quantificationally bound by the attitude verb, giving rise to a simultaneous interpretation.

- (134) a. SIM-Context: You and Aba were supposed to watch a movie last Friday night. Unfortunately, Aba called you to cancel one hour before the movie. She told you: 'I am sick'. The week after you explain to your friend why Aba could not make it on Friday night:
 b. BACK-Context: Aba was absent from work last week due to sickness, but she is fine now. When you saw her back at work yesterday, she told you about it. You report her words today:

$$(135) \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{Aba ka-à} \quad \text{sε} \quad \text{ɔ-yare.} \\ \text{Aba say-LEN COMP 3SG-sick} \\ \text{'Aba said that she was (currently) sick.'} \end{array} \quad (\checkmark \text{SIM} / \# \text{BACK})$$

⁵⁹If the system supplies t_c in embedded contexts, the distinguished variable is locally bound, leading to the same truth-conditional output.

⁶⁰ $\text{Say}(x, w, t) = \{ \langle w, t \rangle : \langle w, t \rangle \text{ is compatible with what } x \text{ says in } w \text{ throughout } t \}$.

(137) *Definedness conditions for (136):*

$\llbracket (136) \rrbracket$ defined iff $g(2) < t_c$

(138) *Compositional interpretation for (136) with selected sub-proofs:⁶¹*

(i) $\llbracket [CP_{embedded}] \rrbracket = \lambda w. \lambda t. \lambda \langle i, t \rangle. \exists e' [t \subseteq \tau(e') \ \& \ sick(w)(e')(g(9))]$

(ii) $\llbracket [V']_{matrix} \rrbracket =$ (by 3*FA, Lex, T&P)
 $\llbracket ka \rrbracket (g(0))(g(4)) (\llbracket \lambda w. \lambda t. \lambda \langle i, t \rangle. \exists e' [t \subseteq \tau(e') \ \& \ sick(w)(e')(g(9)) \rrbracket]) =$
 (by Lex, 2*LC)

$[\lambda p_{\langle s, \langle i, t \rangle \rangle}. \lambda x_e. \forall \langle w', t' \rangle [\langle w', t' \rangle \in Say(x, g(0), \tau(g(4))) \rightarrow p(w')(t')]] (\llbracket \lambda w. \lambda t. \lambda \langle i, t \rangle. \exists e' [t \subseteq \tau(e') \ \& \ sick(w)(e')(g(9)) \rrbracket]) =$ (by LC)

$[\lambda x_e. \forall \langle w', t' \rangle [\langle w', t' \rangle \in Say(x, g(0), \tau(g(4))) \rightarrow \exists e' [t \subseteq \tau(e') \ \& \ sick(w')(e')(g(9))]]]$

(iii) $\llbracket [AspP_{matrix}] \rrbracket =$ (by FA)

$\llbracket [PFV] \rrbracket^{g(4 \rightarrow e'')} ([\lambda e''. \forall \langle w', t' \rangle [\langle w', t' \rangle \in Say(A, g(0), \tau(e'')) \rightarrow \exists e' [t \subseteq \tau(e') \ \& \ sick(w')(e')(g(9))]]])$
 = (by Lex, LC)

⁶¹Compositional steps that affect only the definedness conditions are skipped.

- $$[\lambda t. \exists e[\tau(e) \subseteq t \ \& \ \forall \langle w', t' \rangle [\langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Say}(A, g(0), \tau(e)) \rightarrow \exists e'[t' \subseteq \tau(e') \ \& \ \text{sick}(w')(e')(g(9))]]]]$$
- (iv) $\llbracket \text{TP}_{matrix} \rrbracket = 1$ iff (by FA, T&P)
 $\llbracket \text{AspP}_{matrix} \rrbracket(g(2)) = 1$ iff (by LC)
 $\exists e[\tau(e) \subseteq g(2) \ \& \ \forall \langle w', t' \rangle [\langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Say}(A, g(0), \tau(e)) \rightarrow \exists e'[t' \subseteq \tau(e') \ \& \ \text{sick}(w')(e')(g(9))]]]$
- (v) $\llbracket \text{CP}_{matrix} \rrbracket = 1$ iff (by FA)
 $\llbracket \textcircled{1} \rrbracket(w_c) = 1$ iff (by PA)
 $[\lambda w''. \llbracket \textcircled{1} \rrbracket^{g(0 \rightarrow w'')}(w_c) = 1$ iff
 $[\lambda w''. \llbracket \text{TP}_{matrix} \rrbracket^{g(0 \rightarrow w'')}(w_c) = 1$ iff (by subp. (iv))
 $[\lambda w''. \exists e[\tau(e) \subseteq g(2) \ \& \ \forall \langle w', t' \rangle [\langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Say}(A, w'', \tau(e)) \rightarrow \exists e'[t' \subseteq \tau(e') \ \& \ \text{sick}(w')(e')(g(9))]]]](w_c) = 1$ iff (by 2*LC)
 $\exists e[\tau(e) \subseteq g(2) \ \& \ \forall \langle w', t' \rangle [\langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Say}(A, w_c, \tau(e)) \rightarrow \exists e'[t' \subseteq \tau(e') \ \& \ \text{sick}(w')(e')(g(9))]]]$
(with $g(9) = \text{Aba}$)

Paraphrase: ‘There is an event e , such that e is temporally included in $g(2)$ (with $g(2)$ before t_c), and for all worlds w' and **times t' compatible with what Aba said throughout e** and in the actual world w_c , it follows that there is a **state e' that temporally includes t'** and that is a state of Aba being sick in w' .’

According to the meaning computed in (137) and (138), the attitude holder locates herself at a time that is entirely contained by the embedded state’s temporal interval, leading to a simultaneous interpretation.

3.5.2 LEN-embeddings and temporal *de Dicto*

Similarly to bare clauses, LEN-embeddings primarily yield temporally dependent interpretations. Since LEN exhibits a relative past semantics, these translate into backward-shifted readings in attitude contexts. This is shown for the LEN-under-LEN sentence in (140).

- (139) a. SIM-Context: Awusi follows a pescatarian diet, typically enjoying fish every Friday evening. While chatting with Aba over dinner last Friday, she turned to you and remarked: “I bet Awusi is eating fish right now!” You later report Aba’s thoughts.
b. BACK-Context: Awusi follows a pescatarian diet, typically enjoying fish every Friday evening. Today’s Saturday. Talking to Aba at lunch, she said: “I bet Awusi had fish last night!” You later report Aba’s thoughts.
- (140) Aba gye di-ì se Awusi di-ì fish.
Aba believe-LEN COMP Awusi eat-LEN fish
‘Aba said that Awusi had eaten fish.’ (#SIM / ✓BACK)

The Logical Form for (140) is provided in (142). For *gye di*, I am assuming an event-based semantics similar to the one given for *ka*, the only difference being that the belief-alternatives are introduced by the doxastic function *Dox*. The lexical entry is given in (141). Recall that complement clauses of attitude verbs denote properties of times. In LEN-embeddings, this is the result of λ -abstraction over the local EvalT by the binder

‘ λt_5 ’.

(141) $\llbracket \text{gye di} \rrbracket = \lambda w_s. \lambda e_v. \lambda p_{\langle s, \langle i, t \rangle \rangle}. \lambda x_e. \forall \langle w', t' \rangle [\langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Dox}(x, w, \tau(e)) \rightarrow p(w')(t')]$ ⁶²

For (142), definedness conditions and truth-conditions are computed in (143) and (144), respectively. Importantly, the ordering relation (of precedence) between the two eventualities results from a *de Dicto* interpretation of the embedded tense *past*_{2,5}. This relation is however not asserted but introduced via the presupposition in (77). The presupposition projects up to the abstractor ‘ λt_5 ’ binding *g*(5).⁶³ This, in turn, restricts the RT *g*(2) to times before the attitude time *t*’.

(143) *Definedness conditions for (142) with selected sub-proofs:*

⁶² $\text{Dox}(x, w, t) = \{ \langle w, t \rangle : \langle w, t \rangle \text{ is compatible with what } x \text{ believes in } w \text{ throughout } t \}$.

⁶³For a view consistent with presuppositions percolating upward into attitude predicates, see Geurts, 1999; Maier, 2009, among others.

- (i) $\llbracket \text{CP}_{embedded} \rrbracket$ defined iff (by 2*PA)
 $\lambda w''. \lambda t''. \llbracket \text{TP}_{embedded} \rrbracket^{g(1 \rightarrow w'', 5 \rightarrow t'')}$ defined iff (by FA)
 $[\lambda w''. \lambda t''. \llbracket \text{AspP}_{embedded} \rrbracket^{g(1 \rightarrow w'', 5 \rightarrow t'')}](\llbracket \text{past}_{2,5} \rrbracket^{g(1 \rightarrow w'', 5 \rightarrow t'')})$ defined iff (by T&P)
 $[\lambda w''. \lambda t''. \llbracket \text{AspP}_{embedded} \rrbracket^{g(1 \rightarrow w'', 5 \rightarrow t'')}](g(2): g(2) < g(5))$ defined iff (by 5 \rightarrow t'')
 $[\lambda w''. \lambda t''. \llbracket \text{AspP}_{embedded} \rrbracket^{g(1 \rightarrow w'', 5 \rightarrow t'')}](g(2): g(2) < t'')$ defined
- (ii) $\llbracket V'_{matrix} \rrbracket$ defined iff (by FA, Subp.(i))
 $\llbracket \text{gye di} \rrbracket(g(0))(g(4))([\lambda w''. \lambda t''. \llbracket \text{AspP}_{embedded} \rrbracket^{g(1 \rightarrow w'', 5 \rightarrow t'')}](g(2): g(2) < t''))$ defined
iff (by Lex)
 $\lambda w_s. \lambda e_v. \lambda p_{\langle s, \langle i, t \rangle \rangle}. \lambda x_e. \forall \langle w', t' \rangle [\langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Dox}(x, w, \tau(e)) \rightarrow p(w')(t')](g(0))(g(4))([\lambda w''. \lambda t''. \llbracket \text{AspP}_{embedded} \rrbracket^{g(1 \rightarrow w'', 5 \rightarrow t'')}](g(2): g(2) < t''))$ defined iff (by LC)
 $\lambda x_e. \forall \langle w', t' \rangle [\langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Dox}(x, w, \tau(e)) \rightarrow [\lambda w''. \llbracket \text{AspP}_{embedded} \rrbracket^{g(1 \rightarrow w'', 5 \rightarrow t'')}](w')(g(2): g(2) < t')]]$ defined iff $\underline{g(2) < t'}$
- (iii) $\llbracket (142) \rrbracket$ defined iff
 $\llbracket \textcircled{1} \rrbracket$ defined iff (by FA, T&P)
 $\llbracket \textcircled{2} \rrbracket(t_c)$ defined iff (by PA)
 $[\lambda t'''. \llbracket \text{TP}_{matrix} \rrbracket^{g(7 \rightarrow t''')}] (t_c)$ defined iff (by FA, T&P)
 $[\lambda t'''. \llbracket \text{AspP}_{matrix} \rrbracket^{g(7 \rightarrow t''')}(g(6): g(6) < g(7))](t_c)$ defined iff (by 7 \rightarrow t''')
 $[\lambda t'''. \llbracket \text{AspP}_{matrix} \rrbracket^{g(7 \rightarrow t''')}(g(6): g(6) < g(7))](t_c)$ defined iff (LC)
 $\llbracket \text{AspP}_{matrix} \rrbracket^{g(7 \rightarrow t''')}(g(6): g(6) < t_c)$ defined iff (by subp.(ii))
 $g(6) < t_c$ & $\llbracket V'_{matrix} \rrbracket$ defined iff
 $\underline{g(6) < t_c \ \& \ g(2) < t'}$

(144) *Compositional interpretation for (142) with sub-proofs:*

- (i) $\llbracket \text{AspP}_{embedded} \rrbracket =$ (by FA)
 $\llbracket \text{PFV} \rrbracket(\llbracket \text{VP}_{embedded} \rrbracket) =$ (by PA, Lex, 4*FA, 2*T&P)
 $\llbracket \text{PFV} \rrbracket([\lambda e. [\lambda w. \lambda e. \lambda a. \lambda b. \text{eat}(w)(e)(a)(b)](w(0))(e)(\iota z[\text{fish}(z)])(AW)) =$ (by Lex, LC)
 $[\lambda p. \lambda t. \exists e'[\tau(e') \subseteq t \ \& \ p(e')]](\text{eat}(w(0))(e)(\iota z[\text{fish}(z)])(AW)) =$ (LC)
 $[\lambda t. \exists e'[\tau(e') \subseteq t \ \& \ \text{eat}(w(1))(e')(\iota z[\text{fish}(z)])(AW)]]$
- (ii) $\llbracket V'_{matrix} \rrbracket =$ iff (by 3*FA)
 $\llbracket \text{gye di} \rrbracket(g(0))(g(4))(\llbracket \text{CP}_{emb} \rrbracket) =$ (by Lex+LC, 2*PA)
 $[\lambda p_{\langle s, \langle i, t \rangle \rangle}. \lambda x_e. \forall \langle w', t' \rangle [\langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Dox}(x, g(0), \tau(g(4))) \rightarrow p(w')(t')]]([\lambda w''. \lambda t''. \llbracket \text{AspP}_{emb} \rrbracket^{g(1 \rightarrow w'', 5 \rightarrow t'')}](g(2): g(2) < t'')) =$ (by SubP.(i), Lex)
 $[\lambda x_e. \forall \langle w', t' \rangle [\langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Dox}(x, g(0), \tau(g(4))) \rightarrow [\lambda w''. \lambda t''. [\lambda t. \exists e'[\tau(e') \subseteq t \ \& \ \text{eat}(w'')(e')(\iota z[\text{fish}(z)])(AW)]](g(2): g(2) < t'')](w')(t') =$ (by 2*LC)
 $[\lambda x_e. \forall \langle w', t' \rangle [\langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Dox}(x, g(0), \tau(g(4))) \rightarrow \exists e'[\tau(e') \subseteq (g(2): g(2) < t') \ \& \ \text{eat}(w')(e')(\iota z[\text{fish}(z)])(AW)]]]$
- (iii) $\llbracket (142) \rrbracket = 1$ iff (by 2*FA, 2*PA)
 $[\lambda w''. \llbracket \text{TP}_{matrix} \rrbracket^{g(0 \rightarrow w'')}] (w_c) = 1$ iff (by 2*FA, T&P)
 $[\lambda w''. \llbracket \text{PFV} \rrbracket(\llbracket \text{VP}_{matrix} \rrbracket^{g(0 \rightarrow w'')})(g(6))](w_c) = 1$ iff (by Lex, PA, FA)
 $[\lambda w''. [\lambda p. \lambda t. \exists e[\tau(e) \subseteq t \ \& \ p(e)]]([\lambda e'' \llbracket V'_{matrix} \rrbracket^{g(0 \rightarrow w'', 4 \rightarrow e'')}] (ABA))](g(6))](w_c) =$
1 iff (by subp. (ii))
 $[\lambda w''. [\lambda p. \lambda t. \exists e[\tau(e) \subseteq t \ \& \ p(e)]]([\lambda e''. [\lambda x_e. \forall \langle w', t' \rangle [\langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Dox}(x, w'', \tau(e'')) \rightarrow \exists e'[\tau(e') \subseteq (g(2)) \ \& \ \text{eat}(w')(e')(\iota z[\text{fish}(z)])(AW)]]](ABA))](g(6))](w_c) = 1$ iff

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (2^*LC) \\
 & [\lambda p. \lambda t. \exists e[\tau(e) \subseteq t \ \& \ p(e)]]([\lambda e''. [\forall \langle w', t' \rangle [\langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Dox}(\text{ABA}, w_c, \tau(e'')) \rightarrow \exists e'[\tau(e') \\
 & \subseteq (g(2)) \ \& \ \text{eat}(w')(e')(iz[\text{fish}(z)])(\text{AW})]]]]](g(6)) = 1 \quad (\text{by LC}) \\
 & [\lambda t. \exists e[\tau(e) \subseteq t \ \& \ [\forall \langle w', t' \rangle [\langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Dox}(\text{ABA}, w_c, \tau(e)) \rightarrow \exists e'[\tau(e') \subseteq (g(2)) \ \& \\
 & \text{eat}(w')(e')(iz[\text{fish}(z)])(\text{AW})]]]]](g(6)) = 1 \quad (\text{by LC}) \\
 & \exists e[\tau(e) \subseteq g(6) \ \& \ [\forall \langle w', t' \rangle [\langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Dox}(\text{ABA}, w_c, \tau(e)) \rightarrow \exists e'[\tau(e') \subseteq (g(2)) \ \& \\
 & \text{eat}(w')(e')(iz[\text{fish}(z)])(\text{AW})]]]]
 \end{aligned}$$

Paraphrase: ‘There is an event e , such that e is temporally included in a time $g(6)$ preceding t_c and for all the worlds w' and **times t' that are compatible with what Aba believes throughout e** in the actual world w_c , it follows that there is an event e' , such that e' is time included in a **time $g(2)$ preceding t'** and e' is an event of Awusi eating fish in w' .

According to the meaning computed in (143) and (144), the embedded eventuality holds true of a time preceding that at which the attitude holder locates herself, thus generating a backward-shifted interpretation. Borrowing from the modal semantics terminology, I refer to this reading as temporal *de Dicto*.

One important prediction this analysis makes is the availability of strictly backward-shifted interpretations even in future contexts. In the light of (132-b) repeated in (145-a), this prediction is borne out.

(145) Context: Kwame wants to skip school tomorrow and go to the mall instead. Once he's back the day after, he'll bring a fake note from the doctor to the teacher. This is what he expects: ‘she will think I was sick the day before’.

- a. $\text{\textcircled{a}}\text{kyer\textcircled{a}}\text{kyer\textcircled{e}}\text{ni} \ \text{n\textcircled{o}} \ \text{b\textcircled{e}}\text{-gye} \quad \text{a-di} \quad \text{s\textcircled{e}} \quad \text{me-yare-\textcircled{e}}.$
 teacher DEF PROSP-believe CONS-PTCL COMP 1SG-sick
 ‘The teacher will believe that I was sick.’

Recall that the choice for a relative rather than an absolute past tense semantics for LEN was motivated based on the fact that the utterance time for future attitude reports does not constitute an upper limit to the embedded tense’s denotation. Let me briefly show how this analysis can correctly capture the meaning of (145-a). In order to do so, I will assume for the prospective marker ‘be’ the semantics in (146) (cf. Mucha, 2015).⁶⁴

$$(146) \quad \llbracket \text{PROSP} \rrbracket = \lambda p_{\langle v, t \rangle}. \lambda t_i. \exists e[\tau(e) > t \ \& \ p(e)]$$

With the semantics outlined in (146), we compute the meaning of the sentence in (145-a), whose simplified LF is provided in (147), as shown in (148).⁶⁵

⁶⁴As briefly discussed in section 3.2.2, ‘be’ has traditionally been considered a future tense. While I do not wish to provide an extensive characterization of its properties here, I will simply note that there are two main reasons why the literature’s claims should be refuted. Firstly, ‘be’ is typically used to express future in the past, thus yielding strictly forward-shifted interpretations. Secondly, it cannot combine with any of the other aspectual markers (including *a* and LEN), whereas it can combine with the tense *ná*. For these reasons, I will treat ‘be’ as a (relative) prospective aspect.

⁶⁵I will ignore the contribution of the consecutive marker ‘a’ and treat the serial verb construction ‘begye adi’ as one whole predicate marked with prospective aspect.

(147) $[_{CP} \dots t_c [_{TP} - [_{AspP} PROSP [_{VP} \dots gye-di [_{CP} \dots \lambda t_5 [_{TP} past_{2,5} [_{AspP} PFV$
 $[_{VP} \dots yare]]]]]]]]]]$

- (148) a. $\llbracket (147) \rrbracket$ defined iff $\mathbf{g(2)} < \mathbf{t'}$
 b. When defined, $\llbracket (147) \rrbracket = 1$ iff
 $\exists e[\tau(e) > t_c \ \& \ \forall \langle w', t' \rangle [\langle w', t' \rangle \in Dox(ABA, w_c, \tau(e)) \rightarrow \exists e'[\tau(e') \subseteq g(2) \ \& \ sick(w')(e)(speaker)]]]$
 ‘There is a state e , such that e temporally follows t_c and for all the worlds and times w' and t' compatible with what the unique z , such that z is a teacher, **believed throughout e** in the actual world w_c , it follows that there is an eventuality e' , such that **e' is temporally included in a temporal interval $g(2)$ preceding t'** and e' is a state of the speaker being sick in w' .

According to the meaning given in (148), the sickness-state e' is located at a time that precedes the future time t' at which the teacher locates herself (i.e., some temporal interval holding at two days from UT). This entails that $\tau(e')$ may be placed on a timeline at any point before t' , including times that follow UT.

3.5.3 *ná*-embeddings and temporal *de re*

Thus far, we have observed that the composition of attitude reports for both bare and LEN-embeddings proceeds in a transparent fashion, with a one-to-one form-to-meaning mapping. By contrast, our empirical findings demonstrate that (in past-oriented contexts) *ná*-embeddings are systematically ambiguous between a simultaneous and a backward-shifted interpretation (see (150)). Crucially, according to the semantics adopted for *ná* in section 3.3.2 and repeated in (149), the reference time is not related to the local evaluation time in any possible way.

- (149) a. $\llbracket ná_7 \rrbracket$ defined iff there is a contextually salient time $g(7) [\neg(g(7) \circ t_c)]$
 b. When defined, $\llbracket ná_7 \rrbracket = g(7)$

(150) Awusi ka-à sɛ ná ɔ-yare.
 Awusi say-LEN COMP NA 3SG.sick

- a. SIM: ‘Awusi said that she was sick (at the time).’
 b. BACK: ‘Awusi said that she was sick (back then).’

Following (149), *ná*-embeddings cannot derive BACK via *de Dicto*-construals, in that the RT ‘ $g(7)$ ’ has no compositional access to the local EvalT (i.e. the attitude time in attitude contexts). Consequently, the only available compositional pathway to a backward-shifted reading is given by a *de re* analysis. This is by no means surprising, since *de re* typically targets (nominal or temporal) referential expressions.

On the other hand, the derivation of simultaneous readings can result from three different compositional mechanisms: (i) deletion, (ii) binding, (iii) temporal *de re*. We have seen that, for English and more in general SoT languages, the availability of SIM for the so-called *breakfast*-sentences is diagnostic of a deletion-based analysis. Unfortunately, future contexts won’t provide an ideal testing ground for *ná*-embeddings. Given the lack

of a temporal orientation, *ná*'s tense features do not need to be *deleted* for its presuppositions to be satisfied even in later-than-now scenarios. However, the temporal reference introduced by *ná* does come with a restriction, namely the exclusion of the utterance time as illustrated in (149-a). It follows that, if *ná*'s meaning contribution were invisible to semantic composition when in the scope of an agreeing tense, the embedded *ná*-marked predicate should hold true of a temporal interval that includes UT. These predictions are illustrated in (151).

- (151) *Toy Logical Form for ná-under-ná/LEN embeddings under deletion*
- a. [... [TP past_{2,3}/na₉ ... [VP ka $\forall t'$ [CP λ_{t_5} ~~na~~₇ [AspP STAT [VP ...]]]]]]]
 - b. [... [TP past_{2,3}/na₉ ... [VP ka $\forall t'$ [CP λ_{t_5} t₅ [AspP STAT [VP ... yare]]]]]]]]

As shown in (151), deletion of the most-embedded *ná* leaves a co-indexed trace behind, which is bound by the abstractor ' λ_{t_5} ' and eventually quantified in by the attitude predicate's time ' t' '. This *de se* derivation produces an output equivalent to that of bare embeddings, that is a simultaneous interpretation. Note that if the embedded clause contains a temporal adverb that contains both AT and UT, a double access interpretation arises even for an embedded past tense. This is shown below.

- (152) Reporting on Sunday morning John's statement from the day before:
Yesterday John said that Mary was/is working this whole weekend.

In (152), both present and past-embeddings convey that Mary was working on Saturday and Sunday. As we have seen in chapter 2, the double access interpretation for the embedded present tense follows from a *de re* analysis, preventing both a ULC-violation and a presupposition failure with respect to present's indexicality. A comparable interpretation can be derived for the embedded past via deletion. Here the modification by *this weekend* forces the attitude time to stretch forward and overlap the utterance time.

I will apply the same test to Asante Twi *ná*-embeddings. If the UT-exclusion restriction can be ignored in SoT configurations, then we expect the sentences in (153-b) and (153-c) to be felicitous in the context provided in (153).

- (153) Context: On Saturday you asked Kofi why Ama was not around. Kofi told you: "I think Ama is working this whole weekend." It's Sunday morning now and Ama is working her last shift. A friend asks you why Ama is not at home, you reply:
- a. ϵ nnora ná Kofi gye di se Ama re-yε adwuma dapɛn awiei
yesterday NA Kofi believe COMP Ama PROG-COP work week end
yi.
this
'Yesterday Kofi believed that Ama is working this weekend.'
 - b. # ϵ nnora Kofi gye di-ì se ná Ama re-yε adwuma dapɛn
yesterday Kofi believe-LEN COMP NA Ama PROG-COP work week
awiei yi.
end this
Intended: 'Yesterday Kofi believed that Ama was working this weekend.'

3 Temporal meaning and the composition of attitude reports in Asante Twi (Akan)

- c. # *ennora ná Kofi gye di se ná Ama re-ye adwuma dapɛn*
 yesterday NA Kofi believe COMP NA Ama PROG-COP work week
awiei yi.
 end this
 Intended: ‘Yesterday Kofi believed that Ama was working this weekend.’

In (153), the only viable option is an embedded bare clause. The distal deictic *ná* cannot appear in the complement clause, independently of whether it’s (morphologically or semantically) licensed. The following example bolsters the validity of these findings.

- (154) Context: For two weeks now Ama has been complaining about her health. It’s unclear what she’s got, but every single day until now she’s been telling everyone: “I am sick.”
- a. *Nnawɔtwe mmienu ni ná Ama a-ka se ɔ-yare.*
 week two PROX FOC Ama A-ka COMP 3SG-sick
 ‘For two weeks now Ama has been saying that she is sick.’
- b. # *Nnawɔtwe mmienu ni ná Ama a-ka se ná ɔ-yare.*
 week two PROX FOC Ama A-ka COMP NA 3SG-sick
 ‘For two weeks now Ama has been saying that she was sick.’

In (154), the hybrid perfect *a*, in combination with a duration-quantifying adverbial, forces a universal interpretation of the attitude predicate. The infelicity of the *ná*-embedding shows once more the impossibility for *ná* to yield simultaneous interpretations if these involve overlapping with the utterance time. These data indicate that *ná* is projective even in environments that typically license deletion.

Despite these findings, option (ii) cannot be ruled out on the basis of the DAR-test. It is true that binding of a tense variable produces a *de se* LF akin to the one obtained via deletion. Nevertheless, the fact that a variable’s features can be transmitted via a binding chain allows the presupposition of *ná* to project. Let’s briefly explore what the predictions of a binding-based analysis should look like for *ná* in past-oriented contexts.

- (155) *Toy Logical Form for ná-under-ná/LEN embeddings under binding*
- a. $[_{\text{TP}} \text{past}_{2,3}/\text{na}_9 \dots [_{\text{VP}} \text{ka } \forall t' [_{\text{CP}} \lambda_5 \text{na}_5: \neg(\text{g}(5) < \text{UT}) [_{\text{AspP}} \dots]]]]$
- b. $[_{\text{TP}} \text{past}_{2,3}/\text{na}_9 \dots [_{\text{VP}} \text{ka } \forall t': \neg(t' < \text{UT}) [_{\text{CP}} \lambda_5 \text{na}_5 [_{\text{AspP}} \dots]]]]$

With regard to the examples in (153) and (154), the LF sketched in (155-b) would yield an interpretation for which the embedded predicate holds true of the attitude time *t'*. This temporal interval must simultaneously encompass (via adverbial modification) and exclude (via *ná*’s inherited presupposition) the utterance time. This creates a logical contradiction, which may explain the unacceptability of these sentences. However, a diagnostic more suited for a binding-based analysis emerges when considering permanent states of affairs, such as generics or i-level predicates. As we have seen in chapter 2, these predicates yield cessation implicatures under past tense morphology. While these implicatures disappear in past-tensed attitude contexts for SoT languages, they persist for non-SoT languages. This is illustrated below for English and Russian.

- (156) a. John knew that penguins have / had wings. (English)

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- b. John znal, chto u pingvinov est' / #byli kryl'ya. (Russian)
 John know.PAST COMP at penguins be.PRES / PAST wings
- (157) Context (2150 years ago): Ptolemy to himself: 'Eureka, the Sun revolves around the Earth!'
- a. Ptolemy believed that the Sun revolves / revolved around the Earth. (Eng)
- b. Ptolemey veril, chto Solntse vrashchayetsya / #vrashchalos'
 Ptolemy believe.PAST that Sun revolve.PRES / PAST
 vokrug Zemli. (Rus)
 around Earth.

In (157), the past-tensed variant of the Russian attitude report is unacceptable, in that it correlates with a bizarre interpretation for which what Ptolemy believed is that the Sun used to revolve around the Earth and then stopped doing so. Similar judgments are reported for (156). In both cases, a present tense must be used. Conversely, English reports allow for both tense forms. Asante Twi appears to pattern with Russian, as the following sentences show.

- (158) Context: On Ama's birthday, Kofi made a peculiar statement: 'Obi is Nigerian.' Today, you report it, aware that Obi is, in fact, Ghanaian.
- a. εwɔ Ama awoda nó Kofi ka-à se (# ná) Obi ye Nigerian.
 on Ama birthday DEF Kofi say-LEN COMP NA Obi COP Nigerian
- b. εwɔ Ama awoda nó ná Kofi gye di se (# ná) Obi ye
 on Ama birthday DEF NA Kofi believe PTCL COMP NA Obi COP
 Nigerian.
 Nigerian
- (159) Context: Kofi mistakenly believed that Ama's eyes were blue, whereas, in reality, she has black eyes. Kofi's original belief: 'Ama has blue eyes.'
- a. Kofi gye di-ì se Ama ani ye blue.
 Kofi believe PTCL-LEN COMP Ama eyes COP blue
- b. # Kofi gye di-ì se ná Ama ani ye blue.
 Kofi believe PTCL-LEN COMP NA Ama eyes COP blue
- (160) Context: Last year, on Ama's birthday, Kofi expressed a peculiar belief: 'The moon is a star.' Today, you report it.
- a. εwɔ Ama awoda nó Kofi ka-à se (# ná) ɔseramo nó ye
 on Ama birthday DEF Kofi say-LEN COMP NA moon DEF COP
 nsoroma.
 star.
- b. εwɔ Ama awoda nó ná Kofi re-ka se (# ná) ɔseramo nó
 on Ama birthday DEF NA Kofi PROG-say COMP NA moon DEF
 ye nsoroma.
 COP star.

The sentences in (158)-(160) are only felicitous if *ná* is dropped, irrespective of the matrix

tense. My consultants observed that in these scenarios a semantically *vacuous* reading for the embedded clause is not available. The only possible temporal interpretation indicates that the embedded state ceased to obtain at some previous point. It is worth noting that these sentences involve false attitudes towards permanent states of affairs. In this regard, Khomitsevich (2008, p. 98) reports that in SoT languages like English and Dutch, there exists a preference for past tense when the permanent/generic attitude report is false, and for present tense when it's true. No such preference is attested in Asante Twi, as demonstrated by the following data, where *ná* must always be omitted irrespective of whether the embedded proposition is true or false.

(161) Context: Kofi's old belief: 'Chalk is white.'

- a. Kofi gye di-ì sɛ (# ná) chalk nó yɛ fitaa.
 Kofi believe PTCL-LEN COMP NA chalk DEF COP white
- b. Ná Kofi gye di sɛ (# ná) chalk nó yɛ fitaa.
 NA Kofi believe PTCL COMP NA chalk DEF COP white

(162) Context: Kofi is well-versed in horses. When you purchased your first horse, he offered valuable advice on their diet. However, they recently advised against feeding them beets, and you objected:

- a. Kofi ka-à sɛ (# ná) apɔnkɔ di beets.
 Kofi say-LEN COMP NA horses eat beets
- b. Ná Kofi gye di sɛ (# ná) apɔnkɔ di beets.
 NA Kofi believe PTCL COMP NA horses eat beets

These findings strongly suggest that the simultaneous interpretation for *ná* embeddings cannot result from tense deletion or semantic binding. In the absence of a *de Dicto* construal, the only compositional option is a *de re* analysis. As discussed in the previous chapter, there are contexts where a *de re* construal becomes most salient. These typically involve cases of time misconception and erroneous temporal self-location. Consider the following scenario.

(163) Context: (after Schlenker, 1999, p. 124) Kwesi wakes up after a long afternoon nap. His watch stopped working and shows it's 4pm, but it's actually 6pm. Kwesi knows that Awusi's shift at work ends at 5pm and she's usually back home by 5.30pm. Kwesi thinks: 'It's 4pm, Awusi is at work right now!'. Later that day, you report Kwesi's beliefs.

- a. ? Kwesi gye di-ì sɛ Awusi re-yɛ adwuma.
 Kwesi believe PTCL-LEN COMP Awusi PROG-COP work
- b. Kwesi gye di-ì sɛ ná Awusi re-yɛ adwuma.
 Kwesi believe PTCL-LEN COMP NA Awusi PROG-COP work
- c. Intended: 'Kofi believed that Awusi was at work (at the moment).'

(164) Context: (after Ogihara & Sharvit, 2012, p. 658) Kofi, waking from a coma yesterday, mistakenly believed it was February instead of April. Despite his wife's due date being in March, he concluded that she is pregnant, unaware that it's already April.

- a. ? *ennora* Kofi gye di-ì se ne yere nyem.
yesterday Kofi believe PTCL-LEN COMP 3POSS wife pregnant
- b. *ennora* Kofi gye di-ì se ná ne yere nyem.
yesterday Kofi believe PTCL-LEN COMP NA 3POSS wife pregnant
- c. Intended: ‘Yesterday, Kofi believed that his wife was pregnant (at the moment).’

The sentences in (163) and (164) yield a simultaneous interpretation, in which the attitude holder situates themselves at a time where the embedded state holds. Clearly, from the speaker’s perspective, this state no longer holds at the attitude time. Interestingly, the *ná*-variant was accepted by both speakers, while the bare one was rejected by one of the two. I argue that the bare embedding constitutes a neutral report of Kofi’s beliefs and his temporal location. In contrast, by choosing the *ná*-marked complement clause, the speaker wants to convey that Kofi’s belief holds of a particular time in the past (the one denoted by *ná*) and, in doing so, she signals that Kofi might be mistaken regarding his temporal location.

Building on the analysis outlined in chapter 2, I will assume that *de re* LFs in Asante involve concept generators. Recall that CGs are acquaintance-based and denote functions from times to time concepts. A concept generator is defined as follows (after Sharvit, 2018, p. 221).

- (165) A time-concept generator suitable for x in world w and time t is a function G such that:
- a. The domain D of G is the set of times that x is acquainted with in w at t ; and
- b. $\forall t''$: $t'' \in D(G)$, it follows:
- (i) $G(t'')$ is a suitable time-concept;
- (ii) $\forall \langle w', t' \rangle \in ACC(x, w, t) \rightarrow G(t'')(t')(w')$ is defined⁶⁶;
- (iii) $G(t'')(t)(w) = t''$;
- (iv) $\forall \langle w', t' \rangle \in D(G(t'')) \rightarrow \neg(G(t'')(t')(w') > t')$. (ULC)

Concept generators map the temporal *res* to acquaintance relations, thus providing a way for the attitude holder to describe a particular time to themselves.⁶⁷ Following (ii) and (iii) in the formula in (165), a concept generator is of type $\langle i, \langle i, \langle s, i \rangle \rangle \rangle$: it takes a temporal *res*, an evaluation time and an evaluation world, returning a time. In (iv), Abusch (1997)’s Upper limit constraint is formalized as a restriction on the time output by the concept generator ‘ G ’, thus preventing forward-shifted interpretations.

Consider once more the SIM-biasing context in (166) and the *ná*-under-LEN sentence in (166-a), whose LF is given in (167).

⁶⁶ ACC is a function serving as placeholder for a specific accessibility relation.

⁶⁷Sharvit observes that suitable time-concepts include deictic temporal concepts like ‘now’ or ‘yesterday’, since everyone is acquainted with them. However, what precisely renders certain time-concepts more suitable than others remains unclear. Additionally, the degree of essentiality for the attitude holder to be acquainted with the *res* in the first place, and, consequently, how acquaintance can be precisely defined, remains uncertain. I will return to this point later.

(166) Context: You and Aba were supposed to watch a movie last Friday night. Unfortunately, Aba called you to cancel one hour before the movie. She told you: ‘I am sick’. The week after you explain to your friend why Aba could not make it on Friday night:

- a. ? Aba ka-à sɛ ná ɔ-yare.
 Aba say-LEN COMP NA 3SG-sick
 ‘Aba said that she was sick (at that time).’

The embedded clause in (167) is a function from concept generators to propositions. The CG ‘G₇’ is locally bound and quantified in by the attitude verb. The semantics of propositional attitude verbs such as *ka* (‘say’) needs to be amended accordingly.

- (168) $\llbracket ka_{deRe} \rrbracket = \lambda w_s. \lambda e_v. \lambda p_{\langle \langle i, (i, (s, i)) \rangle \rangle, \langle s, (i, t) \rangle \rangle}. \lambda x_e. \exists G [G \text{ suitable for } x \text{ in } w \text{ at } \tau(e) \ \& \ \forall \langle w', t' \rangle [\langle w', t' \rangle \in Say(x, w, \tau(e)) \rightarrow p(G)(w')(t')]]$

Following (168), propositional attitude verbs additionally quantify over concept generators. Importantly, the embedded aspect phrase is no longer evaluated with respect to the time denoted by the clausal tense (in this case $g(9)$), but rather to the one constructed by the concept generator (in this case $G(g(9))(t')(w')$). This, in turn, avoids the thorny conundrum of keeping the variable $ná_9$ free while, at the same time, having the attitude verb's doxastic time bind into the embedded proposition.

With the revised semantics for 'ka' in (168) and a relevant acquaintance relation suitable for the context in (169), the system is able to derive the simultaneous reading for (167). The resulting definedness conditions and truth conditions are computed in (170) and (171), respectively.

- (169) Given a suitable time-concept generator G :
 $G = \lambda t. \lambda t'. \lambda w'. t$ is a temporal interval including Aba's phone call at t' in w' .
 It follows that $G(g(9)) = \text{'now'}$ (Aba would describe $g(9)$ to herself as 'now'.)
 $G(g(9)) = \text{'now'} \rightarrow G(g(9))(t')(w') = g(9) = t'$
- (170) *Definedness conditions for (167):*
 $\llbracket (167) \rrbracket$ defined iff
 $g(1) < t_c$; (PSP of 'past_{1,3}')
 $\neg(g(9) \circ t_c)$; (PSP of 'na₇')
 $\forall \langle w', t' \rangle \in D(G(g(9))) \rightarrow \neg(G(g(9))(t')(w') > t')$ (ULC)
- (171) *Truth-conditions and denotations of selected nodes from (167):*
 (i) $\llbracket CP_{emb} \rrbracket = [\lambda G'. \lambda w''. \lambda t''. \exists e' [G'(g(9))(t'')(w'') \subseteq \tau(e') \ \& \ sick(w'')(e')(Aba)]]$
 (ii) $\llbracket V' \rrbracket = \llbracket V \rrbracket^{g(0 \rightarrow w, 6 \rightarrow e)}(\llbracket CP_{emb} \rrbracket) =$
 $[\lambda x. \exists G [G \text{ suitable for } x \text{ in } w \text{ at } \tau(e) \ \& \ \forall \langle w', t' \rangle [\langle w', t' \rangle \in Say(x, w, \tau(e)) \rightarrow$
 $\exists e' [G(g(9))(t')(w') \subseteq \tau(e') \ \& \ sick(w')(e')(Aba)]]]]$
 (iii) $\llbracket (167) \rrbracket = 1$ iff
 $\exists e [\tau(e) \subseteq g(1) \ \& \ \exists G [G \text{ a time CG suitable for Aba in } w_c \text{ at } \tau(e) \ \& \ \forall \langle w', t' \rangle [\langle w', t' \rangle$
 $\in Say(Aba, w_c, \tau(e)) \rightarrow \exists e' [G(g(9))(t')(w') \subseteq \tau(e') \ \& \ sick(w')(e')(Aba)]]]]$

Paraphrase: There is an event e , such that e is temporally included in $g(1)$ preceding t_c and there is a time-concept G suitable for Aba in the actual world throughout e , and for all the worlds w' and times t' compatible with what Aba said throughout e in the actual world, it follows that there is a state e' , such that e' temporally contains the temporal interval denoted by $G(g(9))(t')(w')$ — i.e. $g(9)$, with which Aba is acquainted in w' at t' -, and e' is a state of Aba being sick in w' .

Based on the acquaintance relation (169), the attitude holder may describe the *res* $g(9)$ to herself at the attitude time t' with the time-concept 'now'. As a consequence, a simultaneous reading emerges. Similarly, this analysis can account for backward-shifted interpretations obtaining for the same morpho-syntactic configuration. This is shown for the sentence in (172), which receives equivalent truth-conditions. The only difference lies in the time-concept generated from the acquaintance relation R' in (173).

- (172) Context: Awusi was absent from work last week due to sickness, but she is fine now. When you saw her back at work yesterday, she told you about it. You

report her words today:

- a. Awusi ka-à se ná ɔ-yare.
 Awusi say-LEN COMP NA 3SG.sick
 ‘Awusi said that she was sick (then).’

- (173) Given a suitable acquaintance relation R'_c :
 $\lambda t.\lambda t'.\lambda w'$. t is a temporal interval including Awusi’s absence from work surrounding the week that precedes t' in w' .

The concept generator ‘G’ evaluating the embedded predicate maps the temporal *res* $g(9)$ to the time-concept ‘last week’, thereby yielding a backward-shifted interpretation.

As evident, the SIM/BACK ambiguity of *ná*-embeddings is not resolved at LF-level — that is, the two readings do not correspond to distinct semantic representations. Instead, it is purely contextual and ultimately determined by the type of time-concept construed.

Future contexts and suitable acquaintance relations

Finally, we turn to future-oriented contexts. As outlined in section 3.4.1, these contexts seem to result in a degradation of speakers’ judgments for both simultaneous and backward-shifted interpretations. Having defended a *de re* analysis for embedded *ná*, we must conclude that both readings arise from such mechanism, much in the same manner as the past-oriented contexts previously investigated.

Consider the sentences in (174) and (175), which trigger a simultaneous and a backward-shifted interpretation, respectively.

- (174) Context: Kwame wants to go to a party tonight, but he’s grounded. His plan is to sneak out through the window from his bedroom and put a few pillows below the blankets, so that when his mother goes upstairs and checks on him, she will think he’s sleeping!

- a. ? Me maame bɛ-gye a-di se ná me-re-da.
 1POSS mother PROSP-believe CONS-PTCL COMP NA 1POSS-PROG-sleep
 ‘My mother will think that I’m sleeping.’

- (175) Context: Kwame wants to skip school tomorrow and go to the mall instead. Once he’s back the day after, he’ll bring a fake note from the doctor to the teacher. This is what he expects: ‘she will think I was sick the day before’.

- a. ? ɔkyerɛkyerɛni nó bɛ-gye a-di se ná me-yare.
 teacher DEF PROSP-believe CONS-PTCL COMP NA 1SG-sick
 ‘The teacher will believe that I was sick.’

LFs and resulting truth-conditions for (174-a) and (175-a) are provided below.

- (176) Simplified LF for (174-a): $[_{CP} \dots t_c [_{TP} - [_{AspP} PROSP [_{VP} \dots gye-di [_{CP} \lambda G_7 [\lambda w_5 [\lambda t_2 [_{TP} [T [[G_7 na_9] t_2] w_5]]_{AspP} PROG [VP\dots da]]]]]]]]]]]]$

- (177) Truth conditions for (176):⁶⁸

⁶⁸For simplicity, I am assuming ‘PROG’ and ‘STAT’ share the same semantics (that is, they both denote *ongoingness*. It is reasonable to believe that the two are in complementary distribution in that ‘STAT’

When defined, $\llbracket (176) \rrbracket = 1$ iff

$\exists e[\tau(e) > t_c \ \& \ \exists G[G \text{ a time CG suitable for the speaker's mother M in } w_c \text{ at } \tau(e) \ \& \ \forall \langle w', t' \rangle [\langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Dox}(M, w_c, \tau(e)) \rightarrow \exists e'[G(g(9))(t')(w') \subseteq \tau(e') \ \& \ \text{sleep}(w')(e')(\text{speaker})]]]]]$

(with $G(g(9))$ denoting the time-concept ‘now’).

- (178) Simplified LF for (175-a): $[_{CP} \dots t_c [_{TP} - [_{AspP} \text{PROSP} [_{VP} \dots \text{gye-di} [_{CP} \lambda G_7 [\lambda w_5 [\lambda t_2 [_{TP} [_T [[G_7 \text{na}_9] t_2] w_5][_{AspP} \text{STAT} [_{VP} \dots \text{yare}]]]]]]]]]]]]]]$

- (179) Truth conditions for (178):

When defined, $\llbracket (178) \rrbracket = 1$ iff

$\exists e[\tau(e) > t_c \ \& \ \exists G[G \text{ a time CG suitable for the speaker's teacher T in } w_c \text{ at } \tau(e) \ \& \ \forall \langle w', t' \rangle [\langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Dox}(T, w_c, \tau(e)) \rightarrow \exists e'[G(g(9))(t')(w') \subseteq \tau(e') \ \& \ \text{sick}(w')(e')(\text{speaker})]]]]]$

(with $G(g(9))$ denoting the time-concept ‘yesterday’).

Given appropriate acquaintance relations, the truth-conditions in (177) and (179) yield simultaneous and backward-shifted interpretations, respectively.

The fact that these readings obtain at a time later than UT does not constitute a violation of Abusch’s ULC, since this constraint takes the attitude holder’s now and not the actual now as the upper limit for the embedded reference time. Moreover, in contrast to SIM-readings for past-under-*would* in *breakfast*-sentences in English, there is no need to postulate a deletion rule for embedded *ná*, given that its temporal reference is not restricted to times preceding UT. Nevertheless, a potential issue arises when an acquaintance-based analysis is adopted for future reference: how can the attitude holder be acquainted with a time that hasn’t occurred yet? This leads to a more general, often neglected question: what determines the *suitability* of an acquaintance relation? For a mechanism that can determine temporal interpretations only on the basis of relations of acquaintance between the attitude holder and some relevant time, it is striking that most accounts adopting it have little or nothing to say about acquaintance itself and what constrains it.⁶⁹

Recall from chapter 2 that we defined *de re* ascriptions as acquaintance-based, thus involving ‘cognitive contact’ between the attitude holder and the *res*. The notion of ‘cognitive contact’ has sparked extensive debate in philosophical literature. However, this debate has predominantly centered on individuals rather than times. For instance, Kaplan posits three conditions that make an expression α a suitable representation of an individual x to the attitude holder: (i) α denotes x ; (ii) α is an attribute⁷⁰ of x for the attitude holder in the actual world; (iii) α is sufficiently vivid in the actual world (Kaplan, 1968, p. 203). While conditions in (i) and (ii) are satisfied even for future times, (iii) merits closer attention. Kaplan intentionally leaves the definition of ‘vividness’ somewhat vague, referring to a ‘vividness threshold’ (Kaplan, 1968, p. 204). Importantly, Kaplan suggests that condition (iii) serves to exclude individuals from the future or those who haven’t made a lasting impression on the attitude holder. If we were to extrapolate Ka-

closes off state variables, while ‘PROG’ quantifies over event ones. Nothing hinges on this.

⁶⁹To this regard, Sharvit & Moss (2022, p. 56) observe that ‘semanticists who use acquaintance-based frameworks are often reluctant to enter into substantive theorizing about acquaintance itself.’

⁷⁰Kaplan says ‘name’.

plan’s perspective to temporal contexts, defining cognitive contact based on ‘vividness’ would present challenges: arguably, future times are neither particularly vivid nor impact on the attitude holder in the actual world. Building on Kaplan’s work, Lewis introduces the notion of ‘acquaintance relation’, mediating between α and x (Lewis, 1979, p. 542). This acquaintance is framed in terms of a causal-informational relationship, wherein the attitude holder maintains a causal connection to the *res*, enabling them to acquire information about it. However, Lewis’s formulation does not seem to align with our case either.

Coming to our aid are Sharvit & Moss (2022), who argue that *de re* ascriptions in temporal contexts need not adhere to the stringent constraints initially formulated for individuals. Crucially, they contend that the causal-perceptual requirements inherent in Kaplan’s and Lewis’s theories should be relaxed. According to Sharvit & Moss, the attitude holder can establish cognitive contact with times, even if they are not directly acquainted with or affected by them. More specifically, they posit that an acquaintance relation with a time t can be established as long as the attitude holder can orient themselves in relation to t . Consequently, simultaneous interpretations should theoretically remain viable even in future contexts, given that everyone is familiar with their current time, even if it lies beyond the utterance time. This, in turn, should account for (174) and the respective time-concept generated in (177). By analogy, the time-concept ‘yesterday’ generated in (179) is suitable for (175) in that the *res* refers to a time that precedes by one day a time the attitude holder is acquainted with, namely their (future) now.

If we allow *de re* LFs for future times, a lingering puzzle remains: what accounts for the difference in speakers’ preferences for *de re* interpretations between past and future contexts? I speculate that establishing cognitive contact between the attitude holder and the *res* in the actual world is more effortless in past-oriented contexts, given their reference to an actual (past) time. By contrast, future contexts typically denote hypothetical scenarios, creating some distance from the actual world.⁷¹ On this basis, *de re* readings for embedded *ná* may be marginal or subject to speaker’s variation in future compared to past contexts. This difference arises because cognitive contact is already established in the past, whereas it remains anticipated, though plausible, in the future. With reference to my elicitation, both future scenarios I have constructed involve times that are routinely accessed and thus expected to be ‘present in the attitude holder’s mind’ (to borrow Kaplan’s terminology): specifically, ‘bedtime’ for the SIM-biasing scenario in (174) and ‘schooltime’ for the BACK-biasing scenario in (175).⁷²

Let me conclude this section elaborating some more on the semantics of *ná* and its implications for attitude embeddings. Given its deictic nature, one intriguing aspect to consider is that a *de re* ascription of *ná*-marked attitudes may be built into the semantics of the particle. Recall that, whenever *ná* surfaces at LF, the evaluation time t_c is dispensed with. What if, however, we assumed that structures containing *ná* did contain t_c ? On

⁷¹In fact, as we have seen, future meaning is often expressed in natural language with modals.

⁷²The observed variation among speakers may also reflect factors external to *de re* ascription. For example, while the same speakers accepted *ná* in main clauses within future contexts, they indicated a preference for the prospective marker ‘be’ in some scenarios. Another aspect worth considering is the potential for future *de re* ascriptions to arise from an accommodation mechanism, a possibility previously explored for other types of *de re* ascriptions by Aloni (2005). A comprehensive examination of the limits of the observed variability is deferred to future research.

this analysis, the particle *ná* would denote a function of type $\langle i, i \rangle$, taking an EvalT t and outputting a contextually salient reference time other than t . This is illustrated in (180).

- (180) a. $\llbracket ná_7 \rrbracket(t)$ defined iff there is a contextually salient time $g(7)$ $[\neg(g(7) \circ t)]$
 b. When defined, $\llbracket ná_7 \rrbracket(t) = g(7)$

For matrix clauses, we still derive the anti-present meaning that *ná* exhibits (see

- (181) a. LF: $[_{CP} \dots t_c [_{TP} ná_7 [_{AspP} \dots P \dots]]]$
 b. $\llbracket (181-a) \rrbracket$ defined iff there is a contextually salient time $g(7)$ $[\neg(g(7) \circ t_c)]$
 When defined, $\llbracket (181-a) \rrbracket = 1$ iff $p(w_c)(g(9))$.

In complement clauses, *ná*'s EvalT-argument is quantificationally bound by the attitude verb. The resulting meaning is compatible with a backward-shifted interpretation but not with a simultaneous one, as shown below:

- (182) a. $[_{CP} \dots [_{VP} believe \forall \langle w', t' \rangle [_{CP} \lambda t [_{TP} ná_{7,t} [_{AspP} \dots P \dots]]]]]$
 b. $\llbracket (182-a) \rrbracket$ defined iff there is a contextually salient time $g(7)$ $[\neg(g(7) \circ t']$
 When defined, $\llbracket (182-a) \rrbracket = 1$ iff
 $\forall \langle w', t' \rangle \in Dox(\text{Att-holder}, w_c, \text{Matrix-time}) \rightarrow p(w')(g(9))$

Irrespective of whether t' precedes or follows UT, the simplified toy-meaning computed in (182-b) delivers the backward-shifted interpretation if $g(7)$ precedes t' . As evident, this is the only conceivable outcome: $g(7)$ cannot be equal to t' (owing to ' $ná_{7,t}$ ''s presupposition) or follow it (due to the ULC). As a result, despite its isomorphic appeal, this formal set-up fails to generate the available simultaneous interpretation.⁷³

3.5.4 More on temporal *de re* and limits of variability

So far, we have operated under the assumption that referential tenses like *ná* may be interpreted *de re*, much in the same manner as their counterpart in the nominal domain.⁷⁴ Our system comprises two more pronominal tenses: ' t_c ' and 'LEN' 's tense component 'past'. Let's entertain the possibility that a *de re* construal is optionally available for both.

First, let's consider bare embeddings. These have been shown to exhibit a simultaneous interpretation, which results from a *de se* LF. Clearly, for a semantically tenseless clause, this is the only possible outcome. However, if embedded clauses were to project t_c as the local evaluation time, then a *de re* construal would be possible.⁷⁵ This is illustrated for a bare-under-LEN toy example in (183).

⁷³A third option goes as follows: *ná* carries the additional presupposition that its temporal anchor is t_c .

In this manner, *ná*-embeddings can still yield simultaneous interpretations through a *de re* analysis. However, I believe this adds an unnecessary level of complexity to the analysis presented here.

⁷⁴This view is faithful to the original formulation by Abusch (1997), where acquaintance-based analyses were extended to pronominal tenses by analogy with pronouns or referential NPs. This says nothing about the potential for quantificational/indefinite tenses to receive a *de re* analysis. We return to this point later.

⁷⁵Recall that the free variable t_c always denotes a time surrounding UT, irrespective of the syntactic environment where it occurs.

- (183) a. $[_{CP} \dots [_{TP} \text{past}_{3,4} \dots [_{VP} \text{believe } \exists G[\forall \langle w', t' \rangle [_{CP} \lambda G_7 [\lambda w_5 [\lambda t_2 [_{TP} [T [[G_7 t_c] t_2] w_5][_{AspP} \dots P \dots]]]]]]]]]]$
 b. $[[(183\text{-a})] \text{ defined iff } g(3) < t_c \ \& \ \neg((G(t_c)(t')(w')) > t')$
 When defined, $[[(183\text{-a})] = 1 \text{ iff}$
 $\exists G \text{ suitable for Att-holder in } w_c \text{ at } g(7) \ \& \ [\forall \langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Dox}(\text{Att-holder}, w_c,$
 $g(7)) \rightarrow p(w')(G(t_c)(t')(w'))]$

Following (183), a double access interpretation arises: the temporal interval generated by a suitable time-concept must include UT (in compliance with t_c 's indexicality) and the attitude time t' (to prevent a ULC violation). This prediction is borne out in the light of the data discussed in this section on DAR (see (153), repeated below).

- (184) Context: On Saturday you asked Kofi why Ama was not around. Kofi told you: "I think Ama is working this whole weekend." It's Sunday morning now and Ama is working her last shift. A friend asks you why Ama is not at home, you reply:

- a. $\text{ennora} \quad \text{ná} \quad \text{Kofi gye di} \quad \text{sé} \quad \text{Ama re-ye} \quad \text{adwuma dapɛn awiei}$
 yesterday NA Kofi believe COMP Ama PROG-COP work week end
 yi.
 this
 'Yesterday Kofi believed that Ama is working this weekend.'

- (185) Simplified LF for (184-a):

$[_{CP} \dots [_{TP} \text{past}_{3,4} \dots [_{VP} \text{gye-di} [_{CP} \lambda G_7 [\lambda w_5 [\lambda t_2 [_{TP} [T [[G_7 t_c] t_2] w_5][_{AspP} \dots \text{ye-adwuma}]]]]]]]]]]$

In (185), a time-concept $G(t_c) =$ 'this weekend' generates the intended double access reading.

The case of LEN-embeddings is of special concern. A shrewd reader will have noticed that the exceptional simultaneous readings exhibited by LEN-under-LEN attitude reports have yet to be addressed. We have seen in section 3.4.1 that, though marginally, LEN-embeddings might correlate with a simultaneous reading when the embedded clause is modified by an adverbial restricting its evaluation to the attitude time. The relevant data point is repeated below.

- (186) Context: You and Aba were supposed to watch a movie last Friday night. Unfortunately, Aba called you to cancel one hour before the movie. She told you: 'I am sick'. The week after you explain to your friend why Aba could not make it on Friday night:

- a. $\text{Aba ka-à} \quad \text{sé} \quad \text{ɔ-yare-è} \quad \text{saa} \quad \text{nandwo nó.}$
 Aba say-LEN COMP 3SG-sick-LEN DEM night DEF
 'Aba said that she was sick that night.'

An acquaintance-based analysis should be able to handle these cases: if LEN's pronominal tense were evaluated with respect to UT instead of AT in attitude contexts, then a simultaneous interpretation should arise.⁷⁶ The simplified *de re* LF and the resulting

⁷⁶I exclude the possibility that exceptional SIM-readings for LEN-under-LEN might be the result of a

meaning for (186) are given in (187) and (188)

(187) $[_{CP} t_c [\lambda t_4 [_{TP} \text{past}_{3,4} [_{AspP} \text{PFV} [_{VP} \text{Aba-ka} [_{CP} \lambda G_7 [\lambda w_5 [\lambda t_2 [_{TP} [T [[G_7 \text{past}_{6,4}$

(188) $[[(187)]]$ defined iff $g(3) < t_c \ \& \ g(6) < t_c \ \& \ \neg(G(g(6))(t')(w') > t')$
 When defined, $[[(187)]]$ = 1 iff
 $\exists e[g(3) \subseteq \tau(e) \ \& \ \exists G$ suitable for Aba in w_c at $\tau(e) \ \& \ \forall \langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Dox}(\text{Aba}, w_c,$
 $\tau(e)) \rightarrow \exists e'[\tau(e') \subseteq G(g(6))(t')(w') \ \& \ G(g(6))(t')(w') \subseteq \{t: t \text{ surrounds } g(3)\}$
 $\ \& \ \text{sick}(w')(e')(\text{Aba})]]$

From the restriction imposed by the temporal adverbial in (188) on $G(g(6))(t')(w')$, it follows that $G(g(6))(t')(w') = g(6) = g(3)$. In other words, $G(g(6))$ picks out the time-concept ‘now’, thus yielding a simultaneous interpretation.⁷⁷

Having motivated a *de re*-based analysis for LEN-embeddings, two questions need to be addressed:

- (i) Why are simultaneous interpretations much more salient for bare embeddings compared to both *ná* and LEN-embeddings?
- (ii) Why are simultaneous readings for LEN-embeddings so marginal compared to *ná*-embeddings, if they are generated by the same semantic mechanism?

With respect to (i), work in the nominal domain has shown a general preference for semantic binding over co-reference (Reinhart, 1983). Similarly, Schlenker has argued that in several semantic domains *de se* LFs are preferred over *de re* ones, if a situation allows for either.⁷⁸ This is illustrated by the pragmatic principle *Prefer De Se!* given below.

(189) *Prefer de se!* (Schlenker, 2005, p. 17):
 Whenever this is compatible with the situation which is reported, prefer a *de se* over a *de re* Logical Form.

Building on Reinhart and Schlenker’s insights, Ogihara & Sharvit (2012) and Tsilia (2021a)⁷⁹ contend that the same principle is at play for tense in attitude reports and, thus, is responsible for the marginal availability of SIM for *de re* LFs in non-SoT languages. Extending this line of reasoning to Asante, I suggest that the LFs involving a bound tense variable are favoured over those involving a free variable. Although *Prefer de se!* has been originally motivated on a pragmatic basis — since *de se* LFs are prag-

deletion mechanism. As observed earlier, SIM is consistently rejected for LEN-embeddings, unless an appropriate adverbial is inserted. This empirical finding strongly indicates an underlying *de re* representation for SIM-readings of LEN-under-LEN. Moreover, the diagnostics testing *ná*’s vacuity in SoT environments and involving permanent states of affairs was further applied to LEN. However, sentences containing LEN were equally dismissed as nonsensical by the speakers.

⁷⁷Clearly, for any suitable time-concept other than ‘now’, this analysis can also derive the backward-shifted interpretation of LEN-under-LEN attitude reports.

⁷⁸See Schlenker (1999) for logophoric pronouns and Schlenker (2005) for mood.

⁷⁹Tsilia revises *Prefer de se!* advocating for a principle that applies between competing readings rather than logical forms. On this view, the system favours *de se* readings over *de re* ones. I believe this step adds unnecessary parameters of crosslinguistic variation.

matically stronger ⁻⁸⁰ the observed preference can also be tied to well known phenomena in anaphora resolution and semantic processing.

Regarding point (ii), I suggest that a second mechanism comes into play — one that favours imperfective/unbounded event structures over perfective/bounded ones.

This preference can be traced back to general constraints on the way attitudes are conceptualized. Attitudes denote homogeneous mental states that hold toward a proposition in a continuous fashion. Put differently, if we were to break it down into individual infinitesimal moments, an attitude would hold true ‘momentarily’ — that is, for each of these moments. This concept is often referred to in literature as the ‘subinterval property’, as highlighted by Bennett & Partee, 1972.⁸¹ This property is typically associated with unbounded predicates like states and activities. Based on this perspective, state- and activity-denoting attitude predicates might adhere to the following condition:⁸²

- (190) Attitude’s Temporal Homogeneity (ATH)
 Given an attitude P, held by $x_{(e)}$ toward the proposition $q_{\langle s, \langle i, t \rangle \rangle}$,
 $\forall \langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Dom}(P) \rightarrow [q(w')(t') \rightarrow \forall t [t \subseteq t' \rightarrow q(w')(t)]]$

If attitude predicates exhibit temporal homogeneity, it’s logical to expect that the temporal constraints they introduce would also be applied according to this condition. Thus, it’s plausible to suggest that Abusch’s upper limit constraint equally operates at a granular level, targeting each individual subinterval within the attitude’s superinterval. As a result, the reference of the embedded tense is constrained to times that neither follow the attitude’s overarching superinterval nor any of its individual subintervals. While this revision to the ULC doesn’t notably impact shifted interpretations, it significantly affects simultaneous interpretations, contingent on the aspectual value of the embedded clause. To illustrate, let’s examine the timelines below,⁸³ showcasing both backward-shifted and forward-shifted interpretations.

Figure 3.1: Backward-shifted interpretation

⁸⁰Recall that *de se* ascriptions are a special instance of *de re* ascriptions and, as such, are to be prioritized if the speaker is in a position to do so. I am remaining agnostic as to what kind of pragmatic mechanism regulates the competition, but see Schlenker (2005) and Tsilia (2021a) for a more in-depth discussion.

⁸¹Bennett and Partee identify a special class of verb phrases termed ‘subinterval verb phrases’. For these VPs, when they serve as the main verb phrase of a sentence evaluated at some time I, the sentence is true for every subinterval of I, including every temporal moment in I (cf. Bennett & Partee, 1972, p. 72)

⁸²see Arosio, 2019, for homogeneity of temporal predicates.

⁸³ XT_i and XT_f express the initial and the final subinterval of the X-time, respectively (with XT, the embedding Attitude Time or the embedded Eventuality Time)

Figure 3.2: Unattasted forward-shifted interpretation

In the above timelines,⁸⁴ the red-colored area represents the portion of the timeline that is ruled out by the ULC. In attitude reports, the embedded eventuality cannot be temporally located entirely within this portion, else a violation obtains. For the backward-shifted interpretation in 3.1, the eventuality time strictly precedes the ULC's interval⁸⁵ and, therefore, produces an available interpretation. By contrast, in 3.2 the embedded eventuality falls entirely within the ULC's interval, thus excluding the resulting interpretation.⁸⁶

Turning to simultaneous interpretations, the revised ULC highlights an interesting contrast between imperfective and perfective embeddings, as is illustrated in 3.3 and 3.4.

Figure 3.3: Simultaneous interpretation for imperfective embeddings

Figure 3.4: Simultaneous interpretation for perfective embeddings

⁸⁴I am somewhat simplifying here, ignoring the contribution of the embedded reference time and, thus, relating the eventuality time of the embedded predicate directly to the attitude time, that serves as its local evaluation time. For the purpose of shifted interpretations, there is no particular insight to be gained from further illustrating the entailment relation between event time and reference time in the embedded clause. For the same reason, timelines compatible with a simultaneous interpretation are split into one where the embedded predicate is imperfective and another where it's perfective.

⁸⁵In my notation, the ULC's temporal interval in 3.1 can be represented as $(AT_{i+1}, +\infty)$. That is, a temporal interval extending from the first moment following the initial AT's subinterval to positive infinity.

⁸⁶The ULC's interval here starts from the final subinterval of the attitude time for illustrative purposes only: even taking into account the latest possible attitude moment, a forward-shifted interpretation still places the embedded eventuality beyond this time.

In 3.3, the imperfective embedded eventuality temporally includes the attitude time. For this reason, a portion of the eventuality time — specifically, the interval (ET_i, AT_i) — lies outside of the ‘prohibited area’. Stated differently, from ET_i ’s vantage point, AT remains an inviolable upper limit. Conversely, in 3.4, the perfective eventuality is entirely included in the attitude time and, therefore, in the ULC’s interval, leading to a ULC violation. Importantly, a segment of the attitude time — specifically, the interval (ET_f, AT_f) — continues to serve as an unviolated upper limit from any ET ’s viewpoint. Nonetheless, since the ULC must be applied to each of AT ’s subintervals, this distinction becomes irrelevant. To articulate further, while in 3.3 the attitude holder may perceive the embedded eventuality time throughout the entire AT ’s duration as ‘now’, this is not possible for 3.4. In this instance, for any moment within the subinterval (AT_i, ET_{i-1}) , the attitude holder conceptualizes the eventuality time as ‘ n moments after now’. Crucially, this forward-looking description is unsuitable.

These considerations lead us to formulate the following key generalization:

(191) *Prefer unbounded structures!*

In the derivation of simultaneous readings for complement clauses of homogeneous attitude predicates, unbounded attitude reports are preferred over bounded ones.

Recall that *ná* can only combine with an imperfective aspect operator, whereas *LEN* yields a strictly perfective interpretation. Due to the generalization in (191), when conveying overlapping readings, *ná*-embeddings are expected to be systematically preferred over *LEN*-embeddings. Clearly, since both of these interpretations are *de re*-based, the preferred method to express simultaneity in Asante is through bare-embeddings.⁸⁷ All else being equal, this is expected under the *Prefer de se!* principle.⁸⁸

As a final note, let me elaborate more on the exceptional simultaneous readings for *LEN*-embeddings in (186-a). According to the timeline in 3.4, a simultaneous interpretation should be always ruled out. However, there is one instance where a simultaneous interpretation can arise even under perfective embeddings. This can be illustrated as follows:

Figure 3.5: Co-referential interpretations for perfective embeddings

⁸⁷Nonetheless, simultaneous readings for *de re ná*-embeddings are strikingly salient compared to other non-SoT languages. One additional reason for using *ná* instead of *LEN*- or bare embeddings may be attributed to the fact that *ná* can be focused, thereby highlighting the relevant time under discussion.

⁸⁸Conceivably, *Prefer de se!* can only determine a preference between different LFs when their embedded predicates share the same aspectual profile. Saving a detailed discussion for chapter 5, I posit that *Prefer unbounded structures!* takes precedence. More specifically, *de re* unbounded attitude reports can more readily yield simultaneous readings than *de se* bounded attitude reports.

In Figure 3.5, the temporal intervals denoted by the embedding attitude predicate and the embedded eventuality coincide.⁸⁹ Since no single subinterval or moment within AT exists, such that ET is located after it, no ULC violation emerges.⁹⁰ As evident, a sub-scenario of this sort is rather hard to obtain, without any additional (con)textual information. I speculate this is the reason why such interpretations are only (marginally) available: they only arise when adverbials or contextual cues force a co-referential interpretation or, alternatively, in the presence of special temporal constraints imposed by the embedding predicate.⁹¹

3.5.5 *a*-embeddings and the *de re/de se* ambiguity

The last type of embeddings to examine are *a*-embeddings. Our empirical findings in section 3.4.1 painted a rather intricate picture, with speakers suggesting diverse nuanced interpretations available. More specifically, simultaneous interpretations appear to be dependent on the predicate type, with a simultaneous interpretation only natural for *nyem* ('to be/get pregnant') and *da* ('to sleep/to fall asleep'). In both cases, the overlapping interpretation was result-oriented rather than process-oriented, indicating that the attitude time only overlapped with the result state's interval rather than the timespan of the event causing it. For other predicates, simultaneous interpretations were either unavailable or subject to speaker variation.⁹² By contrast, backward-shifted interpretations were generally available irrespective of the type of predicate. However, more inter-speaker variation was found based on the resultative/experiential flavour of the BACK-interpretation or its temporal (in)dependence.⁹³ It is important to stress that *a*-marked attitude reports were regarded as the most natural way to convey simultaneity only in the case of *da*. A closer inspection will reveal that *da* belongs to a class of change-of-state predicates, which preferably bear *a*-morphology to convey that the post-change state obtains at the time of evaluation.

From a formal standpoint, clauses modified by *a*, much like bare ones, are T-deficient and thus evaluated with respect to the local evaluation time (usually, t_c in matrix contexts). Nonetheless, quantification over times is supplied by the extended now perfect 'PERF'. We observed that PERF can further combine with a resultative aspect 'RES', producing resultative or experiential interpretations, or with a stative aspect 'STAT', resulting in universal interpretations. I'll set aside LFs involving the 'PERF+STAT' complex, as universal readings present a distinct case that I haven't explored in attitude contexts and don't significantly contribute to the broader discussion. Instead, my focus will be on the interpretations stemming from the 'PERF'+ 'RES' complex. Let's begin by examining the predictions for *de Dicto* LFs of *a*-embeddings.

⁸⁹Based on the semantics of 'PFV', ET is a subset, but *not* a proper subset, of RT.

⁹⁰Sufficient condition for ULC-compliance is that AT_i be equal to ET_i . ET_f may precede AT_f .

⁹¹One such case can be represented by perception verbs, which notably impose simultaneous interpretations.

⁹²This was the case of *yare* ('to be sick'). However, the speakers who accepted SIM, did so only under a resultative interpretation.

⁹³As a reminder, an embedded predicate is temporally (in)dependent if it's evaluated with respect to AT (UT).

(192) *Toy de Dicto Logical Form for a-marked complement clauses*

[... [CP λw [AspP PERF [ViewP RES_{e4} [VP ... p_{w,e,x} ...]]]]]

(193) $\llbracket \text{CP} \rrbracket$ defined iff $Rel_x(g(4))$ When defined,
 $\llbracket \text{CP} \rrbracket = [\lambda w. [\lambda t. \exists t' [XN(t', t) \ \& \ \exists e [Result(g(4), e) \ \& \ t \subseteq \tau(g(4)) \ \& \ \tau(e) \subseteq t' \ \& \ p(w)(e)(x)]]]]]$

(194) $\llbracket \text{Attitude} \rrbracket (w'')(e'')((193))(y) = \forall \langle w', t'' \rangle \in Att(y, w'', \tau(e'')) \rightarrow [\lambda w. [\lambda t. \exists t' [XN(t', t) \ \& \ \exists e [Result(g(4), e) \ \& \ t \subseteq \tau(g(4)) \ \& \ \tau(e) \subseteq t' \ \& \ p(w)(e)(x)]]](w')(t'')$

From the toy LF in (192), we derive the meaning of the embedded clause in (193). Once this denotation combines with the attitude verb as in (194), the perfect time span ends up being evaluated with respect to the attitude time t'' , since the PTS' final subinterval 't' is quantificationally bound by the embedding attitude verb. Since 't' is temporally included in the result state $g(4)$, it follows that the causing event 'e' must be temporally located before the attitude time. This results in a backward-shifted interpretation, illustrated in the timeline below.

Figure 3.6: *de Dicto* Backward-shifted interpretation of *a*-embeddings

In Figure 3.6, the attitude time t'' is temporally included in the result state $g(4)$. Moreover, t'' serves as the endpoint of the perfect time span t' , which includes the running time of the event e . By definition, the event e left-abuts its result state $g(4)$, thus entailing that the running time of the event e has to precede the attitude time. As a result, a backward-shifted interpretation obtains.

Clearly, the timeline in Figure 3.6 only locates the embedded eventuality with respect to the attitude time. It says nothing about its temporal location relative to the utterance time. This is a desirable outcome in view of data such as (132-c), repeated in (195).

(195) Context: Kwame wants to skip school tomorrow and go to the mall instead. Once he's back the day after, he'll bring a fake note from the doctor to the teacher. This is what he expects: 'she will think I was sick the day before'.

(195) $\text{\textcircled{a}kyer\textcircled{e}kyer\textcircled{e}ni \ n\textcircled{o} \ b\textcircled{e}\textcircled{-}gye \ a\textcircled{-}di \ s\textcircled{e} \ m'\textcircled{a}\textcircled{-}yare.$
 teacher DEF PROSP-believe CONS-PTCL COMP 1SG=A-sick
 'The teacher will believe that I've been sick.'

As discussed earlier, the sentence in (195), in the given context, receives a relative BACK-reading, according to which the speaker's sickness is located before the teacher's thinking time, but after the utterance time. This interpretation can be captured by the LF in (196),⁹⁴ whose meaning is computed in (197)-(200).

(197) $\llbracket (196) \rrbracket$ defined iff $Rel_{tz[teacher(z)]}(g(4))$ When defined,

(198) $\llbracket CP_2 \rrbracket = [\lambda w. [\lambda t. \exists t' [XN(t', t) \ \& \ \exists e [Result(g(4), e) \ \& \ t \subseteq \tau(g(4)) \ \& \ \tau(e) \subseteq t' \ \& \ sick(w)(e)(speaker)]]]]]$

(199) $\llbracket VP_{matrix} \rrbracket = \llbracket gye-di \rrbracket (w'')(e'')((198))(tz[teacher(z)]) = \forall \langle w', t'' \rangle \in Dox(z, w'', \tau(e'')) \rightarrow [\lambda w. [\lambda t. \exists t' [XN(t', t) \ \& \ \exists e [Result(g(4), e) \ \& \ t \subseteq \tau(g(4)) \ \& \ \tau(e) \subseteq t' \ \& \ sick(w)(e)(speaker)]]]]](w')(t'') = \forall \langle w', t'' \rangle \in Dox(z, w'', \tau(e'')) \rightarrow \exists t' [XN(t', t'') \ \& \ \exists e [Result(g(4), e) \ \& \ t'' \subseteq \tau(g(4)) \ \& \ \tau(e) \subseteq t' \ \& \ sick(w')(e)(speaker)]]]$

(200) $\llbracket (196) \rrbracket = 1$ iff $[\lambda w''. \llbracket PROSP \rrbracket (\lambda e''. \llbracket VP_{matrix} \rrbracket)(t_c)](w_c) = 1$ iff $[\lambda w''. [\lambda p_{\langle v, t \rangle}. [\lambda t_i. \exists e''' [\tau(e''') > t \ \& \ p(e''')]]](\lambda e''. \forall \langle w', t'' \rangle \in Dox(z, w'', \tau(e'')) \rightarrow \exists t' [XN(t', t'') \ \& \ \exists e [Result(g(4), e) \ \& \ t'' \subseteq \tau(g(4)) \ \& \ \tau(e) \subseteq t' \ \& \ sick(w')(e)(speaker)]]](t_c)]](w_c)$

⁹⁴Empty nodes are skipped due to space constraints.

$$= 1 \text{ iff} \\ \exists e'''[\tau(e''') > t_e \ \& \ \forall \langle w', t'' \rangle \in \text{Dox}(z, w_e, \tau(e''')) \rightarrow \exists t'[\text{XN}(t', t'') \ \& \ \exists e[\text{Result}(g(4), e) \\ \& \ t'' \subseteq \tau(g(4)) \ \& \ \tau(e) \subseteq t' \ \& \ \text{sick}(w')(e)(\text{speaker})]]]]$$

Having ruled out a deletion analysis for both *ná-* and LEN-embeddings, it remains to be seen whether *a*-embeddings are compatible with a deletion analysis, when embedded under a past-oriented attitude verb. From the *de Dicto* LF in (192), deletion of the embedded quantificational tense PERF may generate the *de se* LF in (201)

(201) *Toy de se Logical Form for a-marked complement clauses*
Deletion: [... [CP λ_w [AspP PERF [ViewP RES_{e4} [VP ... p_{w,e,x} ...]]]]]
 [... [CP λ_w [λ_{t_9} [AspP t₈ [t₉ [ViewP RES_{e4} [VP ... p_{w,e,x} ...]]]]]]]]

The LF in (201) is far from ideal: in order to preserve compositionality, ViewP needs to combine with a silent EvalT pronoun t₈, which was not syntactically present prior to deletion. If we were to accept this tweak, the resulting interpretation would be compatible with a simultaneous interpretation, as is illustrated below:

(202) $\llbracket \text{CP} \rrbracket$ defined iff $Rel_x(g(4))$ When defined,
 $\llbracket \text{CP} \rrbracket = [\lambda w. [\lambda t. \exists e[\text{Result}(g(4), e) \ \& \ g(8) \subseteq \tau(g(4)) \ \& \ \tau(e) \subseteq t \ \& \ p(w)(e)(x)]]]]$

(203) $\llbracket \text{Attitude} \rrbracket(w'')(e'')((202))(y) = \forall \langle w', t'' \rangle \in \text{Att}(y, w'', \tau(e'')) \rightarrow [\lambda w. [\lambda t. \exists e[\text{Result}(g(4), e) \ \& \ g(8) \subseteq \tau(g(4)) \ \& \ \tau(e) \subseteq t \ \& \ p(w)(e)(x)]](w')(t'')]$

Following (203), the eventuality time of the causing event *e* is included within the attitude time *t''*. This should generate a *process-oriented* simultaneous interpretation, for which the attitude time overlaps with the causing event rather than with its result state. For a graphic depiction, consider the timeline in Figure 3.7.

Figure 3.7: *de se* Simultaneous interpretation of *a*-embeddings

The timeline in Figure 3.7 depicts the embedded eventuality as entirely included within the attitude time. Drawing from our previous observations on SIM-generating LFs of LEN-embeddings, such instances violate the ULC. This aligns with the findings in section 3.4.1,

as no process-oriented simultaneous interpretation was evident empirically: all embedded eventive verbs, barring those indicating a change of state, were unanimously rejected by speakers in simultaneous contexts. For these reasons, I conclude that deletion is not attested compositional path for *a*-embeddings either.

Finally, we turn our attention to the *de re* LFs associated with *a*-embeddings. Thus far, our observations indicate that all pronominal tenses in Asante can be interpreted *de re*. However, the extent to which a *de re* LF is available varies across constructions, subject to specific constraints. For *a*-embeddings, two tense forms are potential candidates for serving as the temporal *res*: the pronominal tense t_c and the quantificational tense PERF. Regarding t_c , we've observed that *de re* LFs are feasible, at least for bare embeddings, leading to double access readings. Consequently, such readings are predicted to be possible for *a*-embeddings as well whenever t_c is projected in the embedded clause. To illustrate, consider the following toy LF generated by a *de re* analysis of *a*-embeddings and its corresponding meaning.

- (204) *Toy de re Logical Form for a-marked complement clauses*
 $[... [_{CP} \lambda G_7 [\lambda w_5 [\lambda t_2 [[[G t_c] t_2] w_5] [_{AspP} PERF [_{ViewP} RES_{e_4} [VP \dots P_{w_5, e, x} \dots]]]]]]]]$
- (205) $\llbracket CP \rrbracket$ defined iff $Rel_x(g(4)) \ \& \ \neg(G(t_c)(w')(t'') > t'')$ When defined,
 $\llbracket CP \rrbracket = [\lambda G. [\lambda w^5. [\lambda t^2. \exists t' [XN(t', G(t_c)(w^5)(t^2)) \ \& \ \exists e [Result(g(4), e) \ \& \ G(t_c)(w^5)(t^2) \subseteq \tau(g(4)) \ \& \ \tau(e) \subseteq t' \ \& \ p(w^5)(e)(x)]]]]]]]$
- (206) $\llbracket Attitude \rrbracket (w'')(e'')((205))(y) = \exists G' [G' \text{ suitable for } y \text{ in } \tau(e'') \text{ in } w'' \ \& \ \forall \langle w', t'' \rangle \in Att(y, w'', \tau(e'')) \rightarrow [\lambda G. [\lambda w^5. [\lambda t^2. \exists t' [XN(t', G(t_c)(w^5)(t^2)) \ \& \ \exists e [Result(g(4), e) \ \& \ G(t_c)(w^5)(t^2) \subseteq \tau(g(4)) \ \& \ \tau(e) \subseteq t' \ \& \ p(w^5)(e)(x)]]]]]] (G')(w')(t'')$

In (204), t_c escapes local binding by the attitude predicate and feeds into the concept generator G_7 . The temporal interval denoted by the resulting $G'(t_c)(w')(t'')$ must overlap with t_c (as constructed) and the attitude time t'' (as per the ULC). This double access interval serves as the final subinterval of the perfect time span. The resulting interpretation is illustrated by the timeline in Figure 3.8.

As shown by the timeline in Figure 3.8, the embedded eventuality is located strictly prior to the attitude time, thus resulting in a backward-shifted interpretation. Yet, when comparing this BACK-reading with the one exhibited by the *de Dicto* LF from 3.6, there's a notable difference: for *de re* LFs, the result state must encompass t_c . This key difference sets this interpretation apart from the temporally dependent one derived in (200). This point can be further illustrated with reference to sentence (127-c) repeated below.

- (207) Context: Aba is a great cook. Since she has little time during the week, she tries to do most of her cooking on Sundays, so that she has meals ready for the whole week. Today is Monday and you ask Aba how she spent her Sunday. Unsurprisingly she made food the whole day! You report this later to a friend.
- a. ? Aba ka-à sɛ w-a-noa aduane.
 Aba say-LEN COMP 3SG-a-cook food
 'Aba said that she has cooked some food (at some point).'

Some speakers that accepted (207-a) in the given BACK-biasing context reported an

Figure 3.8: *de re* Backward-shifted interpretation of *a*-embeddings

interpretation whereby the eventuality occurred at some point before, with its effects being felt at UT. Let me show how a *de re* analysis constitutes a good proxy for such a reading.

The meaning computed from the LF in (208) is given below.

(209) $\llbracket (208) \rrbracket$ defined iff $g(6) < g(8) \ \& \ Rel_x(g(4)) \ \& \ \neg(G(t_c)(w')(t'') > t'')$ When defined,

(210) $\llbracket CP_{emb} \rrbracket = [\lambda G. [\lambda w^5. [\lambda t^2. \exists t' [XN(t', G(t_c)(w^5)(t^2)) \ \& \ \exists e [Result(g(4), e) \ \& \ G(t_c)(w^5)(t^2) \subseteq \tau(g(4)) \ \& \ \tau(e) \subseteq t' \ \& \ cook(w^5)(e)(\iota z[food(z))](A)]]]]]]]$

(211) $\llbracket VP_{matrix} \rrbracket \llbracket ka_{deRe} \rrbracket (w'')(e'')((210))(Aba) = 1$ iff $\exists G' [G' \text{ suitable for } Aba \text{ in } \tau(e'') \text{ in } w'' \ \& \ \forall \langle w', t'' \rangle \in Say(Aba, w'', \tau(e'')) \rightarrow [\lambda G. [\lambda w^5. [\lambda t^2. \exists t' [XN(t', G(t_c)(w^5)(t^2)) \ \& \ \exists e [Result(g(4), e) \ \& \ G(t_c)(w^5)(t^2) \subseteq \tau(g(4)) \ \& \ \tau(e) \subseteq t' \ \& \ cook(w^5)(e)(\iota z[food(z))]]]]]]](G')(w')(t'')$

(212) $\llbracket (208) \rrbracket = 1$ iff

$$\begin{aligned} & \exists e'[g(6) \subseteq \tau(e') \ \& \ \exists G'[G' \text{ suitable for Aba in } \tau(e') \text{ in } w_c \ \& \ \forall \langle w', t'' \rangle \in \text{Say}(\text{Aba}, w_c, \tau(e')) \\ & \rightarrow \exists t'[\text{XN}(t', G'(t_c)(w')(t'')) \ \& \ \exists e[\text{Result}(g(4), e) \ \& \ G'(t_c)(w')(t'') \subseteq \tau(g(4)) \ \& \\ & \tau(e) \subseteq t' \ \& \ \text{cook}(w')(e)(\iota z[\text{food}(z)])(\text{Aba})]]] \end{aligned}$$

According to the truth-conditions in (212), the event of cooking is temporally situated within the Perfect time span t' , whose endpoint is determined by $G'(t_c)(w')(t'')$. Considering the context provided in (207), one suitable time-concept for Aba to self-describe t_c is ‘this week’, as this aligns with the timespan during which the result of her cooking becomes relevant. The time-concept satisfies both the ULC, given that the attitude time t'' falls within ‘this week’, and the condition set by the *res* t_c , since UT also lies within ‘this week’. Since the result state of the cooking event e — specifically, the state $g(4)$ of the food being cooked and ready for consumption — surrounds the temporal interval denoted by $G'(t_c)(w')(t'')$, it follows that the event of cooking must precede the attitude time. In essence, the result of having cooked at some earlier time is relevant and holds true for some temporal interval extending from AT to UT. While compatible with a backward-shifted interpretation, I believe the resulting interpretation is primarily a (temporally independent) resultative one. This, in my view, explains why such non-process oriented backward-shifted interpretations are available to some speakers in BACK-biasing contexts, even though they may not be a perfect fit.⁹⁵

If a *de re* analysis of t_c in *a*-marked attitude reports leads to a temporally independent resultative interpretation, it remains to be seen whether a *de re* analysis of PERF leads to the same interpretation. Up to this point, we have remained agnostic as to whether quantificational tenses can be interpreted *de re*. As discussed in this section and in chapter 2, the rationale behind adopting an acquaintance-based approach in the temporal domain stemmed from drawing parallels between tenses and pronouns or nominal referring expressions. Obviously, quantificational forms are not referring expressions. Yet, quantificational DPs exhibit well known *de Dicto/de re* ambiguities.

While quantificational tenses might be suited for *de re* interpretations *conceptually*, a compositional challenge arises. Given the semantics of time-concept generators, the temporal *res* needs to be a time-denoting argument. Excluding the option of type-shifting, in agreement with Sharvit (2018) we can posit that quantificational tenses, when interpreted *de re*, may undergo Quantifier Raising out of the complement clause, leaving behind a co-indexed trace.⁹⁶ The resulting *de re* LF can be illustrated as follows.

(213) *Toy de re Logical Form for a-embeddings (via QR)*

$$\begin{aligned} & [\text{CP}_{\text{mat}} \dots t_c [\overline{\text{PERF}}] [\lambda t_4 [\lambda t_3 [\text{TP} \dots [\text{CP}_{\text{emb}} \lambda G_7 [\lambda w_5 [\lambda t_2 [[G \ t_4]] t_2] w_5]]_{\text{AspP}} \\ & [t_3 [\text{ViewP} \text{RES}_{e_4} [\text{VP} \dots p_{w_5, e, x} \dots]]]]]]]]]]] \end{aligned}$$

In (213), PERF moves to a left-peripheral position in the matrix. As a consequence, the PTS’s final subinterval argument slot is saturated by t_c rather than the attitude time, thus creating a temporal interval extending from an earlier time up to the utterance time. This, in turn, binds the *res* t_4 . Dispensing with the individual compositional steps, from (213), the following relations hold:

⁹⁵This, in turn, aligns with the fact that speakers prefer LEN- or *ná*-embeddings in these contexts.

⁹⁶It is important to note that in Sharvit’s implementation movement is not explicitly blamed on avoiding a possible type mismatch.

- (214) a. $\exists t'[XN(t', t_c) \dots]$ (Perfect time span)
 b. $\exists G[G \text{ suitable for } x \text{ at } \tau(e) \text{ in } w_c \ \& \ \forall \langle w', t'' \rangle \in \text{Att}(x, \tau(e), w_c) \rightarrow \exists e'[\text{Res}(e'', e' \ \& \ \dots)]$ (*de re* attitude verb)
 c. $\tau(e') \subseteq G(t')(t'')(w')$ (causing event included in PTS and overlapping AT)
 d. $t_c \subseteq \tau(e'')$ (result state including UT)

The following timeline illustrates the underlying temporal interpretation.

Figure 3.9: *de re* Simultaneous interpretation of *a*-embeddings

As illustrated by the timeline in 3.9, the resulting *de re* interpretation involves a result state that holds a t_c , with the causing event situated within the PTS t' .⁹⁷ While its temporally independent resultative component aligns with the meaning computed for the *de re* LF in (208), the overlapping relation between the causing eventuality and the attitude time defines it as a novel reading. Specifically, this reading is congruent with a process-oriented simultaneous interpretation. Crucially, as previously noted, SIM-readings that are process-oriented, were absent from our data sample. In essence, SIM-interpretations was invariably dismissed by speakers for predicates that did not determine a change of state. In view of these facts, I argue that in Asante Twi only pronominal tenses may be construed *de re*. The exploration of whether this observation represents a semantic universal will be addressed in chapter 5.

To conclude this section, let me summarize the main findings concerning the range of interpretations of *a*-marked predicates and the formal semantic tools employed to capture them. We have seen that backward-shifted interpretations are generally available for both *de Dicto* and *de re* construals, with the causing event strictly located before a temporal interval containing the attitude time. A point of contrast arises between the two construals when it comes to the temporal location of the result state: while for *de Dicto* ascriptions this state simply overlaps the attitude time, for *de re* ascriptions it needs to further extend to include the utterance time. Consequently, from a result-oriented perspective, the two readings may be regarded as compatible with a simultaneous and a double access interpretation, respectively. Clearly, from a process-oriented perspective,

⁹⁷The ULC forces the temporal interval denoted by $G(t')(t'')(w')$, and extending until t_c , to include the attitude time t'' .

they denote genuine shifted interpretations. By contrast, neither LF can generate a result-oriented shifted interpretation, since the result state has to, at the very least, overlap with the attitude time.⁹⁸ For the same reason, process-oriented simultaneous interpretations are ruled out in that they involve compositional paths (specifically, deletion or a *de re* interpretation of the existential perfect operator) that are unattested in Asante Twi. These findings are summarized in Table 3.5.

	De Dicto/De Se	De Re
Process-oriented <i>SIM</i>	#	#
Result-oriented <i>SIM</i>	✓	(DAR)
Process-oriented <i>BACK</i>	✓	✓
Result-oriented <i>BACK</i>	#	#

Table 3.5: The interpretation of *a*-marked attitude reports in Asante Twi

While we have noted the absence of a process-oriented simultaneous interpretation, certain change-of-state predicates like *da* ('to sleep/to fall asleep') appeared to correlate with such an interpretation. Interestingly, for all speakers, these predicates were the preferred choice for expressing simultaneity. I will delve deeper into this aspect in the following section.

3.5.6 More on change-of-state verbs: a new compositional pathway to SIM

In the preceding section, we explored the potential for simultaneous interpretations associated with a specific category of predicates: change-of-state verbs. Specifically, as highlighted in section 3.4.1, both *da* ('to sleep/to fall asleep') and *nyem* ('to be pregnant/to get pregnant') allowed for a simultaneous relation between the predicate's result state and the attitude verb in *a*-under-LEN/PROSP embeddings. Notably, *a-da* emerged as the preferred choice for expressing simultaneity, overtaking both bare and *ná*-embeddings — commonly regarded as the most conventional means to convey such interpretations. Furthermore, the availability of backward-shifted interpretations for *da* decreased significantly for *da* compared to other predicates. What is even more striking about *da* is the fact that it retaining its status of activity verb across all other TAM or TAnt markers, as shown in our data sample. For instance, when modified by the progressive marker *re*, the resulting interpretation is of ongoingness rather than inchoative ('is sleeping' instead of 'is about to fall asleep').

These facts lead me to believe that the interpretations observed in attitude contexts aren't merely lexically driven but are rooted in the underlying grammar. Nonetheless, the fact that the result state interpretation is particularly strong in the case of *da* merits closer attention and begs the following question: is this an isolated quirk, or does it hint

⁹⁸Clearly, if *a*-marked complement clauses contain the deictic *ná*, a result-oriented BACK-reading becomes possible.

at a broader trait shared among a subset of predicates? To explore this further, I examined several change-of-state predicates within the same attitude contexts investigated in section 3.4.1. Many of these predicates were sourced from Boadi (2008, p. 35), specifically verbs that showcase morpho-phonological distinctions between their stative and habitual forms.⁹⁹

Consistent with our findings for *da*, these predicates are most naturally interpreted as simultaneous, as shown in the examples below. For clarity, I present each target sentence alongside the two temporal contexts in which it was assessed. The paraphrases provided reflect the speakers' intended meanings, thereby indicating their acceptability within the specified contexts.

(i) *Predicate fura* ('to wear'/'to have on')

- (215) a. *SIM-Context*: You gave Ama a piece of clothing for her birthday last year. You never saw her wear it though, so you've grown unsure she even likes it. However, last Friday, your friend Kwesi spotted Ama in a bar and immediately texted you: "Aba is wearing the piece of clothing you gave her!". Excited, you report Kwesi's words to a friend today...
- b. *BACK-Context*: You found a piece of clothing in your classroom this morning. You wonder who might have lost it. Having had a look at the piece of clothing, your friend Kwesi was sure he saw Ama wear it a few days before!

- (216) Kwesi ka-à sɛ Ama à-fùrá ntoma nó.
 Kwesi say-LEN COMP Ama A-wear dress DEF
SIM: 'Kwesi said that Ama had the dress on (at that moment).'
#BACK (referential): Intended: 'Kwesi said that Ama wore the dress.'

(ii) *Predicate soa* ('to carry on the head'/'to have on the head')

- (217) a. *SIM-Context*: Yesterday you were talking with Kofi on the phone. You asked to talk to his wife Aba, but he told you she couldn't reach for the phone as she was busy with something at that moment and couldn't talk to you. You asked what she was up to. He said:
 'She's holding a load on her head. She can't talk to you now.'
- b. *BACK-Context*: Aba came back home with some neck pain last night. You asked Kofi why her neck was hurting. Apparently she had been carrying some load on her head earlier that day!

- (218) Kofi ka-à sɛ Aba à-sòá adeɛ.
 Kofi ka-LEN COMP Aba A-carry.on.the.head load
SIM: 'Kofi said that Aba was carrying a load on her head (at the moment).'
BACK (*resultative*): 'Kofi said that Aba has carried a load on her head.'

(iii) *Predicate nyane* ('to wake'/'to become awake')

⁹⁹Boadi distinguishes between stative and non-stative forms. Recall that the two forms exhibit the same segmental shape but are disambiguated by tone. Interestingly, the paraphrases for several of these forms involve the auxiliary 'to be' or 'to become'.

(219) SIM-Context: It's Sunday. Early in the morning you tried to reach your friend Kofi, but he wouldn't pick up. You called his wife Ama to check whether he was still sleeping or already awake. Luckily for you he was awake.

- a. Ama ka-à sɛ Kofi a-nyane.
 Ama say-LEN COMP Kofi A-awake
 'Ama said that Kofi was awake (at the moment)'

(220) BACK-Context: Last Friday at your birthday party your friend Kofi had a few too many. Once everyone was gone, he was still lying on the floor, dizzy. You suggested he could sleep on the spare bed, but you don't know whether he actually did. But when you saw him this morning he reassured you he actually woke up in the bed!

- a. ? Kofi ka-à sɛ w=a-nyane mpa nó so.
 Ama say-LEN COMP 3SG=A-awake bed DEF on
 'Kofi said that he woke up in the bed.'

In the above attitude reports, *a*-embeddings are systematically accepted by the speakers in simultaneous contexts. According to the resulting interpretation, the result state of the change-of-state predicate obtains at the attitude time. In contrast, backward-shifted interpretations are attested as long as the context licenses a resultative/experiential interpretation, rather than a referential one. For instance, in (215-b), the contexts makes reference to a specific, previous time at which the wearing event holds true. Under these conditions, the sentence is judged false. In (217-b), however, the result state of the event obtains at the attitude time (Aba feels pain) and therefore the sentence becomes acceptable in a backward-shifted scenario. A similar line of reasoning may be extended to (220).

While resultative interpretations are generally available for most predicates modified by *a*, I believe that what makes change-of-state predicates special is their proneness to be coerced into states. On this view, *a*-marked change-of-state predicates in attitude reports produce states that are evaluated relative to the attitude time in *de Dicto* construals, much like bare embedded states. It comes as no surprise, then, that this class of predicates yields overlapping interpretations quite naturally. To illustrate, consider the LF associated with sentence (219), given in (221).

From (221), the meaning of the sentence can be derived compositionally as follows.

(222) $\llbracket (221) \rrbracket$ defined iff $Rel_{Kofi}(g(4)) \ \& \ g(6) < t_c$ When defined,

(223) $\llbracket CP_2 \rrbracket = [\lambda w. [\lambda t. \exists t' [XN(t', t) \ \& \ \exists e [Result(g(4), e) \ \& \ t \subseteq \tau(g(4)) \ \& \ \tau(e) \subseteq t' \ \& \ wake-up(w)(e)(Kofi)]]]]]$

(224) $\llbracket VP_2 \rrbracket = \llbracket ka \rrbracket(w'')(e'')((223))(Ama) = \forall \langle w', t'' \rangle \in Say(Ama, w'', \tau(e'')) \rightarrow [\lambda w. [\lambda t. \exists t' [XN(t', t) \ \& \ \exists e [Result(g(4), e) \ \& \ t \subseteq \tau(g(4)) \ \& \ \tau(e) \subseteq t' \ \& \ wake-up(w)(e)(Kofi)]]]](w')(t'') = \forall \langle w', t'' \rangle \in Say(Kofi, w'', \tau(e'')) \rightarrow \exists t' [XN(t', t'') \ \& \ \exists e [Result(g(4), e) \ \& \ t'' \subseteq \tau(g(4)) \ \& \ \tau(e) \subseteq t' \ \& \ wake-up(w')(e)(Kofi)]]]$

(225) $\llbracket (221) \rrbracket = 1$ iff $[\lambda w''. [\lambda t'''. \llbracket PFV \rrbracket(\lambda e''. \llbracket VP_{matrix} \rrbracket)(g(6): g(6) < t''')](t_c)](w_c) = 1$ iff $[\lambda w''. [\lambda t'''. [\lambda p_{\langle v, t \rangle}. [\lambda t_i. \exists e''' [\tau(e''') \subseteq t \ \& \ p(e''')]]](g(6): g(6) < t''')](\lambda e''. \forall \langle w', t'' \rangle \in$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & Say(Ama, w'', \tau(e'')) \rightarrow \exists t' [XN(t', t'') \ \& \ \exists e [Result(g(4), e) \ \& \ t'' \subseteq \tau(g(4)) \ \& \ \tau(e) \\
 & \subseteq t' \ \& \ wake-up(w')(e)(Kofi)]](t_c)(w_c) = 1 \text{ iff} \\
 & \exists e''' [\tau(e''') \subseteq g(6) \ \& \ \forall \langle w', t'' \rangle \in Say(Ama, w_c, \tau(e''')) \rightarrow \exists t' [XN(t', t'') \ \& \ \exists e [Re- \\
 & sult(g(4), e) \ \& \ t'' \subseteq \tau(g(4)) \ \& \ \tau(e) \subseteq t' \ \& \ wake-up(w')(e)(Kofi)]]]
 \end{aligned}$$

The truth-conditions in (225) are demonstrated by the timeline in Figure 3.10.

Figure 3.10: Simultaneous interpretations of *a*-embeddings with change-of-state verbs

The timeline shows that the awake state of Kofi, namely $g(4)$, temporally includes the attitude time t'' , thus yielding a (result-oriented) simultaneous interpretation. Conceivably, change-of-state predicates like *nyane*, when paired with a resultative perfect, emphasize the result state of the event rather than the preceding process.

Pushing this line of thought further, one could hypothesize that the verb morphology in Asante Twi serves to bridge potential lexical gaps, giving rise to stative predicates not conventionally present in the language’s lexicon.¹⁰⁰ Such a hypothesis gains credibility for a couple of reasons. Firstly, morpho-semantic processes deriving statives from change of state verbs are well documented. For instance derived statives such as deverbal adjectives have been argued to retain the meaning of their source verb — thus contrasting with non-deverbal adjectives — as discussed by Koontz-Garboden, (2010). Secondly, if *a*-prefixation represents a productive process to derive statives from verbs in Asante Twi, one would expect to encounter deverbal statives bearing *a*-prefixes that have fully grammaticalized into adjectives or nouns. This prediction seems to be borne out by the following pairs:¹⁰¹

- (226)
- a. *dwene* (‘to think’) → *adwene* (‘thought’, ‘idea’, ‘mind’)
 - b. *siesie* (‘to mend’) → *asiesie* (‘mend’, ‘decoration’)
 - c. *teetee* (‘to harass’) → *ateetee* (‘harassment’)
 - d. *te* (‘to hear’) → *atesem* (= *a*-hear-matter, ‘hearsay’)

¹⁰⁰In this regard, Osam (2003) notes that predicates in Akan may be associated with different meanings depending on TAM-inflection.

¹⁰¹Appah (2005) illustrates that *a*-prefixation is deployed as a productive strategy for action nominalization in Akan. For example, from *sa* (‘to dance’), one derives *asa* (‘the act of dancing’), or from *kenkan* (‘to read’), *akenkan* (‘the act of reading’). However, Appah does not posit a connection between the prefix *a* in nominalizations and the homograph TAnt marker.

- e. *dwane* ('to bolt') → *deɛ wadwane* (=REL 3SG-a-bolt, 'fugitive')
- f. *wu* ('to die') → *deɛ awuo* ('dead')

3.5.7 Akan as a non-SoT language

The investigation of propositional attitude reports in Asante Twi has revealed three main insights:

- (i) Asante Twi lacks an SoT rule that deletes tense features in agreement configurations;
- (ii) *de re* readings are generally available for pronominal tense forms but vary in availability;
- (iii) the existence of a novel compositional mechanism that facilitates simultaneous readings for change-of-state embeddings.

Similar to non-SoT languages like Japanese, Russian and Hebrew, Asante Twi showcases a transparent mapping of TAM morphology to meaning. Specifically, unmarked forms tend to produce temporally dependent readings, reminiscent of construals with a relative present. On the other hand, overt TAnt markers can also yield simultaneous interpretations through acquaintance based representations. However, the degree of availability of readings associated with these *de re* logical forms varies as a function of certain pragmatic and cognitive factors.

What is most intriguing about Asante Twi is its multiple compositional mechanisms deployed to express temporal relations. Notably, three primary pathways for deriving simultaneity have been identified:

- (a) *de se* representations of bare embeddings, commonly employed across most predicates, providing a genuine report of an attitude.
- (b) *de re* ascriptions of *ná*-embeddings, which shift the temporal perspective to that of the speaker, making them preferable in situations where the attitude holder misconceives their temporal location.
- (c) local binding of the result state of *a*-embeddings, introducing a novel method to achieve SIM, predominantly associated with change-of-state verbs.

With these diverse mechanisms at its disposal, Asante Twi demonstrates a versatile toolkit for deriving similar temporal interpretations, selecting compositional pathways that align best with the context and predicate type.

3.6 Summary

The first part of this chapter was devoted to the investigation of temporal meaning in Asante Twi (Akan), with a focus on the three markers that denote temporal shifting: the final vowel lengthening LEN, the prefix *a* and the sentence particle *ná*. Using the diagnostics in Bertrand et al. (2022) as a foundation, I demonstrated that while LEN and *ná* primarily exhibit referential properties, *a* correlates with existential and universal

readings. One key finding indicated that, within matrix contexts, *ná*-clauses are in complementary semantic distribution with bare ones. Specifically, *ná* makes reference to any salient time, whether past or future, except for the utterance time. Additionally, LEN is characterized by a perfective aspectual profile, evidenced by its ability to trigger actuality entailments and its use as a narrative progression device.

Building upon these identified properties, I have developed a proposal, whereby unmarked predicates in Asante Twi are evaluated by default with respect to the utterance time t_c . At the same time, their eventuality argument is saturated by covert stative and habitual aspect operators. The particle *ná* also associates with covert imperfective aspect. However, it denotes a pronominal tense expressing temporal distance from the utterance time. In contrast, the two affixals LEN and *a* present a higher internal complexity: while LEN exhibits a pronominal relative past tense alongside a perfective aspect, *a* combines an extended now perfect with a viewpoint aspect, which can manifest as either resultative or stative. Specifically, the resultative viewpoint aspect can contribute to both experiential and resultative interpretations based on the QuD. Conversely, when combined with stative aspect, the extended now perfect is able to generate universal interpretations.

In the second part of the chapter, I explored the temporal interpretation of attitude reports, giving special attention to complement clauses containing the three temporal anteriority markers. Let me briefly outline the main findings. Bare clauses primarily yield simultaneous interpretations, wherein the eventuality denoted by the unmarked predicate holds true of a temporal interval that overlaps with the attitude time. Compositionally, this interpretation stems from the initial assumption that bare clauses are tenseless and are therefore interpreted relative to a superordinate temporal operator. In parallel, LEN-marked attitude reports give rise to backward-shifted interpretations as a consequence of the relative tense semantics associated with LEN's tense component.

By contrast, *ná*-embeddings display a systematic ambiguity between SIM and BACK, reminiscent of past-under-past embeddings in SoT languages. However, I advocated for a non-SoT theory wherein both readings emerge from an acquaintance-based approach, thus involving a *de re* interpretation of *ná*. When extending this analysis to LEN-embeddings, it becomes evident that the simultaneous interpretation is only marginally available when an overt adverbial modifies the embedded clause. This limitation arises due to a blocking effect imposed by the upper limit constraint, which operates at a more granular level, thereby excluding bounded event structures. Moreover, the predominant preference for bare embeddings in simultaneous scenarios is motivated on the basis of Schlenker's *Prefer de se!* constraint.

Concluding this exploration, *a*-marked attitude reports give rise to a range of different interpretations: on one side, readily available backward-shifted interpretations tend to be process-oriented and involve temporal shifting with respect to the attitude time or the utterance time. Conversely, simultaneous interpretations are predominantly confined to result-oriented readings associated with change-of-state verbs. Addressing the former, I have adopted both a *de Dicto* analysis — correlating with an experiential interpretation — and a *de re* analysis targeting t_c . The latter directly arises from a *de Dicto* analysis, leading to a resultative interpretation of the *a*-marked predicate.

4 Temporal meaning and the composition of attitude reports in Italian

This chapter explores the composition of temporal meaning in Italian, focusing on tensed propositional attitude reports as well as additional semantic-pragmatic factors affecting the range of interpretations observed. The approach taken here differs from that employed in the previous chapter as Italian TAM system has been subject to extensive scrutiny, both descriptive and formal. Consequently, the theoretical assumptions presented will largely rely on critically evaluated claims from the literature.

Specifically, two phenomena will attract our interest: (i) the contribution of mood and aspect alternation to the interpretation of present-under-past embeddings; (ii) the contribution of epistemic states to the composition of temporally vacuous readings of past-under-past embeddings.

The first section of this chapter introduces the temporal-aspectual system of Italian, focusing on the present tense and simple future on one hand, and the two perfects and the imperfect on the other. After discussing the relevant descriptive and formal literature, it proposes a formal analysis of their meanings. Building on this semantic framework, the remaining sections explore the temporal interpretations of these forms when embedded under propositional attitude verbs. In particular, section 4.2 provides an extensive characterization of double access readings resulting from an embedded present, with a focus on the effects of mood and aspect alternation on its interpretation. It also discusses overlooked phenomena in the Italian literature, such as the temporal interpretation in future contexts. Section 4.3 lays out the basic facts concerning the temporal interpretation of past-oriented forms in attitude contexts, with particular attention to the Sequence of Tense parameter. This exploration reveals an asymmetry between perfect and imperfect embeddings, noting that only the latter appear to correlate with *de se* construals. The composition of these constructions is further investigated in sections 4.4 and 4.5, which argue against the existence of a dedicated SoT rule in Italian. Specifically, section 4.4 relates the exceptional availability of simultaneous readings for perfect embeddings to a *de re* mechanism, while section 4.5 attributes genuinely null readings to an epistemic interpretation of the imperfect. Finally, these insights are tied together in section 4.6, which draws conclusions on the SoT debate surrounding Italian.

4.1 Background: tense and aspect in Italian

This section provides a brief introduction to the Italian TAM system, with emphasis on four indicative tense forms: the present tense (PRES), the synthetic perfect (SPRF),

the analytic perfect (APRF) and the imperfect (IMPF). Given the impossibility to do justice to the vast literature on the topic, for each TAM form, I will primarily identify those properties that will be relevant for the current investigation.¹

4.1.1 Present tense forms: the present tense and the simple future

Present tense in Italian, and more generally in Romance languages, is viewed as an imperfective indexical: Aspectually, it conveys progressive and habitual meaning, as is illustrated in the following examples.

- (1) a. A: Dov'è Gianni? ('Where is Gianni?')
 b. B: Gioca nel cortile. (Progressive)
 pro.3SG play.PRES in.DEF yard.
 'He's playing in the yard.'
- (2) a. A: Cosa fai nel tempo libero? ('What are you doing in your free time?')
 b. B: Suono il pianoforte. (Habitual)
 pro.1SG play.PRES DET piano
 'I play the piano.'

Temporally, it generally evaluates a sentence with respect to the utterance time, akin to the English present. As we have learnt, embedding present under past-tensed attitudes offers the best testing ground for present's indexicality (see (3)).

- (3) # Due anni fa Paolo disse che Marta è incinta. (DAR)
 two years ago Paolo say.SPRF COMP Marta be.PRES pregnant
 Lit. 'Two years ago, Paolo said that Marta is pregnant.'

In (3), an (implausible) double access reading arises, according to which Marta is still pregnant, two years since Paolo spoke about it. The ungrammaticality of the sentence suggests that Italian exhibits an indexical, rather than relative, present.²

The Italian present is also found in future contexts, especially in spoken discourse where it commonly replaces the future. Resorting to present tense to talk about events that are yet to take place is by no means surprising, as similar uses have been observed even in English (Copley, 2008; Karawani & Zeijlstra, 2024; Kaufmann, 2005), where they have been primarily associated with plans and schedules that are set as of UT. Some examples are given below.

- (4) (Adapted from Copley, 2008; Karawani & Zeijlstra, 2024):
 a. Liverpool visit United tomorrow.
 b. Liverpool #(will) beat United tomorrow.

The contrast in (4) shows that, in English, the futurate present can only target predicates denoting a plan or a schedule. Such restrictions are often relaxed in Italian, as the

¹A comprehensive descriptive investigation for the indicative tense system in Italian can be found in Bertinetto (1986). For subjunctive tense forms, see Wandruszka, 1991.

²Exceptions to this general pattern are restricted to special uses such as the narrative present (which is neither indexical nor imperfective) and the immediate future present (which is not imperfective).

following sentences illustrate.

- (5) Il treno parte domani alle 6.
 DEF train leave.PRES tomorrow at.DEF 6
 ‘The train leaves tomorrow at 6.’
- (6) a. A: Hai portato fuori la spazzatura? (‘Did you take out the trash?’)
 b. B: No. Lo faccio stasera.
 no pro.1SG CL do.PRES tonight
 ‘I’ll do it tonight’
- (7) Domani La Juve batte l’Inter e va in testa, ci
 tomorrow DEF Juve defeat.PRES DEF=Inter and go.PRES in head CL
 scommetti?
 bet.PRES
 ‘Tomorrow, Juve will beat Inter and jump to the top of the table, I bet.’

The present-tensed sentences (6) and (7) require the future modal ‘will’ in their English paraphrase, whereas future marking is only optional in Italian. All these examples have a common denominator: they all make reference to an eventuality whose future occurrence is deemed certain or highly likely at UT.³

While the distribution of the Italian futurate present is wider in range than that of the English counterpart, futurate present and future are not completely overlapping in Italian. Consider the following contrast:

- (8) a. Stasera verso le cinque faccio una passeggiata nel parco.
 tonight around DEF five do.PRES DEF walk in.DEF park
 ‘Later at around 5, I’m going for a walk in the park.’
 b. Stasera verso le cinque {??sto/starò} facendo una passeggiata nel
 tonight around DEF five do.PROG.PRES/FUT DEF walk in.DEF
 parco.
 park
 ‘Later at around 5, I’ll be walking in the park.’

In (8-a), the speaker expresses their current goal/desire regarding an upcoming situation. A futurate present is possible in that, from the speaker’s perspective, the eventuality is regarded as certain at UT. Conversely, in (8-b), the future walking event is viewed as ongoing. Clearly, at UT the internal structure of a future event is not accessible and, as a consequence, the present-tensed sentence is degraded. Similarly, present-tensed stative

³One could easily paraphrase these uses with a present-tensed bouletic or epistemic periphrastics or modal:

- (i) a. È previsto che il treno parta domani alle 6.
 ‘It is expected that the train leaves tomorrow at 6.’
 b. No. Ho intenzione di farlo stasera.
 ‘I intend to do it tonight.’
 c. Prevedo che la Juve batta l’inter domani.
 ‘I predict that Juve is going to beat Inter tomorrow.’

predicates in future-oriented contexts are generally odd, unless they denote a plan or a schedule as exemplified in the following.

- (9) Quando mia figlia si trasferirà, {# sono/sarò} triste.
 when POSS daughter SI move.FUT PRES/FUT sad
 ‘When my daughter moves out, I’ll be sad.’
- (10) a. Context: (Speaking about a baby due next month)
 b. A chi {# somiglia/somiglierà tuo figlio (fra un
 to who resemble.PRES/FUT POSS.2SG child in
 mese)?
 one month
 Intended: ‘Who will your child resemble?’
- (11) a. Preparati per la festa dei vicini di domani... (‘Get ready for the neighbours’
 party tomorrow!’)
 b. ... La musica {# è/sarà} alta.
 DEF music be.PRES/FUT high
 ‘...The music will be loud!’
- (12) Ho fallito il test d’ingresso quest’anno, ... (‘I failed the entry test this year’)
 a. ...ma l’anno prossimo {# ho/avrò} più fortuna.
 ...but DEF=year next have.PRES/FUT more luck
 ‘...but next year I’ll have better luck.’
 b. ...ma l’anno prossimo lo {supero/supererò}.
 ...but DEF=year next CL pass.PRES/FUT
 ‘...but I’m going to pass it next year.’
- (13) Domani {sono/sarò} di turno di mattina.
 tomorrow be.PRES/FUT of shift of morning
 ‘Tomorrow I’m on the morning shift.’

Note that some speakers do accept the futurate present even in contexts that do not denote plans or goals.

- (14) ?Oggi riposati ché domani ti stanchi col trasloco.
 today rest.IMP.CL COMP tomorrow CL tire with.DEF move.
 ‘Get some rest today, since tomorrow you’ll get tired from the move.’

I find present tense in these sentences slightly marked. Opting for the future would certainly be the preferred option. I believe that in these cases, regional or dialectal usages are overextended to standard Italian.⁴

The semantics of Italian PRES

Taking into account the empirical data laid out in this section, the Italian present is classified as an indexical rather than a relative tense. What remains to be understood is

⁴Southern varieties, for instance, lack a proper future tense form and thus adopt present tense or modal periphrastics to express future meaning.

whether its temporal domain needs to be widened and include future temporal intervals or if future meaning should not be derived from its lexical semantics. A view in line with the first option is pursued by (Arosio et al., 2004), who adopts a non-past semantics for the Italian present as is given in (15).

- (15) a. $\llbracket \text{pres}_k \rrbracket^{Arosio}$ defined iff $\neg g((k) < t_c)$
 b. $\llbracket \text{pres}_k \rrbracket^{Arosio} = g(k)$

Clearly, this analysis can correctly capture the attested future occurrences for present-tensed predicates, excluding the not available past ones. However, it remains unclear how this analysis can also rule out cases such as (8)-(12), where only future marking is possible. One additional challenge this analysis faces is the availability of universal readings for present tense. As we have previously observed, unlike English, present tense is the preferred option to yield temporal interpretations encompassing a past time and extending until the utterance time.

- (16) Ho la febbre da giorni.
 have.PRES DEF fever for days
 ‘I’ve been sick for days.’
- (17) Derna vive a Tubinga dal 2017.
 Derna live.PRES at Tübingen since.DEF 2017
 ‘Derna has been living in Tübingen since 2017.’
- (18) Andrea è appassionato di fotografia sin da quando era
 Andrea be.PRES passionate of photography ever since when be.IMP
 piccolo.
 small
 ‘Andrea has been passionate about photography since he was a kid.’

The lexical entry in (15) does not allow to derive the correct interpretation for the above sentences. For instance, according to (17), the eventuality holds true of an interval starting at some point in 2017 and extending until now. Clearly, 2017 precedes UT, thus violating the presupposition in (15).

I propose that the Italian present tense simply denotes a temporal interval that surrounds the utterance or context time t_c . This indexical component is reflected in the form of a presupposition imposed on the evaluation time, as is illustrated by the formula in (19).

- (19) a. $\llbracket \text{pres}_{2,3} \rrbracket$ defined iff $\llbracket \text{pres}_{2,3} \rrbracket \in D_{(i,i)} \ \& \ g(2) \supseteq g(3) \ \& \ g(3) = t_c$
 b. $\llbracket \text{pres}_{2,3} \rrbracket(g(3)) = g(2)$

Following (19), ‘ $\text{pres}_{2,3}$ ’ is a function from (reference) times to (evaluation) times, akin to Asante ‘LEN’ ’s doubly indexed tense pronoun. The first index provides the reference time $g(2)$, while the second index supplies the evaluation time $g(3)$. The presupposition in (19-a) constrains $g(2)$ ’s reference to times surrounding UT (being $g(3)$ a time coinciding with t_c). Notably, PRES’s semantics correlates with a pronominal analysis of tense. I

take this fact to result from the Italian present's indexical nature.⁵

Furthermore, in the light of its imperfective aspectual profile, the Italian present projects an imperfective aspect at LF, whose semantics is given in (20).⁶

$$(20) \quad \llbracket \text{IPFV} \rrbracket = \lambda p_{\langle v,t \rangle} . \lambda t_{\langle i \rangle} . \exists e [t \subseteq \tau(e) \ \& \ p(e)]$$

Given this set-up, the system can compute the truth-conditions of a matrix clause with a present-tensed predicate as follows.

- (21) Marco mangia la mela.
 Marco eat.PRES DEF apple
 'Marco is eating the apple.'

(22) *Logical Form for (21):*

- a. LF: $[_{CP} w_c [_{\lambda w} [t_c [_{\lambda t_3} [_{TP} \text{pres}_{2,3} [_{AspP} \text{IPFV} [\lambda e [_{VP} [_{DP} \text{Marco}] [_{V'} \text{mangia-} \\ \text{mela}_{w,e}]]]]]]]]]]]]]]]]]]]$
 b. $\llbracket (22\text{-a}) \rrbracket$ defined iff $g(2) \supseteq t_c \ \& \ t_c = t_c$
 c. $\llbracket (22\text{-a}) \rrbracket = 1$ iff $\exists e [g(2) \subseteq \tau(e) \ \& \ \text{eat}(w_c)(e)(\iota y[\text{apple}(y)])(M)$
Paraphrase: 'There is an eventuality e, such that e temporally includes a temporal interval g(2) that encompasses t_c , and e is an eventuality of Marco eating an apple.'

Note that the temporal interval g(2) comes with no restrictions on its boundaries, allowing it to stretch backward and forward, depending on the context.⁷ Such flexibility is a desirable feature of present's semantics in that it potentially captures its compatibility with universal and (future) double access interpretations. Consider the following examples.

- (23) Derna vive a Tubinga da 7 anni.
 Derna live.PRES at Tübingen since 7 years
 'Derna has been living in Tübingen for the past seven years.'

- (24) Andrea è di turno in ospedale per le prossime tre notti.
 Andrea be.PRES of shift in hospital for DEF next three nights
 'Andrea is on duty for the next three nights.'

In (23) and (24), the temporal interval g(2) picked out by the present tense extends from t_c to include a past and a future time, respectively. Its temporal extension is determined by the *for*-adverbial.

Clearly, as currently formulated, this analysis cannot account for those future temporal interpretations that strictly follow the utterance time. We have demonstrated, however,

⁵An alternative quantificational analysis would be indistinguishable from a pronominal one. Firstly, existential/indefinite contexts cannot serve as appropriate diagnostics for a quantificational/existential tense, since the context time is inherently salient in any given speech context. Secondly, bound variable readings under universal quantifiers can be justified even under a pronominal analysis, considering that the Italian present is associated with an existential quantifier over eventualities in AspP. Ultimately, this choice has no significant impact on this proposal.

⁶Clearly, this characterization of present's imperfective aspect comes with a strong simplification as it says nothing about habitual meaning.

⁷The only restriction being that the utterance time be included in said interval.

that future interpretations for the Italian present are limited in distribution and retain a character of *presentness*, in that they target eventualities that are certain to take place from the perspective of the speech context. The latter has often been referred to as *certainty condition* in the literature (Bertinetto, 1986; Karawani & Zeijlstra, 2024; Kaufmann, 2005; Leech, 2014)⁸ More formally, Karawani & Zeijlstra (2024) and Kaufmann (2005) defend a modal analysis for the futurate present, whereby present tense qualifies the accessibility relation introduced by a covert necessity modal. Dispensing with technical details, I will follow their insights and assume that future meanings for present tense can be attributed to an *epistemic* use of the present tense: future-occurring eventualities whose truth is epistemically accessible from the utterance time (and, thus, that are settled at UT) need not bear future marking.⁹

The future

Alongside the present simple, there exists a second present tense form in Italian: the future. The diachronic development of the Romance future is well documented and derived from a periphrastic comprising an infinitive with the inflected present-tensed modal. The two forms have across time conflated into the synthetic form representing future forms nowadays. This process can be illustrated as follows for Italian:

- (25) a. Mangiare + ho → mangerò
 ‘to eat’ + ‘I have’ → ‘I will eat’
 b. Dormire + ho → dormirò
 ‘to sleep’ + ‘I have’ → ‘I will sleep’

Bertinetto (1991, p. 483) observes that the inflected component ‘to have’ is essentially modal. Also, as is well known, the Romance future may be used as an evidential (Frana & Menéndez-Benito, 2023), with a present temporal orientation.

- (26) *Evidential future in Italian*
 a. Cosa starà facendo Gianni adesso?
 What stay.FUT doing Gianni now
 ‘What could Gianni be doing right now?’
 b. Marica sarà sicuramente a casa a poltrire.
 Marica be.FUT surely at home to idle
 ‘Marica will surely be at home lounging around.’

For these reasons, I believe that the Italian future is best characterized as a present-tensed modal, on a par with English ‘will’. The future’s indexical component is evident, for instance, in attitude complements, where relative readings are strictly ruled out.

⁸Bertinetto anchors the certainty condition to the speaker, contending that the futurate present must involve subjective certainty.

⁹An obvious objection to this view is offered by the impossibility for present-tensed predicates to depict eventualities strictly occurring before UT, though trivially settled at UT. Conceivably these uses are constrained by pragmatic competition between present and past tense.

- (27) Due giorni fa Gianni ha detto che Marica partirà {# ieri /
 two days ago Gianni say.APRF COMP Marica leave.FUT yesterday /
 domani}
 tomorrow
 Intended: ‘Two days ago Gianni said that Marica would leave yesterday / tomor-
 row’.
 Lit. ‘Two days ago Gianni said that Marica will leave yesterday / tomorrow.’

Building on these insights, I will assume that, at logical form, future marking is associated with a modal operator ‘FUT’ hosted in a ModP and scoping below a present tense.¹⁰ A basic architecture is sketched in (28).

For its semantics,¹¹ I am assuming that *FUT* is a future (necessity) modal, hence it introduces universal quantification over times following the local evaluation time (here, the reference time supplied by present tense) as well as existential quantification over possible worlds that are accessible from the local world of evaluation.¹²

(29) $\llbracket \text{FUT} \rrbracket = \lambda w_{\langle s \rangle} . \lambda p_{\langle s, \langle i, t \rangle \rangle} . \lambda t_{\langle i \rangle} . \forall w' [R(w)(w') \rightarrow \exists t' [t' > t \ \& \ p(w')(t')]]$

According to the semantics in (29), *FUT* combines with a world of evaluation and requires a property of worlds (and times) as its second argument. To preserve compositionality, a binder co-indexed with the VP’s world variable is inserted below ModP. Further below, a default perfective aspect (given in (30)) closes off the eventuality argument, mediating between ModP and VP.¹³ The resulting interpretation is shown in (32) for (31).

(30) $\llbracket \text{PFV} \rrbracket = \lambda p_{\langle v, t \rangle} . \lambda t_{\langle i \rangle} . \exists e [t \supseteq \tau(e) \ \& \ p(e)]$

- (31) Stan tornerà.
 Stan return.FUT
 ‘Stan will return.’

¹⁰Recall that this is precisely what we have assumed for English in chapter 2.

¹¹For clarity of exposition, the denotation proposed for *FUT* is simplified, as it does not factor in the evidential component of the Italian future.

¹²The exact nature of said accessibility relation is tangential to our discussion. However, an epistemic modal flavour could be a good fit.

¹³The aspectual value of the future modal in Italian is a complex matter that we cannot feasibly address satisfactorily here. It has been observed, for instance, that the Italian future exhibits both perfective and imperfective uses, although the former are predominant (Bertinetto, 1986, pp. 489–490). For this reason, I will take the future to be essentially perfective, unless the inflected predicate is stative or the context forces an imperfective interpretation.

- (32) a. LF for (31): $[_{CP} w_c [\lambda w_0 [t_c [_{TP} pres_{2,3} [_{ModP} [Mod\ FUT\ w_0]] [_{AspP} PFV [_{VP} Stan-tornare]]]]]]]]$
- b. $\llbracket (32-a) \rrbracket$ defined iff $g(2) \supseteq t_c \ \& \ t_c = t_c$
- c. When defined, $\llbracket (32-a) \rrbracket = 1$ iff
 $\forall w' [R(w)(w') \rightarrow \exists t' [t' > t_c \ \& \ \exists e [t' \supseteq \tau(e) \ \& \ return(w')(e)(S)]]]$
Paraphrase: ‘For all the possible worlds w' accessible from the actual world w_c , there is a time t' such that there is event e such that e is temporally included in t' and e is an event of Stan returning in w' .’

4.1.2 Perfect(ive) forms: the synthetic and the analytic perfect

Turning our attention to the Italian past tense forms, I will focus on the two perfects: the synthetic perfect (SPRF) commonly referred to as ‘Passato Remoto’ (remote past) and the analytic perfect (APRF) known as ‘Passato Prossimo’ (proximal past) in descriptive grammars. For ease of comprehension, the two forms will be discussed in parallel, highlighting the contrastive aspects of their meaning and distribution.

As widely acknowledged,¹⁴ delineating the contours of contemporary Italian language usage, particularly in spoken form, poses a significant challenge due to the pronounced geographic variability in behaviour. This challenge is even more prominent when considering the usage of the two perfect tenses. Given its deep historical origins, pinning down the roots of this variability is no easy task. Consequently, it’s important to note that what follows are just rough approximations applying to areas and speakers whose tense inventory contains both the APRF and the SPRF. For those varieties of Italian that have done away with the distinction between the two perfects, a tailored discussion would be necessary, acknowledging the specific path of neutralization. For current purposes, however, it will suffice to outline the main characterizing features of the two forms, providing a glimpse into the foundation on which the distinction still exists, where it persists.¹⁵

The analytic and synthetic perfect are usually presented together in opposition to the imperfect, in that they both manipulate past reference times and seem aspectually perfective (cf. Arosio, 2010; Bertinetto, 1991; Von Stechow, 2002). As the name suggests, the synthetic perfect (SPRF) is a synthetic form, descendant of the Latin perfect. By contrast, the analytic perfect (APRF) is a compound form comprising a present-tensed auxiliary¹⁶ and a participle. Despite their superficial overlapping distribution, the two forms are not fully interchangeable. Nor can their contrast be explained solely in terms of temporal remoteness, despite the obvious association suggested by the terminology used in Italian grammars. Upon closer scrutiny, a number of divergent properties can be identified, which point to a fairly distinct formal treatment.

(i) *Pronominal vs existential tense*

¹⁴See also the discussion in Bertinetto (1986, p. 409)

¹⁵Approximately, the alternation of the two perfects in spoken discourse survives among southern speakers.

¹⁶Unlike English, Italian adopts both ‘to be’ and ‘to have’ as auxiliaries, depending on whether the lexical verb is unaccusative (‘to be’), or unergative or transitive (‘to have’).

While the synthetic perfect is strongly anaphoric and exhibits predominantly referential properties, the analytic perfect is additionally compatible with existential, experiential readings, which are unavailable with the SPRF,¹⁷ as is illustrated below.

- (33) *Referential context*: Speaking of last year's city marathon...
- a. Lo scorso anno Gianni **corse** la maratona in sole tre ore.
DEF last year Gianni **run.SPRF** DEF marathon in only three hours
- b. Lo scorso anno Gianni **ha corso** la maratona in sole tre ore.
DEF last year Gianni **run.APRF** DEF marathon in only three hours
'Last year Gianni ran the maratona in only three hours.'
- (34) *Experiential context*: Sara is always picking the least expensive dish at the restaurant as she's saving up. You've decided to treat her to a fancy dinner. You ask her:
- a. **Hai** mai **assaggiato** l'aragosta?
AUX ever **taste.APRF** DEF=lobster
- b. ?? **Assaggiasti** mai l'aragosta?
taste.SPRF ever DEF=lobster
Intended: 'Have you ever tried the lobster?'
- (35) *Experiential context*: You've been introduced to Marco. He looks familiar, but you wonder...
- a. Non ricordo se l'ho già visto da qualche parte.
NEG remember if CL=AUX already **see.APRF** at some place
- b. ?? Non ricordo se lo **vidi** già da qualche parte.
NEG remember if CL **see.SPRF** already at some place
Intended: 'I don't remember if I've already seen him somewhere.'

Unsurprisingly, resultative readings correlate with the analytic form only.

- (36) *Resultative Context*: Dinner is ready. You invite Marica to stay and join you for dinner. She replies:
- a. Grazie, ma ho appena cenato.
thanks but AUX just dine.APRF
- b. # Grazie, ma appena cenai.
thanks but just dine.SPRF
Intended: 'Thank you, but I've just had dinner.'

Absolute vs relative tense

The synthetic perfect behaves like an absolute past tense in that its evaluation time is rigidly the utterance time. By contrast, the analytic perfect can make reference to times preceding a local EvalT that differs from UT. Recall that the difference between absolute

¹⁷Existential readings for the SPRF are confined to a few southern non-standard varieties that still adopt a Latin-like synthetic perfect (Sicilian, among others). In Neapolitan, however, despite the prominence of the synthetic perfect, resultative and experiential uses are restricted to the analytic perfect today.

and relative past becomes visibile only in future embeddings, where only a relative past may locate an eventuality after the utterance time as long as it precedes the local EvalT.

- (37) Context: Every three years, you're meeting your former schoolmates for a big class re-union. On this year re-union, Marta revealed she is planning her wedding for next year. She hasn't decided on the details yet, she only sent out a save the date for July 15th 2025. You predict that it's going to be a beach wedding.
- (38) Al prossimo incontro tra tre anni, Marta ci dirà che...
 At.DEF next meeting in three years Marta CL say.FUT COMP
 'Next time we meet in three years, Marta will tell us that...'
- a. # si sposò in spiaggia.
 SI marry.SPRF in beach
 'She got married on the beach.'
 - b. si è sposata in spiaggia.
 SI marry.APRF in beach
 'She got married on the beach.'
 - c. si era sposata in spiaggia. SI marry.PPRF in beach
 'She had got married on the beach.'

Similar patterns are observed in relative clauses, as previously noted by Arosio et al. (2004).

- (39) Context: Maria was born today. As a gift to the parents, a fortune teller predicts her future (after Arosio et al., 2004, p. 48):
- a. Maria sposerà un uomo più giovane che ha vissuto a
 Maria marry.FUT NDEF man more young COMP marry.APRF at
 New York.
 New York
 - b. #Maria sposerà un uomo più giovane che visse a
 Maria marry.FUT NDEF man more young COMP live.SPRF
 New York.
 at New York
 Intended: 'Maria will marry a younger man who lived in New York.'

These empirical data point to a relative past for APRF as opposed to SPRF. This conclusion is however challenged by the following examples depicting future scenarios, where the analytic perfect scopes below a past conditional or a past perfect.

- (40) *APRF-under-Past Cond*
- a. Context: Luca was planning to skip school next Friday and go to a concert instead. However, after remembering that the next parent-teacher conference is coming up soon, he started having second thoughts.
 - b. Luca temeva che fra qualche settimana i suoi genitori
 Luca fear.IMP COMP in some week DEF POSS parents

avrebbero scoperto che # ha saltato/aveva saltato la scuola.
 discover.PAST.COND COMP skip.APRF/PPRF DEF school
 ‘Luca feared that in a few weeks his parents would find out that he skipped school.’

(41) *APRF-under-PPRF*

- a. Context: In preparation for the merger, at tomorrow’s board meeting Marco is expected to present a thorough financial evaluation of the satellite company his firm wants to absorb.
- b. La prossima settimana Marco ci dirà che il giorno prima
 DEF next week Marco CL say.FUT COMP DEF day before
 aveva rivelato al suo capo che # ha gonfiato/aveva gonfiato il
 reveal.PPRF to POSS boss COMP inflate.APRF/PPRF DEF
 valore dell’azienda.
 value of.DEF=company
 ‘Next week, Marco will tell us that the day before he revealed to his boss that the (had) inflated the company’s value.’

In (40) and (41), the lowest embedded APRF cannot yield a temporal *de Dicto* interpretation, for which a past perfect must be used instead. In fact, the felicity of the APRF-marked embeddings can only be rescued in contexts where the school-skipping or the value-inflating events have already taken place as of UT.¹⁸

Modification by LTAs

Both forms can be accompanied by locating temporal adverbials. While APRF poses no restriction on the type of temporal adverb, hodiernal LTAs appear to lead to degradation when modifying SPRF-inflected predicates.¹⁹

(42) Due settimane fa andai / sono andato a trovare Luca.
 two weeks ago go.SPRF go.APRF to visit Luca
 ‘Two weeks ago I paid Luca a visit.’

(43) Marica fu licenziata / è stata licenziata nel 2015.
 Marica fire.SPRF.PASS fire.APRF.PASS in.DEF 2015
 ‘Marica was fired in 2015.’

Universal readings

Universal readings are notoriously absent for most perfects in Indo-European languages, with the present tense being the preferred option for temporal intervals that extend until the utterance time. Recall that universal interpretations are determined by a specific set of adverbials: left-boundary (LB), duration-quantifying (DQ) and universal ones. In Italian, such interpretations are ruled out for either perfect when an LB or a DQ adverb

¹⁸As far as I know, these data have never been discussed in the literature.

¹⁹The more descriptive literature tends to distinguish between the two forms in terms of temporal remoteness, with the synthetic form only felicitous for temporally distant eventualities. As a native speaker accepting both forms, despite a clear preference for the APRF, I can adopt the SPRF even for fairly recent situations, as long as these do not extend into the utterance day.

modifies the predicate, as illustrated by the following examples.

- (44) Context: Derna moved to Tübingen 7 years ago and she's currently still living there.
- a. # Derna ha vissuto / visse a Tübingen per/da 7 anni.
Derna live.APRF live.SPRF in Tübingen for years
 - b. Derna vive a Tübingen da 7 anni.
Derna live.PRES in Tübingen since 7 years
'Derna has been living in Tübingen for 7 years.'
 - c. # Derna ha vissuto / visse a Tübingen dal 2017.
Derna live.APRF live.SPRF in Tübingen since.DEF 2017
 - d. Derna vive a Tübingen dal 2017.
Derna live.PRES in Tübingen since.DEF 2017
'Derna has been living in Tübingen since 2017.'

The sentences in (44-a) may exhibit a durative interpretation, but they entail that the living eventuality is located entirely before UT. Nonetheless, universal interpretations seem to emerge when the perfect-marked predicate is modified by a universal adverbial (Dahl, 2021), but only if the perfect is analytic.

- (45) *Universal context*: The eventuality still holds at UT.
- a. Gianna ha praticato / # praticò sempre sport pericolosi...
Gianna practice.APRF practice.SPRF always sports dangerous.
'Gianna has always practiced dangerous sports.'
 - b. Per tutta la vita ho collezionato / # collezionò francobolli...
for all DEF life collect.APRF collect.SPRF stamps
'All my life I've been collecting stamps.'

Unlike for English, universal readings can be cancelled for the Italian analytic perfect. Consider the following continuations to the sentences in (45).

- (46)
- a. ... finché non ha smesso per via di un infortunio.
until NEG stop.APRF due to NDEF injury
'... until she stopped due to an injury.'
 - b. ... prima di scoprire negli ultimi anni nuovi passatempi.
before to discover.INF in.DEF last years new hobbies
'... before discovering new hobbies in the past few years.'

The cancellability test may be suggestive of a pragmatic solution to the exceptional universal readings arising with universal adverbials. Unfortunately, things are not as simple. In fact, there's a subset of LB-adverbials that allow for universal readings of the analytic perfect that resist cancellation. One example is given below, where the present tense is a possible alternative.²⁰

²⁰For further insights on similar cases, see Bertinetto (1986, p. 418).

4 Temporal meaning and the composition of attitude reports in Italian

- (47) a. Marco ha giocato / gioca a calcio {sin da piccolo} / {da Marco play.APRF play.PRES at football ever since small since sempre}...
 always
 Lt. ‘Marco has been playing / plays football since childhood / forever.’
- b. ??... ma lo scorso giugno ha dovuto smettere.
 but DEF last June must.APRF stop.INF
 ‘... but last June he had to stop.’

I will call these adverbials ‘universal left-boundary adverbials’ (ULBA). ULBAs seem to impose universal quantification akin to universal adverbials and often involve domain-maximizers such as ‘in my life’, ‘always’ or ‘ever since’ (cf. Iatridou et al., 2001). Despite the lack of a systematic investigation in the literature, the fact that universal readings are required under ULBAs has been argued for both English (cf. Iatridou et al., 2001) and German (cf. Von Stechow, 2002). I will return to the universal puzzle later in the section.

Narrative progression and actuality entailments

As previously hinted, the two perfects exhibit a perfective aspectual profile. Consequently, they are expected to be deployed as narration-progressing devices and to display actuality entailments. Both predictions are borne out, as shown in the following.

- (48) *Narrative progression*
- a. Quella mattina mi alzai/sono alzato alle 6, uscii/sono uscito di DEM morning REFL get.up.SPRF/APRF at.DEF 6 go.out.SPRF/APRF of casa alle 7 e alle 7.30 arrivai/sono arrivato al lavoro.
 home at.DEF 7 and at.DEF 7.30 arrive.SPRF/APRF to.DEF work.
 ‘That morning I got up at 6 a.m., left the house at 7 a.m. and arrived at work at 7.30 a.m.’
- (49) *Actuality entailments*
- a. Nel gioco finale, il concorrente fu/è stato in grado di in.DEF game final DEF contestant be.SPRF/APRF able to rispondere,...
 answer
 lit. ‘In the last game, the contestant was able to answer,...’
- b. #... ma rimase/è rimasto in silenzio.
 but remain.SPRF/APRF in silence
 ‘... but remained silent.’

A summary of the temporal-aspectual properties the two perfects exhibit is provided in table 4.1.

	SPRF	APRF
<i>Referential</i>	✓	✓
<i>Relative</i>	x	?✓
<i>Experiential</i>	x	✓
<i>Resultative</i>	x	✓
<i>Modification by LTA</i>	?✓	✓
<i>Universal</i>	x	?x
<i>Narrative progression</i>	✓	✓
<i>Actuality entailment</i>	✓	✓

Table 4.1: Summary: Semantic properties of the two Italian perfects

According to the findings summarized in 4.1, the synthetic perfect SPRF denotes an absolute tense and aligns in all respects with a past perfective form. This is hardly surprising, considered that the Romance simple past is generally viewed as an aorist. More interestingly, the SPRF displays the hallmarks of a purely pronominal tense in that it exhibits referential properties but lacks existential readings. Additionally, it comprises a deictic component restricting its reference to times preceding the utterance time. By contrast, the analytic perfect APRF displays a dual nature: on the one hand, it ticks all the boxes as the SPRF, thus suggesting a past perfective semantics. On the other, it patterns with non-universal hybrid perfects (Bertrand et al., 2022), pointing to an existential tense semantics for the perfect.²¹

The semantics of the two perfects

The semantics of the synthetic perfect SPRF

The insights gained from the empirical section paint a rather straightforward picture for the synthetic perfect, which we have regarded as an absolute past perfective. Thus, the most relevant features that feed into our semantic analysis are its indexicality and perfectivity. As an indexical past tense, the SPRF picks out a salient temporal interval (the reference time) that precedes the utterance time. As a perfective aspect, it quantifies over eventualities that are temporally included within the reference time. A formal rendition is provided as follows:

- (50) SPRF: $[_{TP} [_T \text{past}_{2,3}] [_{AspP} [_{Asp} \text{PFV}]]]$
- (51) a. $[[\text{past}_{2,3}]]$ defined iff $[[\text{past}_{2,3}]] \in D_{(i,i)} \ \& \ g(2) < g(3) \ \& \ g(3) = t_c$
b. $[[\text{past}_{2,3}]](g(3)) = g(2)$
c. $[[\text{PFV}]] = \lambda p_{(v,t)}. \lambda t_{(i)}. \exists e[t \supseteq \tau(e) \ \& \ p(e)]$

In (50) is shown that the SPRF's exponent syncretically spells out two distinct categories: past tense and perfective aspect, which head their respective projections at LF. The past tense is defined as a doubly-indexed pronoun, whose restriction to times preceding UT

²¹In Bertrand et al. (2022), APRF-like perfects represent a sub-type of past perfectives. I believe this classification is slightly misleading.

is built into its presupposition. The lexical entry for ‘PFV’ is the classic Kratzerian semantics for perfective aspect, already assumed in (30) and repeated in (51-c). These meaning components allow us to compositionally compute the meaning of a matrix clause containing a SPRF-inflected predicate, as illustrated below.

- (52) Context: Speaking of the night of the murder...
- a. Luca rimase a casa fino alle 11.
Luca stay.SPRF at house until at.DEF 11
‘Luca stayed at home until 11 p.m.’
 - b. LF: $[\text{CP } w_c [\langle s, t \rangle] \lambda w [\text{t}_c [\langle i, t \rangle] \lambda t'' [\text{TP } [T \langle i \rangle] \text{past}_{2,3} t''']] [\text{AspP} \langle i, t \rangle] [\text{Asp} \text{PFV}] [\langle v, t \rangle] \lambda e [\text{VP } [\text{DP} \text{Luca}] [\text{V}' \text{riman-a-casa}_{w,e}]] [\text{PP} \langle v, t \rangle \text{fino alle 11}]]]]]]$
 - c. $\llbracket (50) \rrbracket$ defined iff $g(2) < g(3) \ \& \ g(3) = t_c$
 - d. $\llbracket (50) \rrbracket = 1$ iff $\exists e[\tau(e) \subseteq g(2) \ \& \ \forall t[11\text{pm} \in \tau(e) \ \& \ t \in \tau(e), \neg(t > 11\text{pm})] \ \& \ \text{stay}(w_c)(e)(H)(L)]$
Paraphrase: ‘There is an eventuality e , such that e is temporally included in $g(2)$ preceding the utterance time t_c , and for all the times t , such that 11pm and t are part of e ’s running time, t does not exceed 11pm, and e is an eventuality of Luca staying at home in the actual world w_c .’

The semantics of the analytic perfect APRF

As previously observed, the analytic perfect appears to share properties with both past perfectives and existential perfects. This aligns with the well-documented diachronic path of the Romance perfect, evolving from a purely resultative periphrastic form - comprising a present tense and a participle indicating a result state — to a fully grammaticalized past perfective (Harris, 1982; Squartini & Bertinetto, 2000).²² In this respect, standard Italian can be seen as having already reached the final developmental stage of the analytic perfect, wherein the APRF has evolved into a fully grammatical past perfective form, albeit with some remnants of the previous phase still surviving.²³ From a synchronic standpoint, the coexistence of features from different diachronic stages raises the question of whether a unified analysis is indeed feasible, or if we should instead presume that the APRF presents two distinct underlying semantic representations.

Let’s briefly consider the available options. Ideally, a satisfactory analysis of the APRF should capture its referential and existential properties, in addition to its relative tense ones. One possibility is to extend to the APRF the domain-restricted quantificational analysis adopted for the English simple past in chapter 2.

$$(53) \quad \llbracket \text{APRF} \rrbracket = \lambda C_{\langle i, t \rangle} . \lambda p_{\langle i, t \rangle} . \lambda t_i . \exists t' [g(C(t')) = 1 \ \& \ t' < t \ \& \ p(t') = 1]$$

In (53), the referential nature of the APRF is reflected by the temporal proform ‘C’, which denotes a contextually salient set of temporal intervals. The reference time variable t' is

²²A similar development has been observed for the German perfect and, similarly to Italian, associated with the progressive loss in spoken discourse of the competing preterite (cf. Fischer, 2018; Seiler & Weber, 2022).

²³As a consequence, the APRF has progressively occupied the semantic space of the synthetic perfect, thus determining for the latter a decrease in use among speakers.

existentially quantified and anchored to EvalT ‘t’. Being the EvalT “lexically bound”, the formula in (53) can only yield relative past readings. Clearly, this semantics can readily account for both referential and existential (indefinite) interpretations. To strengthen the resultative interpretation, one could assume that a resultative-like aspect may be optionally inserted in lieu of the perfective one.

Despite its appealing simplicity, this analysis runs into a few problems. In contradiction to our empirical findings, it predicts the availability of relative readings irrespective of the embedding predicate. Recall that relative readings in future contexts appeared to be natural only when the APRF was embedded under a present-tensed future. Crucially, as shown in (40)-(41), such interpretations are much less natural when the embedding predicate bears past-tensed morphology, for which an embedded past perfect is by far preferred.²⁴

An alternative option is to assume a transparent mapping of its morphological realization to its meaning, whereby APRF’s underlying semantic representation displays a present tense alongside some type of perfect aspect yielding anteriority. For the latter, in line with the previously discussed literature on the perfect, I will assume once more an extended now semantics, repeated below.

$$(54) \quad \llbracket \text{PERF} \rrbracket (p_{\langle i,t \rangle})(t_{\langle i \rangle}) = 1 \text{ iff } \exists t' [\text{XN}(t',t) \ \& \ p(t')] \\ \text{With XN}(t',t) \text{ the time span stretching throughout } t' \text{ and culminating in } t.$$

Recall that ‘PERF’ in (54) is a quantificational tense introducing the perfect time span (PTS), whose final subinterval t is provided by the clausal tense. For the APRF, this always coincides with t_c . Given its dominant perfective aspectual profile, PERF additionally combines with a perfective viewpoint aspect, that saturates the eventuality argument of the VP. With these tools, we can successfully compute the meaning of a matrix sentence with the APRF, as shown in (55)

$$(55) \quad \begin{aligned} & \text{a. Sara ha studiato medicina.} \\ & \quad \text{Sara study.APRF medicine} \\ & \quad \text{‘Sara studied medicine.’} \\ & \text{b. LF: } [\text{CP } w_c [\langle s,t \rangle] \lambda w [\langle i,t \rangle] \lambda t'' [\text{TP } [T_{\langle i \rangle} \text{ pres}_{2,3} t'''] [\text{AspP}_{\langle i,t \rangle} \text{ PERF } [\text{ViewP}_{\langle i,t \rangle} \\ & \quad [\text{Asp PFV}] [\langle v,t \rangle] \lambda e [\text{VP } [\text{DP Sara}] [V' \text{ studi-medicina}_{w,e}]]]]]]]]]] \\ & \text{c. } \llbracket (55\text{-b}) \rrbracket \text{ defined iff } g(2) \supseteq g(3) \ \& \ g(3) = t_c \\ & \text{d. } \llbracket (55\text{-b}) \rrbracket = 1 \text{ iff } \exists t' [\text{XN}(t',g(3)) \ \& \ \exists e [\tau(e) \subseteq t' \ \& \ \text{study}(w_c)(e)(M)(S)]] \\ & \quad \textit{Paraphrase: ‘There is a time span } t' \text{ stretching until some time containing} \\ & \quad t_c \text{ and there is an eventuality } e, \text{ such that } e \text{ is temporally included in } t', \text{ and} \\ & \quad e \text{ is an eventuality of Sara studying medicine in the actual world } w_c. \end{aligned}$$

The interpretation computed in (55-d) is compatible with an experiential reading for the sentence in (55-a).

For the time being, I will simply assume that the resultative readings arise pragmatically, as a consequence of the timespan including t_c . This view is supported by the

²⁴These choices could, of course, be driven by a pragmatic competition between the APRF and the PPRF. However, due to space constraints, I am unable to delve into the intricacies of this account here.

fact that, unlike English, resultative readings for the Italian APRF can be cancelled, as illustrated below.

- (56) a. Marica ha perso le chiavi, ma per fortuna le ha ritrovate.
 Marica lose.APRF DEF keys but for luck CL find.APRF
 ‘Marica lost her keys, but luckily she found them again.’
 b. Luca è uscito di casa stamattina, ma è tornato in tempo per il
 Luca leave.APRF of house this.morning but return.APRF in time for DEF
 pranzo.
 lunch
 ‘Luca left home this morning, but he got back in time for lunch.’

The advantage of this approach is that it can elegantly explain the relative readings in future contexts. Having assumed here that the Italian future is present-tensed, APRF-under-FUT embeddings would involve a sequence of present tense, as exemplified below.

- (57) Una volta lì, Marco noterà che mi *sono presentato* a mani vuote.
 NDEF time there Marco notice.FUT COMP REFL show.up.APRF at hands empty
 ‘Once there, Marco will notice that I showed up empty-handed.’
 a. [... [TP pres_{2,3} [FUT...note [CP ... [pres_{2,3} [PERF ...]]]]]]
 b. With t'' = matrix noticing time & t' = embedded PTS,
 t'' follows t_c & XN(t' , t'') & showing-up event e temporally included in t''

In (57), the embedded present’s features are voided upon agreement with the matrix present, as shown in (57-a). In (57-b) are sketched some simplified temporal conditions holding between the embedded reference time and the embedding predicate time. Since the time-span t' has the noticing time t'' as its final subinterval, and given that this follows t_c (due to FUT) and includes the showing-up event e (due to PFV), the latter ends up being located at some point before t'' . Clearly, nothing prevents the event e from occurring after t_c .

The lack of future relative readings when in the scope of past-tensed predicates further supports a present tense analysis, in that the present tense vacuity for the APRF-inflected predicate cannot be licensed in these configurations, as illustrated below (refer to (40) and (41) for contexts).²⁵

- (58) Luca temeva che fra qualche settimana i suoi genitori
 Luca fear.IMP COMP in some week DEF POSS parents
 avrebbero scoperto che # ha saltato/aveva saltato la scuola.
 discover.COND.PRF COMP skip.APRF/PPRF DEF school
 ‘Luca feared that in a few weeks his parents would find out that he skipped school.’
 a. [... [TP PAST [FUT... find out [CP ... [pres_{2,3} [PERF ...skip-school...]]]]]]

²⁵For formal details, see section 4.4.2. In Armenante (2024a) these distributional patterns are explained in terms of *de re/de Dicto* mismatches between the tense form and the adjoined adverbial. This view is compatible with the one taken here.

- b. $XN(t',g(2)) \ \& \ \tau(e) \subseteq t' \ \& \ g(2) \supseteq t_c \rightarrow \tau(e) < t_c.$ (with ‘e’ a school-skipping event)
- (59) La prossima settimana Marco ci dirà che il giorno prima
 DEF next week Marco CL say.FUT COMP DEF day before
 aveva rivelato al suo capo che # ha gonfiato/aveva gonfiato il valore
 reveal.PPRF to POSS boss COMP inflate.APRF/PPRF DEF value
 dell’azienda.
 of.DEF=company
 ‘Next week, Marco will tell us that the day before he revealed to his boss that
 the (had) inflated the company’s value.’
- a. [... [TP PAST [PERF... reveal [CP ... [pres_{2,3} [PERF ...inflate...]]]]]]
- b. $XN(t',g(2)) \ \& \ \tau(e) \subseteq t' \ \& \ g(2) \supseteq t_c \rightarrow \tau(e) < t_c.$ (with ‘e’ a value-inflating event)

These observations suggest that the underlying semantic derivation of relative readings for APRF-under-FUT embeddings does not stem from the semantics of the APRF only, but is sensitive to the embedding predicate’s tense. One additional prediction made by this approach is the potential availability of future perfect interpretations whenever the APRF’s present tense is semantically interpreted and the predicate refers to a situation settled at UT. This prediction seems borne out.

- (60) Context: A: Don’t be late for dinner!
- a. A: Tranquilla. Per le 5 abbiamo già finito.
 quiet by DEF 5 AUX already finish.APRF
 ‘Don’t worry! We’ll be done by 5 p.m.’
- b. A: ?? Tranquilla. Per le 5 abbiamo già vinto.
 quiet by DEF 5 AUX already win.APRF
 ‘Don’t worry! We’ll have won by 5 p.m.’

Finally, we have demonstrated that universal readings are largely unattested for the two Italian perfects, with the sole exception of cases involving the APRF in combination with universal left-boundary adverbials. Given this restriction, I will argue that a grammatical analysis, wherein special universal interpretations result from a dedicated imperfective viewpoint aspect — as is the case for the English Present Perfect or the Asante hybrid perfect *a* — is not justified. I will suggest, instead, that these special instances must be attributed to the semantics of ULBAs. These adverbs, on the one hand, quantify over the whole time-span through their universal component. On the other, they lexically require that the final subinterval be the utterance time. When ULBAs are dropped this interpretation is simply impossible to construct.²⁶

Despite its wide empirical coverage, the present-tensed perfect analysis still comes short of fully explaining APRF’s properties. For instance, it fails to convincingly account for uses that are typical of past perfectives — namely narrative progression and modification

²⁶Compositionally, in order to derive the intended reading, the ULBA would have to combine with present tense and scope over PERF. I suppose this might raise a few syntactic concerns. I leave a fully-fledged compositional analysis of these constructions for future work.

by LTAs — without resorting to special stipulations. For these reasons, I propose that the analytic perfect is semantically ambiguous between a deictic past perfective and a present-tensed perfective XN-perfect, with the former coinciding with the semantics of the SPRF, repeated below.

- (61) *Past perfective semantics for the APRF*
- a. $\llbracket \text{past}_{2,3} \rrbracket$ defined iff $\llbracket \text{past}_{2,3} \rrbracket \in D_{(i,i)} \ \& \ g(2) < g(3) \ \& \ g(3) = t_c$
 - b. $\llbracket \text{past}_{2,3} \rrbracket(g(3)) = g(2)$

While the semantics in (61) is progressively taking over, the one in (54) still persists. Reasonably, once standard Italian has reached the final stage of the perfect path, the analytic perfect will have lost the meaning components currently associated with the present-tensed XN-perfect.

4.1.3 The imperfect

The imperfect (IMP) is the most versatile tense form in Italian, as it exhibits both temporal and modal properties. I will briefly review them in the following.

(i) Temporal properties

The defining feature of the imperfect is its imperfective aspectual profile. IMP-marked predicates are characterized by unboundedness, which emerges in all its three uses: progressive, habitual and continuity (cf. Bertinetto, 1986). When in the periphrastic construal with the gerund, the IMP can only yield a progressive interpretation. These uses are illustrated in the following examples.

- (62) *Progressive (ongoing activity)*
- a. Quando Sara è tornata, Luana ripassava/stava ripassando la lezione.
when Sara return.APRF Luana review.IMP.-/PROG DEF lecture
‘When Sara returned, Luana was reviewing the lesson.’

- (63) *Habitual (iterative activity)*
- a. Un tempo Carlo leggeva/#stava leggendo i fumetti.
NDEF time Carlo read.IMP AUX.IMP.-/PROG DEF
comics
‘Carlo used to read comic books once.’

- (64) *Continuity (past state or description)*
- a. La spazzola si trovava/#stava trovando sulla mensola in bagno.
DEF brush REFL find.IMP.-/PROG on.DEF shelf in bathroom
‘The brush was on the shelf in the bathroom.’

Generally believed to be a “present in the past” (cf. Bertinetto, 1991, p. 75), the imperfect appears to share many properties with pronominal imperfective tenses, especially in its progressive and continuity uses. More specifically, it is most natural with an explic-

itly provided temporal anchor — through an adverbial or the QuD — as the following examples show.

- (65) Ieri [?](alle 5) camminavo nel parco.
 yesterday at.DEF 5 walk.IMP in.DEF park
 ‘Yesterday at 5 p.m. I was walking in the park.’ (Progressive)
- (66) # Stavi mai scalando l’Everest?
 AUX ever climb.IMP.PROG DEF=Everest
 Intended: ‘Were you ever in the process of climbing Everest?’ (Experiential)
- (67) A: What did you see when you walked past his house?
 a. B: La luce era accesa. C’era un uomo alla finestra.
 DEF light be.IMP on CL=be.IMP NDEF man at.DEF window
 ‘The light was on. There was a man standing at the window.’ (Continuity)

In (65), the sentence sounds odd if the temporal anchor ‘alle 5’ is omitted. Example (66) shows the lack of existential (experiential) readings for the imperfective, which correlates with the anaphoric interpretation in (67), where the IMP refers back to the topic time introduced by A’s sentence.

Expectedly, in contrast to the two perfects, the imperfect cannot progress narration or give rise to actuality entailments.

- (68) *Narrative progression*
 a. Alle 5 leggevo un libro. Successivamente #andavo/sono andato
 at.DEF 5 read.IMP NDEF book subsequently go.IMP/APRF
 al supermercato. Poi in serata vedevo/ho visto un film da
 to.DEF supermarket then in evening see.IMP/APRF NDEF film at
 Giulio.
 Giulio
 Intended: ‘At 5 p.m. I was reading a book. Subsequently, I went to the grocery store. Then, in the evening, I watched a film with Giulio.’
- (69) *Actuality entailments*
 a. Sara era in grado di risolvere il problema, ma non l’ha fatto.
 Sara be.IMP able to solve DEF problem but NEG CL=do.APRF
 ‘Sara was able to solve the problem, but she did not.’

Importantly, unlike the two perfects, the imperfect can yield relative readings. These do not seem to be restricted by the embedding predicate’s tense form.

- (70) Context: Marco is planning to skip his math exam tomorrow. The next day, he’ll justify his absence with an excuse.
 a. Dopodomani Marco dirà all’insegnante che il giorno
 the.day.after.tomorrow Marco say.FUT to.DEF=teacher COMP DEF day
 prima aveva la febbre.
 before have.IMP DEF fever
 ‘The day after tomorrow Marco will tell the teacher that he had a fever the

day before.’

Following this brief empirical discussion, I suggest that temporal uses of the IMP point to an analysis involving a pronominal past tense combined with an imperfective aspect, as given in (71).

- (71) a. $\text{IMP}_{\text{temporal}}$: $[\text{TP past}_{2,3} [\text{AspP IPFV}]]$
 b. $[[\text{imp}_{2,3}]]$ defined iff $[[\text{imp}_{2,3}]] \in D_{\langle i,i \rangle}$ & $g(2) < g(3)$
 c. $[[\text{imp}_{2,3}]](g(3)) = g(2)$
 d. $[[\text{IPFV}]] = \lambda p_{\langle v,t \rangle} . \lambda t_{\langle i \rangle} . \exists e [t \subseteq \tau(e) \ \& \ p(e)]$

Following (71), the imperfect appears as the past-oriented counterpart of the present. The semantics of its tense component varies only minimally compared to that of the SPRF, with the IMP lacking the same indexical restriction. It follows that the second index ‘3’ is locally bound, thus tracking the evaluation time, which need not be the utterance time. This, in turn, generates relative temporal readings. For illustrative purposes, in (72) are computed the truth-conditions of a matrix clause containing the imperfect.²⁷

- (72) a. Alle 5 Marco leggeva.
 at.DEF 5 Marco read.IMP
 ‘Marco was reading at 5 p.m.’
 b. LF: $[\text{CP } w_c [\langle s,t \rangle] \lambda w [t_c [\langle i,t \rangle] \lambda t_3 [\text{TP}_{\langle t \rangle} \text{imp}_{2,3} [\text{AspP}_{\langle i,t \rangle} \text{IPFV} [\langle v,t \rangle] \lambda e [\text{VP} [\text{DP Marco}] [\text{V}' \text{legge-}_{w,e}]]]] [\text{PP}_{\langle i,t \rangle} \text{alle } 5]]]]]]$
 c. $[[\text{(72-b)}]]$ defined iff $g(2) < t_c$
 d. $[[\text{(72-b)}]] = 1$ iff $\exists e [g(2) \subseteq \tau(e) \ \& \ g(2) \subseteq \{t: t \supseteq 5 \text{ p.m.}\} \ \& \ \text{read}(w_c)(e)(M)]$
Paraphrase: ‘There is an eventuality e , such that e temporally includes $g(2)$ preceding the utterance time t_c , and $g(2)$ is included in a temporal interval surrounding 5 p.m. and e is an eventuality of Marco reading in the actual world.’

(ii) Modal properties

The modal properties of the imperfect in Italian (and more generally in Romance languages) have garnered significant attention in the literature (Arregui et al., 2014; Bazzanella, 1990; Bertinetto, 1986, 1991; Dessì Schmid, 2010; Ippolito, 2004). Here, I will briefly outline some of the imperfect’s uses that have been categorized as modal.²⁸

- (73) *Oneiric IMP*
 Sai cos’ho sognato la scorsa notte? Ero con Whitney Houston e duettavamo sul palco di Sanremo!
 You know what I dreamed last night? I be.IMP with Whitney Houston and we duet.IMP on Sanremo’s stage!

- (74) *Hypothetical IMP*

²⁷I am assuming that the temporal adverbial ‘alle 5’ denotes a set of times and is adjoined to AspP, thus composing via predicate modification.

²⁸The terminology adopted is faithful for the most part to the one adopted in Bazzanella (1990). Examples are variously adapted from Bazzanella (1990) and Bertinetto (1986).

- a. Per fortuna sei rimasto a casa, se no ti prendevi un raffreddore!
Good think you stayed home, or you catch.IMP a cold!
- b. A: Sai che sono stato a cena con Del Piero ieri?
B: Sì, certo. E poi c'era la marmotta che confezionava la cioccolata!²⁹
A: You know I had dinner with Del Piero last night?
B: Sure thing. And then there be.IMP the groundhog that package.IMP chocolate!
- c. Se lo sapevo, te lo dicevo!
If I know.IMP it, I say.IMP it. ('If I had known it, I would have told you.')

(75) *Politeness IMP*

- a. A: Desiderava?
B: Volevo del pane.
A: Did you desire.IMP something?
B: I want.IMP some bread.
- b. Venivo a chiederti un favore.
I come.IMP to ask for a favour.

(76) *Potential*

Marica doveva essere già qui. Deve essere successo qualcosa.
Marica must.IMP be already here. Something must have happened. ('Marica should have been here by now...')

(77) *Epistemic-Doxastic*

Cosa c'era domani al cinema?
What be.IMP tomorrow at the movies?

(78) *Planning*

A: Mi dai una mano col trasloco domani?
B: Domani avevo karate.
A: Will you help me with moving tomorrow?
B: Tomorrow I have.IMP karate. ('Tomorrow I was supposed to go to my karate lesson')

What all these uses have in common is their depiction of a situation displaced from the actual world. On this matter, Bazzanella argues that the imperfective morphology in these cases primarily serves as an irrealis marker. Additionally, she claims that in its oneiric, potential, and hypothetical uses, the imperfect retains a past orientation, requiring the reference time to be in the past. However, this is not necessarily the case.³⁰ For example, the oneiric scenario set up in (73) is entirely atemporal; for all we know, the performance on Sanremo's stage could have taken place next year.³¹ Similar considerations can be extended to the hypothetical use of the imperfect, which is predominantly found in con-

²⁹Taken from a famous commercial from the 90s.

³⁰See also the discussion in Ippolito (2004).

³¹A future-oriented modifier does not alter the acceptability of the sentence.

ditionals,³² and, to a lesser degree, to the potential.³³ The epistemic-doxastic imperfect (in (77)) and the planning one (in (78)) involve a (past) schedule or plan in relation to a situation yet to occur. In this respect, they are reminiscent of the epistemic use of the futurate present we have previously discussed, with the IMP's past tense locating the source of information the speaker's belief is based on: in (77), that is when the speaker looked at the movie schedule; in (78), that is a past time when the speaker had made plans for the next day and these seemed still feasible.

The last point leads us to Ippolito (2004)'s proposal, where these uses have been unified under a modal analysis. On her view, the IMP's past restricts an epistemic accessibility relation. The latter is built into the semantics of the 'modal imperfect'. Universal quantification arises by default. Crucially, the IMP's past tense is interpreted temporally, as it refers to a contextually salient past time where the speaker had access to the source of information. For clarity, I will refer to this variable as 'epistemic tense'. Ippolito's analysis is sketched below.

- (79) *The semantics of the modal imperfect* (to be revised) (after Ippolito, 2004, p. 363)
- $$\llbracket [\text{CP} \dots \text{T.IMP } t_2 \dots [\text{VP} \dots \text{p} \dots]] \rrbracket = 1 \text{ iff}$$
- $$\forall w' \in f_{\text{epistemic}}(\text{sp}, w, g(2): g(2) < t_c) \rightarrow p(w')$$
- Paraphrase:* 'In all possible worlds w' compatible with what the speaker knows in w at $g(2)$, such that $g(2)$ precedes t_c , p is true in w' '

In (79), the IMP introduces into the composition an epistemic accessibility relation and its restrictor, that is the variable t_2 , denoting the epistemic tense. The latter picks out a contextually salient time that precedes the utterance time. Note that this analysis remains neutral regarding the temporal interpretation of the proposition p . In Ippolito's system, the VP is only evaluated with respect to a possible world, while the temporal orientation is kept underspecified and is only fixed by an overt temporal adverb. This raises an obvious problem: how can a temporal adverbial compose with a predicate that is not time-dependent in the first place?³⁴ In Ippolito's system, the only tense variable that can be targeted by a temporal adverbial is ' t_2 '. This however leads to nonsensical interpretations, as illustrated below.

- (80) Domani avevo karate
tomorrow have.IMP karate
'Tomorrow I was supposed to go to my karate lesson.'
- a. $\rightsquigarrow w' \in f_{\text{epistemic}}(\text{sp}, w_c, g(2): g(2) < t_c) \ \& \ \text{karate in } w' \text{ at } t \subseteq \textit{tomorrow}$

³²The literature usually distinguishes between a hypothetical use, which only involves counterfactual conditionals, as in (74-c), and a 'fantasy' use, which is reflected by (74-a)-(74-b). Given their similar distribution, they have been grouped together here.

³³Consider the following future-oriented IMP-marked conditional:

- (i) Se la Juve giocava domani, riuscivo a vederla.
if DEF Juve play.IMP tomorrow manage.IMP to see.CL
'If Juve had been playing tomorrow, I could have watched it.'

³⁴I am excluding here the possibility that non-quantificational adverbials such as 'tomorrow' or 'yesterday' may denote complex functions taking a whole proposition as their argument.

- b. $\not\rightarrow w' \in f_{epistemic}(sp, w_c, g(2): g(2) < t_c \ \& \ g(2) \subseteq tomorrow) \ \& \text{karate in } w'$
at t

In (80), the only attested interpretation is the one sketched in (80-a). However, with Ippolito's semantics of the modal imperfect only (80-b) can be derived.

Therefore, I will suggest that the modal imperfect introduces an additional tense variable that saturates the temporal argument of the main predicate. Once again, this is a free variable, the value of which is contextually determined and further constrained by an overt adverbial. I will refer to this second tense variable as 'reference tense'. As a further amendment to (79), I will also assume that both the accessibility relation and universal quantification are lexicalized in the modal imperfect. Its modal base is epistemic (more on this in section 4.5.2).

Aspectually, in comparison to the temporal imperfect, the modal imperfect appears to be underspecified to the extent that the resulting interpretation seems perfective in most instances. This is shown in (81), where a planning imperfect is incompatible with the progressive construal. Ippolito observes that, while interpreted temporally, the modal imperfect is not interpreted aspectually. While I do agree that many of the uses reviewed here seem to lend themselves to a perfective-like interpretation, I argue that her characterization is too strong. Imperfective (progressive) interpretations are possible in some cases, as illustrated by the oneiric imperfect in (82).³⁵

- (81) Domani al cinema davano/#stavano dando Interstellar.
tomorrow at.DEF movie.theater give.IMP-/PROG Interstellar
'Interstellar was playing in theaters tomorrow.'

- (82) Sai cos'ho sognato la scorsa notte? Ero sul palco con Whitney Houston. Stavamo
cantando una canzone quando all'improvviso è andata via la corrente.
'You know what I dreamed last night? I be.IMP with Whitney Houston on the
stage. We sing.IMP.PROG a song when all of a sudden the power went out.'

In the following, I am going to assume that the modal imperfect is aspectually indefinite. Since plans or schedules are viewed as a whole, the default option is the perfective aspect. However, in more narrative uses, an imperfective (progressive) aspect can surface as well.

To summarize, a modal imperfect contributes: (i) a modal quantifying over all possible worlds that are epistemically accessible from a world and a time of evaluation (see (83-a)) ; (ii) an epistemic tense that supplies the evaluation time for (i)³⁶; (iii) an additional tense pronoun (the reference tense) supplying the reference time for the sentence's proposition; (iv) a(n) (im)perfective aspect. The resulting semantic representation is schematically

³⁵Bertinetto (1986, p. 391) observes that among all the modal uses, only the hypothetical is aspectually neutral. All the others maintain an imperfective core. Furthermore, he demonstrates that the temporal imperfect too may exhibit a perfective aspectual profile in some instances.

³⁶This formal rendition differs from Ippolito's in one important way: the epistemic tense variable *imp* is not relativized to the utterance time. It is unclear whether the modal tense is purely indexical or shiftable, as judgments get very subtle when it comes to relative readings. Consider the following example:

- (i) Context: Gianni is planning to visit on the Easter weekend, but he hasn't bought tickets yet. You fear that they might be very expensive and that once he finds out, he'll decide to book for the next weekend instead.

depicted as follows:

- (83) *Modal IMP*: $[_{\text{TopP}} [\square_{w_1} \text{imp}_{2,3}] [_{\text{TP}} \lambda w_0 [_{T'} t_5 [_{\text{AspP}} \text{PFV}(/IPFV)]]]]$
 a. $\llbracket \square \rrbracket = \lambda w_{\langle s \rangle} . \lambda t_{\langle i \rangle} . \lambda x_{\langle e \rangle} . \lambda p_{\langle s, t \rangle} . \forall w' [w' \in f_{\text{epistemic}}(x, w, t) \rightarrow p(w')]$

With these semantic tools in place, we are able to compute the truth-conditions for a sentence containing a modal imperfect, as shown in (84).

- (84) Context: A made plans earlier today to attend a Karate class tomorrow morning. But B just asked A to help B with moving.

a. Domani avevo karate. ('Tomorrow I was supposed to do karate')

b.

c. $\llbracket (84\text{-b}) \rrbracket$ defined iff $g(2) < t_c$.

d. When defined, $\llbracket (84\text{-b}) \rrbracket = 1$ iff

-
- a. ?Una volta scoperto il prezzo, Gianni dirà che veniva il fine settimana successivo.
 week following
 lit. 'Once he finds out the price, he will say that he was coming the next weekend.'

The slight oddness of the sentence may stem from the fact that the speaker's source of information (namely, Gianni checking the ticket prices) is only accessible after the time of the utterance. This aspect warrants further investigation in future research.

$\forall w'[w' \in \mathfrak{f}_{epistemic}(sp, w_c, g(2)) \rightarrow \exists e[\tau(e) \subseteq g(5) \ \& \ g(5) \subseteq \text{tomorrow} \ \& \ \text{do-karate}(w')(e)(g(8))]]$ $g(8) = sp = \text{speaker}$

Paraphrase: in all the worlds w' compatible with what the speaker knows in w_c at $g(2)$ preceding t_c , there is an eventuality e , such that e is temporally included in $g(5)$, which lies within tomorrow, and e is an eventuality of the speaker doing karate in w' .

According to the truth-conditions in (84-d), given what the speaker knows at some earlier time $g(2)$ — that is, when she made plans for the next day — the karate activity occurs at some time tomorrow. Following this analysis, the IMP preserves its past temporal meaning despite the eventuality being located at a future time. We will see in section 4.5 COMP the modal imperfect’s versatile semantics allows us to derive the simultaneous interpretation of IMP-under-perfect embeddings without any further stipulations.

Having looked at the semantic contribution of the modal imperfect, let me conclude this section elaborating on its pragmatic function.

The fact that modal readings of the imperfect involve access to a past source of information often produces a particular pragmatic inference, which can be informally characterized as follows:

- (85) *Pragmatic inference of IMP-marked propositions* (after Ippolito, 2004, p. 365)
 Given a proposition p , if the speakers decides to utter IMP(p) instead of PRES(p), it follows that the speaker has only access to knowledge regarding p at a time $t < t_c$. Therefore, the speaker cannot fully endorse p at t_c .

The inference in (85) can be viewed as a conversational implicature resulting from Grice’s maxim of quantity.³⁷ Applying (85) to a doxtastic-epistemic scenario as in (86), we correctly derive its pragmatic inference.

- (86) a. Context: A and B want to watch a movie at the local theater today. A doesn’t know the schedule, B only checked it yesterday, but doesn’t know if anything changed in the meanwhile. A: ‘What movies are on at the Palladio? today’
 b. Oggi davano *Interstellar*.
 today play.IMP *Interstellar*
 ‘Today they were playing *Interstellar*.’
 c. Paraphrase: ‘Based on the program the speaker checked yesterday, the theater is screening *Interstellar* today.’
 d. \rightsquigarrow the speaker is not sure they’re screening *Interstellar* today.

In (86), B only has access to a past source of information, that is the last time she checked the program. Since A’s question inquires about the schedule at present time, the most informative answer would be present-tensed. The use of the imperfective past instead signals that the speaker is not in a position to utter the alternative *Oggi danno *Interstellar** (‘Today they’re screening *Interstellar*’), thus generating the implicature in

³⁷From Grice (1975, p. 45): ‘Make your contribution as informative as is required (for the current purposes of the exchange). Do not make your contribution more informative than is required.’

(86-d). Note that, if B was updated on today’s schedule, having checked it briefly before A’s question, her answer in (86) would be infelicitous, since it would violate the maxim of quantity. Similar considerations can be extended to the other modal uses discussed in this section. For instance, the imperfect of planning in (78), repeated below, refers once more to a previous time where the speaker formulated a plan.

- (87) a. A: Will you help me with moving tomorrow?
 b. B: Domani avevo karate.
 Tomorrow have.IMP karate.
 ‘Tomorrow I was supposed to go to my karate lesson.’
 c. Paraphrase: ‘Based on the plan the speaker made at some time before A’s question, the speaker is attending a karate lesson tomorrow.’
 d. \rightsquigarrow the speaker is no longer sure she’s doing karate tomorrow.

In (87), B’s decision to use the imperfect instead of the more informative (epistemic) present signals that her plan is no longer firm at UT.

Having introduced the semantics of the present-tensed forms, present and future, as well as the three past-tensed forms, the imperfect, the synthetic perfect and the analytic perfect, we move now to the investigation of temporal phenomena in attitude contexts.

4.2 Present-tensed embeddings: DAR, mood and aspect competition

In this section, we zoom in onto the present tense in attitude reports, specifically focusing on the double access reading (DAR) associated with present-under-perfect embeddings. These constructions represent a particularly intriguing research topic in Italian, since their interpretation is reined in by tense-external factors, such as mood competition and pragmatic reasoning.

In the previous section, we have demonstrated that the Italian present tense is an indexical tense, in that it appears to strictly refer to the utterance time. As shown earlier, this becomes more evident in contexts where DAR correlates with an implausible interpretation:

- (88) Due anni fa Gianni ha rivelato che Sara #è/era incinta.
 two years ago Gianni reveal.APRF COMP Sara be.PRES/Imp pregnant
 lit. ‘Two years ago Gianni revealed that Sara is/was pregnant.’

In (88), the use of present tense morphology is ruled out, thus suggesting that the fact that the embedded state extends until the utterance time is part of the asserted meaning of the sentence and not a pragmatic inference. Against this backdrop, an underexplored research area in formal semantics pertains to the contribution of mood and aspect to DAR.

- (89) (i) *Pres-under-perf embeddings*:³⁸

³⁸In the vast majority of cases, I will indicate mood in the glosses when it becomes relevant for the

- a. Gianni ha giurato che Maria è innocente.
Gianni swear.APRF COMP Maria be.PRES.IND innocent
'Gianni swore that Maria is innocent.'
- b. Gianni ha giurato che Maria sia innocente.
Gianni swear.APRF COMP Maria be.PRES.SUBJ innocent
'Gianni swore that Maria is innocent.'

In (89), the embedded clause allows for either mood. It is important to note that the resulting temporal interpretation is a DAR in both cases.³⁹ However, in certain contexts, the subjunctive mood is ruled out:

(90) (ii) *Pres-under-perf embeddings:*

- a. Chidi ha sostenuto che Janet e Jason sono/siano innamorati.
Chidi claim.APRF that Janet and Jason be.PRES.IND/SUBJ in.love
'Chidi claimed that Janet and Jason are in love.'
- b. Ho sostenuto che Janet e Jason sono/#siano innamorati.
claim.APRF.1SG that Janet and Jason be.PRES.IND/SUBJ in.love
'I've claimed that Janet and Jason are in love.'

While in (90-a), the speaker can report the attitude holder's claim using either the indicative or the subjunctive, mood choice is restricted to the indicative in (90-b) where the speaker and the attitude holder are co-referential. A further parameter of variation is illustrated below (cf. Giorgi, 2006, p. 110), with the past-oriented verb *ipotizzare* (to hypothesize) blocking a DAR-construal when used in the imperfective aspect:

(91) *Perfective vs Imperfective attitude verbs:*

- a. Anna ha ipotizzato che Will sia sposato.
Anna hypothesize.APRF COMP Will be.PRES.SUBJ married
'Anna hypothesized that William is married.'
- b. ??Anna ipotizzava che Will sia sposato.
Anna hypothesize.IMP COMP Will be.PRES.SUBJ married
Intended: 'Anna hypothesized that William is married.'
- c. Anna ipotizzava che Will fosse sposato.
Anna hypothesize.IMP COMP Will be.IMP.SUBJ married
'Anna hypothesized that William was married.'

In (91), the propositional attitude verb 'ipotizzare' can embed a present-tensed (subjunctive) predicate, thus yielding a DAR, as long as its viewpoint is perfective ('ha ipotizzato'). If imperfective ((91-b)-(91-c)), the same verb only allows a tense-agreeing form in the complement clause, thus yielding a (past) simultaneous interpretation only.

discussion. Unless otherwise specified, verbs that are unglossed for mood bear indicative mood.

³⁹It is worth mentioning that mood alternation in attitude reports obtains only with a subset of verbs. For example, factive verbs in Italian, such as *sapere* (to know), trigger indicative mood and are not compatible with subjunctive (at least in affirmative declarative clauses). By contrast, verbs of (dis-)belief, such as *credere* (to think), *dubitare* (to doubt), etc., select almost obligatorily subjunctive mood. Unless otherwise specified, the examples reported in this paper will contain only verbs that can occur with both moods in the scope of an attitude verb.

To sum up, we have seen that languages vary based on whether present tense is relativized to a local evaluation time (the attitude time in attitude reports) or to the utterance time. We have seen that this makes important predictions regarding the interpretation of present-tensed complement clauses in the scope of past-tensed attitude verbs. More specifically, Romance languages such as Italian usually exhibit a double access temporal interpretation, which seems to be constrained by the embedded verb's mood and the embedding verb's lexical aspect. In what follows I will suggest that mood and (viewpoint and lexical) aspect affect DAR in ways that are systematic and predicted by a semantic-pragmatically informed theory. In the next section we will see how these facts are handled by Giorgi (2010a)'s morpho-syntactic analysis, pointing to some of its shortcomings.

4.2.1 Background: Giorgi's theory and its short-comings

As we have seen in chapter 2, most formal approaches to present-under-past attitude reports in languages with an indexical present have involved a temporal *de re* analysis of the present tense. In doing so, these accounts attribute the possibility of a double access reading to the requirements placed on the embedded predicate by the present tense's indexical nature in conjunction with Abusch (1988)'s Upper Limit Constraint (which specifies that the predicate should not extend beyond the attitude time, AT). I will defer the detailed explanation of such a theory to the next section, where a possible implementation for Italian will be presented. For now, it is sufficient to note that semantic theories have mostly overlooked the role of mood in double access constructions. Therefore, in this section, I will concentrate on Giorgi (2010a)'s analysis of present-under-past attitude reports, which provides a clear elucidation of the interaction between the mood of the embedded clause and its temporal interpretation.

Giorgi's syntactic account

The theory laid out in Giorgi (2010a, 2010b) and Giorgi & Pianesi (2004) presents a syntactic account of double access readings in Italian that hinges on the mood of the embedded predicate. Contrary to the tenets of formal semantic theories, which associate DAR with the present tense of the embedded verb, Giorgi's account suggests that it is the indicative mood that licenses a double access interpretation. In other words, a DAR occurs in attitude reports whenever the verb in the complement clause, regardless of its tense, is marked with the indicative mood. According to this perspective, all indicative embeddings result in some form of double access, although it may be more or less apparent at first glance. This point is illustrated below:

(92) *X-under-perf embeddings:*

- a. Marco ha detto che Giorgia gioca in cortile.
 Marco say.APRF COMP Giorgia play.PRES.IND in yard
 'Marco said that Giorgia is playing in the yard.'
 \rightsquigarrow G plays at t overlapping AT & UT
- b. Marco ha detto che Giorgia ha giocato in cortile.
 Marco say.APRF that Giorgia play.APRF.IND in yard

- ‘Marco said that Giorgia played in the yard.’
 \rightsquigarrow G plays at t before AT & UT
- c. Marco ha detto che Giorgia giocherà in cortile.
 Marco say.APRF COMP Giorgia play.FUT.IND in yard
 ‘Marco said that Giorgia will play in the yard.’
 \rightsquigarrow G plays at t after AT & UT

It is clear by now why the present-under-past sentence in (92-a) involves a double access interpretation. Future-under-past embeddings such as (92-c) also correlate with DAR, in that Giorgia’s playing time must strictly follow the utterance time as well as the attitude time⁴⁰ (that is, when Marco spoke). The same is true of past-tensed embeddings, as in (92-b), though in a less obvious way, being AT necessarily located before UT in past contexts. We will come back to this point later when past-in-the-future sentences will be addressed.⁴¹

Relating DAR facts to mood choice illustrates Giorgi’s analysis only indirectly. A more faithful rendition of her theory goes as follows:

- (93) *Giorgi’s theory of double access.:*
- a. indicative and subjunctive clauses are introduced by dedicated complementizers, that for simplicity I will call C^{Ind} and C^{Subj} .
 - b. Indicative tense forms are relational and always evaluated with respect to the local evaluation time (EvalT), whereas subjunctive forms are tenseless.
 - c. The speaker’s now (that is UT) projects syntactically above C and always occurs with C^{Ind} , but need not with C^{Subj} .

Evidence for a tight syntactic link between complementizer and mood comes from a phenomenon dubbed complementizer deletion (C-deletion), that is the omission of the complementizer ‘che’ in Italian complement clauses. Giorgi suggests that C-deletion can only (optionally) target subjunctive clauses, whereas indicative ones only correlate with an overt complementizer in Italian⁴²:

- (94) *C-deletion in embedded clauses* (after Giorgi & Pianesi, 2004, p. 191)
- a. Mario credeva (che) partisse ieri.
 Mario think.PRES COMP leave.IMP.SUBJ yesterday
 ‘Mario thought he/she was leaving yesterday.’
 - b. Mario ha detto #(che) è partito ieri.
 Mario think.PRES COMP leave.APRF.IND yesterday
 ‘Mario thought he/she left yesterday.’

⁴⁰For a future-in-the-past interpretation, whereby Giorgia’s playing time follows the attitude time (but not necessarily the utterance time), a past conditional should be used instead.

⁴¹Leaving aside X-under-present embeddings, where AT=UT and DAR trivially holds, Giorgi also shows that a DAR obtains in future embeddings such as future-under-future sentences: *Marco dirà che Giorgia giocherà nel cortile* (‘Marco will say that Giorgia will play in the yard’). These sentences also require that the embedded event be located at some time following both AT and UT (Giorgia could not possibly play at some time between now and Marco’s statement).

⁴²Despite agreeing with Giorgi & Pianesi’s judgments for (94), I will later argue that the observed correlation is less robust than assumed and does not involve any causation.

Let's now show how (93) correctly captures some of the data. It follows from (93-a) that indicative embedded clauses undergo a double temporal evaluation, in that the predicate is always relativized to EvalT (being indicative tenses relational) and to UT (since C^{Ind} bears the speaker's now), thus yielding a double access reading. By contrast, subjunctive embedded clauses will be co-evaluated with the matrix clause, as subjunctive tenses as well as subjunctive complementizers (C^{Subj}) do not, usually, introduce temporal referents of their own. Dispensing with technical details on the syntactic derivation, we can sketch the resulting structures as follows:

- (95) a. *Indicative embedded clauses in attitude contexts:*
 [matrix ... [V say_{AT} ... [CP ... C^{Ind} UT [... T_{AT} ... [VP p]]]]]
 b. *Subjunctive embedded clauses in attitude contexts:*
 [matrix ... [V say_{AT,iTns}... [CP ... C^{Subj} \emptyset_{iMood} [... $T_{uMood,uTns}$... [VP p]]]]]

In (95-a), the embedded predicate 'p' is evaluated twice, with respect to UT and a EvalT (=AT via binding or co-reference with the time introduced by the matrix). In (95-b), however, the embedded T does not surface with any interpretable features but only contributes morphological agreement with mood and tense specifications c-commanding it (in the null complementizer and the matrix attitude verb, respectively). Given the absence of UT in C^{Subj} , the embedded predicate's temporal variable can only be saturated by AT in the matrix, bringing about a relative interpretation. One important prediction of (95-b) is that, given the licensing condition imposed on subjunctive tense forms in the scope of attitude verbs, only agreeing constellations are possible. This in turn rules out present-under-past as well as past-under-present attitude reports (when the embedded predicate is marked with subjunctive). This for instance would explain the oddness of (91-b) repeated below, with the $uPres$ -feature on the embedded tense unchecked and thus causing the derivation to crash:

- (96) a. ??Anna ipotizzava che Will sia sposato.
 Anna hypothesize.IMP COMP Will be.PRES.SUBJ married
 b. [PAST Anna ... [V hypothesize_{k,iPast} [CP C^{Subj} \emptyset_{iSubj} [... $T_{uSubj,uPres}$... [VP W-married]]]]]

Indicative embeddings, on the other hand, readily generate DAR:

- (97) a. Gianni ha giurato che Maria è innocente.
 Gianni swear.APRF COMP Maria be.PRES.IND innocent
 b. [PAST Gianni ... [V swear t_k ... [CP ... C^{Ind}_{UT} [T t_k [M-innocent]]]]]
 c. M-innocent at g(k) & UT (with g(k) the time Gianni swore.)⁴³
 with g a context-dependent function assigning the relevant referent to the variable t_k .

We have seen, however, that DAR is not restricted to indicative embedded clauses, in

⁴³Formulating Giorgi's syntactic analysis in compositional terms is far from trivial, at least within a Heim & Kratzer (1998)'s framework. For this reason, for the time being, I will simply assume a non-compositional derivation whereby the temporal variable of the embedded predicate *innocent* is exceptionally saturated twice, hence giving rise to a temporal interval stretching from g(k) to UT.

that subjunctive present may scope below a past-tensed attitude verb yielding the same extended temporal interpretation. Giorgi argues that verbs of communication may exceptionally project UT in C even if subjunctive in mood:

- (98) a. Gianni ha giurato che Maria sia innocente.
 Gianni swear.APRF COMP Maria be.PRES.SUBJ innocent
 b. [matrix ... [_V swear_{AT,iTense}... [CP ... C^{Subj}_{UT,iMood} [...T_{uSubj,uPres}... [VP
 M-innocent]]]]]
 c. M-innocent at AT & UT.

Compared to the indicative embedded clause in (97), (98) brings about the same temporal interpretation but through a slightly different derivation, since subjunctive tenses are not relational and thus are not relativized to a local evaluation time⁴⁴. Crucially, according to Giorgi, the complementizer ‘che’ in (97-a) cannot be deleted, suggesting that the overt complementizer ‘che’ does not pattern with the covert one, in that it always projects UT, no matter the clausal mood.⁴⁵

One obvious question, however, (98) raises is: what are the conditions under which subjunctive embedded clauses yield DAR? Is there a special class of verbs systematically allowing double access interpretations and, if so, how can we characterize them in a more precise vein? In what follows, we will address these questions, pointing to some key issues Giorgi’s syntactic theory faces.

Issues with Giorgi’s theory

At first sight, Giorgi (2010a) offers an elegant solution to the DAR puzzle, with only basic assumptions on the syntax of mood and complementizer in clauses embedded under attitude verbs. Upon closer inspection, however, Giorgi’s account leaves many open issues that aren’t satisfactorily addressed in her work. I will discuss some of them here.

(i) No systematic account for DAR with subjunctive forms

As pointed out before, DAR is not strictly ruled out for subjunctive forms. In fact, it is readily available in many contexts, yet restricted when compared to indicative forms. In this regard, no principled explanation of this contrast is provided, as Giorgi merely refers to a special class of verbs of “communication” that allow for DAR with subjunctive mood as well. Note that, to account for the contrast in (91), Giorgi needs to assume lexical ambiguity, for which only ‘ipotizzare’ in (99-a) is a DAR-compatible verb. It is noteworthy stressing that ‘ipotizzare’ is far from an isolated case.⁴⁶ In fact, many attitude verbs follow the same pattern, in that they function as DAR-blockers when their viewpoint aspect is

⁴⁴A second temporal point of access is then directly realized on V. This might sound somewhat stipulative but doesn’t ultimately bear on the discussion laid out here.

⁴⁵According to my own judgment, *Gianni ha giurato Maria sia.PRES.SUBJ innocente*, where the complementizer has dropped, is far from unacceptable and not much degraded compared to the non-DAR counterpart *Gianni ha giurato Maria fosse.IMP.SUBJ innocente*.

⁴⁶For reasons of space, I will not provide more examples. However, I will direct the reader to the following pairs: *riteneva/ha ritenuto* (to think), *sosteneva/ha sostenuto* (to claim), *supponeva/ha supposto*, *immaginava/ha immaginato*, etc., where DAR becomes much more degraded with the imperfective form compared to the perfective second form of the pair.

imperfective rather than perfective.⁴⁷

(99) *Perfective vs Imperfective attitude verbs:*

- a. Anna ha ipotizzato che Will sia sposato.
 Anna hypothesize.APRF COMP Will be.PRES.SUBJ married
 ‘Anna hypothesized that William is married.’
- b. ??Anna ipotizzava che Will sia sposato.
 Anna hypothesize.IMP COMP Will be.PRES.SUBJ married
 Intended: ‘Anna hypothesized that William is married.’

(ii) *Rules out attested non-agreeing configurations under subjunctive*

On Giorgi’s proposal sketched here, subjunctive tense forms are expected to be licensed by a *c*-commanding attitude verb matching in tense features, such that only present-under-present and past-under-past configurations are allowed. As we have seen, however, present subjunctive-under-past embeddings are attested. As a rescue strategy, Giorgi contends that these configurations involve agreement not between the two clausal tenses but between the embedded tense and the embedding complementizer, such that present morphology is licensed by UT in C^{Subj} . One downside of this argument is that it is purely stipulative and as such has no predictive power: UT projects in C^{Subj} only if DAR holds, which in turn only ensues if a present tense can be embedded under an attitude verb. But since present tense must be licensed by UT in *C*, there is no escaping the logical loop. In addition, non-agreeing embeddings are likewise observed for subjunctive past, with the expected interpretation of temporal anteriority:

- (100) Marica è convinto che quella di Andrea fosse solo una
 Marica be.PRES confident COMP DEM of Andrea be.IMP.SUBJ only NDEF
 scusa.
 excuse.
 Marica is convinced that Gianni’s excuse was a mere pretext.’
- (101) Il medico ritiene che il paziente fosse depresso da
 DEF doctor believe.PRES COMP DEF patient be.IMP.SUBJ depressed for
 tempo.
 time
 ‘The doctor believes that the patient had been depressed for some time.’

One possible analysis entertained by Giorgi is to assume that topicalized sentence adverbials introduce referents that might license tense morphology in the embedded clause, akin to UT-present agreement for present-under-past:

- (102) a. Gianni crede che Marco fosse assente alla festa.
 Gianni think.PRES COMP Marco be.IMP.SUBJ at._(DEF,t) party
 ‘Gianni thinks that Marco was absent at the party.’
- b. [_{CP} G. crede_{iPres} [_{TopP} alla festa_{iPast} che [_{VP} M. fosse_{uPast} assente]]]

⁴⁷One important point to note relating to present-under-imperfective past such as (99-b) is that this type of construction seems degraded irrespective of mood, especially if present modifies a stage level predicate. We will come back to this later.

Note that, as (100)-(101) show, overt adverbials, albeit increasing out-of-the-blue sentence acceptability, are far from obligatory. Furthermore, extending the list of licensors to adverbials runs into all sorts of issues, as shown below.

(iii) *Rules in unattested agreeing configurations under subjunctive*

For reasons such as those outlined in (ii), this morpho-syntactic account can equally generate unattested readings for agreeing embeddings. Giorgi shows this is a desirable outcome for past-under-past sentences, as shown below:

- (103) *Past subj-under-past attitude verbs* (slightly adapted from Giorgi, 2006, p. 106)
- a. Fino a stamattina Gianni credeva che Maria partisse
 until this.morning Gianni think.IMP COMP Maria leave.IMP.SUBJ
 ieri/oggi/domani.
 yesterday/today/tomorrow
 ‘Up until this morning, Gianni believed that Maria was leaving yesterday/today/tomorrow.’

In (103-a), the embedded eventuality can be evaluated with respect to a time that precedes or follows the believing time in the matrix. This follows from (93-b), in that subjunctive forms are not relational and only contribute morphological agreement. One potential problem posed by this view is that it contradicts the stipulation discussed in (ii): if adverbials such as *yesterday*, *today* or *tomorrow* are regarded as tense licensors, then the subjunctive imperfect ‘partisse’ can hardly feature in the scope of the future adverbial tomorrow. One way of overcoming this issue is to assume that agreement in this case need not obey locality constraints, being the matrix verb ‘credeva’ a suitable licensor. As is apparent, this hack causes more problems than it fixes, since it disentangles licensing from binding⁴⁸. Consider the following sentence:

- (104) Sara ha detto che Gianni ritiene che Luca fosse all'estero.
 Sara say.APRF COMP Gianni believe.PRES COMP Luca be.IMP.SUBJ
 ‘Sara said that Gianni believes that Luca was abroad.’

If ‘fosse’ in (104) were to be licensed by the matrix past-tensed verb, a simultaneous interpretation should be possible, such that Luca is abroad at Gianni’s thinking time. This reading is however not attested. Similar considerations hold for present-under-present embeddings such as (105) below. Here, however, temporal interpretations other than simultaneity (only for statives) or posteriority are not attested.

- (105) a. Gianni crede che Maria parta domani/#ieri.
 Gianni believe.PRES COMP Maria leave.PRES.SUBJ tomorrow/yesterday
 Lit. ‘Gianni believes that Maria is leaving tomorrow/yesterday.’
 b. Gianni crede che Maria sia triste adesso/#ieri.
 Gianni believe.PRES COMP Maria be.PRES.SUBJ say now/yesterday
 Lit. ‘Gianni believes that Maria is sad now/yesterday.’

If we adopt an analysis whereby subjunctive present is tenseless and evaluated with respect

⁴⁸On the relevant future interpretation for (103-a), the embedded predicate is morphologically licensed by the matrix verb but temporally relativized to the local adverbial.

over through the binder $\lambda 7$. The open temporal variable is closed off by the attitude time, which is quantificationally introduced by the attitude verb. For the latter, I will assume the same semantics adopted for attitude verbs in Asante Twi and repeated below.

$$(108) \quad \llbracket \text{dic-} \rrbracket = \lambda w_s. \lambda e_v. \lambda p_{\langle s, \langle i, t \rangle \rangle}. \lambda x_e. \forall \langle w', t' \rangle [\langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Say}(x, w, \tau(e)) \rightarrow p(w')(t')]^{51}$$

Unfortunately, the output of the logical form in (107) does not yield any plausible reading, as is illustrated in (109).

- (109) a. $\llbracket (107) \rrbracket$ defined iff
 $g(2) < t_c$ (PSP of the matrix past);
 $t' \supseteq t_c \ \& \ t_c = t_c$ (PSP of the embedded present)
- b. When defined, $\llbracket (107) \rrbracket = 1$ iff
 $\exists e[\tau(e) \subseteq g(2) \ \& \ \forall \langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Say}(P, w_c, g(2)) \rightarrow \exists e'[\tau(e') \supseteq t' \ \& \ \text{pregnant}(w')(e')(M)]]$
Paraphrase: ‘There is some eventuality e , such that e is temporally included in $g(2)$, that is a salient time preceding UT, and for all the worlds w' and times t' compatible with what Paolo said throughout e , it follows that there is an eventuality e' , such that e' temporally includes t' , which surrounds UT, and e' is an eventuality of Marta being pregnant in W' .’

The truth-conditions computed in (109-b) make conflicting demands on the attitude time’s reference. On the one the one hand, they locate t' before UT (via the attitude verb’s accessibility relation); on the other, they restrict it to an interval that surrounds UT (via the present tense’s presupposition). Alternatively, a property of times in the embedded clause may also result from having the attitude verb bind into the evaluation time of the embedded present (represented by the second index) — instead of its reference time (represented by the first index). This, in turn, allows the reference time variable to be freely assigned a value through the context. Unfortunately, this option is equally unsuccessful, as it leads to presupposition failure: given present’s presuppositional restriction, its evaluation time can only be t_c or a time that surrounds it. In other words, if the attitude verb bears non-present morphology, its present-tensed complement can only be interpreted *de re*.

Following the analysis outlined in 3.5 for *ná* in attitude reports, I will extend to the Italian present the acquaintance-based analysis that makes use of time-concept generators. Before applying the analysis to a present-under-perfect embedding, let me repeat below how a time-concept generator is formulated.

- (110) A time-concept generator suitable for x in world w and time t is a function G such that:
- a. $\text{Dom}(G) \subseteq \{z: z \in D_{\langle i \rangle}. \ x \text{ bears an acquaintance relation } R \text{ to } z \text{ in } w \text{ at } t\}$; and
- b. $\forall t'': t'' \in \text{Dom}(G)$, it follows:
- (i) $G(t'')$ is a suitable time-concept;
- (ii) $\forall \langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{ACC}(x, w, t) \rightarrow G(t'')(t')(w')$ is defined;

⁵¹ $\text{Say}(x, w, t) = \{ \langle w, t \rangle: \langle w, t \rangle \text{ is compatible with what } x \text{ says in } w \text{ throughout } t \}$.

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- (iii) $G(t'')(t)(w) = t''$;
 (iv) $\forall \langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Dom}(G(t'')) \rightarrow \neg(G(t'')(t')(w') > t')$. (ULC)

An appropriate acquaintance relation for the sentence in (106) can be the following one:

- (111) : $G = \lambda t. \lambda t'. \lambda w. t$ is a temporal interval including Marta's signs and symptoms of pregnancy at t' in w .

If the attitude holder in (106) is acquainted with the 'res', i.e. the reference expressed by the embedded present, through the relation in (111), (106) can receive the semantic representation in (112).

In (112), the time-concept generator G_7 combines with the temporal res, that is the time denoted by the present tense 'pres_{1,3}', a temporal variable t_8 and a world variable w_5 , both quantificationally bound by the attitude verb. Note that the doubly-indexed

pronoun ‘pres_{1,3}’ is correctly evaluated relative to the utterance time, as its EvalT index ‘3’ is abstracted over by the binder below the proform t_c in the matrix CP. In contrast, its reference is contextually determined, as its RT index ‘1’ is free, thereby avoiding the issue that arises with the *de Dicto* LF in (107). Given a *de re*-amended semantics for attitude verbs taking, as repeated in (113), we are able to derive the definedness conditions and the truth-conditions in (114).

$$(113) \quad \llbracket \text{dic-}deRe \rrbracket = \lambda w_s. \lambda e_v. \lambda p_{\langle \langle i, \langle i, \langle s, i \rangle \rangle \rangle, \langle s, \langle i, t \rangle \rangle \rangle}. \lambda x_e. \exists G [G \text{ suitable for } x \text{ in } w \text{ at } \tau(e) \ \& \ \forall \langle w', t' \rangle [\langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Say}(x, w, \tau(e)) \rightarrow p(G)(w')(t')]]$$

$$(114) \quad \text{a. } \llbracket (112) \rrbracket \text{ is defined iff}$$

$$g(2) < t_c \quad \text{(PSP of the matrix past);}$$

$$\text{Dom}(G) \subseteq \{z: z \in D_{\langle i \rangle}. \text{ Paolo bears an acquaintance relation } R_c \text{ to } z \text{ in } w_c \text{ at } g(2)\} \quad \text{(PSP of 'G}_7\text{')}$$

$$\forall \langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Dom}(G(g(1))) \rightarrow \neg(G(g(1))(t')(w') > t') \quad \text{(ULC)}$$

$$g(1) \supseteq t_c \ \& \ t_c = t_c \quad \text{(PSP of the embedded present)}$$

$$\text{b. } \llbracket (112) \rrbracket = 1 \text{ iff}$$

$$\exists e[\tau(e) \subseteq g(2) \ \& \ \exists G[G \text{ a time CG suitable for Paolo in } w_c \text{ at } \tau(e) \ \& \ \forall \langle w', t' \rangle [\langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Say}(P, w_c, \tau(e)) \rightarrow \exists e'[G(g(1))(t')(w') \subseteq \tau(e') \ \& \ \text{pregnant}(w')(e')(M)]]]]$$

Paraphrase: There is an eventuality e , such that e is temporally included in $g(2)$ preceding t_c and there is a time-concept G suitable for Paolo in the actual world throughout e , and for all the worlds w' and times t' compatible with what Paolo said throughout e in the actual world, it follows that there is an eventuality e' , such that e' temporally contains the temporal interval denoted by $G(g(1))(t')(w')$ - i.e. $g(1)$, with which Paolo is acquainted in w' at t' -, and e' is an eventuality of Marta being sick in w' .

Let us break down the meaning sketched in (114) and show that it correctly captures the double access reading of the sentence in (106). Firstly, the time-concept generator G is defined if Paolo bears an acquaintance relation to the res (that is $g(1)$) in the actual world. That means that Paolo must have noticed at $g(2)$ (i.e. at the time of the report) and in the actual world that Marta shows signs and symptoms of a pregnancy. Given the presupposition of the present tense, $g(1)$ is further restricted to times surrounding t_c . This entails that the signs and symptoms that Paolo is acquainted with must extend from $g(2)$ to at least include t_c in the actual world. Crucially, in the truth-conditions sketched in (114-b), Marta’s pregnancy holds true in Paolo’s belief-worlds of a temporal interval ‘ $G(g(1))(t')(w')$ ’ satisfying the acquaintance relation at the attitude time and in the attitude world. This entails that the temporal interval generated via the relevant time-concept ‘ $G(g(1))$ ’ needs to include both the attitude and the utterance time, which is exactly what a double access interpretation requires.

This analysis makes two welcome predictions: (i) the lack of forward-shifted interpretations; (ii) the lack of actuality entailments. As we have discussed in chapter 2 for English, sentences such as (106) cannot reflect a prediction on the part of the attitude holder. More specifically, Paolo could not have said ‘Marta will be pregnant’. Forward-shifted interpretations are ruled out by the upper limit constraint in (114-a), which excludes

forward-looking time-concepts. Furthermore, the truth-conditions in (114-b) are compatible with scenarios where Marta is not actually pregnant. In fact, it's the property denoted by the acquaintance relation to hold true of the actual world (and of the saying time), not the pregnancy itself. More concretely, according to the report, Marta is merely pregnant as long as the signs and symptoms of such pregnancy last. This is a desirable outcome, given that the continuation in (115) does not lead to any contradiction.⁵²

- (115) Context: In preparation for an upcoming movie role as a pregnant woman, Marta has been wearing a silicone belly, successfully fooling everyone, including Paolo!
- a. Paolo ha detto che Marta è incinta... ('Paolo said that Marta is pregnant.')
 - b. ... ma in realtà sta indossando una pancia finta.
but in reality wear.PRES.PROG NDEF belly fake
'... but in reality she's wearing a fake belly.'

It is worth stressing that the cases such as (115) provide another counter-example to Giorgi's account. While Giorgi's theory does not explicitly mention possible worlds, the fact that the indicative present is obligatorily evaluated with respect to the 'speaker's temporal coordinate' seems to imply that the embedded eventuality must hold true in both the actual world and at the utterance time, which contradicts empirical evidence.

4.2.3 The effects of mood and aspect on DAR: a pragmatic approach

This section provides a pragmatic explanation for the patterns observed regarding mood and aspect alternation. We have shown that DAR seems to be influenced by (i) the mood of the embedded predicate, favoring indicative reports over subjunctive ones, and (ii) the grammatical aspect of the embedding predicate, with imperfective attitude verbs typically being excluded in comparison to perfective ones. In what follows, I will propose that mood choice imposes (anti-)presuppositional restrictions on the acquaintance relation, which in turn determines the resulting *de re* reading. On the other hand, imperfective attitude verbs yield an implicature of cessation that conflicts with a double access interpretation.

Maximize Presupposition! and mood alternation

Numerous attempts in both formal and descriptive literature have aimed to elucidate mood distribution, particularly within attitude reports. Let me briefly outline two prominent approaches, primarily devised for French (Schlenker, 2005) and Italian (Portner, 1997).⁵³ Building on Stalnaker (1975)'s theory of indicative conditionals, Schlenker posits that an indicative-marked proposition contains worlds that are included in the context set.⁵⁴ The context set is a set of worlds compatible with what the speaker presupposes. Notably, these worlds must be doxastically accessible to the speaker at a given time, to the extent that the indicative mood exclusively targets worlds that are compatible with

⁵²For an in-depth discussion of DAR's pragmatic conditions, see also Abusch (1997) and Gennari (1999a)

⁵³See also Farkas (1992, 2003) for Romance languages and Villalta (2008) for Spanish.

⁵⁴For a formal definition see Schlenker (2005, p. 21).

the speaker's beliefs (in attitude contexts, the attitude holder's beliefs). By contrast, the subjunctive is felicitous in all instances where the presupposition of the indicative is not satisfied.

While this approach correctly accounts for mood patterns in French, its extension to Italian poses challenges, as verbs of belief in Italian typically select for subjunctive mood. For Italian, Portner assumes that the accessibility relation is not doxastic, but rather "prototypically factive".⁵⁵ Clearly, factive verbs have a prototypically factive accessibility relation in that their prejacent is true, thereby requiring an indicative complement in Italian. Conversely, verbs of belief display an accessibility relation that is not prototypically factive, since people often hold beliefs that are not actually true, thereby justifying the use of the subjunctive mood. Regarding verbs of assertion, it is usually assumed that what individuals assert is true, hence these verbs typically select for the indicative mood.

Despite differences in how they model the accessibility relation, both accounts assume that the subjunctive mood constitutes a semantic default: it does not presuppose anything and is appropriate in all contexts where the indicative is not licensed. This insight will be instrumental to the understanding of the DAR patterns in Italian.

Combining the two approaches, I argue that the indicative mood in DAR-embeddings contributes a presupposition that the acquaintance relation is part of the speaker's context set, which contains the worlds compatible with what the speaker believes. It follows that in present-under-past embeddings, the speaker believes that the attitude holder is appropriately acquainted with a certain time at which the eventuality obtains (the temporal res). This pragmatic inference can be defined as follows:

- (116) *Presupposition of the indicative in present-tensed attitude reports:*
 For a context c and an attitude holder x , a temporal res t , and a relation $R_{c,x}$ through which x is acquainted with t in c , $\forall \langle w', t' \rangle [\langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Dox}(\text{sp.}, w_c, t_c) \rightarrow R_{c,x}(t)(t')(w')]$

It follows from (116) that the indicative mood is licensed in present-tensed embeddings in contexts where the speaker has reasons to believe that an appropriate acquaintance relation can be established between the attitude holder and a relevant temporal interval. If the latter condition fails to obtain, the subjunctive mood must be adopted instead. Principles of pragmatic cooperation (Grice, 1975) demand that the indicative be used for all *de re* reports whose acquaintance relation is *endorsed* by the speaker. This is always the case when the content of the report is known to be true. However, if the speaker adopts the subjunctive, this signals to the addressee that the speaker is not in a position to endorse the acquaintance relation. This pragmatic inference may be derived through a principle akin to *Maximize Presupposition!* (Heim, 1991), as illustrated below (as reformulated in Sauerland, 2008):

- (117) *Maximize Presupposition!* (MP)
 Make your contribution presuppose as much as possible!

⁵⁵Portner defines a prototypically factive accessibility relation in a situation semantics framework. A modal context is viewed as prototypically factive if and only if its typical situations can be expanded to whole worlds including these situations (see Portner, 1997, p. 195).

Given the principle MP in (117), the subjunctive, by virtue of occurring in lieu of the presuppositionally stronger indicative, *anti-presupposes* that the speaker does not believe that an acquaintance relation holds between the attitude holder and the res. This weak inference does not necessarily entail that the proposition is false and, therefore, the DAR does not follow. Rather, it conveys uncertainty/ignorance on the part of the speaker. I believe this weak inference is always computed when the subjunctive replaces the indicative with verbs that allow for the alternation, as is illustrated in (118)

- (118) a. Paolo ha sostenuto che Marta è incinta.
 Paolo claim.APRF COMP Maria be.PRES.IND pregnant
 \rightsquigarrow *the speaker believes that Paolo is acquainted with a temporal interval throughout which Marta's pregnancy symptoms are visible.*
- b. Paolo ha sostenuto che Marta sia incinta.
 Paolo claim.APRF COMP Maria be.PRES.SUBJ pregnant
 \rightsquigarrow *the speaker does not believe that Paolo is acquainted with a temporal interval throughout which Marta's pregnancy symptoms are visible.*

In (118), the subjunctive report, unlike the indicative one, suggests that the speaker cannot endorse the acquaintance relation at the utterance time, either because she knows that Marta is not actually pregnant or because she hasn't been exposed to her pregnancy symptoms herself. Note that the indicative report does not entail that the proposition is actually true. In fact, as we have previously demonstrated, the indicative report may be negated without leading to a contradiction. Given the fact that the indicative here merely presupposes belief towards the acquaintance, this falls out naturally. All the speaker commits to is the existence of Marta's pregnancy symptoms. Whether they signify an actual pregnancy remains uncertain.

Clearly, this account correctly rules out subjunctive reports when the attitude verb is factive, as shown below.

- (119) a. Paolo ha scoperto che Marta è incinta.
 Paolo discover.APRF COMP Maria be.PRES.IND pregnant
 \rightsquigarrow *the speaker knows that Marta is pregnant at a temporal interval t including her pregnancy symptoms and extending to UT and she believes that Paolo is acquainted with t.*
- b. #Paolo ha scoperto che Marta sia incinta.
 Paolo discover.APRF COMP Maria be.PRES.SUBJ pregnant
 \rightsquigarrow *the speaker knows that Marta is pregnant in the actual world at a temporal interval t including her pregnancy symptoms and extending to UT and she does not believe that Paolo is acquainted with t.*

In (119), the factive verb presupposes the truth of the proposition and asserts that the attitude holder knows it. Therefore, due to MP, the speaker must use the presuppositionally stronger indicative and assume that the attitude holder is acquainted with the temporal res.

Let's now examine the challenging cases outlined in (90), where mood alternation appears to be sensitive to whether the speaker coincides with the attitude holder. These are repeated in (120).

- (120) a. Chidi ha sostenuto che Janet e Jason sono/siano innamorati.
 Chidi claim.APRF that Janet and Jason be.PRES.IND/SUBJ in.love
 ‘Chidi claimed that Janet and Jason are in love.’
 b. Ho sostenuto che Janet e Jason sono/#siano innamorati.
 claim.APRF.1SG that Janet and Jason be.PRES.IND/SUBJ in.love
 ‘I’ve claimed that Janet and Jason are in love.’

In (120), the subjunctive is ruled out with a first-person report. Since the speaker is reporting her own claim, she must know whether she is acquainted with the relevant time she’s talking about or not. However, the use of the subjunctive in (120-b) signals that the speaker does not believe that she is acquainted with the temporal interval throughout which (she claimed) the proposition was true. This is of course nonsensical.

First-person reports might be viewed as sub-cases of a more general class of reports where the speaker is an authority on $R_{c,x}$. It has been shown that weak inferences stemming from an MP-like principle (as the one in (118)) may be strengthened by a *competence assumption* and an *authority assumption*, according to which a speaker is opinionated and an authority regarding a certain proposition.⁵⁶ In a similar vein, we might hypothesize that in sentences such as (120-b), the speaker, as the individual holding a certain attitude — must be opinionated and considered an authority regarding the acquaintance relation — i.e., how she herself came into contact with the temporal res. Consequently, a strong inference is drawn, according to which the acquaintance relation is false. This is illustrated below.

- (121) #Ho sostenuto che Janet e Jason siano innamorati.
 claim.APRF.1SG that Janet and Jason be.PRES.SUBJ in.love
- a. $\llbracket (121) \rrbracket = 1$ iff
Paraphrase: ‘There is an eventuality e , such that e is temporally included in $g(2)$ preceding t_c and there is a time-concept G suitable for the speaker in the actual world throughout e , and for all the worlds w' and time t' compatible with what the speaker claimed throughout e in the actual world, it follows that there is an eventuality e' , such that e' temporally contains the temporal interval denoted by $G(g(1))(t')(w')$ — i.e. $g(1)$ surrounding t_c , with which the speaker is acquainted in w' at t' -, and e' is an eventuality of Jason and Janet being in love in w' .’
- b. \rightsquigarrow (weak): *the speaker does not believe that she is acquainted with the temporal interval $g(1)$ throughout which Janet and Jason show visible signs of mutual love.*
- c. \rightsquigarrow (strong): *it’s not the case that Janet and Jason show visible signs of mutual love throughout a temporal interval $g(1)$.*

According to the meaning of (121) as paraphrased in (121-a), the speaker is acquainted with the temporal interval $g(1)$, covering the whole period of time encompassing Jason and Janet’s signs of mutual love. Via the embedded present’s presupposition, this temporal interval includes the utterance time t_c . However, (121-a) clashes with the strong inference yielded by the subjunctive mood in (121-c), according to which the conditions under which

⁵⁶For further details, see Chemla (2008) and Sauerland (2004).

the speaker is acquainted with $g(1)$ do not hold.

Cessation implicature and aspect alternation

One more case where DAR fails to obtain pertains to attitude verbs bearing imperfective morphology (see (91), repeated in (122)).

(122) *Perfective vs Imperfective attitude verbs:*

- a. Anna ha ipotizzato che Will sia/è sposato.
Anna hypothesize.APRF COMP Will be.PRES.SUBJ/IND married
'Anna hypothesized that William is married.'
- b. ??Anna ipotizzava che Will sia/è sposato.
Anna hypothesize.IMP COMP Will be.PRES.SUBJ/IND married
Intended: 'Anna hypothesized that William is married.'
- c. Anna ipotizzava che Will fosse sposato.
Anna hypothesize.IMP COMP Will be.IMP.SUBJ married
'Anna hypothesized that William was married.'

Note that in (122), a present-under-perfect embedding appears to be degraded when the embedding predicate is imperfective, irrespective of mood marking on the embedded predicate. Importantly, the sentences with an IMP-marked attitude verb in (122-b) and (122-c) seem to suggest that the attitude holder no longer holds the reported thought at the utterance time, thus requiring a past-oriented verb in the complement clause. This inference is even more evident in context where the QuD is relativized to UT, as is illustrated by the following exchange.

- (123) A: Does Gianni have any idea where Maria is? She skipped today's meeting.
- a. B: Crede che sia in vacanza.
think.PRES COMP be.PRES on holiday
'He thinks she's on holiday.'
 - b. B: credeva che fosse/#sia in vacanza.
think.IMP COMP be.IMP/PRES on holiday
'He thought she was on holiday.'

In (123), A's question is about the utterance time. While B's answer in (123-a) matches A's question from a temporal standpoint, the one in (123-b) does not. Here, B's use of the imperfect 'credeva' in lieu of the more informative present signals to A that Gianni no longer holds the same belief at the time of the speech.

Inferences of this kind are far from mysterious and have been often associated with Grice's maxime of quantity. More specifically, we have seen in chapter 2 that Altshuler & Schwarzschild (2012) have attributed the cessation implicature arising with past-tensed stative clauses to competition between present and past tense. The resulting scalar implicature can be derived under the assumption that, for stative predicates, present tense entails past tense. We can extend the same reasoning to imperfective predicates, given the fact that imperfectives share with statives their unbounded aspectual profile.

(124) *The temporal profile of imperfectives* For any imperfective proposition p , if p is

true at a time t , then there is a time t' preceding t , such that p is true at t' , and there is a time t'' following t , such that p is true at t'' .

In a similar fashion to what outlined in chapter 2 for statives, we derive from (124) that present-marked predicates entail imperfect-marked ones, given that there is always a time preceding UT at which both predicates are verified. If (imperfective) present and past tenses are scalar alternatives, with present the stronger element on the scale, then opting for the weaker past-tensed alternative triggers an implicature of cessation (CI). Transferring this to the discussion of present-under-(im)perfect embeddings, we are now in a position to account for the aspectual contrast that has emerged. Consider once again the sentence in (125), with the respective meaning paraphrased in (125-b) and its (simplified) cessation implicature paraphrased in (125-c).

(125) Context in (123):

- a. #Gianni credeva che Maria sia in vacanza. ('Gianni thought.IMP that Maria isPRES on holiday.
- b. \llbracket (125-a) $\rrbracket = 1$ iff 'There is an eventuality e , such that e is temporally included in $g(2)$ preceding t_c and there is a time-concept G suitable for the speaker in the actual world throughout e , and for all the worlds w' and times t' compatible with what Gianni believed throughout e in the actual world, it follows that there is an eventuality e' , such that **e' temporally contains the temporal interval denoted by $G(g(1))(t')(w')$ — i.e. $g(1)$ surrounding t_c , with which Gianni is acquainted in w' at t' -, and e' is an eventuality of Maria being on holiday in w' .'**
- c. CI: 'There is no eventuality e , such that e is temporally included in $g(4)$ surrounding t_c and following Gianni's beliefs throughout e , Maria is on holiday at $g(5)$ surrounding t_c .'

According to the bold-faced part of the meaning paraphrased in (125-b), the attitude holder Gianni is acquainted with a time that includes t_c , at which Mary's holiday state holds. Crucially, the use of the imperfect instead of the present in the matrix triggers the cessation implicature in (125-c). This prevents Gianni from believing at t_c that Maria's holiday state holds at t_c . However, if the speaker knows that Gianni no longer holds such belief, then a double access interpretation becomes implausible.⁵⁷

One prediction made by this account is that, if the implicature of cessation is cancelled, then the double access interpretation should be rescued. One possible way to cancel the implicature is to conjoin the imperfect-marked attitude verb with its present counterpart, as is shown below.

(126) Context: Answering a complaint from a player about neverb being picked for the first team...

⁵⁷Technically speaking, Gianni could have been acquainted at $g(2)$ with a temporal interval stretching up to UT and verifying the embedded proposition, with the proposition being false at UT in his belief worlds (for instance, Gianni witnessed signs of Mary being absent on an extended amount of time encompassing UT, but he later (at UT) came to believe that that was not the case). However, this attitude report sounds incoherent in the light of the question it answers.

- a. L'allenatore riteneva #(e ritiene tuttora) che tu sia
 DEF=coach believe.IMP believe.PRES still COMP you be.PRES
 un elemento valido della squadra.
 NDEF element valuable of.DEF team
 'The coach believed and still believes that you are a valuable asset of the team.'

4.2.4 A note on present tense in future embeddings

In closing, I will briefly address the temporal interpretation of present-under-future embeddings. Having looked at instances where the present tense behaves as a strictly indexical tense — thus forcing a *de re* interpretation — these future embeddings reveal possible shiftability for the present.

Following a crosslinguistically stable pattern, present-under-future attitude reports may exhibit simultaneous interpretations. Note that, these readings cannot be simply attributed to a futurate present, considering that they arise even when the certainty condition is not met, as is illustrated in (127)

- (127) a. Venerdì sera, Marica dirà che la festa è noiosa.
 Friday evening Marica say.FUT COMP DEF be.PRES boring
 'On Friday, Marica will say that the party is boring.'
 b. #Venerdì sera la festa è noiosa.
 Friday evening DEF party be.PRES boring
 lit. 'On Friday, the party is boring.'

It is worth noting that the simultaneous interpretation in (127-a) cannot be viewed as the by-product of a future DAR, given that the embedded predicate only holds at a future time. Naturally, future double access interpretations for present-under-future embeddings are attested. However, unlike past DAR, access to UT is not a necessary condition, as the following minimal pair shows.

- (128) a. Fra un mese, per il suo compleanno, Paolo annuncerà a suo
 in one month for DEF his birthday Paolo announce.FUT to his
 padre che Marta è sua moglie...
 father COMP Marta be.PRES his wife
 'A month from now, on his birthday, Paul will announce to his father that Marta is his wife.'
 b. ✓...visto che si sono sposati la scorsa settimana.
 ('as they got married last week.') (✓DAR/✓SIM)
 c. ✓...visto che si sposeranno la settimana precedente.
 ('as they'll get married the week before.') (#DAR/✓SIM)

The simplest solution would be to assume that the present tense can be shifted when c-commanded by an agreeing tense (for instance, the simple future). In fact, this agreement-based account motivated a possible present-tensed semantics for the analytic perfect in section 4.1.2. For the sentence in (127-a), this analysis predicts the following simplified LF and meaning.

Similar results are replicated when the embedded verb bears subjunctive mood. *SIM-Context, eventive*: You called your friend Derna and checked if Andrea was around. Seeing his door shut, Derna figured he might be napping.

- a. Derna credeva che Andrea dormisse.
Derna say.APRF COMP Andrea sleep.IMP.SUBJ
'Derna thought that Andrea was sleeping.'
- b. #Derna credeva che Andrea abbia dormito.
Derna say.APRF COMP Zoe sleep.APRF.SUBJ
'Derna thought that Andrea slept.'

(132) *SIM-Context, stative*: Last weekend, Natasha visited her friend Joyce at her beach house. One evening, when Joyce invited her for a nighttime swim, Natasha declined, saying: 'the water might be too cold for me.'

- a. Nastaha temeva che l'acqua fosse troppo fredda.
Natasha fear.IMP COMP DEF=water be.IMP.SUBJ too cold
'Natasha feared that the water was too cold.'
- b. #Nastaha temeva che l'acqua sia stata troppo fredda.
Natasha fear.IMP COMP DEF=water be.APRF.SUBJ too cold
'Natasha feared that the water had been too cold.'

In addition to simultaneous readings, imp-under-perfect embeddings are associated with backward-shifted interpretations, as is exemplified in (133-a). Clearly, this is the only available reading for perfect-under-perfect embeddings, as examples in (133-b) show.⁵⁸

- (133) *BACK-Context, eventive*: You didn't see Marco the night his flatmate celebrated her birthday. Yesterday, he explained why: he had a late shift.
- a. Marco ha detto che quella sera stava lavorando.
Marco say.APRF COMP DEM evening work.IMP.PROG
'Marco said that he was working that night.'
- b. Marco ha detto che quella sera ha lavorato/lavorò fino a tardi.
Marco say.APRF COMP DEM evening work.APRF/SPRF until late
'Marco said that he (had) worked until late that night.'

These findings are summarized in table 4.2.⁵⁹

	IMP-under-PAST	SPRF-under-PAST	APRF-under-PAST
Simultaneous	✓	#	#
Backward-shifted	✓	✓	✓

Table 4.2: The interpretation of past-oriented attitude reports in Italian

⁵⁸Note that, unlike English, BACK is the only attested interpretation for perfect-under-past embeddings, even if the embedded predicate is stative (see (131-b)).

⁵⁹'PAST' refers to a generic past-oriented form, encompassing both imperfect and perfects.

4.3.2 Sequence of tense and past tense vacuity

The data presented above seem to align with the view that Italian is an SoT language in that the embedded (imperfective) past may be the mere morphological reflection of the matrix past. This is the stance commonly taken in the literature (cf. a.o., Bošković, 2012; Costantini, 2007; Giorgi & Pianesi, 1997). Unfortunately, as we discussed in the previous chapters, past contexts alone cannot conclusively establish whether past simultaneity results from a genuinely *de se* null reading, or it should be attributed to a *de re* mechanism instead.

To address this question, we can deploy the diagnostics so far deployed for English and Asante Twi, which test the availability of null readings for past-tensed embeddings in future contexts and for past generic reports. Consider the sentence in (134), based on Abusch’s *breakfast* sentence.

- (134) SIM-Context: Paolo is organizing a camping trip for the weekend with Marta. He’s worried that Marta didn’t pack enough food. He tells you, “While camping, she’ll get hungry and start complaining. You’ll see!” Later, you report what he said.
- a. Oggi Paolo ha scommesso che durante il campeggio Marta
 today Paolo bet.APRF COMP during DEF camping Marta
 avrebbe detto che aveva fame.
 say.COND.PRF COMP have.IMP hunger
 ‘Paolo bet that during the camping trip Marta would say that she was hungry.’

In (134), a simultaneous relation can be established between Marta’s hunger state and her speaking. Crucially, this time does not precede either the local evaluation time or the utterance time. This entails a presupposition failure for the most embedded imperfect, in that the context does not provide any suitable antecedent for its evaluation time, as is sketched below.⁶⁰

- (135) $[_{CP1} t_c (\lambda_5) [past_{2,3} (\lambda_5) [Paolo\text{-bet } \forall t' \dots [_{CP2} (\lambda_5) [FUT \dots [Marta\text{-say } \forall t'' \dots [_{CP3} (\lambda_5) [imp_{4,5} Marta\text{-hungry } \dots]]]]]]]]]$
- a. ...today(*P’s bet*, t')... t_ccamping time(*M’s speech*, t' ; *M’s hunger*, $g(4)$)....
 b. $\llbracket (135) \rrbracket$ defined iff $g(4) < g(5)$
 c. Via binding: $g(5) = t_c \vee g(5) = g(2) \vee g(5) = t' \vee g(5) = t''$

According to the LF sketched in (135), there are four binding options for $imp_{4,5}$ ’s EvalT (see (135-c)). Following the rough timeline sketched in (135-a), none of these options produces a time that satisfies the definedness condition in (135-b).

Similarly, the imperfect appears to be semantically vacuous when marking a predicate

⁶⁰In a manner akin to the evolution of the simple future, the conditional has also evolved from a past-tensed futurate auxiliary paired with the infinitive of the main verb. For instance, combining “mangiare” with “ebbe” (‘to eat’ + ‘had’) yields “mangerebbe” (‘would eat’). While the simple conditional was widely used in Old Italian to express future in the past (a structure still active in French and Spanish), standard Italian has transitioned to employing the perfect conditional. This shift mirrors the pattern observed in counterfactual conditionals, as discussed in detail by Squartini (1999).

denoting a permanent state of affair in (false or true) attitude reports, as is illustrated below.⁶¹

(136) *False attitude reports:*

- a. Gianni credeva che 9 fosse un numero primo.
Gianni think.IMP COMP 9 be.IMP.SUBJ NDEF number prime
'Gianni thought that 9 was a prime number.'
- b. In passato si riteneva che la Terra fosse piatta.
in past SI believe.IMP COMP DEF Earth be.IMP.SUBJ flat
'In the past it was believed that the Earth was flat.'

(137) *True attitude reports:*

- a. Gli antichi greci sapevano che la Terra era sferica.
DEF ancient Greeks know.IMP COMP DEF Earth be.IMP spherical
'The ancient Greeks knew that the Earth was/is spherical.'
- b. Già da piccolo Marco scoprì che Babbo Natale non
already as small Marco discover.SPRF Santa Claus NEG
esisteva.
exist.IMP
'Even as a child, Marco discovered that Santa Claus did not exist.'

In (136) and (137), the embedded imperfect does not situate the eventuality at any particular time in the past. This is due to the embedded eventuality, which is inherently associated with an *atemporal* property, holding true or false universally. For instance, a *de re* interpretation of (136-a) entails that Gianni is acquainted with a specific past time at which, in his belief, the number 9 was prime. Clearly, this is incompatible with mathematical states of affairs.

It is noteworthy that, although reports of permanent states of affairs are generally acceptable, there is some interspeaker variation concerning breakfast sentences. While I personally find these sentences felicitous in simultaneous scenarios, not all speakers share this view, opting instead for a conditional in the most embedded clause or, in some cases, a present tense. I will return to this point in the next chapter, where I discuss the possible variation within the Western-Romance family.

The presence of null readings in environments that do not appear to semantically license past reference seem to support an agreement-based analysis for the Italian imperfect. Importantly, the perfect-counterparts to (136) and (137) cannot yield temporally vacuous interpretations. Instead, they give rise to strong cessation implicatures, coercing generic/i-level predicates into temporary/s-level predicates.⁶²

If Italian is a Sequence of Tense language, then why do we observe such a striking contrast between the imperfect and the two perfects? More specifically, does a deletion-based rule exclusively target the imperfect and, if so, why is that the case? These questions

⁶¹As pointed out in Khomitsevich (2008), an embedded (imperfective) past is the preferred choice for false attitudes, while true attitudes are most naturally expressed with an embedded present.

⁶²A sentence such as “Gli antichi greci sapevano che la Terra è stata/fu sferica” (‘the ancient Greeks knew that the Earth has been spherical’) strongly implies that the Earth used to be spherical and ceased to be so at some point.

will be addressed in the next two sections.

4.4 The composition of perfect embeddings

The previous section has argued that Italian displays the hallmarks of an SoT language. More specifically, we have seen that in attitude reports, while the imperfect is compatible with both simultaneous and backward-shifted readings, the two perfects strictly yield shifted interpretations. The observed contrast is commonly found in languages distinguishing between perfective and imperfective past tenses, and is reminiscent of that found in Asante Twi between imperfective *ná* and perfective LEN.

This section zooms in on perfect embeddings, demonstrating that the resulting backward-shifted interpretations reveal an underlying *de re* derivation for both SPRF- and APRF-marked reports. I show that, while the former retains relative BACK-readings only in past contexts, the latter, thanks to the deletion of the present tense, yields relative shifted interpretations also in future contexts. Finally, I delve deeper into the absence of an SoT rule for perfects, motivating an acquaintance-based analysis even in the case of some exceptional simultaneous readings in perception reports.

4.4.1 Embedded perfects and temporal *de re*

Let's consider now the composition of SPRF- and APRF-marked embeddings which have an underlying past-tense semantics. Recall that the synthetic and the analytic perfect are unified under the same semantics, when the analytic form is equally used as a past perfective, whose semantics is repeated in (138).

- (138) a. $\llbracket \text{past}_{2,3} \rrbracket$ defined iff $\llbracket \text{past}_{2,3} \rrbracket \in D_{(i,i)} \ \& \ g(2) < g(3) \ \& \ g(3) = t_c$
 b. $\llbracket \text{past}_{2,3} \rrbracket(g(3)) = g(2)$

From the indexical presupposition in (138), it follows that the perfect's local evaluation time $g(3)$ rigidly designates the utterance time. Consequently, the indexed variable denoting the EvalT (that is, the one carrying the index '3') cannot be bound by the attitude verb, but has to remain free or be bound by t_c . To illustrate the point, consider the perfect-under-perfect report in (139).

- (139) *BACK-Context, eventive*: You didn't see Marco the night his flatmate celebrated her birthday. Yesterday, he explained why: he had a late shift.
 a. Marco ha detto che quella sera ha lavorato/lavorò fino a tardi.
 Marco say.APRF COMP DEM evening work.APRF/SPRF until late
 'Marco said that he (had) worked until late that night.'

Both sentences in (139-a) display the same LF in (140), since the perfect form denotes a past perfective in either case.⁶³ As shown for the indexical present, the past tense

⁶³For simplicity, I am ignoring the contribution of the two adverbials. Furthermore, I am assuming that the analytic perfect in the matrix also projects a past perfective, given that the context links Marco's speech to a salient time before today.

variable ‘past_{2,3}’ is also fed to a concept generator ‘G₇’, which additionally combines with two variables denoting the evaluation time and the world of evaluation, respectively.

Because of the syntactic ‘shelter’ built by ‘G₇’ in (140), the res variable ‘past_{2,3}’ escapes binding by the attitude verb (via the binder λt₈). Since the temporal res denotes an actual time salient in the context and not the attitude holder’s now, this is a desirable outcome. The backward-shifted interpretation is arrived at through an appropriate acquaintance relation, which is supplied by the context. A possible candidate is given in (141).

- (141) G = λt.λt'.λw'. t is a temporal interval including the night of the birthday party of Marco’s flatmate at t' in w'.

Through the acquaintance relation in (141), we derive the meaning from (140) in (142)

- (142) a. [[(140)]] defined iff g(1) < t_c (PSP of the matrix past)

$g(2) < t_c \ \& \ t_c = t_c$ (PSP of the embedded past) $\text{Dom}(G) \subseteq \{z: z \in D_{(i)}\}$.
 Marco bears an acquaintance relation R_c to z in w_c at $g(1)$ (PSP of ‘G₇’)
 $\forall \langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Dom}(G(g(2))) \rightarrow \neg(G(g(2))(t')(w') > t')$ (ULC)

- b. $\exists e[\tau(e) \subseteq g(2) \ \& \ \exists G[G \text{ a time CG suitable for Marco in } w_c \text{ at } \tau(e) \ \& \ \forall \langle w', t' \rangle$
 $[\langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Say}(M, w_c, \tau(e)) \rightarrow \exists e' [G(g(2))(t')(w') \supseteq \tau(e') \ \& \ \text{work}(w')(e')(g(8))]]]$
 (where $g(8) = \text{Marco}$)

Paraphrase: There is an eventuality e , such that e is temporally included in $g(1)$ preceding t_c and there is a time-concept G suitable for Marco in the actual world throughout e , and for all the worlds w' and times t' compatible with what Marco said throughout e in the actual world, it follows that there is an eventuality e' , such that e' is temporally included within the temporal interval denoted by $G(g(2))(t')(w')$ — i.e. $g(2)$, with which Paolo is acquainted in w' at t' -, and e' is an eventuality of Marco working in w' .

The truth-conditions sketched in (142-b) present the two eventualities e and e' as temporally independent. The relation of precedence is introduced indirectly via acquaintance of the attitude holder with $g(2)$.

As already discussed in chapter 3 for Asante Twi, acquaintance-based analyses correctly rule out forward-shifted interpretations due to the upper limit constraint. However, they do allow for simultaneous readings under an appropriate time-concept (for example, ‘now’). How do we explain then the systematic absence of these readings for the two Italian perfects?

In the case of Asante LEN-embeddings, I posited that the ULC must apply locally, for each subinterval of the attitude interval, in compliance with the ATH principle, repeated in (143).

- (143) Attitude’s Temporal Homogeneity (ATH)
 Given an attitude P , held by $x_{(e)}$ toward the proposition $q_{\langle s, (i, t) \rangle}$,
 $\forall \langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Dom}(P) \rightarrow [q(w')(t') \rightarrow \forall t [t \subseteq t' \rightarrow q(w')(t)]]$

Given that both perfects share the perfective aspectual profile of LEN, the same rationale is applied to APRF/SPRF-under-past reports. In simultaneous scenarios (such as (130)), an embedded perfect requires that the embedded eventuality be entirely included in the attitude temporal interval. However, the first subinterval of the attitude time serves as an upper limit to the eventuality time, thus leading to a ULC-violation. This is illustrated by the timeline in Figure 4.1.

Technically, ULC-compliant SIM-readings for perfect embeddings would be feasible if the attitude time and the eventuality time coincide (at least for their initial sub-interval). I will revisit this point in section 4.4.3 where I discuss the availability of simultaneous readings for perfect embeddings in perception contexts.

Finally, it is worth stressing that a *de re* analysis neatly rules out relative BACK-readings for SPRF-embeddings (or any past perfective embedding). As shown in section 4.1.2, these interpretations are systematically absent in future contexts, as (144) illus-

$leave(w')(e')(g(9))(L)]]]]$ (where $g(9) = \text{Marica}$)
Paraphrase: ‘There is an eventuality e , such that e is temporally included in $g(2)$ preceding t_c and there is a time-concept G suitable for Marica in the actual world throughout e , and for all the worlds w' and times t' compatible with what Marica said throughout e in the actual world, it follows that there is a PTS t'' extending until the temporal interval denoted by $G(g(1))(t')(w')$ — i.e. $g(1)$, with which Paolo is acquainted in w' at t' -, and there is an eventuality e' , such that e' is temporally included within the PTS t'' and e' is an eventuality of Luca leaving Marica in w' .

The interpretation highlighted in (149-b) locates the embedded eventuality within the temporal interval t' introduced by the perfect. Given that its final subinterval is supplied by the acquaintance-based temporal interval $G(g(1))(t')(w')$, which in turn must include both the utterance time t_c (via the present’s presupposition) and the attitude time t' (via ULC), it follows that Luca’s leaving event is (entirely) situated at some point before t_c and not strictly following t' . The latter is, once more, a consequence of the ATH. I believe this is a good proxy for the shifted interpretation, with resultative flavour, arising from (147).

A second point of departure from SPRF-embeddings pertains to future attitude reports. Recall that, in these contexts, the analytic perfect, unlike the synthetic one, is able to yield later-than-now BACK-readings. As demonstrated in section 4.1.2, relative BACK-readings only arise when the embedding predicate is the simple future. The relevant examples are repeated below.

- (150) Context: Luca plans to skip school next Friday, but he fears his parents might eventually find out.
- a. Fra qualche settimana i genitori di Luca scopriranno che
in some week DEF parents of Luca discover.FUT COMP
ha saltato la scuola.
ski.APRF DEF school
‘In a few weeks Luca’s parents will find out he skipped school.’
- b. Luca temeva che fra qualche settimana i suoi genitori
Luca fear.IMP COMP in some week DEF POSS parents
avrebbero scoperto che # ha saltato/aveva saltato la scuola.
discover.COND.PRF COMP skip.APRF/PPRF DEF school
‘Luca feared that in a few weeks his parents would find out that he skipped school.’

The key insight gained from the contrast in (150) had originally motivated a present-tensed analysis for the existential analytic perfect. Let me show how this unfolds. In (150-a), the embedded present tense is c-commanded by an agreeing tense, considered that a simple future projects a present tense and a future modal at LF. The agreement relation licenses the optional deletion of the embedded present’s semantic features, including its presupposition. The result is a *de Dicto* LF, where what is left of the embedded present is a mere bound variable, as is illustrated in the simplified structure in (151).

facilitate simultaneous interpretations even with perfective/eventive predicates (cf. Kauf & Zeijlstra, 2018; Khomitsevich, 2008; Kusumoto, 1999). This holds true also for Italian, as the following examples show.⁶⁶

- (153) Il custode ha visto che Luca ha preso il pallone dal
 DEF janitor see.APRF Luca take.APRF DEF ball from.DEF storage.room
 ripostiglio.

‘The janitor saw that Luca took the ball from the storage room.’

✓ *SIM*: $take-ball(e,L) \subseteq see(e',J)$

- (154) La commessa ha sentito che Derna ha suonato il campanello.
 DEF clerk hear.APRF COMP Derna ring.APRF DEF doorbell

‘The clerk heard that Derna rang the doorbell.’

✓ *SIM*: $ring-bell(e,D) \subseteq hear(e',C)$

Both examples are compatible with a simultaneous scenario, where the embedded eventuality is temporally contained within the perception time.⁶⁷

Recall that simultaneous interpretations can be derived via a *de re* construal, irrespective of the aspect of the embedded predicate. To dispel the possibility that the simultaneous readings in perception reports originate from a *de se* LF, let’s adjust (153) and (154) slightly and turn them into *breakfast* sentences.

- (155) Context: Luca plans to borrow the ball from the gym during tomorrow’s class break. However, Marta warned him, as the janitor will likely catch him red-handed.

a. #Marta ha detto che il custode avrebbe visto che Luca
 Marta say.APRF COMP DEF janitor see.COND.PRF COMP Luca
 ha preso il pallone dal ripostiglio.
 take.APRF/ DEF ball from.DEF storage.room
 lit. ‘Marta said that the janitor would see that Luca took the ball from the
 storage room.’

b. #*SIM*: $take-ball(e,L) \subseteq see(e',J)$
 ✓ *BACK*: $take-ball(e,L) < see(e',J)$

c. Marta ha detto che il custode avrebbe visto che Luca prendeva
 Marta say.APRF COMP DEF janitor see.COND.PRF COMP Luca take.IMP/
 il pallone dal ripostiglio.
 DEF ball from.DEF storage.room
 ‘Marta said that the janitor would see that Luca was taking the ball from

⁶⁶Sentences only contain the analytic perfect, since this is the most naturally occurring form in these contexts.

⁶⁷Clearly, simultaneous interpretations may as well arise for imp-under-past perception reports.

- (i) Il custode ha visto che Luca prendeva il pallone dal ripostiglio.
 DEF janitor see.APRF Luca COMP take.IMP DEF ball from.DEF storage.room
 ‘The janitor saw that Luca was taking the ball from the storage room.’

Notably, these sentences seem to only exhibit a simultaneous interpretation.

- $$\text{Dom}(G) \subseteq \{z: z \in D_{(i)}. \iota y[\textit{janitor}(y)] \text{ holds an acquaintance relation } R_c \text{ to } z \text{ in } w_c \text{ at } g(2)\} \quad (\text{PSP of } G_7)$$
- $$\forall \langle w', t' \rangle \in \text{Dom}(G(g(1))) \rightarrow \neg(G(g(1))(t')(w') > t') \quad (\text{ULC})$$
- b. $\llbracket (157) \rrbracket = 1$ iff
- $$\exists e[\tau(e) \subseteq g(2) \ \& \ \exists G[G \text{ a time CG suitable for } \iota y[\textit{janitor}(y)] \text{ in } w_c \text{ at } \tau(e) \ \& \ \forall \langle w', t' \rangle [\langle w', t' \rangle \in f_{V_{ideo}}(y, w_c, \tau(e)) \rightarrow \exists e'[G(g(1))(t')(w') \supseteq \tau(e') \ \& \ \textit{take}(w')(e')(\iota b[\textit{ball}(b)])(L)]]]$$

The evidential accessibility relation $f_{V_{ideo}}$ restricts the sets of worlds where the proposition is true to those where the perception holder has direct visual perception of the eventuality depicted by the proposition. This set will arguably exclusively contain worlds where $G(g(1)) = \text{'now'}$.⁷⁰ In other words, the only worlds compatible with the perceptual restriction are worlds where concept generator G generates for the temporal res $g(1)$ the time-concept ‘now’, thus leading to a simultaneous interpretation. Any time preceding would not satisfy $f_{V_{ideo}}$. Any time following it would violate the ULC.

While simultaneous interpretations for perfect(ive) embeddings were previously dismissed due to ULC, in accordance with the ATH, no such violation occurs here. Per $f_{V_{ideo}}$, the embedded eventuality time perfectly aligns with the perception time. This is illustrated by the timeline in 4.2, where the initial subinterval of the eventuality time does not follow the perception time (PT) for any of its subintervals.⁷¹

Figure 4.2: Simultaneous interpretations of perfect embeddings in perception reports

4.5 The composition of imperfect embeddings

This section explores the composition of imperfect-under-past embeddings. Building on the semantics developed in section 4.1.3, I will devise a theory that can handle all available readings of the embedded imperfect, without resorting to an SoT rule. The section is organized in two parts: in section 4.5.1, I will show that the SoT ambiguity in past contexts can be accounted for, assuming different binding configurations for the temporal imperfect. More specifically, backward-shifted interpretations result from local binding of the imperfect’s reference time, while simultaneous interpretation arise when locally binding its evaluation time. In section 4.5.2, I demonstrate that no binding pattern can explain null readings (that is, simultaneous readings associated with future attitude reports and permanent states of affairs). Subsequently, I show that a non-vacuous analysis of the modal imperfect can be maintained in these cases, if the tense variable determining

⁷⁰ $G(g(1)) = \text{'now'}$ entails that $G(g(1))(t')(w') = g(1) = t'$.

⁷¹ XT_i = initial subinterval of XT ; XT_f = final subinterval of XT .

- a. Oggi Paolo ha scommesso che durante il campeggio Marta
 today Paolo bet.APRF COMP during DEF camping Marta
 avrebbe detto che aveva fame.
 say.COND.PRF COMP have.IMP hunger
 ‘Paolo bet that during the camping trip Marta would say that she was
 hungry.’

In section 4.3.2, we demonstrated that in this scenario, the EvalT index fails to identify a suitable antecedent. Neither structurally nor contextually provided temporal referents fulfill the presupposition of the imperfect tense — namely, that its reference precedes a later time (see also (135)). In fact, in *breakfast*-scenarios, the most-embedded tense usually already picks up the furthest future temporal interval. A plausible solution might be to hypothesize that, akin to the past tense in SoT languages, the Italian imperfect might undergo deletion under temporal agreement. We delve into this question further in the subsequent section.⁷⁵

4.5.2 Modal imperfect and null readings

This section delves into the derivation of temporally null readings for imperfect embeddings. Traditionally, these readings have been used to support the existence of an SoT rule and, thereby, the optional vacuity of past tense under suitable licensing conditions. However, I will show that such interpretations primarily arise in *modal* contexts and can still be compositionally built while maintaining the imperfect’s temporal pastness.

Can the imperfect be vacuous?

In the previous section, we have observed that an analysis reliant on a temporal notion of the imperfect is not able to account for so-called null readings arising in breakfast reports and permanent states of affairs. In this respect, Italian perfectly aligns with English and other SoT languages (see also paraphrases in (166) and (167)), in that it admits a past-tensed form that does not superficially convey any temporal pastness. The relevant pieces of data already discussed in section 4.3.2 are repeated below.

- (166) *Breakfast report:*
 SIM-Context: Paolo is organizing a camping trip for the weekend with Marta. He’s worried that Marta didn’t pack enough food. He tells you, “While camping, she’ll get hungry and start complaining. You’ll see!” Later, you report what he said.

⁷⁵In the interest of space, I am omitting the analysis of imperfect-under-future reports here. However, let me point out that, given the array of combinatorial options available, both absolute and relative BACK-readings can be accurately derived under a free variable construal for the RT, with the EvalT variable bound by t_c or (locally) by the attitude verb. Importantly, a bound variable construal for the RT-variable correctly rules out the unattested simultaneous reading due to a presupposition failure. Specifically, it would assert that the RT follows t_c , being bound by the future attitude time, while presupposing that it precedes t_c , as required by the imperfect’s presupposition.

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- a. Oggi Paolo ha scommesso che durante il campeggio Marta
today Paolo bet.APRF COMP during DEF camping Marta
avrebbe detto che aveva fame.
say.COND.PRF COMP have.IMP hunger
'Paolo bet that during the camping trip Marta would say that she was
hungry.'

(167) *Permanent states of affairs:*

- a. Gianni credeva che 9 fosse un numero primo.
Gianni think.IMP COMP 9 be.IMP.SUBJ NDEF number prime
'Gianni thought that 9 was a prime number.'
- b. In passato si riteneva che la Terra fosse piatta.
in past SI believe.IMP COMP DEF Earth be.IMP.SUBJ flat
'In the past it was believed that the Earth was flat.'

At first glance the data in (166) and (167) seemed to lend support for an SoT theory for Italian. However, in the following discussion, I will examine evidence that appears to challenge this view. Taking English as a model SoT language, I will show that a clear divide between English and Italian emerges when it comes to the conditions licensing a null past tense. Specifically, while (vacuous) past tense uses are observed exclusively for the imperfect, they become marginal if not impossible in complements of desire verbs and present X-marked conditionals. Surprisingly, however, these uses manifest themselves in instances where no apparent tense agreement is visible.

(i) *Before clauses*

Building on Sharvit (2014), Sharvit (2018) shows that for English null readings are possible even for eventive predicates in before clauses. Consider the following examples (adapted from Sharvit, 2018, p. 238):⁷⁶

- (168) a. John moved before Ella graduated.
b. John said that he would move before Ella graduated.

When transforming (168-a) into a breakfast report as in (168-b), a null readings obtains, in that, under (168-b)'s most natural reading, Ella's graduation is located after the utterance time. An SoT rule can neatly account for this reading, given that the most-embedded past tense is deleted under agreement with 'would' and 'said' (for compositional details, see Sharvit). Crucially, in (168), the stativity requirement of vacuous readings is lifted, thus suggesting that these readings must be attributed to a grammatical mechanism rather than to a lexical aspectual requirement. Unsurprisingly, similar readings arise in Italian when the before clause contains a subjunctive imperfect. Note that, however, the imperfectivity requirement in this case cannot be lifted, as the following translations show.

- (169) a. Gianni si trasferì prima che Ella si
Gianni SI move.SPRF before COMP Ella SI

⁷⁶Subjects between clauses were varied to prevent competition with the infinitival construction in Italian.

- laureasse/è laureata.
graduate.[SUBJ.IMP]/[IND.APRF]
- b. Gianni ha detto che si sarebbe trasferito prima che Ella si
Gianni say.APRF COMP SI move.COND.PRF before COMP Ella SI
laureasse/#sia laureata.
grauate.SUBJ.IMP/APRF

As previewed in the discussion on perception reports in section 4.4.3, it seems that null readings in Italian cannot be disentangled from imperfect morphology after all.

Similar concerns arise with what I call the ‘triggering problem of SoT’. Sharvit acknowledges, without further elaboration, that while attitude verbs, ‘would’ and ‘want’ serve as SoT triggers, ‘before’ does not. This explains the lack of SoT effects in (168-a) compared to (168-b) and (170-a), which is reported below (the Italian translation is mine).

- (170) (From Sharvit, 2018, p. 241)
- a. Did you want anything from the happy hour menu before it ended?
b. Voleva qualcosa dal menu dell’happy hour prima che
want.IMP something from.DEF menu of.the=happy hour before COMP
finisse?
end.IMP.SUBJ

While Sharvit grapples with explaining the past tense morphology in the matrix clause, she attributes that found in the before-clause to an SoT rule. The Italian translation in (170-b) once again displays the same morphological make-up observed so far.

These observations prompt the question of how to formulate an SoT rule most effectively in Italian without relying on costly stipulations, considering that restrictions arise both in terms of which (past tense) forms are targeted and which forms can actively target.

(ii) *Desire reports.*

Desire reports typically exhibit *fake past* morphology (cf. Iatridou, 2000; Wimmer, 2020), which may license a vacuous past tense in its immediate scope, as is shown in (171).

- (171) I wish you had a car that **worked** perfectly and never **had** issues.
- a. *SIM-reading*: ‘In all the speaker’s wish-worlds, the addressee owns x at t, such that x is a car and x works perfectly at t and x never has issues at t.’

While in English, the bold-faced past tenses may not convey pastness (under a simultaneous reading), the Italian translation requires a present tense.

- (172) Vorrei che tu avessi un’auto che
want.COND COMP you have.IMP.SUBJ NDEF=car COMP
funzioni/^{??}**funzionasse** perfettamente e che non **abbia**/^{??}**avesse**
work.SUBJ.PRES/IMP perfectly and COMP NEG have.SUBJ.PRES/IMP
mai problemi.
never problems.

In (172), the subjunctive imperfect in the relative clause sounds odd as it implies that the car was previously working fine. Note that the observed divergence does not only appear in relative clauses but also in regular attitude reports, as the following naturally occurring sentences exemplify.

- (173) Context: I want my friends to think that I am cool, but they don't seem to.
- a. I wish my friends thought I **was** cool.
 - b. Vorrei che i miei amici pensassero che
want.COND COMP DEF my friends think.IMP.SUBJ COMP
sono/#ero figo.
be.IND.PRES/IMP cool

In (173), mere morphological agreement is not sufficient to license the bold-faced imperfective morphology on the Italian attitude report. Note that the contrast is not specific to the *wish*-construction, as the following example shows.

- (174) a. I'd watch any movie that **had** Michael Fassbender in it.
b. Guarderei qualsiasi film in cui {recita/reciti} /
watch.COND any film in REL act.PRES.IND/SUBJ
??{recitava/recitasse} Michael Fassbender.
act.IMP.IND/SUBJ

(iii) *X-marked conditionals*

One more environment where (morphological) licensing of a vacuous imperfect is not admitted are Present X-marked conditionals. These conditionals typically display conditional mood in Romance languages. As previously discussed in footnote⁶⁰, the conditional shows the same morphological make-up of English *would*, that is past tense + future (cf. von Stechow & Iatridou, 2023; Iatridou, 2000; Thieroff, 2010).⁷⁷ However, in attitude reports of present X-marked conditionals, only English, and not Italian, allows for vacuous readings of an embedded past tense, as shown in (175).⁷⁸

- (175) Context: You doubt John is a conspiracy theorist. However, if he were one, you're convinced he would be a Flat Earther.
- a. If John were a conspiracy theorist, he would think that the Earth **was/is** flat.
 - b. Se Gianni fosse un complottista, direbbe che la
if Gianni be.IMP.SUBJ NDEF conspiracy.theorist say.COND COMP DEF
Terra **è/#era** piatta.
Earth be.PRES/IMP
 - c. Se Gianni fosse un complottista, penserebbe che la
if Gianni be.IMP.SUBJ NDEF conspiracy.theorist think.COND COMP DEF

⁷⁷Thieroff (2010), for instance, glosses the Italian conditional as 'future imperfect'.

⁷⁸The English judgments were provided by three native speakers. For Italian judgments, I relied on my native intuition, which was further confirmed by two additional native speakers.

Terra **sia/#fosse** piatta.
 Earth be.SUBJ.PRES/IMP

In (175), the English attitude report of a present X-marked conditional may contain either a present or a past tense form. Given that the sentence refers to a permanent state of affair (that is the shape of the planet), no salient past temporal referent can be identified. Consequently, the resulting interpretation relies on a vacuous reading of the embedded past tense. By contrast, the Italian counterparts are only felicitous with a present-tensed report. In fact, the past-tensed variant strongly implies that the Earth's shape changed at some point. These results are puzzling in the light of the previously discussed data (see (167)), where similar vacuous uses for the embedded imperfect were attested in plain attitude reports. The same holds for (175), when the report is extracted from an X-marked conditional, as shown below.

- (176) Context: Gianni held a false belief regarding the Earth. He thought 'The Earth is flat.'
- a. Gianni pensava che la Terra fosse piatta.
 Gianni think.IMP COMP DEF Earth be.SUBJ.IMP flat
- b. Gianni ha detto che la Terra era piatta.
 Gianni say.APRF COMP DEF Earth be.IMP flat

Similar results are obtained for s-level predicates, as the following contrast illustrated.

- (177) Context: There's an ongoing party at my place, but I don't think John would like it at all.
- a. If John were here, he would think that the party **is/was** a disaster.
- b. Se Gianni fosse qui, penserebbe che la festa **sia/#fosse**
 if Gianni be.IMP here think.COND DEF party be.PRES/IMP NDEF
 un disastro.
 disaster

Importantly, the use of the imperfect becomes viable in Italian, if embedded under a Past X-marked conditional (see (178) and (179)).

- (178) Context: The hotel where you were staying last weekend was hosting a conference on various conspiracy theories. After spotting your friend Gianni wandering around the hotel, you wondered if he was there for the conference. After reporting what happened to a friend, she points out to you that Gianni cannot be a conspiracy theorist because he recently gave her a globe-shaped world map.
- a. Se Gianni fosse stato un complottista,
 if Gianni be.PPRF.SUBJ NDEF conspiracy.theorist claim.COND.PRF
 avrebbe sostenuto che la Terra **sia/?fosse** piatta.
 COMP DEF Earth be.SUBJ.PRES/IMP flat
- (179) Context: There's an ongoing party at my place. Unfortunately, Gianni isn't here; he fell ill yesterday. However, you doubt he would have enjoyed it.

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- a. Se Gianni fosse stato qui, avrebbe sostenuto
if Gianni be.PPRF.SUBJ claim.COND.PRF COMP DEF party
che la festa è/[?]era un disastro.
be.IND.PRES./IMP

While the present tense remains the most natural choice for reporting Past X-marked conditionals, the acceptability of the embedded imperfect improves. Under an SoT theory, the contrast between Present and Past X-marked conditionals is puzzling.

(iv) Simultaneity without agreement

One last challenge faced by a deletion-based analysis regards the exceptional availability of simultaneous readings in non-SoT configurations. Consider the following examples:

(180) Context: Monica rushed out of the pool because the water was cold. You're now pumping hot water into the pool, but Gianni is sceptical that will work...

- a. Vedrai che ti dirà che l'acqua era ancora
see.FUT COMP CL.2SGDAT say.FUT COMP DEF=water be.IMP still
troppo fredda.
too cold
lit. 'You'll see, she'll tell you that the water was still too cold.'

(181) Context: Sara is planning to go to a club after work and party all night. Tomorrow morning, she'll head straight to work from the club. Unfortunately, she forgot to bring a change of clothes, so now you're worried her boss might notice that she'll be wearing the same sweater.

- a. Attenta ai dettagli com'è, noterà che Sara indossava
attentive to.DEF details as=be.PRES notice.FUT COMP Sara wear.IMP
di nuovo lo stesso maglione.
again DEF same sweater
'Being attentive to details as she is, she'll notice that Sara was wearing again the same sweater.'

The sentences in (180) and (181) are compatible with a (future) simultaneous interpretation despite the lack of temporal agreement between the embedding attitude verb and the embedded imp-marked predicate. Crucially, the sentences above are considerably degraded if the aspectual adverb *still/again* is omitted. Clearly, the alleged vacuity of the embedded imperfect cannot have been licensed by any structurally higher (past-tensed) element in the sentence.

Taken together, these empirical observations raise doubts regarding the existence of an SoT rule governing temporal ambiguities for Italian attitude reports. Specifically, morphological agreement does not seem to be either a sufficient or, in some cases, a necessary condition for licensing tense vacuity. In the next section, I propose an alternative theory that does not rely on an SoT rule.

4.5.3 The proposal: sequence of tense without deletion

Building on the insights from section 4.1.3, this section develops an account of null readings of imp-marked attitude reports that dispenses with tense agreement. Specifically, I will show that these interpretations may be captured if the embedded clause features a modal imperfect, which refers back to an old source of information. Importantly, according to this analysis, the modal imperfect is interpreted temporally and, thus, conveys pastness.

Recall that the imperfect in its modal uses is endowed with an additional modal component, which restricts the IMP-marked proposition to worlds that are epistemically accessible from a contextually salient past time. The latter temporal component preserves the imperfect's pastness, even in its modal uses. This is illustrated again in (182) below.

$$(182) \quad \text{Modal IMP: } [\text{TopP } [\Box_{w_1} \text{ imp}_{2,3}] [\text{TP } \lambda w_0 [\text{T}' \text{ t}_5 [\text{AspP PFV(/IPFV)}]]]]$$

a. $\llbracket \Box \rrbracket = \lambda w_{\langle s \rangle} . \lambda t_{\langle i \rangle} . \lambda x_{\langle e \rangle} . \lambda p_{\langle e, \langle s, t \rangle \rangle} . \forall w' [w' \in f_{epistemic}(x, w, t) \rightarrow p(w')]$

In attitude contexts, the epistemic source is explicitly provided by the attitude verb. I suggest that in this case the epistemic tense $imp_{2,3}$ is always quantificationally bound by the attitude verb, as is sketched in (183).⁷⁹

One key difference from Ippolito's analysis was represented by the insertion of an additional tense variable, the reference tense t_5 , which determines the temporal orientation of the proposition. Note that, in the matrix examples presented in section 4.1.3, this tense variable was usually free and restricted by an overt adverbial. In absence of the latter, I propose that this variable is also bound by the attitude verb.

To derive a simultaneous interpretation, the reference tense variable t_5 needs to be bound by the EvalT-binder λt_2 , which, however, is co-indexed with the epistemic tense

⁷⁹Ippolito argues that a sentence with a modal imperfect like *Cosa c'era domani al cinema?* ('What was there at the movie theater tomorrow?') is equivalent to *Cosa hai detto che c'era domani al cinema?* ('What did you say there was at the movie theater tomorrow?') (Ippolito, 2004, p. 362). I believe Ippolito's paraphrase shows the intimate relation between propositional attitude verbs and modal imperfect.

variable $imp_{2,3}$. In other words, when not free, the reference tense has to be co-bound with the epistemic tense. One way to achieve that is through a temporal variant of the binding operator Σ in (184) (adapted from Buring, 2004; Schwarz, 2012).

$$(184) \quad \llbracket \Sigma_n \text{ XP} \rrbracket^g = \lambda t. \llbracket \text{XP} \rrbracket^{g[t_n \rightarrow t]}(t)$$

The Σ operator is inserted right above the EvalT-binder. It takes a property of times and returns another property of times. When we apply it to the attitude report in (185), we derive the denotation for the complement clause whose LF is given in (186), as illustrated in (187)

(185) Gianni pensava che la Terra fosse piatta.
Gianni think.IMP COMP DEF Earth be.SUBJ.IMP flat

(187) Derivation of the denotation of (186)

(i) When defined, $\llbracket \text{TopP} \rrbracket = 1$ iff

$$\forall w' [w' \in f_{epistemic}(g(9), w, g(2)) \rightarrow \exists e [g(5) \subseteq \tau(e) \ \& \ flat(w')(e)(E)]]$$

(ii) When defined, $\llbracket (186) \rrbracket =$ (by PA)

(iii) $\lambda w. \llbracket \Sigma_5 \rrbracket (\llbracket \lambda t_2. \llbracket \text{TopP} \rrbracket \rrbracket) =$ (by Lex)

(iv) $\lambda w. \lambda t. \llbracket \lambda t_2. \llbracket \text{TopP} \rrbracket^{g[t_5 \rightarrow t]}(t) =$ (by (i), P&T)

(v) $\lambda w. \lambda t. \llbracket \lambda t_2. \forall w' [w' \in f_{epistemic}(g(9), w, t^2) \rightarrow \exists e [t \subseteq \tau(e) \ \& \ flat(w')(e)(E)]] \rrbracket (t) =$ (by LC)

(vi) $\lambda w.\lambda t.[\forall w' [w' \in f_{epistemic}(g(9), w, t) \rightarrow \exists e [t \subseteq \tau(e) \ \& \ flat(w')(e)(E)]]]$

To derive the meaning of the sentence in (185), (vi) is applied to the denotation of the attitude verb, as is illustrated in (189) for the LF in (188)

- (189)
- a. $\llbracket (188) \rrbracket$ defined iff
 - $g(7) < t_c \ \& \ t_c = t_c$ (PSP of the matrix imperfect)
 - $t'' < t_c$ (PSP of the embedded epistemic tense)
 - $\forall \langle w'', t'' \rangle \in Dox(G, w_c, \tau(e')), \neg(t'' > t'')$ (ULC)
 - b. $\llbracket (188) \rrbracket = 1$ iff
 - $\llbracket cred- \rrbracket(w^8)(e^4)(\llbracket (186) \rrbracket)(G) = 1$ iff
 - $\exists e' [g(7) \subseteq \tau(e') \ \& \ \forall \langle w'', t'' \rangle \in Dox(G, w_c, \tau(e'))$
 - $\rightarrow \forall w' [w' \in f_{epistemic}(g(9), w'', t'') \rightarrow \exists e [\tau(e) \subseteq t'' \ \& \ flat(w')(e)(E)]]]$ (where $g(9) = \text{speaker}$)

Paraphrase: ‘There is an eventuality e' , such that e' temporally includes $g(7)$ preceding t_c , and for all the worlds w'' and times t'' compatible with Gianni’s thoughts in w_c throughout $\tau(e')$, for all the worlds w' compatible with speaker’s knowledge at t'' in w'' , there is an eventuality e , such that e temporally includes t'' and e is an eventuality of the Earth being flat in w' .’

As a result of the computations in (189-b), the object of (false) belief is relativized to worlds that are compatible with both the attitude holder’s believes in the actual world at some salient past time and with the speaker’s knowledge in the attitude worlds at the attitude time. The speaker’s past source of knowledge in this case is the time at which Gianni shared his thoughts. Through the binding operator Σ , the reference tense in the embedded clause is also bound by the attitude verb, thus generating a simultaneous

interpretation. Note that, as illustrated in (189-a), the presupposition of the epistemic tense is not canceled; rather, it projects through its binder up to the attitude verb. As a consequence, the modal imperfect is interpreted temporally, since it refers to a past attitude time where a certain attitude was formulated. Viewing a propositional attitude as a source of information clarifies why past-tensed propositional attitude verbs license a modal imperfect in their complement.

Before turning to Abusch's *breakfast reports*, let me briefly discuss the pragmatic effect of the modal imperfect in embedded contexts. Recall that, in its modal uses, the imperfect triggers an inference that the speaker is not in a position to endorse the proposition at the utterance time. While this conversational implicature in matrix contexts arises straightforwardly from the competition between the imperfect and the present tense, things are less trivial in embedded contexts. Firstly, in matrix clauses of attitude reports, the competition between an IMP-marked attitude verb and its present tense alternative generates the cessation implicature we discussed earlier. Due to that, the content of the report is not endorsed by the speaker at the utterance time. For permanent states, which aren't tied to a specific time, this inference implies the falsity of the proposition, regardless of the temporal interval in which it's evaluated. This inference aligns well with that of a modal imperfect. Secondly, in complement clauses, no inference can be attributed to the embedded imperfect. In the scope of an IMP-marked attitude verb, as discussed in section 4.2, a present tense is often not a suitable competitor, as its use is blocked by the same cessation implicature.

For the *breakfast sentences*, I suggest that the same mechanism is at play, the only difference being the more complex syntactic nesting. A possible derivation is illustrated below for sentence (166), repeated in (190).

- (190) Oggi Paolo ha scommesso che durante il campeggio Marta
 today Paolo bet.APRF COMP during DEF camping Marta
 avrebbe detto che aveva fame.
 say.COND.PRF COMP have.IMP hunger
SIM: 'According to Paolo earlier, Marta will say tomorrow: "I'm hungry"'

To derive the intended simultaneous interpretation, I assume that the conditional perfect in future-in-the-past constructions spells out a future modal combining with a past tense.

Zooming in on the most-embedded CP, we derive its denotation, as sketched in (191)

- (191) *LF of CP₃*

- (192) *Denotation of CP₃*

$$\llbracket (191) \rrbracket = \lambda w. \lambda t^5. [\forall w' [w' \in f_{epistemic}(g(9), w, g(2)) \rightarrow \exists e [t^5 \subseteq \tau(e) \ \& \ \text{hungry}(w')(e)(g(10))]]]$$
 (where $g(9)$ = speaker; $g(10)$ = Marta)

One key difference from the LF of the complement clause in (186) is that in (191) the epistemic tense variable t_2 remains locally free, thus allowing the Σ operator to bind it in CP_2 , as is illustrated below.

- (194) *Denotation of CP₂*

$$\llbracket (193) \rrbracket = \lambda w. \lambda t. \forall w'' [R(w)(w'') \rightarrow \exists t' > t \ \& \ \exists e' [\tau(e) \subseteq t' \ \& \ \forall \langle w''', t''' \rangle \in \text{Say}(M)(w'')(\tau(e')) \rightarrow \llbracket (191) \rrbracket (w''')(t''')]] =$$

$$\lambda w. \lambda t. \forall w'' [R(w)(w'') \rightarrow \exists t' > t \ \& \ \exists e' [\tau(e) \subseteq t' \ \& \ \forall \langle w''', t''' \rangle \in \text{Say}(M)(w'')(\tau(e'))$$

$$\rightarrow [\forall w' [w' \in f_{ep}(g(9), w''', g(2)) \rightarrow \exists e [t''' \subseteq \tau(e) \ \& \ \text{hungry}(w')(e)(g(10))]]]]]$$

After composing the denotation of (194) with the matrix attitude verb, we derive the meaning of the overall sentence as in (196)

- (196)
- a. $\llbracket (195) \rrbracket$ defined iff
- $g(22) < t_c \ \& \ t_c = t_c$ (PSP of the CP₁'s past)
 - $t^4 < t_c$ (PSP of the CP₂'s past)
 - $t_4 < t_c$ (PSP of the CP₃'s epistemic tense)
 - $\neg(t^4 > t^4)$ (ULC of CP₁)
 - $\neg(t''' > t''')$ (ULC of CP₂)
- b. $\llbracket (195) \rrbracket = 1$ iff
- $\exists e''[\tau(e'') \subseteq g(22) \ \& \ \forall \langle w^4, t^4 \rangle \in \text{Dox}(P)(w_c)(\tau(e'')) \rightarrow \llbracket (193) \rrbracket(w^4)(t^4) = 1$ iff
 - $\exists e''[\tau(e'') \subseteq g(22) \ \& \ \forall \langle w^4, \boxed{t^4} \rangle \in \text{Dox}(P)(w_c)(\tau(e'')) \rightarrow$
 - $\forall w''[\text{R}(w^4)(w'') \rightarrow \exists t' > t^4 \ \& \ \exists e'[\tau(e) \subseteq t' \ \& \ \forall \langle w''', t''' \rangle \in \text{Say}(M)(w'')(\tau(e'))$
 - $\rightarrow [\forall w' [w' \in f_{ep}(g(9), w''', \boxed{t^4}) \rightarrow \exists e[t''' \subseteq \tau(e) \ \& \ \text{hungry}(w')(e)(g(10))]]]$]

According to the definedness conditions in (196-a), the epistemic tense in the most-embedded clause is interpreted temporally in that it makes reference to a time that precedes UT. Importantly, this time differs from the one that provides a temporal reference to CP₃'s eventuality, which is locally bound by CP₂ attitude verb. This establishes a simultaneous interpretation without having to void the imperfect's tense features. The semantic temporal contribution of the modal imperfect can be outlined as follows: among the worlds appropriately partitioned for the evaluation of the most-embedded proposition (namely, worlds that are 'assertively' accessible from the doxastic worlds w^4), only worlds that are compatible with the speaker's knowledge at Paolo's betting time t^4 are considered. These are worlds where, for instance, Marta is believed to have packed too little or worlds where the camping trip is expected to be particularly tiring.

Pragmatically, a present under a perfect conditional is not a suitable competitor, given that the resulting DAR interpretation is implausible. However, somewhat more interesting is the case of the competition between the perfect conditional and the simple future.

- (197) Paolo ha scommesso che Marta dirà che ha fame.
 Paolo bet.APRF COMP Marta say.FUT COMP have.PRES hunger.
 ‘Paolo bet that Marta will say that she is hungry.’

Compared to (190), in (197) the speaker takes a present perspective. Clearly, a present-oriented epistemic stance signals a higher degree of confidence towards the proposition’s truth compared to a past epistemic stance. As a consequence, by using (190), a conversational implicature is derived, whereby the speaker is not endorsing the content of the report.⁸⁰ This is far from surprising, as counterfactual inferences have already been reported for embeddings containing a perfect conditional (cf. Bertinetto, 1986).

4.5.4 Implications of the theory and further extensions

In the remainder of this section, I will explore some of the implications of the theory developed previously and subsequently review a few empirical cases that, in my view, provide support for a modal imperfect analysis in SoT configurations.

If it looks like deletion...

Clear-cut instances of null readings attributed so far to a modal analysis have always displayed an imperfect embedded under a past-tensed operator (or a chain thereof). Two important questions that arise are: (i) why does a modal imperfect usually feature in agreeing configurations? (ii) Are there any cases that do not involve tense agreement?

Question (i) has partially already been tackled at the end of section 4.5.3, when we have observed that a modal imperfect requires a past source of information as its antecedent. If the embedding predicate denoted a present referent, the attitude report would be undefined, given that, under a modal imperfect construal, there is no salient past time at which the embedded proposition worlds are epistemically accessible from the attitude worlds, as is illustrated in (198).

- (198) Paolo ritiene che Maria sia/#fosse francese.
 Paolo believe.PRES COMP Maria be.PRES/IMP French

In a sense, the tense in the embedded clause must agree with the matrix tense. However, this constraint does not stem from a morpho-syntactic principle; instead, it follows from the semantic requirements of the tense itself. On this view, the emergence of such readings in SoT configurations is simply a consequence of the attitude verb explicitly providing the past source of information in these structures.

Similar observations can be extended to *breakfast reports*, where a modal imperfect is only licensed when in the scope of a perfect conditional. If the perfect conditional is replaced with a simple future, a simultaneous interpretation becomes much less natural.

- (199) Ieri Paolo ha scommesso che domani durante il campeggio
 yesterday Paolo bet.APRF COMP tomorrow during DEF camping
 Marta dirà che aveva fame.
 Marta say.FUT COMP have.IMP hunger

⁸⁰I leave the formal details of the computation of such an implicature for future work.

Out of the blue, the sentence in (199) is odd in that the modal imperfect cannot identify a suitable antecedent. Although, the matrix offers a past temporal referent (that is, the betting time), the epistemic stance switches from past to present under the embedded future *dirà* ('will say'). As a consequence, the more informative present tense must be used in lieu of the imperfect, as is shown in (201-b).⁸¹

Lastly, let me briefly address the exceptional SIM-cases without agreement sketched in (180) and (181). One relevant example is repeated in (200).

- (200) Context: Monica rushed out of the pool because the water was cold. You're now pumping hot water into the pool, but Gianni is sceptical that will work...
- a. Vedrai che ti dirà che l'acqua era ancora
 see.FUT COMP CL.2SGDAT say.FUT COMP DEF=water be.IMP still
 troppo fredda.
 too cold
 lit. 'You'll see, she'll tell you that the water was still too cold.'

In (200), a simultaneous interpretation is possible despite the absence of a past tense sequence. Although the attitude verb is present-oriented, the aspectual adverb *ancora* in the complement clause makes the previous iteration of the relevant eventuality salient. It is this time that serves as past source of information and that licenses the imperfect morphology on the verb.

More on the pragmatics of the modal imperfect

So far we have observed that the pragmatic effects of the modal imperfect persist in attitude reports. Now Let me elaborate further on the pragmatic interpretation of *breakfast reports*. As previously discussed, the pragmatic inference yielded by the modal imperfect in these sentences is due to the competition with the present-under-future embedding, as is illustrated by the minimal pair below.

- (201) a. Ieri Paolo ha scommesso che domani durante il campeggio
 yesterday Paolo bet.APRF COMP tomorrow during DEF camping
 Marta avrebbe detto che aveva fame.
 Marta say.COND.PRF COMP have.IMP hunger
- b. Ieri Paolo ha scommesso che domani durante il campeggio
 yesterday Paolo bet.APRF COMP tomorrow during DEF camping
 Marta dirà che ha fame.
 Marta say.FUT COMP have.PRES hunger

While (201-b) can yield an epistemically neutral reading, with (201-a) the speaker does not endorse the report. In fact, the sentence may be felicitously followed up by a 'but I wonder' continuation. The contrast is even clearer when speaker and attitude holder align.

⁸¹Given the deictic nature of the future, the most embedded proposition is evaluated from the speaker perspective at UT. It's this change of temporal/epistemic perspective that rules out the use of the imperfect in the embedded clause. I will not elaborate further on whether the present tense embedded under future in breakfast reports reflects an epistemic present or a vacuous tense.

- (202) a. ??Ieri ho deciso che dopo due settimane avrei detto a Maria che pranzavamo per l'ultima volta insieme.
 yesterday decide.APRF COMP in two weeks say.COND.PRF to Maria COMP lunch.IMP for DEF=last time together.
 'Yesterday I decided that after two weeks I would tell Maria that we were having our last lunch together.'
- b. Ieri ho deciso che fra due settimane dirò a Maria che pranziamo per l'ultima volta insieme.
 yesterday decide.APRF COMP in two weeks say.FUT to Maria COMP lunch.PRES for DEF=last time together
 'Yesterday I decided that in two weeks I'll tell Maria that we are having lunch for the last time together.'

The first person report is extremely odd. It seems to ascribe contradictory states of affair to Gianni: on the one hand he's informing the hearer of his decision, on the other he's casting doubt on it or even expressing disbelief. By contrast, the present-tensed report is perfectly adequate. Note that the choice of verb and aspect is crucial: if Gianni had used a verb+aspect combination that is sensitive to cessation implicatures, then the breakfast-continuation becomes perfectly fine, even if reported by Gianni himself.

- (203) (Fino a) ieri pensavo che fra due settimane avrei detto a Maria che pranzavamo per l'ultima volta insieme.
 up to yesterday think.IMP COMP in two weeks say.COND.PRF to Maria COMP lunch.IMP for DEF=last time together
 ↪ the speaker no longer believes that p.

The sentence in (203) triggers a strong inference that the embedded proposition is false as a result of Gianni no longer believing it.

It is worth stressing that this theory does not imply that all simultaneous readings for IMP-marked attitude reports must be reduced to a modal imperfect construal. In fact, these represent only a small subset. The canonical way to derive past simultaneity remains the *de se* binding mechanism with a temporal imperfect that was outlined in section 4.5.1.

Nevertheless, in principle, simultaneous readings for past-under-past embeddings may also be linked to an epistemic past analysis. This is exemplified by the following scenario:

- (204) Yesterday, Anna texted Bea that she wanted to join her and Carlo at 5pm, but she hasn't been replying to Bea's texts since. Now it's 4.55 pm, but Carlo is growing impatient.
- a. Carlo: Dov'è Anna?
 'Where's Anna?'
- b. Bea: Ha detto che #ha/aveva intenzione di passare alle 5.
 Bea say.APRF COMP have.PRES/IMP intention to stop.by at.DEF 5

‘Bea: “She said that she was planning to stop by at 5”’

The sentence in (204-b) yields a simultaneous reading, with Anna’s intention to show up holding at the time it was conveyed. I believe this reading can be lumped together with an epistemic interpretation, as the following (im)possible continuations show:

- (205) ‘Ha detto che aveva intenzione di passare alle 5, ... (‘She said she was planning to join at 5...’)
- a. ...ma temo non si presenterà...’ (‘but I’m afraid she won’t show up.’)
- b. #...quindi sarà qui a momenti. (‘so she’ll be here any minute.’)

Is the modal imperfect only *de se*?

Despite the epistemic and pragmatic enrichment, simultaneous interpretations derived via a modal imperfect share with those involving a temporal imperfect their *de se* nature. In both cases, the IMP-marked proposition is evaluated against the attitude holder’s now. Specifically, both types involve a binding construal where the embedded RT is bound by the attitude verb. By contrast, backward-shifted readings result from distinct derivations, as the EvalT is bound by the attitude verb only in the case of a temporal imperfect.⁸² This begs the question of whether the imperfect exhibits *de re* readings alongside *de se* ones. Following the picture laid out in this thesis, a *de re* LF should be in principle feasible when *Prefer de se!* does not preclude it (i.e., when there is no *de se* competitor). Of course, teasing apart the two resulting interpretations is no easy task, especially in the case of simultaneous readings.

An appropriate test to diagnose the availability of *de re* SIM is offered by Schlenker (1999, p. 142).

- (206) On Tuesday, Roberta read a chart at the hospital and said: ‘The doctor on duty on Tuesday was Derna, but today it’s Andrea’. Of course, Roberta was mistaken about that day’s date. She mistakenly thought it was already Thursday.
- a. ?Martedì Roberta ha sostenuto che Derna era il medico di turno.
 Tuesday Roberta claim.APRF COMP Derna be.IMP.IND DEF doctor of duty.
 ‘Last Tuesday, Roberta claimed that Derna was the doctor on duty.’

In (206-a), the (simultaneous) *de se* reading is false, given that it’s Andrea the doctor on duty at Roberta’s now. In contrast, the *de re* interpretation is true. While the sentence is a bit odd in the given context, its acceptability improves if Roberta is not ascribed any competing attitudes regarding her own now. Interestingly, the sentence is ruled out in the same context, if the embedded imperfect is subjunctive, as is illustrated in (207).

- (207) #Martedì Roberta ha sostenuto che Derna fosse il
 Tuesday Roberta claim.APRF COMP Derna be.IMP.SUBJ DEF doctor
 medico di turno.
 of duty.

⁸²For a modal imperfect, backward or forward-shifted interpretations emerge from a free variable interpretation of the reference tense. In this respect, an epistemic BACK-reading resembles a *de re* interpretation, since the reference time is interpreted *extensionally*.

‘Last Tuesday, Roberta claimed that Derna was the doctor on duty.’

The subjunctive imperfect in (207) seems to impose a self-ascription to the attitude holder. I leave an investigation of the observed mood effects to future work.⁸³

Generalized epistemic past, ULC and X-marking

Epistemic past vs Klecha (2016)

Since Klecha (2016), it has been observed that the ULC may be violated for a restricted set of attitude verbs including verbs of desire (see (208)).

- (208) Adapted from Klecha (2016, p. 3):
- a. John hoped Mary **tried** to kill him first. (✓FORW)
 - b. John hoped Mary **missed** the cut. (✓FORW)
 - c. Thirteen months. Mary prayed she **survived** that long. (✓FORW)

The attitude reports in (208) denote forward-shifted interpretations, whereby the embedded eventuality holds at a time that follows the attitude time, thus violating the ULC. Klecha defends a theory where ULC-like constraints are lexicalized as a presupposition and hardwired in the modal base of attitude verbs. Abstracting away from formal details, Klecha shows that attitude verbs with a doxastic, reportative or epistemic modal base must obey the ULC, as their modal base restricts the attitude worlds w' and times t' to temporal segments up to t' .⁸⁴ As a result, past-tensed reports of past-tensed reportative or belief-verbs do not exhibit forward-shifted interpretations, as illustrated below.

- (209) a. John thought Mary tried to kill him first. (#FORW)
 b. Thirteen months, Mary said she survived that long. (#FORW)

By contrast, attitude verbs with bouletic, deontic or teleological modal base as in (208) can flout the ULC, as their modal base partitions the attitude world-time pairs as to include temporal sections from the attitude time onward.⁸⁵ On this view, it's the type of attitude verb that determines the range of temporal interpretations its clausal complement admits and not a universal cognitive constraint.

Klecha makes two more assumptions regarding the interpretation of attitude reports: the existence of a Kratzerian SoT rule and an Abusch-style non-past semantics for the present. Consider for instance the sentence in (208-b). Following Klecha's theory, its underlying simplified structure is the one in (210-a), with the resulting (simplified) interpretation as that paraphrased in (210-b)

⁸³Judgments for both sentences are subtle and warrant a more systematic empirical investigation. While I'm entertaining the possibility that (indicative) imperfect embeddings might additionally involve *de re* construals, it's worth noting that (non-conclusive) arguments against this view have been presented in Giorgi, 2009; Ippolito, 2004.

⁸⁴Klecha calls these temporal sections 'actual histories'. In other words, reportative and belief verbs can only be backward-looking.

⁸⁵Klecha calls these temporal sections 'future histories'.

- (210) a. [PAST ... J-hope [NPAST ... M-miss-the-cut]]
 b. ‘For all worlds w' and times t' compatible with John’s desires at some past time t'' and in the actual world w_c , there is a time t , such that $t \geq t'$ & Mary misses the cut in w' at t .’

Semantically, the interpretation paraphrased in (210-b) is equivalent to that of the sentence ‘John hoped that Mary misses the cut.’ and is compatible with a forward-shifted reading for which the embedded eventuality follows the time of hoping. Crucially, once the syntactic structure is sent to the PF component of the system, the morphological realization of NPAST is optionally transformed into PAST following an SoT-based feature transmission mechanism. As a result, the sentence is spelled out as in (208-b).

Note that the semantic derivation producing (210-b) goes through because the attitude verb *hope* has a bouletic modal base, which in turn allows for forward-looking reports. However, in the case of belief reports such as (209-a), although the semantic derivation produces an interpretation that is compatible with both SIM and FORW in a similar fashion, the shifted reading is filtered out to avoid a clash with the doxastic modal base of *believe*. This is due to the presupposition of the attitude verb that only allows for temporal segments up to the attitude time. As a consequence, whenever an SoT rule applies, the only attested interpretation for these sentences is a simultaneous one.

While Klecha’s theory elegantly explains several temporal patterns attested for English attitude reports, I contend that the modal imperfect embeddings discussed so far cannot be lumped together with Klecha’s cases. Recall that forward-shifted interpretations are readily available also for Italian desire reports. However, these are restricted to imperfect embeddings, as illustrated below.

- (211) FORW-Context: Marta’s hope: “Luca is going to miss”’
 a. Marta ha sperato che Luca mancasse il bersaglio.
 Marta hope.APRF COMP Luca miss.IMP.SUBJ DEF target
 ‘Marta hoped that Luca missed/would miss the target.’
 b. #Marta ha sperato che Luca abbia mancato il bersaglio.
 Marta hope.APRF COMP Luca miss.APRF.SUBJ DEF target
 ‘Marta hoped that Luca missed/would miss the target.’

Importantly, forward-shifted interpretations are available even for reportative and doxastic attitude verbs.

- (212) a. Marta credeva che Luca mancasse il bersaglio. E invece
 Marta believe.IMP COMP Luca miss.IMP DEF target and instead
 è rimasta piacevolmente sorpresa quando l’ha centrato!
 remain.APRF pleasantly surprised when CL.3SG.ACC=AUX hit.APRF
 ‘Marta believed that Luca would miss the target. Instead she was pleasantly surprised when he hit it!’
 b. Marta ha detto che ci raggiungeva più tardi.
 Marta say.APRF COMP CL.1PL.ACC reach.IMP more late
 ‘Marta said she would join us later.’

Conceivably, a theory constraining temporal relations only on the basis of the embedding

predicate's modal base cannot satisfactorily explain the data in (212).⁸⁶

Attitude reports embedded under X-marked predicates

One additional implication of this proposal pertains to the absence of null readings under X-marked operators that are not past-oriented. In section 4.5.2, we demonstrated that the imperfect cannot yield simultaneous readings when embedded under a simple conditional, marking either a desire predicate akin to *wish* or the consequent of a present X-marked conditional. Interestingly, the acceptability of the imperfect was much improved when embedded under past X-marked conditionals. While these data challenged the view that the imperfect might be vacuous under tense agreement, the contrast between present and past X-marked conditionals was puzzling. This is repeated below.

- (213) Under a simultaneous reading:
- a. Se Gianni fosse un complottista, sosterrebbe che la
 if Gianni be.IMP.SUBJ NDEF conspiracy.theorist say.COND COMP DEF
 Terra è/~~#era~~ piatta.
 Earth be.PRES/IMP
 'If Gianni was a conspiracy theorist, he would claim that the Earth is/was flat.'
- b. Se Gianni fosse stato un complottista, avrebbe sostenuto
 if Gianni be.PPRF.SUBJ NDEF conspiracy.theorist claim.COND.PRF
 che la Terra è/[?]era piatta.
 COMP DEF Earth be.PRES/IMP flat
 'If Gianni had been a conspiracy theorist, he would have claimed that the Earth is/was flat.'

Building on Kaufmann (2023)'s analysis of X-marked conditionals, I posit that the puzzle finds an easy solution, under the hypothesis that only past X-marked conditionals exhibit a 'temporal past'.

In a nutshell, according to Kaufmann, all X-marked conditionals exhibit a layer of *fake past*⁸⁷ that is interpreted modally (Iatridou, 2000; Schulz, 2014). This operates a modal expansion on the set of possible worlds quantified over. In addition to this layer, past X-marked conditionals exhibit a layer of *real past*, which is interpreted temporally and shifts the evaluation time of the antecedent-worlds back to a time when they were still accessible (see also Mizuno & Kaufmann, 2018). Contributing to these insights are two key data points from lifetime effects and countermathematicals. I illustrate the latter, but see also Kaufmann (2023, p. 408) for the former.

- (214) *Countermathematicals* (Kaufmann, 2023, p. 411)
- a. If 9 were even, it would be divisible by 2.

⁸⁶With this, I do not intend to imply that my theory is incompatible with Klecha's. It is entirely possible that the constructions for which the two theories were devised involve different types of SoT configurations.

⁸⁷The term 'fake past' commonly found in the conditionals literature should not be equated to the notion of 'vacuous' or 'null' tense adopted here for SoT phenomena.

- b. ??If 9 had been even, it would have been divisible by 2.

In (214), the antecedent denotes a universal mathematical truth. While the present X-marked conditional in (214-a) is felicitous, the past one in (214-b) is odd and can only be rescued, for instance, in a scenario where the speaker as a child was incorrectly taught that 9 was even.

Note that these observations can be extended to Italian, as shown below.

- (215) a. Se 9 fosse.IMP primo, sarebbe.COND divisibile per due.
 b. ??Se 9 {fosse stato}.PPRF.SUBJ primo, {sarebbe stato}.COND.PRF divisibile per due.

Despite the different formal implementation, Kaufmann's analysis of the semantic contribution of the (additional) *real past* in past X-marked conditionals roughly resembles that of the epistemic past adopted here for the modal imperfect. In both cases, the past tense manipulates the temporal coordinate of the accessibility relation.

Under Kaufmann's account, it becomes clear why in Italian (as opposed to English) a modal imperfect cannot be licensed in the scope of a single X-marking layer. Present X-marked conditionals and X-marked desire-predicates cannot make reference to a salient past source of information, given their fake past morphology. Conversely, past X-marked conditionals include an additional layer of past, which introduces a suitable antecedent for the modal imperfect (i.e., the time at which the proposition-worlds are accessible).

To conclude this section, we have demonstrated that Italian patterns at first glance parallel those of English and SoT languages by expressing simultaneous readings via past-tensed embeddings. Furthermore, using breakfast contexts and permanent states of affairs as diagnostics, we have tied the existence of simultaneous 'null' readings in attitude reports to an embedded imperfect. However, departing from well-established SoT accounts, I have proposed a theory that derives these readings without relying on an agreement-based mechanism, but appealing to the modal semantics of the imperfect instead. Specifically, the imperfect is interpreted as past, as the content of the report is evaluated against a past source of evidence, with simultaneity emerging via the default binding of an RT variable.

4.6 Italian as an SoT language and present tense vacuity

In relation to the SoT debate, the picture emerging from this chapter can be subsumed as follows:

- (216) *The SoT status of Italian*
- Italian is an SoT language**, in that (past and future) simultaneous readings are primarily conveyed via a sequence of the same tense form.⁸⁸
 - The Italian **present may be semantically vacuous** under agreement.
 - The Italian **past tense forms — including the two perfects and the imperfect — are never semantically vacuous.**

⁸⁸Tense form in a broad sense.

The generalizations in (216) enrich the crosslinguistic landscape by highlighting micro-variation within the SoT family. Alongside canonical SoT languages involving tense deletion/agreement, there seem to exist languages such as Italian where this is restricted to the present tense. An outstanding question arising from (216) is why a language should allow for the co-existence of (216-b) and (216-c). In other words, why would a language allow for deletion of tense features if the morphological form is present but block it if it's past? A related question is: Is tense vacuity the only way we can characterize SIM-readings for present-under-present embeddings in Italian?

To answer this question, let me briefly remind the reader that the optional vacuity of the present tense was assumed to account for specific readings attested in future contexts, namely SIM for present-under-future and BACK for APRF-under-future. Furthermore, an agreement-based theory additionally accounts for the absence of shifted readings for the analytic perfect in the scope of a perfect conditional or a past perfect.

Despite the theoretical appeal, this analysis is not without its downsides. First of all, it might overgenerate, allowing for unattested simultaneous readings in present-under-present configurations. Consider the APRF-under-APRF embedding in (217).

- (217) Marta si è finalmente accorta che ha perso il telefono, #però
 Marta SI AUX finally realize.APRF COMP lose.APRF DEF phone but
 poi lo ha trovato.
 then CL.3SG.ACC find.APRF
 lit. 'Marta has finally realized that she lost her phone, but then she has found it.'
- a. [pres_{4,3} ...pres_{2,3}]: ... $\exists t'$ [XN(t' , g(4)) & ... $\exists t''$ [XN(t'' , t')... p(t')] (g(4) \supseteq t_c)
 b. [pres_{4,3} ...pres_{2,3}]: ... $\exists t'$ [XN(t' , g(4)) & ... $\exists t''$ [XN(t'' , g(4))... p(t'')] (g(4) \supseteq $t_c \subseteq$ g(2))

In (217), the adverb and the predicate type force a resultative present-tensed interpretation of the analytic perfect. In turn, this is expected to license deletion on the embedded present tense, thus producing a BACK-like interpretation for which the losing of the phone happened at some point within the temporal interval extending until the realizing time (see (217-a)). Clearly, this is not what the sentence means, as its unacceptable continuation shows. In fact, the only available reading appears to be the one sketched in (217-b), where the embedded present is semantically interpreted.

Similar conclusions are reached in view of the data in (218), where the embedded proposition can cease to hold only if containing a past tense form.

- (218) Marica ha scoperto che il vaso #è/era rotto,
 Marica discover.APRF COMP DEF vase be.PRES/IMP broken and
 e lo ha prontamente aggiustato.
 CL.3SG.ACC AUX promptly fix.APRF
 lit. 'Marica has found out that the vase is/was broken and has immediately fixed it.'

In (218), an embedded vacuous present tense would yield a simultaneous reading, indicating that the vase was broken at the time of discovery. Nothing, however, prevents

the broken state from ending. Unless, of course, the embedded present is semantically interpreted, resulting in a double access reading.

A second concern pertains to relative clauses — whose temporal interpretation we have largely overlooked here. Although present-tensed relative clauses generally show purely indexical readings (see (219)), simultaneous interpretations are equally attested, especially for restrictive/*de Dico* interpretations (see (220)).

- (219) Domani Paola intervisterà il senatore che sta parlando alla
tomorrow Paola interview.FUT DEF senator COMP speak.PRES.PROG at.DEF
radio.
radio
'Tomorrow Paola will interview the senator that is speaking at the radio.'
- a. ✓ *de re*: $t_{speak} \subseteq t_c < t_{interview}$
b. # *de se*: $t_{speak} = t_{interview} > t_c$
- (220) Domani la clinica ammetterà solo i pazienti che sono
tomorrow DEF clinic admit.FUT only DEF patients COMP be.PRES
gravemente malati.
seriously ill
'Tomorrow the clinic will admit only patients who are seriously ill.'
- a. ✓ *de re*: $t_{ill} \subseteq t_c < t_{admit}$
b. ✓ *de se*: $t_{ill} = t_{admit} > t_c$

Accounting for (220-b) in the same vein as its complement clause counterpart is problematic.⁸⁹ Arguably, nominal adjuncts like relative clauses are syntactic islands and, therefore, opaque to mechanisms such as agreement.⁹⁰ In fact, in Kratzer (2009), 'fake indexicals' in similar configurations involve a different derivation.

Note that one additional reason for assuming an agreement-like analysis for the English present is offered by Aonuki (2022). Aonuki shows that present-under-future relative clauses may receive either a simultaneous or a forward-shifted interpretation, based on the lexical aspect of the embedded predicate. Importantly, forward-shifted readings suggest an SoT analysis, since futurate uses for the same predicate are not attested in matrix contexts, as is illustrated below.

- (221) Context: A fortune teller looking into her crystal ball (adapted from Aonuki, 2022, p. 99)
- a. In 2026 you will meet a man who falls in love with you. (FORW)
b. #In 2026 a man falls in love with you.

Crucially, in Italian, forward-shifted readings for present-under-future relative clauses are absent (see (222)), thus weakening the argument for tense-agreement.

- (222) a. Nel 2026 incontrerai un uomo che si
in.DET 2026 pro.2SG meet.FUT DET man COMP SI

⁸⁹This is however precisely the option adopted by Ogiwara & Sharvit (2012), where intensional operators like FUT can bind the trace left by a vacuous present in a relative clause.

⁹⁰Thanks to Seth Cable (p.c.) for pointing this out to me.

- #innamora/innamorerà di te.
 fall.in.love.PRES/FUT of you
 b. #Nel 2026 un uomo si innamora di te.
 in.DET 2026 DET SI fall.in.love.PRES with you

The solution offered by Kratzer builds on Anand & Nevins (2004) and Schlenker (1999, 2003b)'s hypothesis that some operators are able to shift indexicals, thus binding context indices akin to what suggested by Cable (2005). In our case, following an idea from Cable (2015), the future can be viewed as a context-shifting operator, binding evaluation times of indexicals.⁹¹

One advantage of this analysis is the fact that it can additionally account for *de Dicto* shifted interpretations of APRF-under-future embeddings in both attitude reports and relative clauses (see (223)).

- (223) Lunedì, Marta intervisterà il candidato che ha vinto le elezioni
 Monday Marta interview.FUT DEF candidate COMP win.APRF DEF elections
 il giorno prima.
 DEF day before
 'On Sunday, Marta will interview the candidate who won the election the day before.'

For completeness, it's worth mentioning that an agreement mechanism cannot be rescued for relative clauses even if we assumed that feature transmission could be aided through the mediation of a lexical governor like the main verb. Consider the following sentence.

- (224) Entro i 50 anni Luca avrà sposato qualcuno che lavora
 within DEF 50 years Luca AUX.FUT marry.PRF someone REL work.PRES
 al governo.
 at.DEF government.
 'By the age of 50, Luca will have married someone who works in government'

The sentence in (224) is compatible with a (future) simultaneous interpretation. If we were to assume that agreement between the present in the relative clause and the present-tensed future in the matrix was mediated by the lexical verb *married*, it would be hard to justify why the tense features do not appear on the latter.⁹²

Now, while this narrative is attractive, it's not without its pitfalls. Particularly, its formal implementation poses several challenges. For instance, it's unclear how the future may shift indexical tenses leaving deictic temporal adverbials unshifted.⁹³ Unfortunately, the proper treatment of the present in future contexts remains an open puzzle to be addressed in future work. Despite that, as will become apparent in chapter 5, one emerging

⁹¹Along the same lines, Giorgi (2010b) suggests that the future can shift the 'speaker's coordinate'.

⁹²By contrast, in *Maria deve aver pensato che io fossi Giacomo* 'Maria must have thought that I was Giacomo', a null reading arises although the matrix verbal paradigm is present-tensed. Depending on the theory, this shows that the past participle is either semantically active or bears intervening past tense morphology. Clearly, neither is consistent with an explanation in terms of agreement for (224).

⁹³Obviously, sentences such as 'In two days Marta will interview a man who will be elected president tomorrow.' does not have a forward-shifted reading for which the man is elected president in three days.

crosslinguistic pattern indicates that the present tense can always be shifted in future contexts, irrespective of the syntactic domain. Therefore, I take the question of present tense vacuity to be orthogonal to that of the SoT typology. In other words, determining whether a language has a Sequence of Tense and, more specifically, licenses tense vacuity, can only be answered by examining the past tense.

In this respect, the possibility for Italian to derive simultaneity through an epistemic past adds a new parameter of variation, whereby tenses in SoT languages may be considered as vacuous (*+Vac*) or non-vacuous (*-Vac*). This prediction is taken up in the next chapter.

4.7 Summary

This chapter provided a detailed investigation into how temporal meaning arises in Italian, especially within attitude contexts. In section 4.1, I introduced the temporal-aspectual system of Italian, focusing on the present tense, the imperfect, and the two perfect forms. I showed that, like English, the Italian present tense is essentially indexical. Similarly, the synthetic perfect denotes a deictic pronominal tense, relativized to the utterance time. In contrast, the analytic perfect, reflecting its historical development, displays a systematic ambiguity between a pronominal past and a present-tensed perfect. The imperfect is more complex; its anaphoric properties reflect its pronominal semantics. However, following Ippolito (2004)'s work, we demonstrated that the imperfect is not restricted to a past temporal orientation but can also be used in future contexts. Nonetheless, even in future scenarios, the imperfect retains its pastness, referencing a past source of information.

In section 4.2, I focused on the double access reading produced by present-under-past constructions. This interpretation is attributed to a *de re* analysis. More interestingly, I showed that DAR is less natural under subjunctive mood compared to indicative mood due to the pragmatic principle *Maximize Presupposition!*. Similar observations are extended to the competition between the imperfective and perfective aspects of the embedding predicate, explained in terms of cessation implicatures.

Section 4.3 presented the basic empirical facts regarding the temporal interpretation of past-oriented forms in attitude contexts, with particular attention to the Sequence of Tense parameter. This exploration reveals an asymmetry between perfect and imperfect embeddings, noting that only the latter appear to correlate with *de se* readings.

Building on these empirical findings, section 4.4 offered a compositional derivation of backward-shifted interpretation that appeals to temporal *de re*. While this analysis correctly predicts the availability of BACK-readings only in past contexts for the synthetic perfect, for the analytic perfect, the attested relative shifted interpretations in future contexts result from the deletion of the present tense. Furthermore, I argued that a deletion analysis must be ruled out for the exceptional simultaneous readings observed in perception reports.

Section 4.5 explored the composition of imperfect-under-past embeddings without resorting to an SoT rule. In the first part, I show that the SoT ambiguity in past contexts can be explained by assuming different binding configurations for the temporal imperfect. In the second part, I note that this analysis cannot be extended to genuine null readings. For these, I adopted a modal analysis of the imperfect, relying on its epistemic properties.

Finally, section 4.6 discussed potential issues related to an SoT analysis of the embedded present, offering an alternative solution in terms of context-shifting. This analysis is particularly attractive for Italian because it avoids postulating an SoT rule that only targets present tense. This issue is explored in greater detail in the next chapter.

5 Discussion: towards a cross-linguistic model

This chapter builds on the theoretical and empirical insights gained in the previous chapters, aiming to integrate them within the larger crosslinguistic landscape. The ultimate goal is to develop a novel model that accounts for the observed variability in Sequence of Tense phenomena, by considering all the relevant contributing factors.

Departing from existing models which suffer from non-falsifiability and the introduction of unconstrained parameters of variation, I propose an alternative predictive model, whose boundaries of application are clearly defined. With this in mind, I seek to make two primary contributions: (i) demonstrate that parameter-setting for languages is not arbitrary but rather determined by efficiency-based criteria and a clear division of labour between present and past tense; (ii) shed light on variability concerning temporal *de re*, thereby expanding on the *de re* Variability parameter introduced at the outset of this thesis and repeated in (1).

- (1) *The De Re Variability parameter* (after Bochnak et al., 2019, p. 446)
Languages vary in the degree of availability of temporal *de re*.

Section 5.1 delves into the *de re* Variability parameter, conducting a thorough exploration of the conditions influencing the extent to which temporal *de re* is available. This investigation unveils factors inherent to the semantic shape of tense forms as well as those rooted in broader cognitive-pragmatic principles. In contrast, Section 5.2 shifts its focus to the SoT parameter, downplaying its typological relevance in light of empirical findings from Western Romance languages and German. Proceeding to Section 5.3, a preliminary proposal for a new model is outlined, centered on the shiftability of present tense and its interplay with past tense. Furthermore, two potential counterexamples are discussed, namely Washo and Modern Greek. Lastly, Section 5.4 extends the discussion, contemplating how linguistic economy and transparency might offer insights into the observed variability.

5.1 Constraints on *de re* attitudes and the crosslinguistic landscape

Building on the empirical and theoretical insights from the preceding chapters, this section aims to formulate generalizations regarding the derivation of simultaneous interpretation in attitude reports. Specifically, in line with Bochnak et al. (2019), I argue that the availability of *de re* in natural language cannot be reduced to a categorical distinction.

To this end, I show that *de re* ascriptions are systematically constrained by seemingly universal factors, ultimately determining the observed gradable patterns.

First, let me summarize the main findings on Asante and Italian. In Asante Twi, the most fruitful compositional strategy for deriving simultaneous readings involves *de se* LFs associated with bare embeddings. Alongside this bound-variable representation, Asante makes use of a *de re* mechanism that targets the two pronominal tenses *ná* and LEN. However, while (*de re*-based) simultaneous interpretations are generally available for the imperfective distal tense, they are severely restricted for the perfective past pronoun and are only attested when a modifier forces co-reference between embedding attitude and embedded reference times. The reason for this divergent behaviour has been attributed to two principles: *Prefer de se!* and *Prefer unbounded structures!*

In a remarkably similar manner, Italian derives simultaneous interpretations via (epistemically neutral or enriched) *de se* LFs involving an imperfective tense. Comparably, *de re* LFs for the two perfective forms are generally ruled out in attitude reports and are only feasible under perception verbs biasing co-temporal interpretations. Importantly, the same principles limiting *de re* LFs for unbound tense forms and perfective tense forms in Asante Twi also apply in Italian.

Looking at it from another perspective, both languages appear rule out *de re* ascriptions for their existential/quantificational tense forms. In particular, when compared to the pronominal forms *ná* and *IMP*, the two quantificational tenses *a* (in Asante) and *APRF* (in Italian) resist acquaintance-based analyses.¹

5.1.1 The *de re* variability parameter

Placed within the broader cross-linguistic context, the patterns highlighted for Asante and Italian do not constitute two isolated cases. In what follows, I will explore the underpinnings of the variability postulated by the parameter in (1), which can be subsumed as in (2).

(2) *Factors affecting the availability of simultaneity and de re ascriptions:*

- (i) Pronominal/deictic > Quantificational/relative
- (ii) *de se* LFs > *de re* LFs
- (iii) Imperfective aspect > perfective aspect
- (iv) Perception, factive verbs & deictic adverbials

(i) Pronominal/deictic > quantificational/relative

Quantificational and relative tenses tend to resist a *de re* analysis compared to pronominal or deictic tenses.

The reason behind (i) is straightforward. A *de re* analysis for tense in attitude reports was originally introduced in view of its pronominal properties (Abusch, 1997, p. 5). These properties have, for instance, promoted the analogy with *de re* attitude ascriptions of referential DPs. Although *de re*-based theories have since been extended to quantificational

¹In this summary, I'm omitting the exceptional simultaneous readings of resultative *a* with change-of-state verbs. I will simply note that these readings are also associated with a *de se* construal, and, for this reason, can be grouped together with bare embeddings.

tense (Ogihara, 1996; Sharvit, 2018), this expansion has not been motivated on empirical grounds. Thus, the view pursued in this thesis aligns with the original conceptualization of *de re* tenses, by regarding pronominal tenses as ideal candidates for acquaintance-based accounts.

In a sense, the familiarity property usually associated with definite descriptions (whether time- or individual-denoting) appears to be a key component of *de re* accounts, given that they assume acquaintance of the attitude holder with the temporal/individual res. Conversely, establishing acquaintance with a given referent is more challenging in the case of quantificational tenses, which typically yield existential, indefinite temporal interpretations. Quantificational analyses for past tense markers which lack simultaneous readings in SoT embeddings have been documented, for instance, for Atayal and Javanese (Chen et al., 2021), Medumba (Mucha, 2015), and Awing (Mucha & Fominyam, 2017). In these studies, the absence of simultaneity serves as a diagnostic for a quantificational analysis of the past tense in the respective language.²

Particularly suitable for a *de re* analysis are deictic or absolute tenses. Given their strict evaluation with respect to the utterance time, deictic tenses, unless shifted, must be interpreted extensionally, thus allowing in principle for co-reference with the attitude time. This is for instance the case of Asante *ná*, which consistently expresses distance from the utterance time irrespective of the syntactic embedding. On the other hand, relative tenses (even when pronominal) are relativized to the local evaluation time and, consequently, are expected to display a lower degree of temporal transparency (i.e. of *de re* temporal evaluation).³

Can relative or quantificational tenses ever be interpreted *de re* and yield simultaneous readings? We have argued that in some special cases the Asante relative pronominal tense *LEN* appears to be compatible with overlapping readings. However, these interpretations are marginal and only possible when an overt adverbial forces co-reference. Recall that the corresponding semantic representation involves long-distance binding of *LEN*'s evaluation time with the utterance time (see (3)).

$$(3) \quad [\text{CP } t_c \boxed{\lambda t_4} [\text{TP past}_{3,4} [\text{AspP PFV} [\text{VP } \textit{Attitude} [\text{CP } \lambda G_7 [\lambda w_5 [\lambda t_2 [\text{TP } [T \boxed{\text{past}_{6,4}} \\] t_2] w_5] [\text{AspP} [\text{AspP} \text{ PFV} [\text{VP} \dots]]]]]]]]]]]]$$

It is unclear whether we want our system to allow for (3) in the first place. However, we could speculate that, if feasible, long-distance binding comes at a cost. This in turn may further explain why *de re* interpretations are harder to obtain for *LEN*-like tenses compared to *ná*-like tenses.

As shown in chapter 2, another *de re*-resistant form is the Japanese past tense marker *ta*.⁴ Recall that Japanese, unlike Hebrew and Russian, exhibits a ‘well-behaved’ past tense,

²However, Sharvit (2018) claims that “whether or not tenses are quantificational is orthogonal to the controversy surrounding SoT”.

³Gitxsan seems to constitute an exception, in that its (covert) relative pronominal tense displays a systematic ambiguity in attitude contexts. However, Aonuki (2021) shows that the covert tense comes with a non-future restriction.

⁴There is a lively debate in the literature regarding whether *ta* is a tense or an aspect, as well as whether it displays pronominal or a quantificational properties. I refer the reader to Aonuki (2021), Ogihara (2017), and Ogihara (1996) for a detailed discussion. In short, while Ogihara’s view leans toward a quantificational analysis, with existential closure semantically encoded (Ogihara, 2017; Ogihara

which consistently yields backward-shifted interpretations, irrespective of the syntactic environment. In Ogihara & Sharvit (2012), which assumes that temporal *de re* is in principle available for any given language, the absence of SIM for Japanese is attributed to the fact that the *res*-moved past tense leaves a full copy behind (as opposed to Hebrew, where the moved tense leaves a trace). Having dismissed *res*-movement as a viable option on independent grounds, it is worth discussing how concept generators can handle the Japanese case. In Sharvit (2018), which deploys CGs, existential tenses freely move to extensional positions leaving a *de re* trace behind (see (4)). However a working analysis for the *de re* past in Japanese is not clearly spelled out.

$$(4) \quad [t_c \lambda t_0 \boxed{\text{PAST}_{1,0}} \lambda t_2 \dots [\text{PAST}_{3,0} \dots [\text{say} [\lambda G_7 [\lambda w_5 [\lambda t_4 [\boxed{[[G_7 \boxed{t_2}]] t_4]} w_5] \dots]]]]]]]]$$

Clearly, (4) does not rule out a simultaneous interpretation, as the QR'ed 'PAST' denotes a time that precedes t_c , but not necessarily the attitude time. To force a backward-shifted interpretation, a copy of the existential tense has to scope below the attitude verb. Note that a solution along the lines of Ogihara & Sharvit (2012) will not suffice: given the type of CGs, a full copy of a quantificational tense cannot compose directly with the time-concept generator. We face two options: (i) CGs are type-shifted and take quantificational *res*-tenses as arguments, (ii) the *de re* past tense undergoes local raising within its intensional domain and might further move up to an extensional position. I regard (i) as theoretically and typologically implausible. A formal implementation of (ii) is sketched in (5)

$$(5) \quad [t_c \lambda t_0 (\boxed{\text{PAST}_{9,0}} \lambda t_2) \dots [\text{PAST}_{3,0} \dots [\text{say} [\lambda G_7 [\lambda w_5 [\lambda t_4 \boxed{[\text{PAST}_{9,4}} \lambda t_9 \boxed{[[G_7 \boxed{t_9}]]} t_4]} w_5] \dots]]]]]]]]$$

Intuitively, the short-distance movement of 'PAST_{9,4}' is preferred over long-distance QR due to locality. Given that its evaluation index '4' is locally bound by the attitude verb, the LF in (5) generates BACK only, regardless of whether it further moves up. In other words, to produce simultaneous interpretations, quantificational tenses like Japanese *ta* must move long-distance, skipping clause-internal landing sites (as in (4)). I believe this illustrates why from a formal perspective simultaneous readings are so difficult to obtain for existential tenses, even when they are interpreted *de re*. By contrast, pronominal tenses can be interpreted *de re* in situ (and possibly yield SIM) without any additional structural manipulations.

(ii) *de se* LFs > *de re* LFs

The upshot of the above discussion is that the computational system tends to opt for less complex compositional pathways whenever they're accessible. This is precisely what *Prefer de se!* aims to regulate. Its formulation is repeated in (6):

$$(6) \quad \textit{Prefer de se!} \\ \text{Whenever this is compatible with the situation which is reported, prefer a } \textit{de se} \\ \text{over a } \textit{de re} \text{ Logical Form.}$$

& Sharvit, 2012) or structurally supplied (Ogihara, 1996), Aonuki adopts a (relative) pronominal semantics.

The pragmatic principle in (6) explains why in non-SoT languages (with a relative present) simultaneous readings are less accessible for past-tensed embeddings compared to present-tensed ones. The reasoning goes as follows:

(i) Simultaneous readings are usually *de se*, as they involve self-locating attitudes. (ii) Two logical forms are compatible with a *de se* simultaneous interpretation: a *de se* LF with a relative present and a *de re* LF with an undeleted past. (iii) *Prefer de se!* requires that the *de se* LF be used over the *de re* one.

Clearly, if condition (i) is not met, reports with an underlying *de re* LF become viable, as the competing *de se* interpretation is false. This is, for instance, the case of mistaken temporal identity that we have been using to diagnose *de re* readings for non-vacuous tenses. However, it would be incorrect to reduce *de re* interpretations only to cases where the attitude holder is mistaken regarding their self-location.⁵ The view that temporal *de re* is restricted to a small subset of cases is indeed challenged by its natural occurrence in a number of languages (cf. a.o. SIM/BACK-readings for Asante *ná*-under-past (this thesis); SIM-readings in Russian past-under-past Khomitsevich, 2008; BACK-readings in Washo bare-under-past Bochnak et al., 2019 and SIM-readings in Tlingit past-under-past Cable, 2017). With this in mind, I posit that while *Prefer de se!* determines a general preference for *de se*/bound variable construals over *de re* ones, its application alone does not cause any blocking effect on the latter.

One more case where a *de re* past tense may be preferred to a relative present is when the speaker wants to express a strict earlier-than-now simultaneous reading, without any risk of a double access evaluation. Indexical interpretations for a relative present/non-past are indeed in principle available if this is not entirely shiftable (more on this in section 5.3). In Asante twi, for instance, my consultants have reported that *ná*-under-past may be preferable to bare-under-past in cases where the speaker wants to explicitly convey cessation of the eventuality at UT. Similarly, according to one Russian consultant, the present-under-past report in (7) is marked compared to its past-under-past counterpart.⁶

- (7) Context: Two years ago today you were walking in the park with Zhenya. You spotted Lena having a stroll with her dog. You thought she might have gained some weight, but Zhenya told you “she is pregnant, didn’t you know?”. After exactly two years, today, you report Zhenya’s words. You say:
- a. ?Žénja skazala čto Lena beremenna.
Zhenya say.PAST.PFV COMP Lena pregnant
- b. Žénja skazala čto Lena byla beremenna.
Zhenya say.PAST.PFV COMP be.PAST Lena pregnant
‘Zhenya said that Lena was pregnant.’

A key prediction that follows from (6) is that a language lacking a dedicated *de se* construal will resort to *unconstrained* temporal *de re*. I believe this is the case of the tenseless language Hausa, whose backward-shifted interpretation can only result from a *de re* mechanism (cf. Bochnak et al., 2019).

⁵In this respect, Ogihara & Sharvit (2012) claim that “[in non-SoT languages] a *de re* interpretation is allowed in principle, but in practice it is exercised only in special circumstances”.

⁶In Russian, the copula ‘be’ is dropped in the present tense.

(iii) Imperfective aspect > perfective aspect

The aspectual contrast often found in both SoT and non-SoT languages has been detailed in chapter 2. Departing from aspectual-pragmatic accounts that hinge on the superinterval property of statives or imperfectives, we have offered an alternative view that combines the temporal homogeneity of attitudes with the upper limit constraint. This has led to the formulation of the principle *Prefer unbounded structures!* repeated in (8).

(8) *Prefer unbounded structures!*

In the derivation of simultaneous readings for complement clauses of homogeneous attitude predicates, unbounded attitude reports are preferred over bounded ones.

The preference for unbounded eventuality structures in SIM-contexts results in the general absence of SIM-readings for eventive and perfective predicates. This observation leads however to an important caveat: in most of the examples throughout this thesis, the matrix verb is either eventive or marked with perfective aspect. Does this mean that eventive/perfective attitude verbs are also homogeneous? The short answer is “yes”. Given the way attitudes are conceptualized, it is plausible that even reportative predicates (which usually take an event variable) are associated with an internal mental state that is homogeneous. Conceivably, the event linked to the attitude verb may still be viewed *perfectively* (i.e., as a whole); however, its underlying mental state must remain homogeneous. This important distinction becomes apparent in the fact that attitude verbs lexically encode reference to times associated with a certain mental state (i.e., the attitude holder’s self-location), which is compatible with, but remains distinct from, the time of the corresponding eventuality.

(iv) Perception or factive verbs, and deictic adverbials

Finally, two more factors that have been shown to favour simultaneous interpretations for *de re* tenses are perception and factive verbs, as well as deictic adverbials. While the presence of SIM-readings for perfective embeddings under perception verbs has been linked to a *de se* LF, I have argued in 4 that the resulting interpretation must be ascribed to a *de re* mechanism. More specifically, perception verbs semantically encode the source of (perceptual) acquaintance between the attitude holder and the *res*, thus making a *de re*-ascription more accessible. Furthermore, perception reports have a strong bias towards a co-temporal interpretation, given that the perception of *p* typically manifests itself through direct experience of *p*. This key point illustrates why (8) can be waived in the case of perception reports: if attitude and eventuality times perfectly overlap, no violation of the local ULC arises. Arguably, factive reports exhibit a weaker bias towards overlapping interpretations. However, given that they presuppose the truth of the report in the actual world, they facilitate a *de re* interpretation in a similar manner (cf. Grønn & Von Stechow, 2010; Kratzer, 1990).

In the case of deictic adverbials like *then*, simultaneity obtains compositionally, as the temporal modifier restricts the attitude complement’s temporal evaluation to times overlapping with the matrix time. A relevant example was discussed in chapter 3, in connection to the exceptional simultaneous readings of LEN-under-LEN, only possible when the embedded past tense is modified by a deictic adverbial picking out the matrix time.

Obviously, Asante Twi is far from an isolated case. It has been observed that *then*-induced simultaneous interpretations for past-under-past are available for several languages with a relative present (cf. a.o. Vostrikova, 2018 for Russian, Ogihara & Sharvit, 2012 for Hebrew, Tsilia, 2021a for Modern Greek, section 5.2.2 for German). One crucial finding with respect to this phenomenon is the disappearance of a simultaneous reading if the deictic adverb modifies a present-tensed clause. Below I provide two examples for Hebrew and Russian.

- (9) *then*-effects in Hebrew (Ogihara & Sharvit, 2012, p. 640):
- a. lifney alpayim šana, Yosef xašav še Miriam ahava oto
before two.thousand year Yosef think.PAST that Miriam love.PAST him
az.
then
- b. #lifney alpayim šana, Yosef xašav še Miriam ohevet oto
before two.thousand year Yosef think.PAST that Miriam love.PRES him
az.
then
SIM: ‘Two thousand years ago Yosef thought that Miriam loved him then.’
- (10) *then*-effects in Russian (personal elicitation):
- a. #Žénja skazala čto togda Lena beremenna.
Zhenya say.PAST.PFV COMP then Lena pregnant
- b. Žénja skazala čto togda Lena byla beremenna.
Zhenya say.PAST.PFV COMP then be.PAST Lena pregnant
SIM as in (7): ‘Zhenya said that Lena was pregnant then.’

The fact that *then*-like adverbials are able to strengthen *SIM*-readings for the embedded past but block them for the embedded present may seem puzzling initially. However, these facts find a natural explanation assuming that *then*, apart from favouring a co-temporal interpretation,⁷ forces a *de re* interpretation. Being a distal deictic temporal adverb, *then* is obligatorily evaluated with respect to the utterance time, as it encodes temporal distance from the speaker’s now (see (12) for a rough semantics). This translates into the impossibility for a tense modified by *then* to be evaluated with respect to the attitude time.⁸ This point is illustrated for the Russian minimal pair in (9) in the simplified LF below, under *togda*’s semantics given in . For clarity of exposition, indices only track evaluation times.

- (11) a. $[_{CP} t_c \lambda t_0 [past_0 \dots Zhenya skazat [_{CP} \lambda t_4 [_{TP} [T togda_{0/\#4} pres_{\#0/4}] \dots]]]]$
b. $[_{CP} t_c \lambda t_0 [past_0 \dots Zhenya skazat [_{CP} \lambda t_4 [_{TP} [T togda_{0/\#4} past_{0/4}] \dots]]]]$
- (12) Semantics for *then* (cf. Armenante, 2024a; Vostrikova, 2018)
 $\llbracket then_{7,0} \rrbracket$ defined iff $g(0) \circ t_c \ \& \ g(7) \neq g(0)$
 When defined, $\llbracket then_{7,0} \rrbracket = g(7)$

⁷Being essentially anaphoric, *then* is naturally anchored to the attitude time, unless the context provides an external temporal referent. For reasons of space, I cannot present a satisfactory analysis of *then*, but see Schiffrin (1990, 1992) and Vostrikova (2018).

⁸In other words, tenses intersecting with deictic adverbs can be interpreted neither *de se* nor *de Dicto*.

Modification of a present-tensed complement clause by *then* produces the uninterpretable LF sketched in (11-a). Here the embedded present and the adverb *togda* compose intersectively and are, therefore, evaluated with respect to the same EvalT. Given the deictic nature of *togda*, this must be the θ -indexed variable (i.e., t_c , via λ -binding). Crucially, the embedded relative present cannot denote a time that overlaps t_c , because this would cause leave the presupposition in (12) unsatisfied. Put differently, modification of a present-tensed attitude report by the deictic *then* is always ruled out, due to the fact that either local or non-local binding of the embedded EvalT results in unmet definedness conditions for the embedded clause.

By contrast, a past-tensed complement clause modified by *then* produces an interpretable LF, as sketched in (11-b). The key difference from (11-a) is that the past tense can receive a *de re* interpretation and be evaluated with respect to t_c , given that it denotes a time other than t_c , thus fulfilling *then*'s presupposition. Obviously, if interpretable, this structure cannot be compatible with either a *de se* or a *de Dicto* LF in view of the fact that t_c rigidly designates *then*'s EvalT.⁹ For this reason, *then*-effects serve as a reliable diagnostic for the availability of *de re* ascriptions in a given language.¹⁰

5.1.2 *de re* variation and cumulative effects

In conclusion to this section, I will elaborate more on the factors facilitating temporal *de re*, particularly concerning simultaneous readings. First and foremost, a word of caution. While these factors influence the extent to which temporal *de re* is available in predictable ways, accurately gauging this extent appears problematic. Conceivably, the discussed factors and principles may interact and impose restrictions on tense interpretation in different ways across languages, potentially contingent on additional language-specific properties.

Importantly, the properties listed in (2) are not ranked by impact; rather, they all contribute individually or collectively to the availability of temporal *de re*. This being said, while (iii) and (iv) may certainly enhance not naturally occurring *de re* interpretations, arguably (i) and (ii) serve as their primary engine.

On this premise, I propose that the co-existence of multiple *de re* 'boosters' leads to cumulative effects, whereby the accessibility of *de re* ascriptions is a function of the number of co-occurring *de re* boosters. For illustrative purposes, let's consider a hypothetical language A, which, despite lacking a *de se* tense (such as a relative present or a vacuous past, cf. (ii)), exhibits a marker T, which is a pronominal tense (cf. (i)). Given the (i)+(ii) cumulative effect, we predict that A possesses a high degree of availability of temporal *de re* with respect to T, thereby freely enabling simultaneous readings for T-under-T embeddings. Sadly, type-A languages have not yet been documented. Now, let's imagine there exists A's twin language B. Just like A, B exhibits a pronominal tense T'. Moreover, B lacks a dedicated temporal shifter (such as a relative past or a perfect), thus rendering *Prefer de se!* inactive. Clearly, B can only express backward-shifted interpretations

⁹This view is faithful in spirit to Vostrikova (2018). In Armenante (2024a), I show that the observed restrictions on tense-adverb pairings stem directly from Keshet (2010)'s Intersective Predicate Generalization.

¹⁰The implications of *then*-effects provide a fresh angle on why (SIM and BACK) *de re* readings naturally arise for the particle *ná* in Asante. In a way, *ná* can be regarded as a tense-equivalent of *then*.

through a *de re* construal for T'. As we have previously observed, Hausa exemplifies a type-B language.

In light of these considerations, an intriguing empirical and theoretical question arises: why are type-A languages not attested if type-B are? A possible explanation goes along these lines: a heavier semantic burden is placed on simultaneity compared to shifted meaning. As we have seen, the notion of temporal simultaneity is not only associated with regular overlapping interpretations, but also with null readings. The challenge posed by a *de re*-only theory is its ability to accommodate only the former. If we assume that null readings are a semantic primitive, the inability to convey them significantly restricts a language's expressive capabilities. This suggests that if a language had a type-A-like parametric setup, it would be compelled to develop a *de se* compositional strategy to handle null readings.¹¹

On the opposite side of the spectrum we find a language X with existential/relative tenses T'' competing with a dedicated *de se* tense Z''. Type-X languages are expected to be *de re*-resistant, given that Z'' narrows T'''s scope in compliance with *Prefer de se!*. Specifically, if T'' is a past tense and Z'' a relative present, simultaneous readings are most likely conveyed through Z''. The key takeaway is that type-X languages are predicted to exhibit a low degree of temporal *de re*. One example could be Japanese.

Can type-X languages ever allow for *de re* simultaneous readings? This is where (iii) and (iv) come into play. In this regard, it has been argued that, in exceptional cases, even Japanese may generate simultaneous readings for past-under-past. In particular, overlapping interpretations become more easily accessible with perception reports (Saito, 2015), factive attitude reports (Ogihara, 2017; Tsilia, 2021a),¹² and even (for some speakers) with doxastic/reportative attitude reports modified by the deictic *then* (Kusumoto, 1999; Tsilia, 2021a).¹³ These uses are illustrated as follows.¹⁴

(13) *Perception reports* (from Saito, 2015, p. 37)

- a. Taroo-wa [kirin-ga heya-ni hai-ru/tta no]-o mi-ta.
Taro-TOP kirin-NOM room-to enter-PRES/PAST no-ACC see-PAST
'Taro saw a kirin enter the room.'

(14) *Factive reports* (from Ogihara, 2017, p. 12)

- a. Taroo-wa [zibun-ga gan-dat-ta to] shit-te-ita.
Taro-TOP self-NOM cancer-COP-PAST COMP know-PROG-PAST
'Taro knew that he had cancer.'

(15) *Reportative reports and then-effects*

- a. Junko-wa [Satoshi-ga sono-toki byooki-dat-ta to] it-ta.

¹¹Mucha has indeed suggested that simultaneous readings in Hausa, as opposed to shifted ones, obtain via a bound-variable construal.

¹²Ogihara speculates that clausal complements of *know* differ from other attitude complements in that they might resemble complex NPs introduced by *the fact that*. As such, they can scope out and be evaluated relative to the utterance time. While Ogihara does not justify the analogy on syntactic grounds (for instance, he does not show that *know*-complements are opaque to extraction), I believe that the resulting derivation would not differ too much from a *de re* analysis.

¹³For Ogihara, however, embedded clauses containing *sono-toki* can only be backward-shifted (cf. Ogihara & Sharvit, 2012, p. 640).

¹⁴Transliteration and glosses are mine.

Junko-TOP Satoshi-NOM that-time sick-COP-PAST COMP say-PAST
 ‘Junko said that Satoshi was sick then.’

The above examples are all compatible with a simultaneous interpretation, with the embedded past relativized to the utterance time via a *de re* derivation.¹⁵

So far, we have examined two cases situated at opposite ends of the *de re* spectrum. However, the space in between is occupied by various parametric configurations stemming from (2), each contributing to a gradable distribution regarding the availability of temporal *de re*. With this, I wish to stress the importance of developing a model that takes into account more nuanced variables to describe the observed variation in SoT phenomena, especially in connection to simultaneity. Having explored the principles regulating temporal *de re*, we will turn to temporal *de se* in the next section.

5.2 SoT languages and vacuous past

While in the previous section we have explored in some detail the constraints on variability of temporal *de re*, the focus of this section will be on temporal *de se*. As outlined in chapter 2, historically cross-linguistic variation in the SoT realm has been viewed primarily through the lens of the so-called SoT parameter — that is, whether a language has a rule voiding the semantic contribution of a morpho(-semantically) licensed tense. This is illustrated by Bochnak et al. (2019)’s parameter sketched below.

(16) *The Sequence of Tense parameter* (Bochnak et al., 2019, p. 412)
 A language does/ does not allow for Past-under-Past Deletion.

More specifically, Ogihara & Sharvit (2012) define deletion in these terms: “a tense that is *c-commanded* by an agreeing tense (past-under-past, present-under-present) may optionally be converted into a zero-tense”. The two key points of the definition are *c-commanding* and *agreement*. There is general consensus that the former involves locality.¹⁶ Regarding the latter, the conditions governing tense agreement are far from clear (see also the discussion in section 4.5). While the recent literature has remained vague on the issue, the prevailing trend appears to favor a morpho-syntactic notion of agreement.¹⁷ As a drawback, all efforts to precisely formulate the conditions allowing deletion rely on English as the reference language.

Following the SoT parameter in (16), among the SoT languages patterning with English are cited Germanic languages, Western Romance languages and Modern Greek. Unfortunately, a detailed map of SoT languages has not yet been drawn. However, a popular list goes back to Bošković (2012).

(17) *Bošković’s classification*

¹⁵Kusumoto has a different take on (15). In her system Japanese tense morphemes need to be licensed locally, leading her to argue that the embedded past tense is licensed by *sono-toki*. I don’t have much to offer in this regard, aside from noting that her perspective aligns well with a *de re* analysis of the embedded past tense.

¹⁶But see Schlenker (1999) for counter-arguments.

¹⁷See also Ogihara (1996) and Schlenker (1999), who discuss cases of semantic licensing for tense deletion.

- a. SoT languages: English, Dutch, Modern Greek, Spanish, French, German, Italian.
- b. non-SoT languages: Russian, Polish, Czech, Serbo-Croatian, Romanian, Hebrew, Japanese, Korean, Hindi, Turkish, Malayalam, Bangla, Angika.

Similarly, Grønn & Von Stechow (2010) report that SoT languages “include Germanic languages and Romance languages” providing examples from English, German, Norwegian and French.

At first glance of the list in (17), the two groups differ in one important way: while non-SoT languages exhibit a decent degree of linguistic diversity, SoT languages are all Indo-European and closely related. One lingering suspicion arises: Sequence of Tense might not be as widespread as commonly assumed.

A second issue pertains to the criteria that have led to this classification. As far as I am aware, several SoT languages (especially Western-Romance) have not been properly tested. General assumptions about their belonging to the SoT group stem from the fact that these languages, like English, allegedly have an indexical present and convey past simultaneity via a past tense form (usually, the imperfect). However, as seen in the previous chapter, Italian does not involve an SoT rule, as it employs *de se* compositional strategies that dispense with tense deletion. This is concerning.

In the remainder of this section, I will show that the SoT parameter has been subject to severe misconceptions. I will demonstrate that while French and Spanish align with Italian in that they do not resort to deletion to derive simultaneous (null) readings, German is in all respects a non-SoT language. What remains of the classic SoT family are some West-Germanic languages (English and Dutch) as well as North-Germanic languages (Danish, Norwegian, Swedish, Icelandic).

5.2.1 The case of Western Romance languages

Following the prevalent assumption in descriptive grammars that WR languages exhibit sequence of tense, formal accounts have proposed a deletion-like mechanism for Spanish (Rodríguez, 2004), French (Grønn & Von Stechow, 2010; Schlenker, 1999) and Portuguese (Ferreira, 2017). Similar to Italian, WR languages, in fact, typically possess an indexical present and convey simultaneous readings with an embedded imperfect. Examples for Spanish and French are provided below:

(18) *SoT ambiguity in French:*

- a. Marie a dit que Jean avait faim.
Marie say.APRF COMP Jean have.IMP hunger
‘Marie said that Jean was hungry.’ (✓SIM/✓BACK)
- b. Marie a dit que Jean a faim.
Marie say.APRF COMP Jean have.PRES hunger
‘Marie said that Jean is hungry.’ (#SIM/✓DAR)

(19) *SoT ambiguity in Spanish*

- a. María dijo que Juan tenía hambre.
María say.SPRF COMP Juan have.IMP hunger

- ‘María said that Juan was hungry.’ (✓SIM/✓BACK)
 b. María dijo que Juan tiene hambre.
 María say.SPRF COMP Juan have.PRES hunger
 ‘María said that Juan is hungry.’ (#SIM/✓DAR)

Note that, just like in Italian, French and Spanish imp-under-past embeddings (such as (18-a) and (19-a)) yield a strong preference for a simultaneous interpretation, unless an external referent is grammatically or contextually made salient. In chapter 4, this preference was motivated on the basis of the temporal imperfect’s pronominal shape. However, in *breakfast* contexts, judgments are much less clear. Recall that, according to the classic view, in these embedding configurations the most-embedded past tense cannot convey pastness and must be therefore semantically vacuous. Two examples are given below.

- (20) Context (*French*): Jean is organizing a camping trip for the weekend with Marie. He’s worried that Marie didn’t pack enough food. He tells you, “While camping, she’ll get hungry and start complaining. You’ll see!” Later, you report what he said.
- a. ??Hier, Jean a parié qu’à un moment donné, pendant le
 yesterday Jean bet.APRF COMP=at NDEF moment given during DEF
 camping, Marie dirait qu’elle avait faim.
 camping Marie say.FUT.IMP COMP=she have.IMP hunger
- b. Hier, Jean a parié qu’à un moment donné, pendant le
 yesterday Jean bet.APRF COMP=at NDEF moment given during DEF
 camping, Marie dirait qu’elle a faim.
 camping Marie say.FUT.IMP COMP=she have.PRES hunger
SIM: ‘Yesterday Jean bet that at some point while camping Marie would say that she was hungry.’
- (21) Context (*Spanish*): María is going on a blind date tomorrow. All she knows is that the guy is French. Juan knows that María finds French guys attractive, so he’s confident that her initial reaction upon seeing him will be: ‘He’s cute.’
- a. ?Juan era seguro de que María pensaría que el tipo era
 Juan be.IMP sure COMP María think.FUT.IMP COMP DEF guy be.IMP
 guapo.
 cute
- b. Juan era seguro de que María pensaría que el
 Juan be.IMP sure COMP María think.FUT.IMP COMP DEF guy
 tipo es guapo.
 be.PRES cute
SIM: ‘Juan was sure that María would think that the guy was/is cute.’

For both languages, the imp-marked report is marked. In particular, in a simultaneous context, sentence (20-a) was strongly dispreferred by my French consultants, despite being perfectly natural in a backward-shifted context.¹⁸ Interestingly, although a double

¹⁸For (21-a), one speaker found the sentence perfectly acceptable, whereas two judged it slightly marked.

access reading is not plausible in the given context, the present-tensed alternative was considered perfectly acceptable. Unsurprisingly, these judgements are replicated for false beliefs of permanent states of affairs embedded in breakfast reports, with once more some interspeaker variability regarding Spanish.¹⁹

- (22) Context (*French*): Leo lives in Quebec, raised by French parents. This explains his non-local accent, which is why she's often mistaken for a French tourist. Jean expects the same to happen once he introduces him to Marie.
- a. ??Jean était persuadé que Marie penserait que Leo était
 Jean be.IMP convinced COMP Marie think.FUT.IMP COMP Leo be.IMP
 français.
 French
- b. Jean était persuadé que Marie penserait que Leo est français.
 Jean be.IMP convinced COMP Marie think.FUT.IMP COMP Leo be.PRES French
 'Jean was sure that Marie would think that Leo was French.'
- (23) Context (*Spanish*): Simon, an American, has been living in the UK for quite some time now. He's developed a thick English accent, which often leads people to mistakenly believe he's English. According to Juan, María will be the next one to fall for it.
- a. ?Juan estaba seguro de que María pensaría que Simon era
 Juan be.IMP sure María think.FUT.IMP COMP Simon be.IMP English
 inglés.
- b. Juan estaba seguro de que María pensaría que Simon
 Juan be.IMP sure María think.FUT.IMP COMP Simon be.PRES
 es inglés.
 English
 'Juan was sure that María would think that Simon was English.'

Importantly, imp-marked false beliefs of permanent states are readily accepted in simple past embeddings. In these contexts, an embedded present tense is usually ruled out.

- (24) a. Marie pensait que Leo était français.
 Marie think.IMP COMP Leo be.IMP French
- b. María pensaba que Simon era inglés.
 María think.IMP COMP Simon be.IMP English

A deletion-based SoT theory cannot easily explain the contrast between breakfast and simple past reports. This is even more puzzling for languages like French and Spanish, which transparently show imperfective morphology on the verb paradigm expressing future in the past. A related inexplicable asymmetry pertains to the fact that the observed strong preference for simultaneous interpretations in imp-under-past embeddings decreases in future contexts to the point of becoming borderline acceptable. This raises

¹⁹In the interest of transparency, It's worth mentioning that my consultants for Spanish are native speakers of different varieties.

the question: why do underlying identical morpho-syntactic configurations yield distinct interpretative choices if they involve the same compositional derivation?

What I would like to propose next is that Western Romance languages, on a par with Italian, make use of selective λ -binding to derive simultaneous or backward-shifted readings in simple imp-under-past embeddings. In addition to this conventional temporal interpretation, the Western Romance imperfect also produces a modal interpretation with an epistemic past,²⁰ as outlined in section 4.5.2. While both mechanisms generate a *de se* simultaneous interpretation without voiding the imperfect's past features, they differ in terms of accessibility of the epistemic source. Specifically, breakfast reports involve long-distance binding of the most-embedded imperfect on the part of the sigma operator (please refer to subsection 4.5.3 for compositional details). This in turn might explain why these sentences are marked for some speakers.²¹

To further validate this theory, I conducted a small-scale experiment employing X-marked conditionals to test the licensing conditions of simultaneous readings. Below, I outline the methodology and predictions, and subsequently, I discuss the results.

Methods

Drawing from the diagnostics developed in section 4.5.2, X-marked conditionals serve as testing ground for the SoT rule. The languages tested are: English, Dutch, French and Spanish. For each language, three native speakers were consulted. Participants were asked to provide responses to a short questionnaire comprising present/past-tensed attitude reports of (present and past-tensed) X-marked conditionals (for a full list of the experimental items per language, see Appendix A). Sentences were rated on a scale of 1 (totally unacceptably) to 5 (totally acceptable) based on how well they fit the given context. The items involved either a permanent state of affair or an s-level predicate. A sample trial for each predicate type is provided below.

- (25) Context (*Permanent*): You doubt John is a conspiracy theorist. However, if he were one, you're convinced he would be a Flat Earther.
- a. If John were a conspiracy theorist, he would think that the Earth was flat. (X-pres, past)
 - b. If John were a conspiracy theorist, he would think that the Earth was flat. (X-pres, pres)
- (26) Context (*s-level*): There's an ongoing party at my place, but I don't think John would like it at all.
- a. If John were here, he would think that the party was a disaster. (X-pres, past)

²⁰The existence of an Italian-style modal imperfect for WR languages is independently documented (see Arregui et al., 2014; Cipria & Roberts, 2000; Dessì Schmid, 2010 for Spanish, and Giorgi & Pianesi, 1997; Hacquard, 2009 for French). Interestingly, Arregui et al. (2014) observe that the imperfect in most Slavic languages cannot be used to refer to past plans.

²¹Beside interspeaker variation, there appears to be microvariation within the Italo-Western Romance family, as null readings of the embedded imperfect in breakfast reports are harder in French, compared to Italian and Spanish (and possibly Portuguese, cf. Ferreira, 2017). A tentative explanation will be attempted in section 5.3.

- b. If John were here, he would think that the party is a disaster.(X-pres, pres)
- c. If John had been here, he would have thought that the party was a disaster.
(X-past, past)
- d. If John had been here, he would have thought that the party is a disaster.
(X-past, pres)

Predictions

The experiment employs English and Dutch as a baseline, given their absence of a Romance-like imperfect and their typical reliance on a Sequence of Tense rule to derive simultaneity. In this case, simultaneous interpretations are expected to be felicitous for a past embedded under the consequent of both past and present X-marked conditionals, given that the past tense may be semantically vacuous under morphological agreement.

On the other hand, in the case of French and Spanish, these interpretations are expected to be degraded compared to the baseline when the X-marked conditional is present. This follows from the fact that X-marked conditionals are present oriented and, thereby, cannot license an epistemic past. By contrast, acceptability is predicted to increase with past X-marked conditionals, as they inherently involve an epistemic past. These predictions are illustrated in table 5.1. Here the predictions made by the two theories are compared to an alternative third theory (non-SoT past a-la-Japanese), in which the past tense can be neither vacuous nor epistemic. To prevent confusion between tense and conditional conditions, in tables and graphs, I refer to present and past X-marked conditionals as simple and complex conditionals, respectively.

	Vacuous past	Epistemic past	Non-SoT past
Simple conditionals	✓	#	#
Complex conditionals	✓	✓	#

Table 5.1: Predictions on past tense’s acceptability in attitude reports of X-marked conditionals

For completeness, I additionally report predictions on present tense. These are less clear and not particularly interesting for the comparison at hand, since all four languages possess an indexical present. In principle, an asymmetry between relative and indexical present is expected under past X-marked conditionals, with higher acceptability for relative present languages compared to indexical ones.

	Relative present	Indexical present
Simple conditionals	✓	✓
Complex conditionals	✓	?#

Table 5.2: Predictions on present tense’s attitude reports of X-marked conditionals

Results

Results for Present X-marked conditionals are reported in Figure 5.1.

Figure 5.1: Simple conditionals in SoT languages: English, Dutch, French, Spanish

For present X-marked conditionals, both English and Dutch speakers readily accepted past-tensed reports. In fact, this appeared to be the preferred option to yield simultaneous interpretations. By contrast, the same reports were rated extremely low by both French and Spanish participants. For these speakers, these contexts only admit a present-tensed report.

Focusing on the two Western Romance languages, I compare ratings between present and past X-marked conditionals in Figure 5.2. The chart shows that adding a past layer in X-marked conditionals increases past tense's acceptability, especially for French. This is even more clear looking at the line graph in 5.3, which displays a nice cross for French. For Spanish, despite a rise in ratings, past-tensed reports still score relatively low, suggesting they're not particularly acceptable in these contexts. These findings are summarized in Table 5.3.

	English, Dutch	French	Spanish
Simple conditionals	✓	#	#
Complex conditionals	✓	✓	?

Table 5.3: Past tense's acceptability in simultaneous attitude reports of X-marked conditionals for English, Dutch, French, Spanish.

Discussion

West-Germanic languages such as English and Dutch display the hallmarks of a genuine SoT language, in that past tense morphology can be invisible to semantic composition

Figure 5.2: Simple vs complex X-marked conditionals in French and Spanish (column chart)

Figure 5.3: Simple vs complex X-marked conditionals in French and Spanish (line graph)

under morphological agreement. Following the terminology introduced at the end of the previous chapter, I will refer to these types of languages as *+Vac*-languages.

On the other hand, both French and Spanish speakers strongly reject the use of past tense in reports of present X-marked conditionals, suggesting that this morphology cannot be semantically vacuous. Consequently, akin to Italian, French and Spanish are categorized as *-Vac*-languages.

Furthermore, our findings reveal a telling contrast between conditional types in French. Specifically, past-tensed reports of past X-marked conditionals receive high acceptability ratings. This supports an epistemic past analysis. Results are less straightforward for Spanish: despite an increase in acceptability compared to present X-marked conditionals, these sentences were not rated particularly high in past X-marking environments.

While the partly divergent behavior in Spanish may seem surprising, it is noteworthy that Spanish participants independently disliked past X-marked conditionals. They reported that these conditionals are not particularly acceptable in a non-past setting, as intended in the design.²² Therefore, caution is warranted, and these findings should be replicated in a large-scale study, supported by statistical evidence. Nonetheless, the collected data contribute to painting a different picture than what has been assumed so far in the literature.

5.2.2 Is German an SoT language?

Commonly assumed to be an SoT language (Bošković, 2012; Grønn & Von Stechow, 2010; Kamp, 2022), German reveals an intricate picture suggesting a mixed set-up.

First of all, akin to the English past, von Stechow (1999) observes that the preterite (*Präteritum*) in standard German can be semantically vacuous under past-tensed attitude verbs.²³ According to von Stechow, these readings do not arise for the analytic perfect (*Perfekt*). This contrast is exemplified in (27).

- (27) Preterite/Perfect-under-preterite embeddings. (von Stechow, 1999, p. 98)
- a. Fritz dachte, dass es 8 Uhr war.
 Fritz think.PRET COMP it 8 time be.PRET
 ‘Fritz thought that it was 8 o’clock.’ (✓SIM/✓BACK)
- b. Fritz dachte, dass es 8 Uhr gewesen ist.
 Fritz think.PRET COMP it 8 time be.APRF
 ‘Fritz thought that it has been 8 o’clock.’ (#SIM/✓BACK)

It is worth noting that the preterite in von Stechow’s system is viewed as a deictic/absolute tense, akin to a temporal pronoun. To derive the simultaneous reading for (27-a), von Stechow assumes that semantically the embedded clause contains a zero tense, which receives its preterite shape through a Kratzerian feature-transmission system at phonological level. By contrast, for the analytic perfect von Stechow adopts an XN semantics, thus viewing the perfect as an existential tense. This theory was later revised in Von Stechow (2002), where the perfect is correctly treated as genuinely ambiguous between a past tense and different instantiations of an XN-perfect. Although, to the best of my knowledge, in his subsequent work von Stechow never addressed the implications of his revised theory for attitude contexts, we will see that a past tense semantics of the perfect can explain some attested interpretations that have gone unnoticed in the literature so far.

Alongside the preterite, three more forms have been argued to trigger simultaneous interpretations: the two subjunctive forms *Konjunktiv I* (the present subjunctive) and *Konjunktiv II* (the past subjunctive), as well as the indicative present (cf. also Fabricius-

²²Past X-marked conditionals were present or future oriented to avoid trivially high ratings for past tense. However, it is well known that future counterfactual conditionals, as opposed to past ones, are restricted to contexts involving a salient past time at which an intervening cause precluded the possibility of the antecedent-eventuality obtaining at a later point (cf. Ippolito, 2013; Kaufmann, 2023). Due to design constraints, this past intervention was probably not easily accessible for some speakers.

²³For an overview of German tense system, see Fabricius-Hansen (1986).

Hansen, 2004; Weber & Pröll, 2019).

- (28) Lina: ‘I don’t have time.’ (adapted from von Stechow, 1999, p. 98)
- a. Lina sagte, dass sie keine Zeit hat. (PRES.IND)
 - b. Lina sagte, dass sie keine Zeit habe. (PRES.SUBJ)
 - c. Lina sagte, dass sie keine Zeit hatte. (PRET.IND)
 - d. Lina sagte, dass sie keine Zeit hätte. (PRET.SUBJ)
 - e. #Lina sagte, dass sie keine Zeit gehabt hat/habe. (APRF)

Given the wealth of tense options, von Stechow ends up suggesting that all the four forms yield vacuous readings and have therefore the same *de se* LF. Nevertheless, von Stechow has to concede that German appears much “messier than English”.

As is evident, this proposal raises serious concerns regarding the morpho-syntax/semantics mapping. Why would for distinct forms share the same underlying semantic representation? Relatedly, why would German ‘develop’ an SoT rule for one of its past tense forms, considering it already deploys dedicated *de se* tense forms?

In later work, while maintaining an SoT theory for the preterite, Grønn & Von Stechow (2010) propose that attitude verbs in German may optionally carry a subjunctive feature transmitted to their complement, thus selecting for either subjunctive tense form. In this regard, the present and the preterite subjunctive are treated as essentially tenseless, a view consistent with Weber & Pröll (2019). Regrettably, this theory remains silent on the indicative present and its correlation with analogous interpretations.

The research we have reviewed does not provide convincing evidence in support of an SoT theory for standard German. In particular, the language was never subjected to the relevant diagnostics utilized in this thesis, such as permanent states reports and breakfast contexts. It is by now clear that the mere availability of past simultaneous readings for s-level predicates is not a sufficient condition for an analysis postulating tense vacuity. With reference to the corpus data discussed in Grønn & Von Stechow (2010), these include book translations from either English or Norwegian original sentences. Given that the two source languages have SoT, there is an obvious priming concern, in that the translator might favour preserving the original tense form over changing it. An interesting example in this respect is offered by the following sentence (example (6G) in Grønn & Von Stechow, 2010, p. 116), which my consultants rejected in favour of a present-tensed counterpart.²⁴

- (29) Die Leute sagten, dass Hanna Stines Kind war.
 DEF people say.PRET COMP Hanna Stine.GEN child be.PRET
 ‘They said that Hanna was Stine’s child.’

The remaining sentences containing an embedded indicative preterite and compatible with a simultaneous reading are all in the scope of a factive ((10)-(15)) or perception verb ((63)-(67)). Two examples are given below.

- (30) Er wusste, dass sie dort stand.
 he know.PRET COMP she there stand’.PRET
 ‘He knew she was standing there.’

²⁴Unfortunately, the paper does not provide enough context to fully evaluate the desired interpretation.

- (31) Aber er sah, dass sie nicht ganz sie selbst war.
 but he see.PRET COMP she NEG completely she self be.PRET
 ‘But he saw that she wasn’t completely herself.’

The preceding section has shown that factive and perception environments facilitate *de re* interpretations of past tenses. Interestingly, an analysis akin to this is embraced by Grønn & Von Stechow (2010) for Russian past-under-past factive/perception reports, yet not extended to German.

Finally, it is particularly telling that the only (uncontroversial) data point involving a genuine attitude report exhibits *then*-effects (sentence (9G) in the paper, here reported in (32)).

- (32) Man erzählte sich, dass inzwischen wilde Tiere in den Zimmern
 one tell.PRET REFL COMP in.the.meantime wild animals in DEF rooms
 hausten.
 live.PRET
 ‘It was said that wild animals were now living in the rooms.’

In (32), the anaphoric adverbial *inzwischen* (‘in the meantime’) forces a *de re* interpretation of the modified preterite (cf. Armenante, 2024a).

In what follows, I will demonstrate that German is not an SoT language, as *de se* null readings are not expressed through past tense embeddings, rather via a shiftable present. However, though less common, simultaneous interpretations for both preterite and perfect embeddings are attested and derived via a *de re* mechanism. First of all, under a simultaneous interpretation, an agreeing past tense form is ruled out in (i) reports of permanent states of affair, (ii) breakfast reports, (iii) reports of present X-marked conditionals.

(i) Reports of permanent states

- (33) Jan: ‘9 is a prime number.’
 a. Jan dachte, dass 9 eine Primzahl ist/sei.
 Jan think.PRET 9 NDEF prime.number be.PRES.IND/SUBJ
 b. #Jan dachte, dass 9 eine Primzahl war/gewesen ist.
 Jan think.PRET 9 NDEF prime.number be.PRET/APRF
 ‘Jan thought that 9 was a prime number.’
- (34) Nadine: ‘The Sun is a planet!’
 a. Nadine glaubte, dass die Sonne ein Planet ist/sei.
 Nadine believe.PRET COMP DEF Sun NDEF planet be.PRES.IND/SUBJ
 b. #Nadine glaubte, dass die Sonne ein Planet war/gewesen ist.
 Nadine believe.PRET COMP DEF Sun NDEF planet be.PRET/APRF
 ‘Nadine believed that the Sun was a planet.’

The above examples show that null readings in reports of permanent states require a

present tense, even if the state no longer holds at the utterance time.²⁵ The relative nature of the German present tense is confirmed by the following sentence.

- (35) Vor 2 Jahren hat Jan gesagt, dass Sarah schwanger ist/sei.
 before 2 years AUX Jan say.APRF Sarah pregnant be.PRES.IND/SUBJ
 ‘Two years ago Jan said that Sarah was pregnant.’

Arguably, the exclusion of past tense forms such as the preterite and the analytic perfect weakens the SoT status of German.²⁶

However, it is worth reporting that, while the German perfect is systematically ruled out in SoT contexts, some speakers do accept the preterite in these configurations, even within clauses supposedly expressing generic statements. One example is given in (36).

- (36) Lina: ‘Derna ist Italienerin.’
 a. Vor einer Woche hat Lina gesagt, dass Derna Italienerin
 before NDEF week AUX Lina say.APRF COMP Derna Italian
 ist/sei.
 be.PRES.IND/SUBJ
 b. Vor einer Woche hat Lina gesagt, dass Derna Italienerin
 before NDEF week AUX Lina say.APRF COMP Derna Italian
 ?war/#gewesen ist.
 be.PRES.PRET/APRF
 ‘One week ago Lina said that Derna was Italian.’

Although the preterite variant in (36-b) is judged odd by several speakers, some rate the sentence as acceptable, even under a null interpretation. The same speakers additionally accept similar sentences in purely intensional contexts, where a subjunctive form or the present would be expected (e.g., *Lina dachte, dass Derna Italienerin war*, ‘Lina thought that Derna was Italian’). This puzzling inter-speaker variation seems however limited to (i), as a non-SoT view of standard German finds additional support in (ii).

(ii) *Breakfast reports*

- (37) a. Letzte Woche habe ich beschlossen, dass ich Sarah nach zwei Wochen
 last week AUX I decide.APRF COMP I Sarah after two weeks
 mitteilen würde, dass sie unsere neue Geschäftsführerin
 communicate AUX.PRET.SUBJ COMP she our new CEO
 ist/sei.
 be.PRES.IND/SUBJ
 b. #Letzte Woche habe ich beschlossen, dass ich Sarah nach zwei Wochen
 last week AUX I decide.APRF COMP I Sarah after two weeks

²⁵A detailed exploration of the distinct pragmatic meaning associated with the present subjunctive compared to the indicative one would take us too far afield. For an in-depth discussion, refer to Fabricius-Hansen (2004)

²⁶Despite its morphological make-up, I do not view the *Konjunktiv II* as a past tense from a semantic perspective, as it cannot shift the evaluation time.

mitteilen würde, dass sie unsere neue Geschäftsführerin
 communicate AUX.PRET.SUBJ COMP she our new CEO
 war/gewesen ist.
 be.PRET/APRF
 ‘Last week I decided that after two weeks I would tell Sarah that she was
 our new CEO.’

- (38) Stine is rumoured to announce tomorrow: ‘Hanna is my child.’
- a. Die Leute spekulierten, dass Stine verkünden würde, dass
 DEF people say.PRET, COMP Stine announce AUX.PRET.SUBJ COMP
 Hanna ihr kind ist/sei.
 Hanna her child be.**PRES**.IND/SUBJ
- b. Die Leute spekulierten, dass Stine verkünden würde, dass
 DEF people say.PRET, COMP Stine announce AUX.PRET.SUBJ COMP
 Hanna ihr kind war/gewesen ist.
 Hanna her child be.**PRET**./APRF
 ‘People were speculating that Stine would announce that Hanna was her
 child.’

Contrary to their present-tensed counterparts, sentences (37-b) and (38-b) can only yield backward-shifted interpretations, although each embedding predicate bears past tense morphology.

(iii) Reports of X-marked conditionals

Following the methods outlined in section 5.2.1, X-marked conditional reports were additionally used as testing ground for an SoT rule in German. The small experimental survey comprised once more five experimental items (see examples below as well as Appendix A for a full list) rated on a scale of 1 to 5 by six native speakers. Each item was presented across four conditions, based on the tense form embedded in the report of the conditional consequent (i.e., present indicative, preterite indicative, present subjunctive and preterite subjunctive). Results are reported in Figure 5.4.

- (39) Context (*Permanent*): Marie struggles with math. However, she recently learnt that all even numbers are divisible by two.
- a. Wenn 7 eine gerade Zahl wäre, würde Marie denken, dass sie durch zwei teilbar ist. (Pres IND)
- b. Wenn 7 eine gerade Zahl wäre, würde Marie denken, dass sie durch zwei teilbar war. (Past IND)
- c. Wenn 7 eine gerade Zahl wäre, würde Marie denken, dass sie durch zwei teilbar sei. (Pres SUBJ)
- d. Wenn 7 eine gerade Zahl wäre, würde Marie denken, dass sie durch zwei teilbar wäre. (Past SUBJ)
 ‘If 7 were even, Marie would think that it was/is divisible by two.’
- (40) Context (*s-level*): Harry Kane got badly injured in the last game. He’s unlikely to feature in any of the next Bayern games.

- a. Wenn Kane nächste Woche spielen würde, würde der Trainer denken, dass er ein Außerirdischer ist. (Pres IND)
- b. Wenn Kane nächste Woche spielen würde, würde der Trainer denken, dass er ein Außerirdischer war. (Past IND)
- c. Wenn Kane nächste Woche spielen würde, würde der Trainer denken, dass er ein Außerirdischer sei. (Pres SUBJ)
- d. Wenn Kane nächste Woche spielen würde, würde der Trainer denken, dass er ein Außerirdischer wäre. (Past SUBJ) ‘If Kane played next week, the coach would think he was an alien.’

Figure 5.4: X-marked conditional reports in German

The results in Figure 5.4 display the anticipated ceiling ratings for the indicative present. In contrast, reports featuring the preterite indicative scored at the floor. Somewhat surprisingly, acceptability ratings for the present subjunctive were not particularly high, especially in present conditionals, with participants expressing a preference for the indicative present in colloquial register.

These empirical findings indicate a clear semantic asymmetry between the present tense and the past tense forms, thus suggesting (contrary to von Stechow, 1999) fairly different compositional pathways available for these forms.²⁷

Nevertheless, a few questions remain: first of all, are simultaneous readings possible for the preterite and the analytic perfect in past contexts? Can present tense yield over-

²⁷The different parametric setup of standard German, compared to the other Western Germanic languages, is reflected in other domains where SoT patterns are usually found. Consider the contrast below, first observed in Wimmer (2020):

- (i)
 - a. I just wish I knew what went on inside that little head of his.
 - b. I wish you were playing when I was visiting. (SIM)
- (ii)
 - a. Ich wünschte, ich wüsste, was in seinem Kopf vor sich {geht / ?ginge}.
 - b. Ich wünschte, du spieltest, wenn ich da {bin / ?wäre}.

lapping readings even in contexts where it competes with past tense forms? To address these questions, I designed a small sentence completion task, where my consultants were instructed to fill in the gap with an inflected form of the bracketed verb. An example is given in (41).

- (41) Context: Marie usually goes to bed early and is able to sleep through noise. Apparently she even slept throughout the Midnight Mass last year, as the priest pointed out as it unfolded.
- a. Der Priester sagte, dass Marie _____. (schlafen)
 ‘The priest say.PRET that Marie ... (sleep)’

For (i), the preferred option to express simultaneity were the present indicative *schläft* and the preterite indicative *schlief* (‘slept’). The analytic perfect *hat geschlafen* (‘has slept’) was mostly dispreferred. For stative predicates, simultaneous readings for the past tense forms appear even less acceptable (see (42)).

- (42) Context: I didn’t see Marie at the Christmas party last year. According to her colleague Lena, she was currently sick.
- a. Bei der letzten Weihnachtsfeier sagte Lena, dass Marie krank _____. (sein)
 ‘At the last Christmas party, Lena said that Marie ... (be) ill.’

For (42), a strong preference for the present indicative or subjunctive was reported. By comparison, both the preterite and the perfect were degraded, with the latter rejected by most consultants.²⁸

Crucially, simultaneous readings become available for both past tense forms if a deictic adverbial modified the embedded clause. In these cases, the present tense is ruled out. This is illustrated in the two sentences in (43), situated in their respective contexts.

- (43) a. Der Priester sagte, dass in dem Moment Marie
 DEF priest say.PRE COMP in DEM moment Marie
 #schläft/schlief/geschlafen hat.
 sleep.PRES/PRET/APRF
- b. Bei der letzten Weihnachtsfeier sagte Lena, dass Marie zu dem
 at DEF last Christmas.party say.PRET Lena COMP Marie at DEM
 Zeitpunkt krank #ist/#sei/war/gewesen ist/
 time sick be.PRES/PRET/APRF

²⁸It is worth reporting that there was one case where the embedded analytic perfect was naturally offered by consultants. This involved an analytic perfect in the matrix, with a recent past scenario, as given in (i).

- (i) Context: Earlier today I called Marie, but her daughter Lucy picked up the phone instead. According to Lucy, Marie was asleep at the time I called.
- a. Lucy hat gesagt, dass Marie _____. (schlafen)
 ‘Lucy say.APRF that Marie ... (sleep)’

The same configuration was however rejected in a similar context with an embedded stative predicate. I leave this as an open puzzle.

The general patterns observed in (43) align with a *de re* theory for the embedded preterite and perfect, while the embedded present aligns with a *de se* theory. The observation that, in certain simultaneous contexts, the preterite is more acceptable than the perfect cannot solely be attributed to *Prefer unbounded structures!*, as German lacks the same aspectual contrast seen in Romance languages.²⁹ This preference seems to derive from the deictic pronominal semantics commonly associated with the preterite, in contrast to the quantificational semantics of the perfect. However, it's noteworthy that the German perfect, particularly in southern dialects, has largely evolved into a past tense, to the extent that it has fully replaced in meaning the preterite (Braun, 2023). This, in turn, may explain the availability of simultaneous *de re* readings within attitude contexts.

Despite the neat division of labour sketched above, data on permanent states reports in (i) seem to challenge the formulated generalizations. As previewed, some speakers seem to accept (at least for some predicates) vacuous readings of the preterite under tense agreement. While a precise assessment goes beyond the scope of this subsection, let me note that from a simple corpus search it becomes clear that the distribution of null readings for the preterite is marginal compared to that of the present. In light of its limited range, it would be misleading to speak of a generalized SoT rule for German. Nevertheless, we cannot simply ignore data pointing to the existence, albeit restricted, of optional tense deletion.

For the moment, I can only offer a modest explanation. Let's assume that all Germanic languages used to have an optionally vacuous past alongside an indexical present. At some point — probably due to language contact — the German Present developed into a shiftable indexical, thus making the SoT mechanism redundant. From this diachronic perspective, today's SoT readings may be regarded as a mere reflection of a linguistic relic. This view seems to gain credit in light of the absence of null readings for the perfect. Recall that the German perfect has undergone a well known semantic change, evolving into a past tense and replacing *de facto* the preterite in colloquial register and in southern varieties. Given that the SoT rule is grammatically and not lexically encoded, this cannot have been “inherited” by the perfect, as it took over the preterite's functions and uses. In a sense, if proven to be correct, this diachronic view might provide further evidence for the fact that deletion-like readings for the preterite are the remnant of a mechanism that has largely become inactive in standard German today.³⁰

Regarding the German present, I cannot conclusively determine here its degree of shiftability. Let me simply note that, akin to Russian and Hebrew, simultaneous (relative) interpretations seem restricted to intensional operators, such as attitude verbs and the future modal. They are however excluded in past-tensed relative clauses, as exemplified in (44).

- (44) Gestern habe ich mit dem Mann gesprochen, der weint.
 yesterday AUX I with DEF man talk.APRF REL cry.PRES
 a. #*Relative*: ‘Yesterday I talked to the man who was crying then.’

²⁹While aspect isn't explicitly marked morphologically, the default interpretation leans toward perfective (Musan, 2002). Nonetheless, imperfective uses are documented for both forms under suitable adverbials or periphrastics (Braun, 2023).

³⁰In Grønn & Von Stechow (2010, fn.5) the preterite and the analytic perfect are also assumed to be semantically equivalent.

- b. *Indexical*: ‘Yesterday I talked to the man who is crying now.’

Based on these observations, a plausible analysis for the German present tense might be that of a shiftable indexical, whose index can be shifted by intensional operators — along the lines of what Schlenker proposes for the Russian present (Schlenker, 2003a).

To conclude this section, our empirical investigation revealed that several languages commonly assumed to have an SoT rule don’t quite fit the mold. Focusing on Western-Romance and West-Germanic languages, two key observations were reached: firstly, Western-Romance languages employ an epistemic past to generate null readings, akin to Italian; secondly, German, unlike English and Dutch, aligns more closely with non-SoT languages. Instead of relying on an SoT rule, German primarily expresses simultaneity through a shiftable present.

This latter finding is particularly intriguing. Despite belonging to the West Germanic branch, German does not exhibit Sequence of Tense. The puzzle deepens when considering the entire Germanic branch of the Indo-European family. North Germanic languages like Norwegian, Swedish, and Danish, for instance, all conform to the SoT pattern observed in Dutch and English. In light of this, German appears anomalous.³¹

5.3 Towards a new SoT model

Building on the insights gained in the previous sections, this section attempts to take the first steps towards a new crosslinguistic model that can account for the observed variation in SoT phenomena.

5.3.1 Existing typological models and their short-comings

Before delving into my proposal, let me briefly recap the main points covered in the existing models. Grønn & Von Stechow (2010) and Ogihara & Sharvit (2012) (O&S) ascribe the observed variation to the presence or absence of an SoT rule, where tense features may remain optionally uninterpreted. The SoT parameter, in turn, leads to the traditional division between SoT and non-SoT languages. To account for the micro-variation within the non-SoT family, both theories propose that an “undeletable” past tense may yield *de se*-like readings through a *de re* derivation. This mechanism explains the availability of simultaneous interpretations for past-under-past embeddings in many non-SoT languages.

Expanding on the last point, O&S observe a further sub-division, whereby *de re* tenses may leave traces or full copies when moving out of the scope of the attitude verb. As is defined, this binary distinction only admits two possibilities: a) *de re* traces generate earlier-than-UT interpretations compatible with simultaneity, b) *de re* copies generate exclusively backward-shifted interpretations. However, based on recent crosslinguistic findings from under-researched languages, Bochnak et al. (2019) reveal that variation in temporal *de re* is not as categorical, but rather gradient. While what shapes this gradient

³¹While a full account of German’s divergent behavior lies beyond the scope of this thesis, let me simply note that German differs from the aforementioned languages in one critical aspect: it retains mood alternation. A possible connection between mood loss and SoT will be suggested in the next section.

variability is not clearly identified in Bochnak et al. (2019), we have shown in section 5.1 that several universal factors can be isolated.

What all these approaches have in common is the introduction of several parameters of variation, which do not stand in any apparent relation to one another. Setting the *de re* parameter aside for the moment, for any given language four possible combinatorial options are possible, as illustrated in Table 5.4.

	Present tense	SoT rule	
Type I	<i>+Shift</i>	<i>-Vac</i>	East-Asia, Balto-Slavic, Finno-Ugric
Type II	<i>-Shift</i>	<i>+Vac</i>	Most Germanic
Type III	<i>+Shift</i>	<i>+Vac</i>	MG, Washo
Type IV	<i>-Shift</i>	<i>-Vac</i>	n/a

Table 5.4: Basic SoT Variation following traditional typological models

In the simplified model sketched in Table 5.4, languages vary based on whether their tense inventory features: (i) a shiftable/relative (*+Shift*) or an indexical (*-Shift*) present tense; or (ii) tense markers that are semantically vacuous under an SoT rule (*+Vac*) or always semantically interpreted (*-Vac*).

Type I languages have a shiftable present but no tense deletion. This parametric combination is the most commonly found in natural language, including, among others, Japonic-Koreanic languages, many Niger-Congo languages, Balto-Slavic languages, Finno-Ugric languages, as well as Romanian. Type II languages, characterized by an indexical present and an SoT rule, are much less common and are mostly confined to the Germanic branch of the Indo-European family. Type III languages utilize two identical *de se* mechanisms to express null readings: a shiftable present and a vacuous past tense. These are even rarer commodity, with only Modern Greek and Washo falling in this category, to the best of my knowledge.³² Finally, type IV languages involve neither a shiftable present nor a deletable past tense. Given their impossibility to express null readings, they are ruled out by Ogihara & Sharvit (2012).³³

One drawback of this model is its prediction that all three attested options should be equally available in natural language. However, we observe a notable contrast in their frequency. In this regard, it remains unclear why type III languages are almost nonexistent, while type II languages appear to be specific to a subgroup of languages.

Extending the picture sketched in Table 5.4, O&S introduce two additional parameters of variability: (i) whether languages have pronominal, quantificational tenses or both; and (ii) whether *de re* tenses leave traces or full copies. When all four parameters are considered, the model predicts 18 different language types (see also Sharvit, 2014). This raises a second point of concern about the risk of overgeneration (cf. Ogihara & Sharvit, 2012, p. 663), which leads to the question: do all these language types actually exist?

³²Schlenker (1999) argues that Upper Austrian might also constitute a type III language. However, his limited set of data offers no conclusive evidence. In fact, Upper Austrian seems to align with German.

³³As discussed in section 2.7, the ban on type IV languages stems from the violation of the *Embeddability principle* (cf. Sharvit, 2003).

5.3.2 Re-casting the SoT typology

Based on this premise, section 5.2 has revealed that languages traditionally thought to employ an SoT rule are not as prevalent as previously assumed, thereby undermining the SoT rule's standing as a macro-parameter of variation. Specifically, we have discovered that, while German lacks an SoT rule and instead utilizes a relative present, Italo-Western Romance languages, despite exhibiting SoT configurations, do not employ an SoT rule; rather, they utilize a semantically interpreted epistemic past.

What I propose instead is that the only relevant macro-parameter of variation in SoT phenomena is the shiftability of present tense. On this view, languages vary based on whether they have a “somewhat” relative present or an indexical present.³⁴ Clearly, languages with an indexical present must be able to express null *de se* readings through alternative mechanisms. These include lexical strategies such as the the Romance imperfect or grammatical ones like tense deletion.

One crucial departure from the previous models lies in the mutual interaction of these parameters. While in O&S's model, for instance, all four parameters operate independently, I posit that, in languages with a binary tense system, the shiftability of the present tense directly impacts the compositional pathways available for the past tense.³⁵ This key observation aligns with a general economy-based view of linguistic phenomena, where the syntax-semantics mapping is constrained by principles of efficiency and optimization (cf. Fox, 2000). According to this perspective, present and past-tensed predicates are less likely to share the same underlying semantic representation, thus conforming to an optimal division of semantic labour.

A direct implication of this proposal is that languages equipped with a relative present should not require an SoT rule, as both inborn relative present and deleted past tense correlate with the same *de se* LF. This, in turn, explains why $\{+Shift, +Vac\}$ pairings are rarely found.

The second main tenet of the proposal pertains to the present tense's shiftability. In line with Sharvit (2014), I argue that this property is not determined in binary terms, but varies across a continuum, from hardly shiftable (purely indexical) to completely shiftable (strictly relative). The shiftability spectrum is illustrated in Figure 5.5.

At the upper hand of the scale in Figure 5.5 are languages where the present tense is completely shiftable. These, for example, include Japanese, whose present tense shifts (i) under future-like operators, (ii) in attitude contexts and (iii) in relative clauses. Mainly shiftable languages also exhibit relative readings for pres-under-future and pres-under-past attitude reports, but not for pres-under-past relative clauses. Russian and Hebrew can be grouped within this class. By contrast, a partially shiftable present tense can only be shifted by future operators, while retaining its indexical meaning in every other

³⁴“Present tense” here should be viewed as a place-holder standing for present, non-past, or any (c)overt variable/operator ranging over times and compatible with present reference in matrix clauses. Following this definition, Asante Twi, for instance, would fall under the *+Shift* rubric.

³⁵Note that an attempt to build economy-based constraints into the SoT mapping is made in Sharvit (2014). However, this proposal suffers from the same issues identified earlier: firstly, it lacks empirical support for the many theoretically predicted options; secondly, it rests on arbitrary assumptions regarding the pronominal/quantificational nature of tenses in a language. For instance, languages with both pronominal and quantificational tenses are excluded, which contradicts claims in Ogihara & Sharvit (2012).

Figure 5.5: The spectrum of present tense’s shiftability in natural language.

syntactic environment. This behaviour is exemplified by many Germanic languages and Italo-Western Romance languages.

Finally, at the lower end of the scale are predicted languages with a purely indexical present. For these languages, present tense is not expected to shift, even under a future operator. As far as I know, no such languages have been attested.³⁶ A possible explanation is once more dictated by economy principles: given the relatively infrequent occurrence of future simultaneity, it is reasonable to adopt an indexical present to report the attitude holder’s future now, rather than developing a dedicated mechanism. In this respect, the perspectival shift associated with the present tense in future embeddings is reminiscent of that triggered by the narrative present (cf. Bary, 2022; Klecha, 2018; Pancheva & Zubizarreta, 2023). On this view, it is not surprising that natural language makes use of a mechanism that is already available. Of course, on an SoT account of present-under-future, the distinction between partially shiftable and purely indexical becomes irrelevant. But we have already seen that this line of reasoning comes with its own set of problems.

Pushing this further, I suggest that the gradient crosslinguistic distribution of both temporal *de se* (for present tense) and temporal *de re* (for past tense) is not accidental. As previously argued, the semantic inputs of present and past tenses are not independent of each other; rather, one form limits the semantic space of the other. While this explained the rare occurrence of *+Shift*, *+Vac* languages, the same reasoning can be extended to temporal *de re*, particularly in connection with simultaneous readings. More concretely, if a language possesses a completely shiftable present tense, it is less likely to opt for *de re* mechanism to generate the same interpretation. From this perspective, it becomes clearer why temporal *de re* is heavily constrained in languages like Japanese compared to Hebrew or, especially, Russian and Asante Twi. Of course, whether *de re* is in principle feasible or not is still determined on the basis of the conditions listed in (2).

To give the fully picture, the degree of present’s shiftability does not only affect vacuous

³⁶However, one potential candidate is the non-future tense in Gitxsan. On Aonuki’s analysis, irrespective of the semantic domain, the pronominal tense is strictly interpreted *de re*, even in future embeddings. Nevertheless, it’s not clear how null readings would be expressed in Gitxsan, as the language appears to lack *de se* construals altogether, thus possibly violating Sharvit’s Embeddability principle.

or *de re* past tense, but also epistemic past tenses — on condition that the two forms yield comparable interpretations. In light of this, we can provide a suitable answer to the Romance puzzle discussed in section 5.2.1. Recall that, in breakfast contexts, the future-in-the-past report is degraded in French compared to Spanish and Italian, when it embeds a past tense. In contrast, present tense in French constitutes the most natural option for these reports. Assuming that present tense in French always shifts under a future operator, no matter its tense marking, a lower acceptability of an epistemic past tense in these constructions might be expected. As a consequence, French might be placed on the scale in 5.5 between partially and mainly shiftable.

Putting all the pieces together, the observed variation can be illustrated through the tree diagram in Figure 5.6

Figure 5.6: Tree diagram of SoT variation.

In the interest of exposition, the simplified model in Figure 5.6 depicts only macro-classes of shiftability. As we have said, further subdivisions can be identified, following a continuum from a low degree of shiftability (rightmost node of the tree) to a high degree (leftmost node). Clearly, this model represents only a rough description of natural language variability. First of all, not all tense systems across languages can be categorized in terms of a present-past opposition. In the intentional simplification made here, most covert tenses are lumped together with present tenses, including TAM paradigms of tenseless and optional tense languages.

Moreover, this model does not factor in aspect. We have seen that in aspect-prominent languages, the same range of temporal interpretations can be achieved, despite the lack of tense morphology. Note, however, that *de se* readings in aspect-based accounts can only be generated assuming a purely tenseless analysis (see Asante Twi in this thesis) or a

covert temporal pronoun ranging over RTs (see Hausa and Samoan Bochnak et al., 2019).³⁷ Therefore, for the sake of crosslinguistic comparability, these languages are classified as having a (mainly or completely) shiftable present tense.

In light of the important role played by the property of shiftability for present tense and its broader implications on SoT phenomena, we need to entertain the possibility that shiftability is a universal tense property not only restricted to the present tense category. More concretely, does shiftability in the past tense also come in different shades? The short answer is yes. Empirically, however, past tense's shiftability is very hard to determine. Let me elaborate more on this point.

It is relatively easy to distinguish between the opposite sides of the spectrum, that is between a purely indexical or deictic past tense and a relative one. For instance, the Italian synthetic perfect always expresses pastness with respect to the utterance time. While shifted readings in past-under-past embeddings do not constitute a reliable diagnostic criterion due to the ULC, future embeddings revealed that relative BACK-readings are not attested for SPRF-marked complements, thus pointing to its deictic nature. On the other hand, the Japanese past tense appears to display strictly relative readings, even when interpreted *de re*. Following the denotation adopted for the present tense, we might label the Italian synthetic perfect SPRF as a purely indexical past and the Japanese past tense *ta* as a completely shiftable past tense.

The nuanced cases are however tricky. Consider the English past tense: past contexts are again not applicable. Future contexts do not help much either: the presence of relative BACK-readings can be attributed to either context-shifting (owing to the future modal) or to the past tense's relative semantics. We hit a standstill. Luckily for us, languages with graded tenses exist. Notably, these provide a window into past tense's indexicality/shiftability. Specifically, Cable (2015) has shown that past tense markers in Gikūyū are indexical under past-tensed attitude, but may shift under future. In contrast, graded tenses in Medumba seem to shift systematically in attitude embeddings (Mucha & Fominyam, 2017). Therefore, past tenses in Gikūyū can be regarded as partially shiftable, while Medumba exemplified a language with (at least) mainly shiftable past tense.

As a final remark, economy constraints are built into the model in Fig. 5.6. One undesirable consequence is the impossibility for the model to predict $\{+Shift, +Vac\}$ patterns. The literature has however discussed two members of this class: Washo and Modern Greek. We turn to them in the next sub-section.

5.3.3 Two apparently divergent languages: Washo and Modern Greek

As previewed in the preceding section, in its current configuration, the model illustrated in 5.6 appears too strong, as it rules out $[+Shift, +Vac]$ -languages. In particular, Washo and Modern Greek have been depicted as displaying a relative or shiftable tense construal alongside a vacuous past. In what follows, I review the two individual cases and consider whether they constitute solid counter-arguments to my generalizations.

³⁷For both tenseless, aspect-prominent languages Hausa and Samoan, simultaneous readings are derived by binding a covert tense variable. This variable in matrix contexts denotes by default (or displays a strong preference for) the utterance time.

The case of Washo

Washo is an optional tense language, where past reference arises from zero as well as past tense marking, as is illustrated in (45) (from Bochnak, 2016).

- (45) a. watlí: zí:gin lébikhay-i.
 morning chicken cook-IND
 ‘This morning I cooked chicken.’
 b. watlí: wáḡaw-uḡil-i.
 morning good-PAST-IND
 ‘It was nice this morning.’

Washo unmarked clauses can receive, in principle, a present, past as well as a future interpretation. Consequently, Bochnak suggests that a covert pronominal tense supplies the reference time via context assignment (see (46-a)). The reference of this pronoun can be optionally restricted to past by *uḡil*, which serves as the overt past tense and is given an identity-function semantics, as in (46-b).

- (46) [TP [T T₁ (uḡil)] [AspP P]]
 a. [T₁] = g(1)
 b. [uḡil] = λt: t < t_c. t

Importantly, Bochnak demonstrates that both bare-under-bare and past-under-past attitude reports in Washo are systematically ambiguous between a backward-shifted and a simultaneous interpretation. In fact, only past-under-bare embeddings unambiguously yield BACK (cf. Bochnak, 2016, p. 266). Simultaneous readings are easily accounted for under λ-binding of the pronoun T₁, akin to a relative present construal. For past-under-past embeddings, Bochnak suggests that the embedded past can be optionally deleted under an SoT rule, thus generating an LF that is identical to bare embeddings. This theory seems particularly attractive, given the absence of SIM-readings for past-under-bare embeddings, where the embedded past tense features in a non-agreeing constellation Bochnak et al., 2019, p. 420.

The fact that Washo utilizes two distinct morphological realizations to derive the same interpretation is surprising, especially considering that one of them involves unnecessary phonological spell-out followed by semantic deletion. This creates a rather peculiar linguistic redundancy. On closer inspection, however, a few objections to Bochnak’s analysis can be raised.

Firstly, there is no reliable empirical basis for adopting an SoT analysis. Specifically, Bochnak does not show that null readings equally arise for past-under-past embeddings in breakfast contexts or reports of permanent states. Consider the data point in (47), taken from Bochnak (2016, p. 264) and offered to consultants in the two contexts in (48).

- (47) Tim degumdí?ye? Mé?-uḡil-a? dihamuy-unil-i.
 Tim name COP-PAST-DEP think-PAST-IND
 ‘I thought that your name was Tim.’

- (48) a. SIM-Context: You see a man in the street and say ‘Hi Tim!’ He tells you

- his name isn't Tim. You apologize, and say:
- b. BACK-Context: You run into your old friend. His name used to be Tim, but you heard that he changed his name since you last saw him.

While the embedded predicate in (47), namely 'be one's name', is commonly viewed as a generic, the sentence is elicited in both SIM- and BACK-contexts, forcing an s-level interpretation. Interestingly, Bochnak reports that at first one of the two speakers rejected the sentence in a simultaneous context, thus only accepting a shifted reading.

Clearly, this data point alone cannot conclusively support a vacuous interpretation of the embedded past. Indeed, both *de re* and λ -binding accounts can yield comparable interpretations. Particularly intriguing is the possibility for *ujil* to be interpreted *de re*. Given its pronominal deictic nature (supported by its anaphoric uses Bochnak, 2016, p. 253), the overt tense is *de re*-transparent. Moreover, its compatibility with aspectually imperfective meanings (see Bochnak, 2016, p. 249) prevents any blocking effect on the part of *Prefer unbounded structures!*. In fact, appealing to its pronominal nature, a *de re* analysis the past tense embedded under past is adopted in Bochnak (2016) to derive backward-shifted readings in Washo. Despite the same set of empirical data, this analysis is later revised in Bochnak et al. (2019), where *ujil* receives a purely quantificational semantics. Being no longer a deictic pronoun but a relative quantificational tense, under the new semantics shifted interpretations naturally stem from a temporal *de Dicto* analysis, without resorting to *de re* manipulations. However, this revision is not justified on either empirical or theoretical grounds.

A second objection regards the absence of simultaneous interpretations for past-under-bare attitude reports. At first glance, this might constitute evidence for a deletion over a *de re* analysis of past-under-past. Conceivably, simultaneous *de re* readings for the embedded past should arise regardless of the embedding predicate, considering that even bare predicates can express past reference in Washo.³⁸ Nevertheless, recall that the conditions licensing tense deletion under agreement are not exclusively morpho-syntactic. In fact, null readings in English are additionally found with semantically past-oriented licensors, even if they do not display any overt past tense morphology. On this view, if Washo has Sequence of tense, then the embedded past tense should be invisible to semantic composition even under a bare attitude predicate, provided that the context makes a past referent for the latter salient.

The critical discussion of Washo leaves us with no conclusive answer as to the best way to account for simultaneous readings for past-under-past embeddings. The lack of analogous interpretations for past-under-bare appears to be problematic under both an SoT-based and a *de re* account. In any case, Washo's parametrization as a *+Vac* language warrants further empirical investigation.

The case of Modern Greek

As previewed, simultaneous readings in Modern Greek (MG) are conveyed embedding either a present or a past tense (Schlenker, 1999). Contrary to Washo, both strategies are able to yield genuine null readings, in that both present and past-tensed embeddings

³⁸While this point is not fully explored in Bochnak et al., 2019, it is conceded by Bochnak in p.c.

are commonly found in both breakfast reports and false beliefs of permanent states of affair (Tsilia, 2021a). This has led the literature to assume for both the same underlying semantic representation, which is the result of either an inborn bound variable or the by-product of tense deletion (Schlenker, 1999; Sharvit, 2018; Tsilia, 2021a).

The above facts have received additional empirical support. Specifically, Tsilia (2021a) found in an offline study that past simultaneous readings are attested for both embedded present and past, with the latter being the significantly preferred option.

Through Tsilia’s work, intriguing similarities emerge between Modern Greek and Italo-Western Romance (IWR) languages, highlighting in MG features in the context of SoT that align with aspects attributed in this thesis to IWR languages. Specifically, null readings for SoT configurations arise when the complement clause contains the imperfect. Importantly, for imp-under-past embeddings the default interpretation is a simultaneous one, with a backward-shifted reading strengthened by context or overt adverbials, akin to what we have observed in Italian (see (49))

- (49) a. O Giannis eipe oti i Maria itan arrosti.
 Jannis say.PAST COMP Maria be.IMP sick
SIM: ‘Jannis said that Maria was sick (at the time he spoke).’
BACK: ‘Jannis said that Maria had been sick.’
- b. O Giannis eipe oti i Maria ine arrosti.
 Jannis say.PAST COMP Maria be.PRES sick
SIM: ‘Jannis said that Maria was sick (at the time he spoke).’

Similarly to Spanish and French, the verb compound expressing future in the past consists of a future particle ‘tha’ with the imperfect. Therefore, breakfast reports in MG exhibit a familiar paradigm, with an imperfect embedded under a ‘future imperfect’. Note that, contrary to canonical past-under-past reports, judgments for breakfast reports are not as clear-cut. In particular, my consultant, rejected one out of three sentences under a simultaneous interpretation, when the complement clause contained a past tense instead of the present. This is illustrated below.

- (50) Context: Maria is visiting her friends in Argos in two weeks. Jannis, however, doesn’t want to see her. This is his plan: once Maria is in Argos in two weeks and calls him, he will tell her “I’m currently abroad”.
- a. Hthes o Yannis apofasise oti se dyo evdomades tha eleghe
 yesterday DEF Yannis decide.PAST COMP in two weeks FUT say.IMP
 sta Maria oti vrisketai sto exoteriko.
 to Maria COMP be.located.PRES at abroad
- b. #Hthes o Yannis apofasise oti se dyo evdomades tha eleghe
 yesterday DEF Yannis decide.PAST COMP in two weeks FUT say.IMP
 sta Maria oti vriskotan sto exoteriko.
 to Maria COMP be.located.IMP at abroad
 ‘Yesterday Yannis decided that in two weeks he would tell Maria that he was abroad.’

For (50-b), only a backward-shifted interpretation is reported, thus making the sentence

not felicitous in the given context. Nonetheless, sentences with the same configuration but containing a different predicate were accepted, suggesting that null readings are indeed possible for Modern Greek (one example is given in (51)). Nevertheless, their degraded acceptability compared to past contexts, where they represent the most salient interpretation, is hardly accounted for by a theory that postulates deletion of the most-embedded imperfect.

- (51) Context: Maria asked her boyfriend Jannis to meet in two weeks. Yesterday, Yannis heard through a common friend that Maria wants to break up with him. Therefore, he speculated that she might say “This is the last time we’re having lunch together” when they meet in two weeks.
- a. Hthes o Yannis pisteve oti se duo evdomades i Maria
 yesterday DEF Yannis believe.IMP COMP in two weeks DEF Maria
 tha tou eleghe oti gevmatízoun gia teleutaia fora mazi.
 FUT him say.IMP COMP feast.PRES for last time together
- b. Hthes o Yannis pisteve oti se duo evdomades i Maria
 yesterday DEF Yannis believe.IMP COMP in two weeks DEF Maria
 tha tou eleghe oti gevmatzan gia teleutaia fora mazi.
 FUT him say.IMP COMP feast.IMP for last time together
 ‘Yesterday Yannis believed that in two weeks Maria would tell him that they
 were having lunch together for the last time.’

Let me also add that for those breakfast reports accepted in a simultaneous context, my consultant reported no particular difference in terms of truth-conditional meaning between the embedded present and past tense. However, the speaker remarked that past-tensed variants additionally yield an inference that the attitude holder no longer holds the reported belief at the utterance time. These facts are reminiscent of findings in Western-Romance languages discussed in section 5.2.1.

A tentative explanation for this similarity may lie in a common underlying compositional mechanism deriving the null readings: the epistemic past. If this is correct, we should find a clear asymmetry between present and past in Modern Greek in SoT contexts that license deletion but not an epistemic past. Following the methodology already applied to West Germanic and West Romance languages, I tested the two theories in reports of X-marked conditionals.³⁹

Design and methods

In this larger scale experiment, participants (n=18) recruited through friends or on the internet rated the acceptability of 11 target sentences within a SIM-biasing context, following the paradigm sketched in section 5.2.1. Out of the 11 items, 8 comprise reports of present X-marked conditionals (*Simp*) and 3 reports of past X-marked conditionals (*Compl*), with the former group including 6 items with s-level predicates (*Stage*) and 2 with permanent or generic states of affair (*Generic*). Each item was presented in both

³⁹The morphological make-up of X-marked conditionals in Modern Greek mirrors that of Romance languages (see Iatridou, 2000).

present and past-tensed variant, as is illustrated below.⁴⁰

- (52) Context (*Generic*): You doubt John is a conspiracy theorist. However, if he were one, you're convinced he would be a Flat Earther.
- a. An o Kóstas ítan synomosiólogos, tha písteve oti i
if DEF Kostas be.IMP conspiracy-theorist FUT believe.IMP COMP DEF
Gi íne epipédi.
Earth be.PRES flat
- b. An o Kóstas ítan synomosiólogos, tha písteve oti i
if DEF Kostas be.IMP conspiracy-theorist FUT believe.IMP COMP DEF
Gi ítan epipédi.
Earth be.IMP flat
Intended: 'If Kostas were a conspiracy theorist, he would believe that the Earth was flat.'
- (53) Context (*Stage, Simp*): Kostas has been slacking off the entire semester, not studying a single hour for his exam tomorrow. For this reason, he's contemplating skipping tomorrow's session and waiting until the next one. If he did show up, he knows the professor would say: "you are unprepared".
- a. An o Kóstas édine exetáseis ávrio, o kathigitís tou tha élege
if DEF Kostas give exam tomorrow DEF professor POSS FUT say.IMP
oti íne aproetoímasos.
COMP be.PRES unprepared
- b. An o Kóstas édine exetáseis ávrio, o kathigitís tou tha élege
if DEF Kostas give exam tomorrow DEF professor POSS FUT say.IMP
oti ítan aproetoímasos.
COMP be.IMP unprepared
'If Kostas was taking the exam tomorrow, his professor would say that he was/is unprepared.'
- (54) Context (*Stage, Comp*): Kostas has been slacking off the entire semester, not studying a single hour for his exam tomorrow. For this reason, he has decided not to take the exam tomorrow and will instead wait until the next session. Had he showed up, he knows his professor would have said: "you are unprepared".
- a. An o Kóstas éiche dósei tis exetáseis ávrio, o kathigitís
if DEF Kostas AUX.IMP give.PRF DEF exam tomorrow DEF professor
tou tha éiche pí oti íne aproetoímasos.
POSS FUT AUX.IMP say.PRF COMP be.PRES unprepared
- b. An o Kóstas éiche dósei tis exetáseis ávrio, o kathigitís
if DEF Kostas AUX.IMP give.PRF DEF exam tomorrow DEF professor
tou tha éiche pí oti ítan aproetoímasos.
POSS FUT AUX.IMP say.PRF COMP be.IMP unprepared
'If Kostas had taken the exam tomorrow, his professor would have thought that he was unprepared.'

⁴⁰For a full list of items, see Appendix A.

Predictions of the two competing theories with respect to the embedded past tense are given in Table 5.5. As discussed for IWR languages, a contrast between the two theories is expected when it comes to present X-marked conditionals, as an epistemic past cannot be licensed in an environment lacking a suitable past antecedent.

	Vacuous past	Epistemic past
Simple conditionals	✓	#
Complex conditionals	✓	✓

Table 5.5: Predictions on past tense’s acceptability in attitude reports of X-marked conditionals

Given its shiftable nature, MG present tense offers an ideal standard of comparison, in that it is expected to correlate with overlapping interpretations in both present and past X-marked conditionals. More specifically, under an SoT account, no difference in ratings should be observed between present and past in either conditional report. However, under an epistemic past account, present tense should evoke much higher ratings than past tense in the simple condition (i.e., in present X-marked conditionals), compared to the complex condition (i.e., in past X-marked conditionals).

Results and Discussion

Results for Present X-marked conditional reports are given in Figure 5.7. They show a striking contrast regarding tense choices in Present X-marked conditional reports, as the acceptability of past-tensed embeddings appears degraded compared to present-tensed ones. Scores for past tense increase when embedded under a past X-marked conditional, as Figure 5.8 shows. By contrast, the acceptability of present tense drops going from present to past X-marked conditionals.

These findings align more closely with an epistemic past theory, which is able to easily explain the clear asymmetry between present and past tense in present X-marked conditionals. Under this account, the increase in acceptability in past X-marked conditionals is also expected, considering that these constructions make reference to a past epistemic source through the additional past tense layer in the antecedent. However, the acceptability for these reports is not particularly high, reflecting once more a general markedness of complex conditionals in future contexts, as already noted for French and Spanish. However, the acceptability for these reports is not particularly high, reflecting once more a general markedness of complex conditionals in future contexts, as already noted for French and Spanish.

Figure 5.7: Acceptability of Present X-marked conditional reports in SIM-contexts

Figure 5.8: Acceptability of attitude reports in SIM-contexts in simple and complex conditionals.

Two aspects of these findings are somewhat surprising and merit further discussion. First, the embedded imperfect does not yield the floor effects observed for WR languages. In particular, despite not being the preferred option, some speakers did accept past-tensed embeddings to some degree. Second, the borderline acceptability of present tense in past X-marked conditionals is not expected under either account. While these conditionals are perceived as not very natural in future contexts, the lower ratings for present tense might receive a pragmatic explanation. In light of their counterfactual meaning, past X-marked conditionals might favour the pragmatically enriched epistemic past over the pragmatically neutral present tense.

The fact that the past tense is not universally ruled out in present X-marked conditionals becomes even more evident when participants are split into two groups: Group_1 (n=10), for whom the past tense is consistently unacceptable, and Group_2 (n=8), for whom the past tense is somewhat acceptable in more than half of the cases. The results of the post hoc analysis are illustrated by the line diagram in Figure 5.9 (limited to items with stage-level predicates).

Figure 5.9: Acceptability of X-marked conditional reports across two groups.

While the acceptability of the present tense does not seem to differ compared to the aggregate analysis, a clear contrast emerges with respect to the past tense. For Group_1 participants, this becomes borderline acceptable only in past X-marked embeddings, whereas for Group_2 speakers its average acceptability sits on the high-end of the scale even in present X-marked conditionals.

One way to interpret these data is to assume that MG speakers can be grouped into -*Vac* and +*Vac* speakers. On the one hand, -*Vac* speakers have an epistemic past as part of their linguistic competence, but not an SoT rule. These are exemplified by Group_1. On the other, +*Vac* speakers possess, besides a shiftable present, an SoT rule (and possibly an epistemic past). These are exemplified by Group_2. Despite its appealing simplicity, I don't think this line of reasoning can satisfactorily account for the observed variation among speakers. First, rating scores for the past tense do not reach the ceiling effects found in English and Dutch, even when considering only Group_2 responses. More concerningly, the preference for the past tense noted by Tsilia in simple attitude reports disappears.

While I can't provide an exhaustive answer to the MG puzzle at this stage, let me note that some participants that accepted the embedded past tense identified a distinctive semantic contribution compared to the present tense. Specifically, past-tensed reports were understood as implying the existence of a salient past time at which the relevant eventuality could have occurred. In light of this, a lurking hypothesis is that even present X-marked conditionals in Modern Greek might involve an epistemic past construal akin to past X-marked ones. To test this hypothesis, as a follow-up question, I offered a present X-marked conditional sentence in a past counterfactual context (see (55)). The sentence was readily accepted by all speakers, scoring a perfect 5 out of 5.⁴¹

⁴¹Note that English and Romance counterparts to this sentence are strictly excluded in past contexts. In fact, present X-marked conditionals can only receive a non-past temporal interpretation. Also, This finding is not consistent with what the literature has claimed about Modern Greek conditionals (von Fintel & Iatridou, 2023; Iatridou, 2000). I leave this issue for future research.

- (55) Context: I hosted a party yesterday. Unfortunately, Kostas couldn't make it, which is a pity since he would have liked it for sure.
- a. An o Kóstas erchótan chthes, tha to apolámvane.
 if DEF Kostas come.IMP yesterday FUT it enjoy.IMP
 'If Kostas had come yesterday, he would have enjoyed it.'
 lit. 'If Kostas came yesterday, he would enjoy it.'

If the antecedent of an X-marked conditional in MG can refer to a salient past temporal interval, even when containing only one *layer of past*, then native speakers might exploit this to interpret past-tensed reports of present X-marked conditionals under a simultaneous interpretation. To put it differently, when presented with a past-tensed conditional report situated within a (simultaneous) context that does not admit a past temporal interpretation, speakers are faced with two options: reject the sentence under a backward-shifted interpretation or enrich the context to accommodate an epistemic past reading.⁴² We could speculate that the first strategy is adopted by Group_1 speakers, while the second is used by Group_2 speakers. From this perspective, the inter-speaker variation in MG is reduced to the speaker's willingness to bridge gaps between the semantic representation of the target sentence and the context where it's evaluated.

5.4 Variability, linguistic economy and transparency

To wrap up this chapter, I'd like to share some final thoughts on how linguistic economy and semantic transparency provide insights into the variability we see.

The economy-based model developed here prevents languages from tethering the same semantic representation to different tense forms. On this basis, languages with a [+Shift, +Vac] setting show semantic redundancy and, thus, are predicted to be ill-conceived. Nevertheless, under the theory defended here, null readings in Modern Greek do arise from more than one *de se* representation: one that involves a shiftable present and one that relies on an epistemic past. The logical implication is that for a language to interpret a past tense epistemically should not be *as expensive* as deleting its semantic features. Why should this be the case? One reason might have to do with transparency: the linguistic system tends to favour a transparent mapping of form to meaning, avoiding restructuring or further manipulations, if possible. A second reason can be attributed to the richer pragmatic meaning associated with the epistemic past, thus indicating that the two forms do not yield perfectly overlapping interpretations.

The last point is better understood when looking at Greek through a diachronic lens. It has been long noted that Ancient Greek, unlike Latin, lacked Sequence of Tense, with attitude reports requiring that their tense form match that of the original statement (cf. Kühner, 1872). Despite the preference for a transparent mapping strategy through a shiftable present, it has been argued that Ancient Greek additionally utilized a now lost oblique optative mood as a substitute for an SoT rule (cf. Dosuna, 2017). This

⁴²A consultant that accepted the past tense variant even for a counterfactual, as that in (39), tied the resulting interpretation to a past scenario where the attitude holder was doing her homework. Incidentally, this is precisely the kind of interpretation triggered by counterfactuals in past X-marked conditionals, according to Kaufmann (2023).

idea has been however challenged in recent times. In particular, Dosuna, 2017, p. 72 demonstrates that the oblique optative originated as an epistemic modal, later developing into an evidential, becoming eventually a mere marker of reported speech. As Faure (2023) puts it, under this approach, “the OO was an evidential marker, indicating that the speaker is not committed to whether the source of the utterance is reliable (an idea revived by Lillo 2020)”. As the reader might have guessed, this epistemic use is reminiscent of that associated here with the modal imperfect in Romance languages. What I’d like to suggest, in a leap of faith pending future empirical research, is that at some stage, the imperfect took over the epistemic use of the oblique optative through a process of semantic weakening, therefore fully replacing it. This view is indirectly supported by recent independent findings on the Greek imperfect. Particularly, Hollenbaugh (2021) shows that in the Ancient Greek imperfect both imperfective and perfective uses could be identified. Following its subsequent change, it developed from a Slavic-like imperfect into a Romance-like imperfect. While Hollenbaugh does not discuss modal or epistemic properties explicitly, we know from Arregui et al. (2014) that these constitute a feature distinguishing the Slavic imperfect from the Romance one (Hollenbaugh, 2021, p. 73).⁴³ This brief diachronic digression demonstrates that compositional roads within temporal *de se* may exist beside canonical ones (i.e., variable-binding of a shiftable present or of a deleted past), as long as they make a non-trivial contribution from a modal standpoint.

Although Greek offers a model example to shed light on the possible co-existence of multiple compositional devices relying on temporal *de se*, it says little regarding the rare nature of the SoT rule. Based on our empirical observations, the SoT rule appears to be prominent only in one branch of the Indo-European family. Why is so difficult for languages to display tense agreement? A possible reason was already hinted at the start of this section: the linguistic system has a general preference of transparent mapping of form to meaning. From this perspective, deletion can be viewed as a last resort strategy - if a given language has neither the lexical nor the grammatical means to express null temporal readings, then its past tense morphology may be invisible to semantic composition. Yet, several instances of non-transparent mapping are observed in natural languages. Moreover, agreement and concord phenomena are well-documented in non-temporal domains. So what makes tense deletion special after all? Deletion appears to be problematic not only on an empirical basis, but also at a conceptual level. Compared to other agreement phenomena, the systematic optionality of tense deletion constitutes a unicum. For instance, languages with subject-verb agreement display no optionality. Similarly, in many negative concord languages negative agreement is obligatory (Penka, 2020). Yet, as of now, no *+Vac* language with an obligatory SoT rule has been documented (cf. Pancheva & Zubizarreta, 2023). If, for whatever reason, tense morphology must always be able to be semantically interpreted, it is then not as surprising that its vacuity under agreement exhibits a restricted distribution in comparison to other agreement phenomena obligatory in nature. Expanding on this point, the next subsection demonstrates that transparency-

⁴³It is noteworthy that the oblique optative was very much restricted to past-tensed contexts. Simultaneous readings in these contexts could be also expressed through an infinitive imperfect (Bary, 2012). We could speculate that, when Greek transitioned from non-finite to finite only complement clauses, the indicative imperfect replaced its non-finite counterpart, thus serving as the catalyst for the observed change.

based models have appeared to be adequate also experimentally.

5.4.1 The view from processing

Findings from empirical studies seem to align with a transparent composition of tense morphology in attitude reports. This is for instance the view adopted by Giuliano Armenante (2022). In a series of offline and online studies testing the SoT ambiguity in English, despite both SIM- and BACK-readings being available, a preference for the latter emerges. In line with their empirical results, Giuliano Armenante (2022) hypothesize that composition of attitude reports is guided by the principle *WYSIWYG* (*What you see is what you get*), for which transparent composition is favoured over structural manipulations. Along the same lines, Mucha et al. (2023) report higher acceptability ratings for BACK compared to SIM in English past-under-past reports. Mucha et al. (2023)'s work is particularly interesting because it further compares English to a *-Vac*-language like Polish. The materials used in the two studies, however, display a high heterogeneity, with roughly half of the embedded predicates containing an s-level predicate and half an i-level or generic-like predicate. One example for each type is given below.⁴⁴

(56) *s-level predicate*

- a. Context: Last week, Emma said to Ben: “Milo is^{SIM} / was^{BACK} sick.”
- b. Target: Emma said that Milo is^{Pres} / was^{Past} sick.

(57) *Generic predicate*

- a. Context: Last weekend, my boss said to Ben: “Leo is^{SIM} / was^{BACK} a smoker.”
- b. Target: My boss claimed that Leo is^{Pres} / was^{Past} a smoker.

While this design manipulation was not intentional, it might have affected the results in various ways. In particular, the high number of generic predicates in the embedded clause is expected to dilute simultaneous interpretations in Polish past-under-past embeddings. These configurations in a *-Vac* can only receive an overlapping reading through a *de re* interpretation of the embedded past. Crucially, in the case of reports of permanent states of affairs, *de re* LFs are usually incompatible with such readings. Despite this, Mucha et al. (2023) find that simultaneous readings are attested for Polish past-under-past, albeit evoking acceptability scores that are significantly lower than English. In a sense, these results indirectly confirm that *de re* readings are far from marginal.⁴⁵

⁴⁴Mucha et al. (2023) adopt a 2x2 design (Context: SIM vs BACK; Tense: Pres vs Past). I refer the reader to the paper for details.

⁴⁵Interestingly, the results in Mucha et al. (2023) show no significant difference between the two languages with respect to SIM-readings of present-under-past, with both embeddings rated equally high by participants. While this finding might be unexpected under an indexical semantics of the English present, it is hardly surprising when considering the potential issue with the items discussed earlier. Conceivably, habits like ‘being a smoker’ do not cease over the weekend.

5.5 Summary

This chapter took stock of the empirical and theoretical insights gained in the previous chapters and evaluated them against existing models of cross-linguistic variation.

Section 5.1 tackled the inner workings of the *de re* Variability parameter, revealing both language-specific and language-independent factors contributing to the inter-linguistic and cross-linguistic availability of temporal *de re*. Section 5.2 turned to the SoT parameter, which was severely undermined following an empirical investigation targeting Western Romance languages and German. An alternative model was proposed in section 5.3, centering on the shiftability of present tense and its interplay with past tense. Lastly, Section 5.4 extended the discussion, reflecting on economy and transparency as two guiding principles of linguistic diversity.

6 Concluding remarks

6.1 Summary of research

This thesis aims to provide new insights into the inter- and cross-linguistic variation in the temporal interpretation of attitude reports, particularly regarding the Sequence of Tense (SoT) phenomenon. The main takeaway from this investigation is that the observable variability can be predicted by both language-specific factors (such as the semantic make-up of tense forms in the given language) and language-independent principles (such as general principles of semantic-pragmatic competition). This leads to a model that is diagnostic rather than merely descriptive.

In Chapter 2, we introduced two parameters of cross-linguistic variation: the SoT parameter and the temporal *de re* variability parameter, noting that the binary nature of these parameters falls short of explaining the considerable micro-variation recently unveiled in the literature.

Chapters 3 and 4 present case studies on Asante Twi and Italian, respectively. For Asante Twi, our exploration revealed a composite system where temporal interpretations arise from different morpho-syntactic representations. Focusing on the simultaneous reading, we showed that Asante Twi employs both *de se* and *de re* mechanisms. The former result from a transparent derivation and are not linked to the SoT rule. The latter is particularly interesting because it targets both the imperfective distal tense *n'a* and the perfective past LEN. Notably, temporal *de re* is most prominent with *n'a*, pointing to surprising inter-linguistic variation. Furthermore, Asante Twi displays a previously untested compositional pathway to simultaneity associated with the perfect *a* combining with change-of-state predicates. In contrast, Italian patterns more closely with English and other SoT languages. However, I argued against the existence of an SoT rule on empirical grounds, instead adopting a compositional strategy that relies on selective λ -binding and an epistemic interpretation of the embedded imperfect.

Chapter 5 integrates the empirical and theoretical findings from the previous chapters to provide broader cross-linguistic generalizations. An in-depth examination of *de re* patterns identified both language-specific and language-independent factors contributing to the degree of availability of temporal *de re* within and across languages. Conversely, a subsequent empirical investigation considerably weakened the SoT parameter, which appears restricted to a small subset of languages. I suggest that this is likely due to a general preference in natural language for transparent mapping of form to meaning. From this perspective, the SoT rule should be viewed as a last resort strategy for a language, used only when no other transparent option is available to express *de se*-like interpretations. Given the undermined status of the SoT rule parameter, I propose an alternative economy-based model that hinges on the semantic nature of present tense and its degree of shiftability: a high degree of shiftability of present tense in a language

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predicts a higher probability for the competing past tense to be semantically interpreted (and, thus, a higher resistance to deletion and temporal *de re*), and vice versa. Crucially, contrary to existing theories, this proposal excludes the existence of languages that exhibit multiple *de se* mechanisms making the same truth-conditional contribution (cf. Oghihara & Sharvit, 2012). In this respect, I questioned the validity of Washo and Modern Greek as genuine SoT languages with a shiftable present.

The main contributions of this thesis can be summarized in three points: (i) it emphasizes the role of present tense shiftability as a valid diagnostic of cross-linguistic variation, promoting it as a substitute for the SoT parameter; (ii) it does not rely on arbitrary or reverse-engineered assumptions about the semantics of tense as pronominal/quantificational or absolute/relative, but rather incorporates these into the model as predictors for temporal *de re*; (iii) it sheds further light on the compositional intricacies related to the temporal interpretation of attitude reports and the strategies available given a limited number of auxiliary assumptions.

Appendix A: Experimental items

English

- (1) Context: You doubt John is a conspiracy theorist. However, if he were one, you're convinced he would be a Flat Earther.
 - a. If John were a conspiracy theorist, he would think that the Earth was flat.
 - b. If John were a conspiracy theorist, he would think that the Earth is flat.
- (2) Context: There's an ongoing party at my place, but I don't think John would like it at all.
 - a. If John were here, he would think that the party is a disaster.
 - b. If John were here, he would think that the party was a disaster.
 - c. If John had been here, he would have thought that the party is a disaster.
 - d. If John had been here, he would have thought that the party was a disaster.
- (3) Context: Mary struggles with math. However, she recently learnt that all even numbers are divisible by two.
 - a. If 7 were an even number, Mary would think that it was divisible by two.
 - b. If 7 were an even number, Mary would think that it is divisible by two.
- (4) Context: Torres got badly injured in the last game. He's unlikely to feature in any of the next Liverpool games.
 - a. If Torres played next week, Benitez would think that he is an extraterrestrial.
 - b. If Torres played next week, Benitez would think that he was an extraterrestrial.
- (5) Context: Torres got badly injured in the last game, ruling him out for the upcoming match against Manchester United - a significant setback for Liverpool. The press is now favoring United to have the edge.
 - a. If Torres had played against United, the press would have written that Liverpool were the favorites. Siena: 5 Andy M: 5 Aron: 2
 - b. If Torres had played against United, the press would have written that Liverpool are the favorites.

Italian

- (1) Context: Dubiti che Gianni sia un complottista. Tuttavia, se lo fosse, sei sicuro che sarebbe un terrapiattista.
 - a. Se Gianni fosse un complottista, direbbe che la Terra è piatta.
 - b. Se Gianni fosse un complottista, direbbe che la Terra era piatta.

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- c. Se Gianni fosse un complottista, penserebbe che la Terra sia piatta.
 - d. Se Gianni fosse un complottista, penserebbe che la Terra fosse piatta.
- (2) Context: L'hotel in cui soggiornavi lo scorso fine settimana ospitava un convegno su diverse teorie del complotto. Dopo aver avvistato il tuo amico Gianni aggirarsi per l'hotel, ti sei chiesto se si trovasse lì per il convegno. Dopo aver riferito quanto accaduto ad un'amica, lei ti fa notare che Gianni non può essere un complottista, perché di recente le ha regalato un mappamondo a forma di globo.
- a. Se Gianni fosse stato un complottista, avrebbe sostenuto che la Terra è piatta.
 - b. Se Gianni fosse stato un complottista, avrebbe sostenuto che la Terra era piatta.
 - c. Se Gianni fosse stato un complottista, avrebbe sostenuto che la Terra sia piatta.
 - d. Se Gianni fosse stato un complottista, avrebbe sostenuto che la Terra fosse piatta.
- (3) Context: In questo momento sto ospitando una festa a tema anni 70 a casa mia. La band sta dando fondo alla discografia degli Abba, gruppo che Gianni detesta. Per fortuna non è presente perché si è ammalato due giorni fa.
- a. Se Gianni fosse qui, direbbe che la festa era un disastro.
 - b. Se Gianni fosse qui, direbbe che la festa è un disastro.
 - c. Se Gianni fosse stato qui, avrebbe detto che la festa era un disastro.
 - d. Se Gianni fosse stato qui, avrebbe detto che la festa è un disastro.
- (4) Context: Marta fa fatica con la matematica di base. Tuttavia, di recente ha imparato che i numeri pari sono divisibili per due.
- a. Se 7 fosse pari, Maria direbbe che è divisibile per due.
 - b. Se 7 fosse pari, Maria direbbe che era divisibile per due.
- (5) Context: Totti si è infortunato seriamente nella scorsa gara. Per questo motivo, la sua presenza in campo nelle prossime partite è fortemente in dubbio.
- a. Se Totti giocasse la prossima settimana, l'allenatore direbbe che era un alieno.
 - b. Se Totti giocasse la prossima settimana, l'allenatore direbbe che è un alieno.
- (6) Context: Totti si è infortunato seriamente nella scorsa gara. Per questo motivo salterà il derby della prossima settimana. Questo è un duro colpo per le speranze della Roma di vincere quella partita. La stampa adesso ha ribaltato i pronostici e ritiene che la Lazio sia favorita.
- a. Se Totti avesse giocato il derby, i giornali avrebbero scritto che la Roma era la favorita.
 - b. Se Totti avesse giocato il derby, i giornali avrebbero scritto che la Roma è la favorita.

French

- (1) Context: Tu doutes que Jean soit un conspirationniste. Cependant, s'il l'était, tu es convaincu qu'il serait un platiste.

- a. Si Jean était un conspirationniste, il penserait que la Terre est plate.
 - b. Si Jean était un conspirationniste, il penserait que la Terre était plate.
- (2) Context: Il y a une fête en cours chez moi, mais je ne pense pas que Jean l'apprécierait du tout.
- a. Si Jean était là, il penserait que la fête était un désastre.
 - b. Si Jean était là, il penserait que la fête est un désastre.
 - c. Si Jean avait été présent, il aurait pensé que la fête était un désastre.
 - d. Si Jean avait été présent, il aurait pensé que la fête est un désastre.
- (3) Context: Marie a du mal avec les mathématiques. Cependant, elle a récemment appris que tous les nombres pairs sont divisibles par deux.
- a. Si 7 était un nombre pair, Marie penserait qu'il est divisible par deux.
 - b. Si 7 était un nombre pair, Marie penserait qu'il était divisible par deux.
- (4) Context: Mbappé s'est blessé lors du dernier match. Il est peu probable qu'il participe aux prochains matchs du PSG.
- a. Si Mbappé jouait la semaine prochaine, l'entraîneur penserait qu'il est un extraterrestre.
 - b. Si Mbappé jouait la semaine prochaine, l'entraîneur penserait qu'il était un extraterrestre.
- (5) Context: Mbappé s'est gravement blessé lors du dernier match. Pour cette raison, il ne jouera pas la finale de la Coupe du monde dans quelques jours. Il s'agit d'un énorme revers pour la France. La presse estime désormais qu'elle n'est plus la favorite.
- a. Si Mbappé avait pu jouer la finale demain, la presse aurait écrit que la France était favorite.
 - b. Si Mbappé avait pu jouer la finale demain, la presse aurait écrit que la France est favorite.

German

- (1) Context: You doubt Jan is a conspiracy theorist. However, if he were one, you're convinced he would be a Flat Earther.
- a. Wenn Jan ein Verschwörungstheoretiker wäre, würde er glauben, dass die Erde flach ist.
 - b. Wenn Jan ein Verschwörungstheoretiker wäre, würde er glauben, dass die Erde flach war.
 - c. Wenn Jan ein Verschwörungstheoretiker wäre, würde er glauben, dass die Erde flach wäre.
 - d. Wenn Jan ein Verschwörungstheoretiker wäre, würde er glauben, dass die Erde flach sei.
- (2) Context: There's an ongoing party at my place, but I don't think Jan would like it at all.
- a. Wenn Jan hier wäre, würde er denken, dass die Party eine Katastrophe ist.

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- b. Wenn Jan hier wäre, würde er denken, dass die Party eine Katastrophe war.
 - c. Wenn Jan hier wäre, würde er denken, dass die Party eine Katastrophe sei.
 - d. Wenn Jan hier wäre, würde er denken, dass die Party eine Katastrophe wäre.
- (3) Context: Mary struggles with math. However, she recently learnt that all even numbers are divisible by two.
- a. Wenn 7 eine gerade Zahl wäre, würde Marie denken, dass sie durch zwei teilbar war.
 - b. Wenn 7 eine gerade Zahl wäre, würde Marie denken, dass sie durch zwei teilbar sei.
 - c. Wenn 7 eine gerade Zahl wäre, würde Marie denken, dass sie durch zwei teilbar wäre.
 - d. Wenn 7 eine gerade Zahl wäre, würde Marie denken, dass sie durch zwei teilbar ist.
- (4) Context: Harry Kane got badly injured in the last game. He's unlikely to feature in any of the next Bayern games.
- a. Wenn Kane nächste Woche spielen würde, würde der Trainer denken, dass er ein Außerirdischer ist.
 - b. Wenn Kane nächste Woche spielen würde, würde der Trainer denken, dass er ein Außerirdischer sei.
 - c. Wenn Kane nächste Woche spielen würde, würde der Trainer denken, dass er ein Außerirdischer war.
 - d. Wenn Kane nächste Woche spielen würde, würde der Trainer denken, dass er ein Außerirdischer wäre.
- (5) Context: Kane got badly injured in the last game, ruling him out for the upcoming match against Bayer Leverkusen - a significant setback for Bayern. The press is now favouring Leverkusen to have the edge.
- a. Wenn Kane gegen Leverkusen gespielt hätte, hätte die Presse geschrieben, dass Bayern der Favorit sei.
 - b. Wenn Kane gegen Leverkusen gespielt hätte, hätte die Presse geschrieben, dass Bayern der Favorit ist.
 - c. Wenn Kane gegen Leverkusen gespielt hätte, hätte die Presse geschrieben, dass Bayern der Favorit wäre.
 - d. Wenn Kane gegen Leverkusen gespielt hätte, hätte die Presse geschrieben, dass Bayern der Favorit war.

Spanish

- (1) Context: You doubt John is a conspiracy theorist. However, if he were one, you're convinced he would be a Flat Earther.
- a. Si Juan fuera un conspiracionista, diría que la Tierra es plana.
 - b. Si Juan fuera un conspiracionista, diría que la Tierra era plana.
- (2) Context: There's an ongoing party at my place, but I don't think John would like it at all.

- a. Si John estuviera aquí, diría que la fiesta es un desastre.
 - b. Si John estuviera aquí, diría que la fiesta era un desastre.
 - c. Si John hubiera estado aquí, habría dicho que la fiesta es un desastre.
 - d. Si John hubiera estado aquí, habría dicho que la fiesta era un desastre.
- (3) Context: I'm hosting a party tomorrow, but I don't think Juan would like it at all. Thankfully he's not coming.
- a. Si Juan hubiera venido mañana, habría pensado que la fiesta es un desastre.
 - b. Si Juan hubiera venido mañana, habría pensado que la fiesta era un desastre.
- (4) Context: Mary struggles with math. However, she recently learnt that all even numbers are divisible by two.
- a. Si el 7 fuera un número par, María diría que es divisible por dos.
 - b. Si el 7 fuera un número par, María diría que era divisible por dos.
- (5) Context: Torres got badly injured in the last game. He's unlikely to feature in any of the next Liverpool games.
- a. Si Torres jugara la semana que viene, su entrenador pensaría que es un extraterrestre.
 - b. Si Torres jugara la semana que viene, su entrenador pensaría que era un extraterrestre.
- (6) Context: Torres got badly injured in the last game, ruling him out for the upcoming match against Manchester United - a significant setback for Liverpool. The press is now favoring United to have the edge.
- a. Si Torres hubiera podido jugar contra el United, la prensa habría escrito que el Liverpool era el favorito.
 - b. Si Torres hubiera podido jugar contra el United, la prensa habría escrito que el Liverpool es el favorito.
- (7) Context: Juan has been slacking off the entire semester, not studying a single hour for his exam tomorrow. For this reason, he's contemplating skipping tomorrow's session and waiting until the next one. He knows the professor would say: "you are unprepared".
- a. Si Juan hiciera el examen mañana, el profesor diría que no está preparado.
 - b. Si Juan hiciera el examen mañana, el profesor diría que no estaba preparado.
- (8) Context: Juan has been slacking off the entire semester, not studying a single hour for his exam tomorrow. For this reason, he has decided not to take the exam tomorrow and will instead wait until the next session. He knows the professor would have said: "you are unprepared".
- a. Si Juan hubiera hecho el examen mañana, el profesor habría dicho que no estaba preparado.
 - b. Si Juan hubiera hecho el examen mañana, el profesor habría dicho que no está preparado.

Dutch

- (1) Context: You doubt Bart is a conspiracy theorist. However, if he were one, you're convinced he would be a Flat Earther.
 - a. Als Bart een complotdenker was, zou hij denken dat de aarde plat was.
 - b. Als Bart een complotdenker was, zou hij denken dat de aarde plat is.
 - c. Als Bart een complotdenker zou zijn, zou hij denken dat de aarde plat was.
 - d. Als Bart een complotdenker zou zijn, zou hij denken dat de aarde plat is.
- (2) Context: There's an ongoing party at my place, but I don't think Bart would like it at all. Thankfully he's not here.
 - a. Als Bart hier was, zou hij denken dat het feest een ramp is.
 - b. Als Bart hier was, zou hij denken dat het feest een ramp was.
- (3) Context: I'm hosting a party tomorrow, but I don't think Bart would like it at all. Thankfully he's not coming.
 - a. Als Bart morgen was gekomen, zou hij hebben gedacht dat het feest een ramp was.
 - b. Als Bart morgen was gekomen, zou hij hebben gedacht dat het feest een ramp is.
- (4) Context: Anne struggles with math. However, she recently learnt that all even numbers are divisible by two.
 - a. Als 7 een even getal zou zijn, zou Anne denken dat het deelbaar is door twee.
 - b. Als 7 een even getal zou zijn, zou Anne denken dat het deelbaar was door twee.
- (5) Context: Robben sustained an injury in the last game, making it unlikely for him to feature in the upcoming game for PSV.
 - a. Als Robben volgende week zou spelen, zou zijn coach denken dat hij een alien is.
 - b. Als Robben volgende week zou spelen, zou zijn coach denken dat hij een alien was.
- (6) Context: Bart has been slacking off the entire semester, not studying a single hour for his exam tomorrow. For this reason, he's contemplating skipping tomorrow's session and waiting until the next one.
 - a. Als Bart morgen examen zou doen, zou zijn professor denken dat hij onvoorbereid was.
 - b. Als Bart morgen examen zou doen, zou zijn professor denken dat hij onvoorbereid is.
- (7) Context: Bart has been slacking off the entire semester, not studying a single hour for his exam tomorrow. For this reason, he has decided not to take the exam tomorrow and will instead wait until the next session.
 - a. Als Bart morgen examen had gedaan, zou zijn professor hebben gedacht dat hij onvoorbereid is.
 - b. Als Bart morgen examen had gedaan, zou zijn professor hebben gedacht dat

hij onvoorbereid was.

Modern Greek

- (1) Context: You doubt John is a conspiracy theorist. However, if he were one, you're convinced he would be a Flat Earther.
 - a. An o Kóstas ítan synomosiológos, tha písteve óti i Gi éinai epípedi.
 - b. An o Kóstas ítan synomosiológos, tha písteve óti i Gi ítan epípedi.
- (2) Context: There's an ongoing party at my place, but I don't think John would like it at all.
 - a. An o Kóstas ítan edó, tha písteve óti to párti éinai mia katastrofí.
 - b. An o Kóstas ítan edó, tha písteve óti to párti ítan mia katastrofí.
- (3) Context: I'm hosting a party tomorrow. Kostas will probably skip it, as he's still sick. However, even if he made it, I'm pretty sure he wouldn't like it at all.
 - a. An o Kóstas erkhotán ávrio, tha písteve óti to párti éinai mia katastrofí.
 - b. An o Kóstas erkhotán ávrio, tha písteve óti to párti ítan mia katastrofí.
- (4) Context: I'm hosting a party tomorrow, but I don't think Kostas would like it at all. Thankfully he's not coming.
 - a. An o Kóstas íkhe érthei ávrio, tha íkhe skefthí óti to párti éinai katastrofí.
 - b. An o Kóstas íkhe érthei ávrio, tha íkhe skefthí óti to párti ítan katastrofí.
- (5) Context: I hosted a party yesterday. Unfortunately, Kostas couldn't make it, which is a pity since he would have liked it for sure.
 - a. An o Kóstas erkhotán khthes, tha to apolámvane. (Pres CF in the past)
 - b. An o Kóstas íkhe érthei khthes, tha to íkhe apolávsi.
- (6) Context: Maria struggles with math. However, she recently learnt that all even numbers are divisible by two.
 - a. An to 7 ítan zygós arithmós, i María tha íkhe óti borí na diairetheí me to dýo.
 - b. An to 7 ítan zygós arithmós, i María tha íkhe óti borúsne na diairetheí me to dýo.
- (7) Context: Kostas sustained an injury in the last game, making it unlikely for him to feature in the upcoming game for his team.
 - a. An o Kóstas épaigne tēn epómenē evdomáda, o propontítis tou tha nómime óti éinai exogínos.
 - b. An o Kóstas épaigne tēn epómenē evdomáda, o propontítis tou tha nómime óti ítan exogínos.
- (8) You're hesitant about congratulating Kostas on his new look when you see him tomorrow. You fear it might cause a misunderstanding. He might believe: "she loves me".
 - a. An to élega aftó ston Kóstā ávrio, tha nómime óti ton agapó.
 - b. An to élega aftó ston Kóstā ávrio, tha nómime óti ton agapoúsa.
- (9) Context: Kostas is injured and is missing a key game for his team right now. His

team is currently two goals down. Kostas' coach thinks: "if only Kostas were on the pitch! We would still stand a chance to win the game!"

- a. An o Kóstas épaigne aftī tī stigmī, o propontítis tou tha písteve óti i omáda échei akóma pithanoútes na kerdísei to pechnídi.
 - b. An o Kóstas épaigne aftī tī stigmī, o propontítis tou tha písteve óti i omáda íche akóma pithanoútes na kerdísei to pechnídi.
- (10) Context: Kostas got injured two weeks ago and missed a key game for his team yesterday. After the first half, the team was already three goals down and the coach looked resigned. However, today you speculate that things could have been much different with Kostas on the pitch!
- a. An o Kóstas íkhe péihe khthes, metá to prōto imíkhrono o propontítis tou tha íkhe skefthí óti i omáda échei akóma pithanoútes na kerdísei to pechnídi.
 - b. An o Kóstas íkhe péihe khthes, metá to prōto imíkhrono o propontítis tou tha íkhe skefthí óti i om
- (11) Context: Kostas has been slacking off the entire semester, not studying a single hour for his exam tomorrow. For this reason, he's contemplating skipping tomorrow's session and waiting until the next one. If he did show up, he knows the professor would say: "you are unprepared".
- a. An o Kóstas édine exetáseis áfrio, o kathīgítīs tou tha élige óti éinai aproetoímastos.
 - b. An o Kóstas édine exetáseis áfrio, o kathīgítīs tou tha élige óti ítan aproetoímastos.
- (12) Context: Kostas has been slacking off the entire semester, not studying a single hour for his exam tomorrow. For this reason, he has decided not to take the exam tomorrow and will instead wait until the next session. Had he showed up, he knows his professor would have said: "you are unprepared".
- a. An o Kóstas íkhe dósei tīs exetáseis áfrio, o kathīgítīs tou íkhe pei óti éinai aproetoímastos.
 - b. An o Kóstas íkhe dósei tīs exetáseis áfrio, o kathīgítīs tou íkhe pei óti ítan aproetoímastos.

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